

Public Value of Festivals and Events

A Case Study of Paisley's City of Culture Events Legacy

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Abstract

This study investigates the economic and social value created by public, cultural events in the town of Paisley, Scotland. Paisley, having suffered deindustrialisation and social problems invested in a culture-led urban regeneration scheme fronted with cultural events. Few studies assess both social and economic value of events, making this study a contribution to understanding of event value created beyond a single field. A mixed method approach was used to add to that literature.

The economic part of the study is conducted using cost-benefit analysis tools including willingness-to-pay through double-bounded dichotomous choice and conjoint bundles, as well as travel cost analysis. The social (and specifically public) value is understood through a public value framework. The addition of this framework is the main theoretical contribution of the study. Using Bozeman and Johnson's concepts of progressive opportunity and public sphere, the study evaluates public value failures relating to equity and deliberation. Through Nabatchi's (2012) interpretation of Bozeman's 'normative consensus', the public value, and values of agreeing with cultural investment is discussed.

The social value including sense of community, pride in place, and social cohesion were considered more important than possible economic gains by most of the respondents. The willingness-to-pay was £13.67 per respondent and event, over 200 % of the public outlay. The minority of local shopkeepers which were negatively affected by the events were mostly tolerant because of the perceived collective gains from the events programme. A total experience value of £33 was estimated excluding local shopping adding an additional £35 per visitor to the local economy, compared to a £6.80 public investment.

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Abbreviations

BID	Business improvement district
CAHSC	Culture, arts, health and social care
CBA	Cost-benefit analysis
CEA	Cost-effectiveness analysis
COSLA	The Convention of Scottish Local Authorities
DCMS	Department for culture, media and sport
ECoC	European capital of culture
EIA	Economic impact analysis
EU	European Union
GDP	Gross domestic product
HM	His/her Majesty's
HSCP	Health and social care partnership
I/O	Input/output
NGO	Non-governmental organisation
NHS	National health service
NOAA	National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration
NPF	National performance framework
NPV	Net present value
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
OLS	Ordinary Least Squares
PV	Public value
QoL	Quality of Life
RC	Renfrewshire council
rUK	Rest of the United Kingdom (usually from a Scottish perspective)
SDG	Sustainable development goals
SIMD	Scottish index of multiple deprivation
SWB	Subjective wellbeing
TCM	Travel cost method
UK	United Kingdom
UKCoC	UK City of Culture
UN	United Nations
US	United States
USD	US Dollar
WTA	Willingness-to-accept
WTP	Willingness-to-pay

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1 Introduction

Festivals and events contribute to a long range of positive effects (Getz, 2010). The value created is not ephemeral, but real and stretches long periods before and after the runtime of the event. Although every part of the event ecosystem – organisers, governmental actors, attendees, businesses, non-profits, and academics – agree with the previous statement, the value is not easily captured (Mair et al., 2021). How to weigh social value against economic? What counts as an economic gain, and what is just a displacement of money from one place to another? What are the most relevant variables? There is no consensus in the research community on these matters (Fitzgerald and Maharaj, 2022).

As will be demonstrated, the limited understanding of the value of events leads to considerable uncertainty about the long-term effects of events. In the public sector, decision-makers need to compare the value of events to that of other public spending: what is a plausible way to compare a local historical celebration to that of another social worker? Overly cautious estimates will stifle cultural exuberance (Lamond & Platt, 2016). Conversely, optimistic use of economic multiplier effects and double counting will make events seem like almost magical providers of jobs, business, and positive reputation (Lowes, 2004).

Economic effects take up most of the literature on the value of events (Foley et al., 2015). Yet, social effects are created too – a free-of-charge event without economic transactions does not entail a real value of zero. Lord Darlington in Oscar Wilde's *Lady Windemere's Fan* defines a cynic as 'a man who knows the price of everything and the value of nothing.' This characteristic could be extended to economic models of events that disregard all value beyond monetary transactions.

During the last three decades, a growing body of literature has been challenging the economic models not just in terms of events, but also more generally in the public sector (Getz, 2020). There are critical perspectives, with the edge towards New Public Management, but also simply alternative or complementing ways of describing the value of public sector interventions (Lamond & Platt, 2016). The most prominent school of thought

providing an alternative is public value theory (van der Zwet & Connolly, 2021). Public value theorists aim to derive value not just from quantifiable parameters, but from areas valued by the public. These may be less straightforward as measuring tools. The economic models versus the allegedly truer, but less quantifiable, concepts of value remain the major line of conflict in the evaluation of public value (O'Flynn, 2019).

Paisley, a town in Scotland, has invested greatly in culture to achieve a wider value of urban regeneration, increased reputation, and a turn towards a sustainable service economy. From 2014, investment in cultural infrastructure increased manifold. The initial goal was to be named UK City of Culture (UKCoC) 2021. This did not happen; the bid was lost to Coventry in December 2017. The loss did not hinder continued investment, and now Paisley has seen ten years of cultural transformation.

The flagship programme for showcasing festival capabilities was the public events programme in Paisley. The local authority, Renfrewshire Council invested in creating a showcase for the UKCoC bid. Considerable resources were also spent on gauging the economic value created and event satisfaction.

The final decision to make Coventry, not Paisley, UKCoC in 2021 was announced in December 2017. The losing bid did not stifle investments. Instead, the bid was seen as making leverage towards increased urban regeneration and social value creation possible. In the communication with the public, stakeholders, and grant-giving institutions, as well as internal and policy documents, Renfrewshire Council speaks of the value created with the cultural programme beyond economic effects (Renfrewshire Council, 2018). Quantifications and specifications of value lie on the economic side, whereas the social and public value side tend to be implicit or unaccounted for. This is by no means unique to Renfrewshire Council, not least due to the limited understanding of the actual effects of events.

The Paisley events programme thus presents an opportunity to explore the issue of event value further. Taking into account the most types of value will require several sets of theoretical concepts, as well as an established overarching model that accepts several types of input: public value.

1.1 Aim

This research aims to understand the value of public events and festivals better, specifically using the case of Paisley and through a public value framework. The study bridges traditionally conflicting methods of event evaluation and aims to improve public investment strategy (Bozeman, 2007). This will be realised through three research objectives:

Expressed as concrete research objectives, the aims of the research are to:

1. Measure the economic effect of public events in Paisley 2016-2019 through analysis of spending related to the events.
2. Evaluate the experience of those events, based on the revealed and stated preferences of event visitors and local businesses.
3. Understand social and public value impacts of Paisley public events, through a public value framework with social value tools.
4. Explore the possibilities of public value theory as a tool for analysing quantitative and qualitative data from cultural events.

Paisley is an especially good candidate for these aims because it did not win the UKCoC designation. Major events evaluate their programmes but losing bids do not use the same evaluation techniques, even in cases like Paisley where a losing bid was a calculated risk still part of the strategy. The slogan after the loss, “The journey continues...” (Paisley.is, 2017), bears witness that Renfrewshire Council keeps investing in step changes towards cultural and economic regeneration.

By combining economic with social and public value calculations, a more full-grain image of value creation may be painted. There are very few studies making use of public value analysis/management for events and festivals (the full list of exceptions in English: Foley et al., 2015; McPherson et al., 2017; Girginov & Preuss, 2022). Likewise, there are few, although

a growing number of studies on the public value of culture: Meyrick and Barnett (2021) mention some exceptions, and some studies on heritage and IT in culture creation use public value as a framework (Scott, 2010; Ibrus et al., 2019). None are looking specifically at cultural events. This is a curious gap in research considering the substantial interest gained by the study of public value in recent years. Thus, the study aims to widen the scope of topics feasible to study with a public value framework. This includes bridging economic and social/public methods. The latter points mean developing new theoretical tools to achieve aims 3. and 4.

1.2 Paisley

Paisley is Scotland's largest town, home to some 78,000 people. The town was founded in the Middle Ages, when it grew to ecclesial prominence, being a religious centre for large parts of southwestern Scotland. Never its own diocese (until Paisley became a catholic diocese in 1948), the life surrounding Paisley Abbey was still of great regional importance. High Stewards, regents, and saints all share their final rest in the Abbey, which is Paisley's foremost historical tourist attraction. It is now surrounded by a large lawn free of buildings on three sides, with White Cart Water on the fourth. Mirren, a 6th-century saint, founded what is now the Abbey, and Saint Mirren is both the patron of Paisley and the name of the town's football club, playing in the Scottish Premiership.

The ecclesial architecture shapes Paisley to this day. There are more than a dozen churches in inner Paisley; some modern buildings or parts of apartment buildings, but more prominently, many beautiful pieces of centuries-old architecture with steeples, towers, and rose windows. As is common in Scotland, some of the old churches have been refurbished into other functions, such as a youth theatre group (PACE, 2022)

During the 18th century, Paisley's industrial significance grew. With the Clark and Coats families, the production of textiles and sewing threads was amongst the most important in Scotland. During the second half of the 19th century, Paisley mills produced the most sewing thread in the world. But the lasting legacy lay in the textiles. Importing the Persian *boteh*

pattern (Illustration 1), popular in India during British colonialism, Paisley textile manufacturers mass-produced shawls and other items with the pattern now known globally as the *paisley* pattern. *Illustration 1. The local authority bears the boteh or paisley pattern as their heraldic symbol. (Source: Renfrewshire Council)*

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From the late 1800s, the population of Paisley was well over 100,000 (Census of Scotland, 1911). Wealth was significant. Paisley still has the second densest concentration of listed buildings, after Edinburgh (Paisley 2021, 2016). Perhaps most stunningly, the gothic revival Thomas Coats Memorial Church remains the largest Baptist Church in Europe.

During the second half of the 20th century, three main industries: the automotive industry, the textile industry, and the marine industry in nearby Port Glasgow all experienced steep decline. The British automotive industry imploded, the textile industry was outsourced to predominantly Asian countries, and shipping through Port Glasgow all but disappeared.

The population, which peaked at above 120,000, declined to around 70,000. Industrial towns and cities across Scotland faced a brain drain for generations (Mercer & Forsyth, 1974). Western Scotland became one of the most socioeconomically deprived areas of the UK. The *Glasgow effect* was discovered; an extensively studied phenomenon where life expectancy and health dropped to levels not easily explained by the standard models for public health (Walsh et al., 2010). Glasgow is just an 11-minute train ride from Paisley, and

though comparisons with *The Second City of the Empire* are inevitable, Paisley has remained separate, despite high numbers of commuters, and affluent Glasgow suburbs taking up much of the Renfrewshire local authority.

The effects of the industrial decline had a tremendous effect on Paisley, lagging or regressing in many important demographic measures of quality of life: drug abuse, life expectancy, income, and crime. In the 2016 Scottish Index of Multiple Deprivation, the most deprived area in Scotland was found in the Paisley ward of Ferguslie.

During the late 20th century, the neighbouring city found a new identity with its investment in culture and mega-events; Glasgow's Garden Festival in 1988, the designation as European City of Culture in 1990, and the Commonwealth Games in 2014. These all helped make Glasgow into an international textbook example of how investment in culture and events could rebrand a city with a tarnished reputation.

During the first years of the 2000s, Paisley's local authority Renfrewshire Council invested in traditional methods of urban regeneration. Brick-and-mortar developments, rebuilding the High Street, and supporting retail businesses slowly losing already meagre sales to malls and online shopping. During the turn of the decade, this method for regeneration was deemed ineffective by Renfrewshire policymakers. New businesses did not flow into town, Paisley remained far behind in socioeconomic standing, and though surrounding Renfrewshire had grown to a thriving area, Paisley had not.

Around 2010, a new approach to urban regeneration started taking shape, which would use culture and heritage as drivers of change and create a lever to achieve the rebirth of Paisley's heydays (Renfrewshire Council, 2014). The use of culture as an engine for urban change had been a key feature of the UK debate on urban regeneration during the previous two decades. It had been endorsed by influential voices in the UK, including government ministers, and Paisley's neighbour Glasgow was one of the international textbook examples of how this approach could transform a city.

The culture-led approach would come to shape the political reform work in Renfrewshire for the foreseeable future. The first major public testament to this turn was *Paisley: The Untold Story* (Renfrewshire Council, 2014). This was a “Paisley Town Centre Asset Strategy And Action Plan, which sets out an ambitious plan for the regeneration of Paisley town over the next 10 to 15 years”. One of the key features (and reasons) to do regeneration by cultural investment was that Paisley aimed to bid for UK City of Culture 2021.

1.2.1 Paisley for UK City of Culture 2021

The concept *UK City of Culture* was instigated by the UK government in the late 2000s (DCMS, 2021). The success of Liverpool as the European Capital of Culture in 2008 (and Glasgow in 1990) had created the want for a domestic, recurring, peripatetic, large-scale event. Those years saw a string of large events in the UK: the 2012 London Summer Olympics and the Glasgow 2014 Commonwealth Games were already in the pipeline, and Glasgow’s status as an international example of urban renaissance through culture were all contributing factors.

In 2013, the hosting of the Derry~Londonderry UK City of Culture set the stage for future bids (UK Government, 2010). The next year, Paisley made bidding a key part of their regeneration strategy. *The Untold Story* outlines the key steps needed to be taken for a serious bid and names the strategy *heritage-led regeneration* (Renfrewshire Council, 2014). The key projects started shortly after that: renovating the museum and library completely and turning the old town hall into a public space for culture and events. Other, comparatively smaller, but still substantial investments in redevelopments of the Coats Observatory started around the same time. Whereas the study you are currently reading is an outcome of a later generation of Renfrewshire cultural policy, the corresponding PhD thesis of that period was about heritage, namely Alison McCandlish’ *Bidding for City of Culture Status: Revealing Hidden Heritage through Creative Research Methods and the role of digital cultural asset mapping* (McCandlish, 2019).

The Department for Culture, Media, and Sports, which organises the UKCoC bidding competition, expects a formulated plan for the outcomes. The instructions include both

what should happen during the bidding period, as well as during the event year, and the legacy programmes. UK City of Culture applications for 2025, the latest available at the time of writing, are expected to reply to 99 direct questions, from legacy handling to risk management, financing, and volunteering programmes (DCMS, 2021). The questions show how the DCMS wants bidders to show consciousness about many of the aspects discussed in this chapter and the previous two; economic impact, multiplier optimism, social value, legacy, and demonstrated strength of the delivering institutions.

The fact that Paisley was a *town* bidding for *city* of culture was not played down; it was used as evidence that towns could take on major events as well. Paisley's disadvantaged position and socioeconomic problems are well-known across Scotland and became a part of the narrative of a town's rise to its former levels of glory, in a new shape for a new era. Key outcomes were meant to include an increased service sector, especially in the creative economy, a thriving and more high-profile retail environment in central Paisley, people moving into Paisley from other areas, including into the new and redeveloped residential buildings, and increased investment in the area.

In 2017, the incumbent Labour administration in the local authority lost the local elections in favour of the Scottish National Party, having been close competitors for several election cycles. The SNP councillors supported the cultural transformation, which had been developed with cross-party support. The SNP councillors continue to speak highly of the reform programmes first implemented by Labour and were part of developing the deeply integrated model for how to put culture into every part of the local authority's activities past the investment programme's end date. Paisley's regeneration has now taken on an SNP ownership after six years in office, with Labour still largely supporting the reforms.

Two of the main features of the bid and its legacies were the *step changes* and the *partnership approach*. The Department for Culture, Media, and Sports, which hosts the bidding process, has step changes as an integral part of the guidance for applicants (DCMS, 2021). Bidding cities are required to identify a number of areas (DCMS explicitly specifies social, economic, and cultural; DCMS, 2021) where developmental steps will be taken as part of the bidding process. The changes are not primarily meant to get the infrastructure in

place for the hosting of events but rather to be able to display a commitment to a long-term change.

The step changes submitted by Paisley's bid were:

1. Radically change Paisley's image and reputation in Scotland, the UK, and internationally.
2. Raise prosperity and increase wellbeing in our communities.
3. Paisley will be recognised for its cultural innovation.
4. Transform Paisley into a vibrant town centre.
5. Develop a sustainable and resilient creative economy in Renfrewshire.

The change of focus mirrors the general turn towards social value, inclusion, and sustainable development which have been an increasing focus in event policy; this will be continually discussed throughout the study. The partnership approach is not explicitly required by the DCMS, but it was a part of RC's bid and aligned with the Scottish national events strategy (Visit Scotland, 2015). The 2015-2025 events strategy in Scotland, published by Visit Scotland (and their events bureau EventScotland) ambitiously lays out Scotland as "The Perfect Stage" (which is EventScotland's slogan). Part of their extensive methodology for hosting and supporting events explored more in Chapter 4, relies on a sustainable partnership being formed (Visit Scotland, 2015). In Paisley's case, NGOs, private businesses (mainly represented by the Business Improvement District formed some years earlier in cooperation with the Council), and local and national public organisations all teamed up to govern the bid under the lead of the local authority (Paisley 2021, 2018).

The partnership approach was part of forming a tentative consensus around what the bid would ensue, as well as informing stakeholders about changes, and creating synergies from cooperation. Small grants were made available for particular NGOs with small economies to make the participation worth their while. The partnership met continuously throughout the bidding process and kept working past the designation date (explored in Chapter 7). In time, the partnership transformed into the Future Paisley partnership board, a long-term organisation for legacies from the 2021 bid and The Untold Story strategies.

Representatives from all sectors of society were invited to work together for a successful bid.

Some of these were offered direct incentives, such as NGOs being supported by small grants for participation. The private sector was offered a role in the co-creation of the bid and the Business Improvement District, Paisley First, had been created during the culture-led period in co-operation with the local authority.

1.2.2 Paisley public events programme

During the bidding process, up to eight ambitious events and festivals were hosted each year in Paisley with some activities for the public, an increase both in extent, funding, and number. Most of the events are entirely free of charge. The profile differs greatly between the events. The Monte Carlo Rally Start was a limited 3,500-visitor one-day event for people with a niche interest. By contrast, the award-winning Halloween festival is the largest in the region, with high renown and tens of thousands of guests coming from across southern Scotland.

The bidding process for UK City of Culture saw an unprecedented period of investment in Paisley. Over a hundred million pounds would be spent over 10 years on heritage, regeneration, and culture related to the strategy (360 Architects, 2020). Though some of these funds were meant for more general urban development projects, the cultural investment and development budget increased dramatically over a long stretch of years. The most conspicuous projects were the redevelopments of physical buildings, but another visible change was the focus on festivals and events.

The events programme in Paisley doubled the budget during the bidding years and beyond. The local music festival (The Spree) started hiring well-known acts with high-profile shows. Paisley hosted national and international events such as the National Pipe Band Championships and the Vintage Monte Carlo Rally start. Some years later, Renfrewshire Council started a popular book festival in liaison with other public and private organisations (from 2020) and got the right to host one of two UK-wide openings of the *Unboxed: Creativity in the UK* festival in 2022 (Illustration 2), branded the “Brexit festival” in the media (Independent, 2022).

Illustration 2. Unboxed: Creativity in the UK opening. The show The History of the Universe in 25 minutes is projected on Paisley Abbey. (Photo: Niclas Hell)

The events evaluated in this study are:

January: Monte Carlo Rally Start

For five years, the Rallye Monte Carlo Classique, a version of the classic Monte Carlo Rally still starting around Europe, and driven with historical cars, had its British starting point in Paisley. This event had a weekday night dedicated to it, with shows of classic cars and family activities. In 2019, the start moved to nearby Clydebanks. The event is free of charge, with 3,500 attendees in 2018.

April: Paisley Food and Drink Festival

From 2015 on, Paisley hosted a food festival. It was initially branded a “Food and beer festival” but changed to the current name with fewer craft beer stalls and more family activities. For two days, food and drink merchants from the area and beyond sell their products, as well as several beer gardens, bars, and restaurants expanding with purpose-

built patios and concerts. Free entrance. The “Foodie” subculture was a substantial target group in addition to locals, with many thousand people following such social media outlets in Southern Scotland. 15,000 attendees in 2018.

May: British Pipe Band Championships

Between 2016 and 2019, the British Pipe Band Championships, unofficially called the world championships, were hosted in Paisley 2016-2019, intended to continue to at least 2021. The contract was not renewed after 2021 (Pipes | Drums, 2022). Usually hosted on a weekend day, it was a free-of-charge event where pipe bands from all of Britain competed against each other. The tourism attracted was to a large extent band members and their friends and relatives. 17,000 attendees in 2018.

July: Sma’ Shot Day

In 1856, the weavers of Paisley won an early workers’ rights conflict against the mill owners. This has been celebrated in one form or the other ever since. Now, it is commemorated in the Sma’ Shot Cottages, a museum for the weavers of Paisley. In addition, Renfrewshire Council co-hosts Sma’ Shot Day in early July. It is a community celebration of the textile history of Paisley, free of charge. 15,000 attendees in 2018.

September/October: The Spree

Being the only mainly ticketed event in Paisley’s festival calendar, the Spree festival gathers a range of high and medium-profile shows in Paisley. Spanning around ten days (two weekends plus a few shows in the weekdays in between), it brings in visitors from around a large area. In addition to the paid shows, there are temporary bars as well as a minor free public programme of culture, as well as an increased cultural activity in private venues. 11,000 attendees in 2018.

October/November: Paisley Halloween Festival

An award-winning event, the Paisley Halloween festival is the crown in the Paisley event calendar. With light shows projected on the Paisley Abbey, a two-day programme at a

handful of sites across Paisley, the Halloween Festival is the most visited as well as most expensive event for the organisers. 34,000 attendees in 2018.

November: Paisley Fireworks Extravaganza

A twenty-minute fireworks display on the lawn by the Abbey. Preceded by smaller shows and surrounding activities at bars and street vendors, the lion's share of the attention is the fireworks display. Mostly attended by locals. 25,000 attendees in 2017 (no evaluation in 2018).

November/December: Christmas Lights Switch-on

On one of the last days of November or the first of December, the Christmas lights are switched on in Paisley. This is done with a similar event as the fireworks; a one-night show with heavy focus on the instant when lights are switched on. 25,000 attendees in 2017 (no evaluation in 2018).

These events are complemented by other events. Most prominently, the Paisley Book Festival has become prominent, despite starting in 2020 and turning digital in 2021. The Business Improvement District, Paisley First, brings in rides and shows, as well as art walks and activities related to increasing footfall in Paisley. Hogmanay, Pantomime, and other seasonal activities are well-visited. Doors Open Days are hosted by the council. In the summertime, there are open-air music shows.

Nonetheless, the eight events and festivals above are of particular interest to Renfrewshire Council. They have several common features: most of them cause rerouted traffic, closed streets, and cancelled or extra buses. They are centrally organized by the events office at Renfrewshire Council. They are expensive relative to other public events in Paisley. Most of all, they create a wealth of data through Council-commissioned evaluation reports carried out by consultancies.

1.2.3 Paisley into the future

The current investment programme, initiated by *Paisley: The Untold Story* (Renfrewshire Council, 2014) will come to an end in 2024. After that, the cultural programmes will need to “go mainstream”, as one interview respondent put it. Renfrewshire Council budgets will need to achieve long-term stability without large-scale loans, and in principle, the cultural programmes developed shall be in place. The key brick-and-mortar developments, the Museum, Townhall, Library, Arts Centre, and Coats Observatory are set to open their doors after being delayed due to the Covid-19 pandemic and not winning the UK City of Culture. This poses a range of new challenges to Paisley. But also new opportunities.

Events not organised by Renfrewshire Council are being hosted to a greater extent than previously seen. These are both community or local events such as the Paisley Comic Con, or national celebrations and festivals: the 2022 Scottish Trans Pride was hosted in Paisley as well as the 2023 Scotland Vegan Festival.

Urban regeneration projects are set to continue, including a possible reimagining of the High Street, just over a decade since its pedestrianisation around 2010. Buildings are bought and rebuilt by the council in a more traditional brick-and-mortar regeneration still needed in the partially derelict Paisley town centre. But many of the flagship projects are supposed to start delivering on their promises. The commitments from 2014-2017 need to pay off. This research dives deeper into how well the programmes related to events and festivals have worked and where they are moving.

The Paisley 2021 Partnership Board, consisting of stakeholders from all sectors, kept working beyond 2017 despite its initial *raison d'être* ending with the UKCoC. There were persisting connections tied in the years around the bid. The discussion on what priorities need to be kept in place by funding, and what programmes need to naturally fade into a legacy state will take a significant role in the local debate for years to come. The quality of these decisions will benefit from the cooperation with academic research.

1.3 The structure of this study

This chapter has introduced the topic, and the aim, and given a background to the issue. Chapters 2, 3, and 4 constitute a review of the literature on key concepts, theories, and developments in areas relevant to the study. Chapter 5 explains the research design, and the following two chapters present the findings. Chapter 8 analyses those findings with the help of theoretical tools laid out in chapters 2-4 and Chapter 9 presents conclusions, contributions, and a final discussion.

Chapter 2 engages with the evaluation of events. This includes theories of economic, social, and public value. The discussion of the largely prevailing method for policymaking relating to festivals and events, cost-benefit analysis, is critically analysed to be able to make use of it in liaison with other evaluation techniques. Other methods for economic evaluation are closely examined as some secondary data used in this study are based on those methods. Social value (or impact) analysis is another way of approaching events to understand what they contribute. This is discussed to support data analysis with the categories of social value. The field of critical event studies, in which some of the social value scholars publish, is discussed. Cost-benefit tools for social value evaluation are presented

Chapter 3 presents urban regeneration theory concerning culture, including events, festivals, and heritage. presents urban regeneration theory concerning culture, including events, festivals, and heritage. This correlation is the main reason for the cultural strategy and bidding process instigated in Paisley by Renfrewshire Council. Empirically, this chapter presents the social issues and benefits of investing in events. It discusses the problems of event hosting as an urban regeneration strategy and the emerging field of critical event studies. A very brief history of major events is presented. This chapter also presents public value analysis, the main theoretical framework including the main indicators of public sphere, progressive opportunity, and normative consensus.

Chapter 3, Bidding for major events, explores how a city or country may receive a major event designation. What a bid is, how they differ between major events, and what it means for the bidding city. The bidding process to the UKCoC is the driving force behind this study,

and motivations for such bidding are discussed. Here, the UK City of Culture event itself is presented thoroughly. So is the issue of bidding processes being high-risk endeavours, and how the literature suggests bids be structured: for winning, but also for compensating for a lost bid.

Chapter 4 engages with the evaluation of events. This includes theories of economic, social, and public value. The discussion of the largely prevailing method for policymaking relating to festivals and events, cost-benefit analysis, is critically analysed to be able to make use of it in liaison with other evaluation techniques. Other methods for economic evaluation are closely examined as some secondary data used in this study are based on those methods. Social value (or impact) analysis is another way of approaching events to understand what they contribute. This is discussed to support data analysis with the categories of social value. The field of critical event studies, in which some of the social value scholars publish, is discussed. Cost-benefit tools for social value evaluation are presented

Chapter 5, Methodology, lays out the study's methodological structure. It develops the usage of a pragmatist research paradigm, and a discussion of the way this study utilises mixed methods research. The usage of theory: cost-benefit analysis and public value theory including social value are presented as tools for data analysis and guiding collection. The data collection is presented, as well as the methods and sampling. Discussions of aims and research objectives are developed more than the tentative definitions in this chapter.

Chapter 6, Quantitative findings, presents the quantitative data results (including secondary data). Quantitative data includes both economic and public value to a large degree, and the bulk of the data collection is displayed in this chapter. No analysis is performed; that is saved for Chapter 8. However, the value-based structure gives indications about key findings.

Chapter 7, qualitative findings, presents the in-depth interviews with elite actors and observation data collected. Though less data in absolute terms than in chapter five, the qualitative interviews develop an image of the decisions made in Paisley to support the bid, and the sentiments about what values are created through the public events programme.

Findings are presented without analytical tools. Public value is more accentuated in the qualitative data.

Chapter 8, analysis, makes use of the theoretical concepts defined in the literature review (chapters 1-3). The analysis is performed according to the research design developed in chapter four. Here, a partial cost-benefit analysis is performed to give a sense of the economic value of the events programme. As an alternative way of measuring value, public value created from the events are discussed; many of these are not easily, or not correctly captured by CBA methods.

Chapter 9: conclusions, is the final chapter. Here, aims, research objectives and contributions are brought back in. Limitations of the study are discussed based on the analysis. Future research and implications for real-world applications are presented.

2 Public value of events and urban regeneration

During the last thirty years, events and culture have been studied as a driver of urban regeneration (Bianchini & Parkinson, 1994). Since then, it has been a popular method for revitalising urban environments, creating interest in culture and the city, creating economic growth and even socioeconomic equity. The original pioneer spirit of the early 1990s has now been updated to guidance documents from international organisations and governments (OECD, 2019). Still today, towns and cities are coming out of intense spending and policymaking periods with debt and disappointment. What are the known strategies and pitfalls known from three decades of research?

One of the key contributions of this study relates to the usage of public value in the context of cultural events as a driver of urban regeneration. Public value perspectives have proved a growing challenge for mainstream perspectives: evaluating public interventions with public instead of economic perspectives get significantly different results and indicate different priorities (Meyrick & Barnett, 2021). This chapter therefore begins by presenting public value and its potential to transform this field of study.

After that follows a brief introduction to urban regeneration in the UK and contemporary debates on how culture can shape urban environments and vice versa. Concepts presented in those sections, including culture-led regeneration, cultural regeneration, and mega-event management, will all return in virtually every chapter below. As it has grown into the mainstream, the use of culture and events in urban transformation has also attracted increasing critical scholarship, which is discussed at the end of the chapter. Some critiques of current practices and the adverse effects of event-led regeneration practices are discussed in the next chapter.

2.1 Key concepts

The key concepts presented in this literature review are those shown in Table 1. They are some of the most utilised analytical tools, as well as partial underpinnings of the research

design. The conceptual framework is interdisciplinary, but all except the public value concepts are commonplace in the field of event studies.

Thereafter follows a brief introduction to urban regeneration in the UK, and contemporary debates on how culture can shape urban environments and vice versa. Concepts presented in those sections, including culture-led regeneration, cultural regeneration, and mega-event management will all return in virtually every chapter below. As it has grown into the mainstream, the use of culture and events in urban transformation has also attracted increasing critical scholarship, which is discussed at the end of the chapter. Some critiques of current practices and negative effects of event-led regeneration practices are left to the next chapter.

Table 1. Key concepts of the study.

Concept	Location	Key citation for this study
Public Value	2.2	Bozeman (2007)
Progressive opportunity	2.2	Bozeman and Johnson (2015)
Public sphere	2.2	Bozeman and Johnson (2015)
Normative consensus	2.2	Nabatchi (2012)
Culture-led regeneration	2.5	Bianchini and Parkinson (1994)
Cultural regeneration	2.5	Evans and Shaw (2004)
Mega-event/major events	2.4 and 3.2	Müller (2015)
Leverage/legacy	3.3	Chalip (2017)
Cost-benefit analysis	4.2	Dasgupta and Pearce (1972)
Economic impact analysis	4.4	Myerscough (1988)
Willingness-to-pay	4.3	Breidert et al. (2006)
Travel cost analysis	4.3	Mishah and Quah (2007)
Social value	4.6	Smith et al. (2021)

The guiding principle is that of public value. Defined right after this introduction, it is the overarching evaluation tool, intended to encompass both economic and social value. This is operationalised and explained in addition to the specific concepts of progressive

opportunity, public sphere, and normative consensus, all constituting value creation in senses which cannot be understood by other common evaluation techniques.

Economic value is defined through the standard evaluation method cost-benefit analysis and its auxiliary techniques willingness-to-pay and travel cost analysis. These are described in-depth due to their strong bearing on the data. Economic impact analysis, a more lightweight evaluation method, is also presented due to it being used by secondary data sources and thus its part of the analysis. Social value, less studied by CBA and EIA, is a cluster of values such as sense of community and social cohesion, which has long been understood to be important in culture and events. Until recently, they have not been of mainstream interest in event evaluation (Getz, 2010).

These three areas of value are used to understand the empirics, defined by the event-related concepts presented in chapters 2 and 3. Culture-led regeneration and cultural regeneration are the key techniques used to reach policy goals in Renfrewshire Council. It intended to create leverage and legacy through investment in a mega-event (though the concept is contested below) bid.

2.2 Public Value

Public sector organisations aim to provide value to the public in a way not dissimilar to how private companies provide value to shareholders. In essence, approaches like cost-benefit analysis want to synthesise this value. Where social value of events always was known to exist, the specific theoretical perspectives were not synthesised or unified; wellbeing, happiness, socioeconomic perspectives, and SIA were all alternatives without consensus in the academic community. Indeed, the breadth of potential new evaluation techniques was part of Getz's (2012) call for novel types of event studies and scholars.

One perspective developed as a direct response to New Public Management and monetary measurability as the primary imperative was *public value* (Moore, 1995; Bozeman, 2002). The NPM focus had laid on rationalisations, effectivity, and a slimmed public sector for the

previous decade, borrowing techniques from the private sector and the principles initially from Taylorism (Newman, 2005). Service provision according to strict rules cannot be the sole goal of public administration, according to Stoker (2006). Instead, *value creation* in the sense of things the public prioritises needs to be prioritised. Because the public defines what is valuable, central themes are transparency, scrutiny, (in some cases) deliberation, and removal of the monopoly of public service (Conolly & van der Zwet, 2021).

Despite coming from a need for an alternative, CBA and public value analysis are not always fit to do the same jobs. Instead, public value management wants to perform some of the tasks which are not reliably solved with a CBA perspective and vice versa (Bozeman, 2007). The criticism of CBA is that since it became *the* technique for evaluating public interventions, the public sector will be evaluated based on a method designed for infrastructure. Applications in the cultural, social, and educational world may come out lopsided or, worse, give harmful policy recommendations (positives and negatives discussed by O'Brien, 2010).

The first influential author of public value as a tool for public administration was Moore (1995). His work takes a “managerial” position. “What managers need to do to produce value [is] far more ambiguous” in the public sector (Moore, 1995:28). His work criticises the NPM methods by contrasting public value to private value. His work focuses on managerial decision-making procedures and public sector efficiency. Moore criticises the *citizen as consumer* logic of NPM. O’Flynn (2021) deepens the discussion on public value’s relation to NPM; she points out that Moore’s (1995) intention of using the words *public value* was, at least partially, provocative. Even before NPM ideas were commonplace, there was a widespread sense that governments did not *create* value, but rather were a “necessary evil” to provide some basic services (O’Flynn, 2021). Using the word value challenged that idea.

Despite mainly focusing on decision-making processes within the confines of the public sector, Moore discusses an alternative process via public deliberation. Deliberative models, a decentralised approach to democracy with an increased focus on discussion, accessibility, and openness, have been an undercurrent in political science during the last decades (Gutmann & Thompson, 2004). It has also been challenged for its unclear methods of responsibility and the problems with falsifying the effectiveness through research (Mutz,

2008). Moore notes these contradictions and calls the idea of a fully deliberative system “utopianism” (Moore, 1995:181). Despite this, he tentatively opens up a deliberative system with aspects of direct democracy and expert judgement rather than populism.

This aspect has been more in focus by Bozeman (2007) and his co-authors (e.g. Beck Jørgensen & Bozeman, 2016; Bozeman & Johnson, 2015). Bozeman and Johnson (2015) argue that Moore “Clearly [...] has no specific take on normative public values“. Bozeman’s “Public policy applications”; the usage of public value to study and inform policy, can work as a tool for studying policy according to a set of values not available in economic evaluation methods. These are normative and variable but enable a much broader set of values than CBA can. To this end, Bozeman (2002) traces notions of public interest and value, including a discussion about microeconomics’ ability to respond to public sector queries about value creation. According to many influential philosophical (and indeed some from economics, such as the critique of social choice; Sen, 1979) notions of value surveyed by Bozeman, that ability is limited.

Meynhardt and Jasinenko (2020:224) tautologically define public value as that which is “valued by the public”. Though this definition is not very useful and meant partially as a thought-provoking exercise, it does say something. The public may subjectively decide what is valuable to them. This contrasts with other definitions of value, such as rights-based approaches (Cornwall & Nyamu-Musembi, 2004) and transformative research, where a value system is already imposed (Mertens, 2007). Though the NPM and CBA approaches use different types of the same understanding of value: aggregated individual preference of utility (see the section on Pareto economics), the *public* is not the same. Conolly and van der Zwet (2021:8) define the difference in the understanding of ‘public interest’ as:

“New public management: “Aggregation of individual preferences, captured in practice by senior politicians or managers supported by evidence about customer choice.”

Public value management: “Individual and public preferences produced through a complex process of interaction involving deliberative reflection over inputs and opportunity costs.”

Public value perspectives’ inclusive (and partially deliberative) ideals also extend to value creation. Torfing et al. (2021) review the increasing importance of co-creation for public

value; several advantages arise by defining the problems and devising solutions for them between what typically would be viewed as producers and consumers. Having a co-creation process built into the system increases the sense of ownership. Services and other values are more likely to match needs when beneficiaries are part of the design process. Stakeholders in a creative process are likely to engage more and explore “their unmet social needs and then proceed to design and test prototypes for new and better service solutions” (Torfing et al., 2021). A dynamic of co-creation also lacks some transaction costs of the market liberal ideas of the NPM system, changing service providers on the market of the public-financed market based on preferences. Indeed, the ‘quasi-market’ of NPM (Dunleavy & Hood, 1994) creates a mobility where both employees, management, and especially consumers are incentivised to leave rather than stay with service providers; “the consumers of public services (e.g. parents in schools or patients in health care) vote with their feet which provider fulfil better their needs” (Lapuente & van der Walle, 2020:467.) The transaction costs rise, and other issues seen on markets but not typically in public sector goods arise: centre-periphery problems due to demand structure and branding becomes crucial.

Public value theory’s focus on process, not only outcome (the latter of which NPM is fully committed to), relates to the interest in improved democracy in the public sector (O’Flynn, 2007). Moore (1995) contends that the definition of what is public value ultimately lies with the elected politicians, even though a larger degree of freedom is given to the civil servants who are asked to reflect on their value creation. The measurability problems of this approach have been questioned altogether (Spano, 2014).

With different scholars taking the public value concept to mean quite different things, Alford and O’Flynn (2009) discuss whether public value could be used as an umbrella concept, encompassing the rhetoric used to challenge NPM as well as a “yardstick” (O’Flynn, 2021) with which to measure public sector performance. They (Alford & O’Flynn, 2009) note that there is no consensus in sight on whether public value is an empirical or normative theory. Moore’s normative process approach, and those wanting to provide a working evaluation tool to replace, not merely critique, NPM, may agree on some points, but the empirical/normative remains.

Normative consensus, discussed in depth below (in Nabatchi's, 2012, sense), feeds into the discussion about whether the essential object of study is public *value* or *values*, which bears similarities to the empirical/normative dimension. Mazzucato (2018, 256) discusses normative consensus as the *values* deciding what is good public governance, thus defining value. O'Flynn (2021) suggests that a working umbrella concept might accept both, but that such a point has not yet been reached for the public value scholarship. Meyrick and Barnett (2020) regard this as a main conflict in the public value debate, contributing to the definitional problems of public value.

2.2.1 Normative Consensus

To create public value, knowing what the public wants and values is necessary. The democratic ideal states that members of the public should be able to speak their minds and let their needs, wants, and opinions shape the public sector and political environment. Part of the public sector's mission is to execute that political will as expressed in elections. It is also understood that there will be significant differences in opinions about what is valuable, thus making public debate and different parties necessary institutions in the democratic system.

Nabatchi (2012) has developed Bozeman's (2007) concept of "normative consensus" to deal with this. A consensus about what is valuable and how valuable it is likely impossible in a large group of citizens. However, the consensus about subjective matters such as political decisions must be the goal of the public sector and the democratic discussion. Economic evaluation methods treat utility as identical for identical services (though the aggregated individual preference methods by no means require it). Nabatchi relies on Bozeman's (2002; Bozeman 2007) discussion of public value creation being dependent on a relative lack of public value *failures*. Bozeman defines them as "Public value failure occurs when neither the market nor public sector provides goods and services required to achieve public values" (Bozeman, 2007:144). Nabatchi adds the distinction between public *value* and public *values*. Similar to the vernacular use, the value of an organisation is not necessarily related to its values. Nabatchi states that "Public value refers to an appraisal of what is created and

sustained by government on behalf of the public” (2018), reminiscent of Moore’s discussion of public sector tools for efficient value creation. By contrast, public values relate to the normative judgements made by people. Public values strongly affect the public value: it must be in line with the values of the constituents. An optimum match would be a normative consensus.

The consensus-building process can thus be regarded as an instrumentalised way of keeping the bid together and a prerequisite for an optimum outtake of public values. Shaping a limited consensus around the bidding process may give access to new opportunities to use public means in ways which would have created much less value before the moving of the public opinion. McGillivray and McPherson address this in their article on how to leverage public value through culture in sports mega events (2015). They discuss the public value of consensus and the potential pitfalls of not having public support in the organisation of a mega-event. They do not use Nabatchi’s understanding of the normative consensus as a value. The argument can be made stronger with Nabatchi’s tool; all public values are at parity with the strength of the consensus about how valuable an intervention is. Shortly put, a tentative ‘normative consensus’ is not just important to be able to keep a bid going and increase the chances of success, but also that an important portion of the values created are the positive experiences and sentiments from constituents, no matter which material gains may be accrued from the hosting.

2.2.2 Public value according to Bozeman

In public value analysis, goods are not treated as necessarily quantifiable monetary integers. Everything in a rigid Cost-benefit analysis is either accounted for or treated as an “intangible” value which is disregarded in the decision-making process. Value is mapped more widely according to what is valued rather than what can be pinned down to a conversion rate, either by gauging actual preferences or by imposing a set of premises (Meynhardt, 2009). A PV study may account for a long range of values which would be considered intangible in a CBA. Typically, these values will include some quality of life and wellbeing, and in some applications a deliberative element (Bozeman, 2007). The public value perspective is used as an umbrella for the non-CBA methods in this study: public

sphere, progressive opportunity, and social value. Public value does not, like CBA, primarily work as a decision-making tool, but rather a guide for management in aligning values with needs in the public sector (Moore, 1995) or creating tools for a discussion about what is valuable and how to achieve that (Bozeman, 2007). Public value, spanning a wide range of methods and data sets, relates to research objective 2, and its evaluation of social effects. It also covers the entire objective 3, constituting the theory development aspect of the study.

2.2.2.1 Public Sphere

Public sphere as a public value is presented by Bozeman and Johnson (2015). They define it as the opportunity to communicate about value and priorities of resources, which is a value in itself. This is a deliberative approach to value creation, turning against Moore's (1995) critical view of deliberative models, focusing on public value rather than public values. In the context of this study, it is a type of "precursor value" (Bozeman & Johnson, 2015) which is required for public values to be created democratically. A *normative consensus* (Nabatchi, 2012) is the strife for a desirable, but impossible position of general agreement of these priorities, to achieve a better alignment between investments and aggregated individual wants and needs. This process towards a (partial, flawed) consensus can only be achieved with an active public; co-creation as well as deliberation (Conolly & van der Zwet, 2021). Bozeman calls it a "supra-value" in that it relates to his thought of public value as similar to a market with supply, demand, and market failures (Fukumoto & Bozeman, 2019)

2.2.2.2 Progressive opportunity

The other specific public value studied is progressive opportunity. Presented in the same article as a public sphere, Bozeman and Johnson (2015) develop the idea that the conditions necessary for everyone's equal realisation of their potential is a value in itself. The article clearly states that progressive opportunity is not synonymous with equity: "Collective actions and public policies addressing structural inequalities and historical differences in opportunity structures" are more desirable than typical egalitarian reforms (Bryson et al., 2015). In terms of events, progressive opportunity can help update priorities to what is

valuable to those in need. McPherson et al. (2017) put into question how useful “investments in sporting venues, transport infrastructure, and the regeneration of urban locations” are to this end and propose progressive opportunity as a tool to study constructive change.

In terms of urban regeneration, progressive opportunity has a role to play in relation to space. Urban areas are inequitable in terms of allocation of resources and space, correlating with other types of socioeconomic factors. Tan and Samsudin (2017) show how space dedicated to parks is based on the socioeconomic status of the area; Powers et al. (2020) found that access to recreational spaces correlated with several indicators of deprivation, including ethnicity and income; more high-quality urban spaces are developed for affluent areas.

2.2.3 Public value of Culture and events

Public value theory is an apt tool for studying culture, a point made by Meyrick and Barnett (2021). One advantage is the low degree of methodological rigidity; not just attributed to the normative-empirical dimension, but also that is quite possible to use both qualitative and quantitative methods. In their study, cultural investments are evaluated in terms of public value creation, which is especially relevant in times of crisis and austerity, as culture is likely to be downsized.

Meynhardt and Jasinenko (2020) show how a clear operationalisation can strengthen the results of quantitative studies in public value. Their study, with variables crafted from Meynhardt’s (2009) four dimensions mentioned above, was a step towards standardising public value variables. With general questions like theirs (e.g. “[Item X] contributes to the quality of life in Switzerland.”) and robust statistical calculations, the comparability will increase, especially if quantitative PV studies adopt similar questions. This does not bridge the gap between economical calculation and non-economic, but the generalisable model is nonetheless a strong argument against the argument that PV is not quantifiable.

Evaluations based on public value have the potential to add new perspectives to spheres typically surveyed with other means. Moore's (1995) model makes frequent use of real-world examples such as garbage collection whereas Bozeman engages with policy areas more overtly difficult to evaluate according to cost-benefit models, such as science policy (e.g. Bozeman & Sarewitz, 2011). Major events are an area of study where economic models have been used extensively (where evaluation is performed at all) to motivate the great expenses associated with planning and organisation. Culture, on the other hand, is an area where values have been considered intangible and thus difficult to reliably estimate (O'Brien, 2010). Indeed, it might even be difficult to estimate the economic value of cultural assets through typical evaluation methods as culture is difficult to compare or substitute for other goods and services. The not-for-profit structure of some comparable institutions on the 'private market' may make relevant comparisons difficult as well (Wnuczak, 2018).

The tendency towards non-marketable values of cultural goods makes public value one possible alternative for developing an understanding of the values created. Other alternatives are discussed throughout this chapter. Somewhat surprisingly, the literature on the public value of culture and/or events is not extensive. Initially raised by Malcolm Foley, Gayle McPherson, and David McGillivray (2015; McPherson et al., 2017), the first articles used Bozeman's (2002) *policy failure* perspective (mentioned above) to discuss the PV issues of the Rio Olympics to keep public protest at bay; the consensus around policy was too weak. Cocreation of value in the UK events policy as a factor of success is lifted, and the effects of the contrary; "citizens are likely to become more sceptical about assertions of public value from mega events in terms they do not understand and within which they feel no connection to information, evaluation, and monitoring processes" (Foley et al., 2015). The intention is to add a broadened discussion on value creation, normative understandings of value, and consensus in a field dominated by economic evaluations. The major event trade provides many intangibles, whilst dependent on heavy investment programmes governed by CBA; this type of policy should be at the heart of public value scholars.

Later additions to the field of public value of culture have primarily included cultural *heritage*. Papi et al. (2018) adapt a wide range of public value literature to be able to

estimate the PV of culture in an Italian town, not having precedents in that area of study. They work with a transparent, quantifiable model of directly measuring the values accumulated by culture in the areas of public value, social value, economic value, and intangible value. Daniel Fujiwara (Fujiwara et al., 2021), the leading author of the Green Book's evaluation of culture, uses the term "public value" in a report for the British Film Institute, evaluating access to film heritage. Here, the Green Book approach of SWB and WTP is used, but with no theoretical discussion of the subject. This indicates further the contested status and the usage of the expression in a non-committing way. Others focus on goods relating to culture or events, such as Ibrus et al. (2019) in their study of how the Eurovision Song Contest can develop public service media; the focus on technological innovation and leverage places it far away from studying the event directly. The limited literature on public value in culture; virtually unknown for cultural major events, is likely to be addressed in research in the years to come.

The transformative potential of public value is particularly visible in the high hopes of transformation based on urban regeneration; periods of heavy investment meant to revitalise urban environments. The chapter now turns towards that setting, contextualising the environment of the empirical aspects of this study.

2.2.4 Public value and cost-benefit analysis

Belfield (2014) develops a way of discussing CBA in relation to Public Value, although the combination is unorthodox. Belfield (2014:98) states that "CBA is the fundamental economic approach to understanding and creating public value when markets fail", referring to the shadow pricing of non-market behaviour. Not being a direct economic value, and being provided by the public sector, it more closely resembles a public value than an economic one.

Barry Bozeman, a major influence on the public value concepts in this study, does not agree, something which Belfield also discusses. Bozeman (2002) wants to separate the "value" and the "price" as different things, where CBA can only really state the latter, whereas PV provides an understanding of the sooner. Nevertheless, some of Bozeman's concepts are

explicitly analogous to an economic language. His presentation of public value failures (Bozeman, 2007) is to be understood as market failures, but in the provision of value to the public. Thus, he designs a language for public sector non-transactional value provision.

Mazzucato and Ryan-Collins (2019) see Bozeman's public value failure as a central tenet of PV theory: that the public sector is supposed to be "correcting market failures to enhance economic efficiency". They disagree with this view, which according to them is held by most major PV scholars: Bozeman's and Moore's (1995) view of especially the public sector relies on a (neo)classical understanding of economics no longer defining the public sector. Instead, Mazzucatto and Ryan-Collins state that the public sector is successful when it does not try to compensate for market failures, but rather "creating public spaces, goods, or services as an objective in itself" (2019:9).

Belfield (2014) gives the example of mega-events in why it is important to find a way between CBA and PV, and notes the importance of getting benefits and costs correctly. Omitted variables or incorrect calculations may cause a severe misunderstanding of the value created. Looking at another critique of event evaluation, such as Chalip (2014) or Müller (2015), there is a case for not accepting large events as public goods as objectives in themselves, but rather as levers to other objectives, such as urban regeneration.

Major events are thus examples of where Mazzucato's and Ryan-Collins (2019) critique of public value is less applicable: the decision to host a large event is more inspired by neoclassical economic calculation. At the same time, as Belfield (2014) notes, mega-events are highly sensitive to miscalculation and needs to take onboard other explanation models than CBA, with Belfield suggesting public value. Therefore, event studies are an interesting ground for the intermarriage between these two theories.

2.3 Urban Regeneration in the UK

Urban regeneration in the UK goes back over 100 years, with the renewal of the early industrial areas in the major cities (Tallon. 2020). Large-scale regeneration projects have

gone on in one form or another since the early 1900s and remain major infrastructural expenses of the public sector. Political attention of urban policy in the post-war period until this day has been aimed at urban regeneration; Jones and Evans (2013:2) argue that the very word contains a moral imperative of cleansing action, rather than *redevelopment* as it was often called before the 1980s. This review, then, is a very short review of UK urban regeneration leading up to the culture-led approach, leaving out important currents such as the New Town Movement and others related to the Garden City (Wakeman, 2016) and the 'A Policy for the Inner Cities' paradigm shaping some more conservative developments during the 1980s (Department of the Environment, 1977). The focus lies on what primarily created the breeding ground for the culture-led approach.

Turok (2006) gives a typology of three urban regeneration paradigms: urban renaissance, social inclusion, and economic competitiveness. Tallon (2020) links *urban renaissance* in a UK context to an early 2000s government programme for diverse use of urban space, redevelopment of underused spaces, and a wide range of cardinal virtues from environmentally friendly to high focus on social services (the Sustainable Communities programme described in a report by ODPM, 2005). *Social inclusion* relates to programmes aimed primarily at the socioeconomically deprived. It focuses on the potential for social value from urban planning, including sense of community and social trust (Miles & Paddison, 2016). Finally, the *economic competitiveness* agenda is aimed at (re)igniting businesses, creating jobs, and increasing output (Tallon, 2020). The ideal types of these paradigms can and do spill over into different methods and hopes for urban regeneration in practice.

The post-war period in the UK meant rebuilding war-torn urban centres, but also redevelopment of inadequate older housing by complete demolishing and rebuilding (Jones & Evans, 2013). The same idea was seen across other parts of the world during the same period, including the "urban renewal" agenda in the United States, and the "sanering" (literally 'decontamination', though usually amicably translated as 'sanitation') of the Scandinavian countries (Verkasalo & Hirvonen, 2017). This mirrors the ambitions and large-scale public interventions of the era, where the hope of an inclusive, democratic, non-warring society was built on the ruins of the failed ideas of the previous half-century.

This first generation of post-war urban regeneration took place as a means of improving the physical environment of people: housing, business spaces, and urban spaces in general. The target was broad, usually including affordable housing and modernisation at the same time (Jones & Evans 2013:2). This has shaped the image of urban redevelopment as being primarily about rebuilding physical structures: deviation from that norm is sometimes underlined, such as in Tach (2009) noting that it is “not just brick and mortar”. Instead, a more general development of urban life may well be categorised as regeneration.

During the 1970s and 80s, a strong surge of waterfront developments and hyper-regeneration was seen, with the ambition of creating attractive rather than inclusive spaces, available primarily to affluent people and businesses. Tallon (2020:63) summarises the most well-known of these, the Docklands in London: “the property-led regeneration of Canary Wharf; place marketing and image transformation; flagship developments; gentrification; and social exclusion.” A strong public control (also subject to critique) gave way to a strong private control shaped by Thatcherism.

In the 1990s, whilst waterfronts and affluent areas were still being built, urban redevelopment was shaped by several competing movements. One was the emergence of public-private partnerships and property-led regeneration, focusing on entrepreneurship as a driver (Harding, 1998). Another model, competing for attention during the 1990s onward, was the culture-led approach. A driver of mega-events, heritage, culture, and urban redevelopment, it rose to (inter)national prominence during the same period.

2.4 Culture in Urban Regeneration

In the field of urban regeneration, the usage of culture (Wansborough & Meegan, 2010), events (Papanikolau, 2012), heritage (Jones & Ponzini, 2018), and sport (Peachey et al., 2015) have formed a partially overlapping patchwork of strategies for urban regeneration. Tallon (2021) notes that this plethora of methods is not a unified theory or practice; community culture groups, cultural healthcare, mega-events, and heritage flagship

programmes may be quite different both policy-wise and practically. The common trait is the view that leisure and entertainment may have a transformative power.

The inspiration to invest in culture comes from disciplines not necessarily closely related to urban planning engineers and human geography, sociology, political science, economics, and cultural studies. These features are all cultural in Bocock's and Thompson's (1992) sense: that culture as a concept has widened to the general cultivation of humans, their enterprises, and the physical environment they develop. This is analogous to the scope of culture-led urban schemes, not solely looking at culture as artistry. Regeneration models using culture are favoured by policymakers around the world – not least in the UK – and have seen impressive growth during the last 30 years (Miles & Paddison, 2016). Having reached a point where culture needs to be included in all regeneration plans for the contemporary city (Tallon, 2020:243), the implementation does not need to be strictly according to a set model.

Public-private partnerships such as BIDs have also been used extensively in liaison with culture; urban regeneration becomes a common roadmap and incentive for businesses to engage (Atkinson et al. 2019). The practice of using festivals and events as a vehicle for urban regeneration is a part of a well-documented method. It can be traced back to two related strands of regenerating urban space: regeneration by culture and regeneration by (mega) events. Both of these methods, separately or together, have been one of the fastest-growing ways of performing urban regeneration, with immense interest from media, governments, and researchers (García 2004). In this chapter, the theoretical basis and important findings are outlined.

During deindustrialisation, several models were tried to meet unemployment and economic decline, but not all were successful (Gómez 2002). Though few urban centres were as affected as similar cases in the US (Michigan, Appalachia), many European towns and cities are still living with the consequences of a major employer such as a plant or mine going defunct or moving abroad during the 1960s or 1970s. One of the textbook examples of a response to this development perceived as successful by policymakers and researchers is Glasgow, bordering Paisley (Bianchini, Parkinson 1994, 30).

The Glasgow urban regeneration in the 1980s was an example of so-called *culture-led regeneration* (García 2004). Often associated internationally with the cases of Glasgow, Bilbao, and Barcelona (OECD 2008, Gómez 2002), investment in cultural professionals and institutions (including flagship programs of renewing cultural environments and buildings) are leading the way for general physical renewal, economic growth, and jobs. The Glasgow and Barcelona examples are associated with schemes culminating in mega-events: Glasgow as the European Capital of Culture in 1990, and Barcelona as host for the Olympics and Paralympics in 1992. The Bilbao has been associated with the physical cultural feat of the Guggenheim Museum which opened in 1997 (Gonzalez 2010). Despite what made these regeneration efforts famous, they are rather culminations of long-term, multi-sector projects which led to attracting interest from the worlds of arts, sports, and culture.

Though the state of knowledge has developed a great deal during the last decades, the discussion laid out by Myerscough (1988) to help develop (and then document) the Glasgow and other British approaches to economic evaluation of culture. It was, in the words of Edwards, “ground-breaking in UK cultural policy in its articulation of the economic value of the arts in economic terms, notably with regard to the city economy” (2018:81). He was a strong proponent of tourism, estimating that Glasgow needed five times as many locals visiting stage culture to reach the same employment effect as visits by tourists, and proposed a more centralised cultural administration in local authorities (1988:101). His model was part of what became Glasgow’s approach to economic value, which subsequently became the UK’s exemplar and a textbook example of culture-led regeneration. His proposal to increase public cultural expense even, or perhaps especially, in times of austerity has shaped today’s policy environment.

While urban regeneration comes from a tradition of tearing down deprived or dilapidated areas in cities and replacing them with new ones, modern regeneration considers economic, physical, social, community, employment and education, and housing issues (Roberts & Sykes 2008). This widened focus of regeneration studies has provided results which supply local and national governments with a better understanding of which kinds of regenerative efforts are economically and socially viable, long-term social effects on inclusion and

deprivation, and which kinds of cities and towns may benefit from what kind of schemes (Tallon 2021:125).

One proponent of using what's called *creative industries* in reimagining and strengthening the competitiveness of cities is the urban studies scholar Richard Florida. Florida has produced several books and articles in the early 2000s onward with the *creative* being a central concept (Florida 2002; Florida 2005). Florida's work proposes that classical indicators of wealth such as industry or business are increasingly obsolete. Instead, the creative class: designers, artists, researchers, and other people with creative vocations, are creating the wealth based on culture, R&D, and high-end service economy better fit for today and the future (Florida 2002). The theory prescribes certain policymaking, and during the first twenty years of the 2000s, Florida's writings have been used as a theoretical basis for numerous cities to increase investment in attracting the right creative professionals rather than other projects of physical urban development (Bereitschaft & Cammack, 2015). The success of a town can, according to this theory, partially be measured with indexes of how many creative professionals reside or work in the city.

Since the publication of his first book, Florida's writings have been heavily criticised by other scholars of urban studies, sociology, and other disciplines (Bereitschaft & Cammack, 2015). The evidence of success tied to the proportion of creative professionals is weak, and other factors are often better fit to explain economic and social differences (O'callaghan, 2010). The public policies often pursued to incite creatives to move in have been deemed by some as creating unnecessary gentrification and centre/periphery problems (O'callaghan, 2010). Despite not being a theory of specifically urban regeneration, Florida's ideas have contributed to the notion of the creative, well-educated, hipster middle class as a group which can transform an urban environment not just for themselves, but for the benefit of all.

2.4.1 Major Events

Large-scale, international events have existed at least since the original Olympics, 3000 years ago. The Olympics and Paralympics games are still the largest recurring events in the world

today (Müller, 2015). In 1851, the first World Fair took place in London, and the modern Olympics started in Athens in 1896. Since then, these two events have been the most well-known and ambitious international gatherings. Bidding for or hosting mega-events may open a space of exceptional opportunity for policymakers and planners, which Vainer (2011) calls 'cities of exception' drawing on Agamben's concept of 'state of exception' (2005), which describes how democratic control and routines can be circumvented by the culture of exceptions forming around the massive effort needed to host a successful mega-event.

Events, especially mega-events have been described in economics and advertisement terms when being part of regeneration efforts, sometimes overshadowing the features central to the people attending the events and living near the venue: social and cultural factors of community, arts, and human achievements (Mooney 2016). While these effects are central to the understanding of events, some social aspects of events lack good tools for evaluation (Misener et al. 2015). For a broad understanding of event effects as a regenerative tool, a holistic analysis of economic, social, and cultural aspects needs to be performed, including long-term effects and changes both external and internal to the local government and other hosting bodies. The study of mega-events has become increasingly interested in these issues, as well as including different timescales in similar studies, to understand leverage as well as legacy, not visible in a study simply comparing the predictions with the outcomes.

Every year since 1985, the European Union has named one or more cities *European Capital of Culture (ECOC)*. This designation has a strong association with promoting common European culture, heritage, and economic growth (EU 2014). The dual focus of supporting the culture sector and tourism, and working with softer values such as common understanding, has been a strong appeal for bidding cities. Calculations of the gross added value of ECoC years have been very positive beforehand as well as in evaluations after the event (Gomes & Libero-Cano 2016). The ECoC designation has since become an important arena for getting attention, attracting investors and tourism, or indeed regenerating an area.

Others have followed in the footsteps of ECoC. There are national and regional designations relating to culture in the Americas ([The American Capital of Culture](#)), the Arab World ([Alesco, 2023](#)), and the United Kingdom (Department for Culture Media & Sport 2017), among

others. While the definitions are slightly different, the common denominators include driving tourism to the area, creating regional integration and understanding, celebrating local culture, and shedding light on the city's heritage. This is true for UKCoC as well, although the focus on international regional understanding is somewhat less important, and the urban and social regeneration of the hosting community is greater than in the other City of Culture designations.

Cities in the UK have hosted ECoC twice: Glasgow in 1990 and Liverpool in 2008. These were both regarded as highly successful in an ECoC context (Garcia & Cox 2013). Indeed, the idea of creating a separate UK City of Culture designation was "Inspired by Liverpool's huge success as European Capital of Culture in 2008", using them as a positive precedent (UK Government 2010). Glasgow has hosted a range of one-off large-scale events: Glasgow's Miles Better 1983, Garden Festival 1988, ECoC 1990, Year of Architecture & Design 1999, Commonwealth Games 2014, COP26 2020. The success of Glasgow had not passed unnoticed in the rest of UK society, and the Bilbao of Barcelona success stories were also well-known: then British Culture Secretary Tessa Jowell proposed to English cities that they could become 'New Bilbaos' in 2003, and Secretary for Communities and Local Government Ruth Kelly said Manchester should aspire to become the 'Barcelona of the North' in 2006 (Gonzalez 2010). The UKCoC aspires to create similar effects that Glasgow and Liverpool managed to create during their respective years as ECoC, where social impact, urban regeneration, and economic growth played important parts (Garcia & Cox 2013). This is evident in the bidding process, where regeneration, as well as social and economic impact, are important factors (Department for Culture Media & Sport 2017). The ECoC and UKCoC designations are both smaller in scale than the global mega-events, with a different theme but with similar ambitions of bringing people and cultures together, promoting international human accomplishments, and not least giving the hosting city or country a boost in investment, tourism, and infrastructure. No UKCoC designation has been won by a city in the UK's top ten cities by population size, and only two of them: Birmingham and Sheffield, have been shortlisted (both for the 2013 designation).

More recently, the popularity of mega-events and their effects have led several advisors to recommend towns and cities bidding for events with highly ambitious programmes

supporting bids, even when they are unlikely to win (OECD 2010; McGillivray & Turner 2017:3). The mere momentum gained by a full-scale bid for a mega-event may create many of the effects sought after by local governments. The *festivalisation of public space*, to transform urban space to be associated with large-scale events, will often bring a tail of perpetuating the public areas as venues for events, not necessarily on the mega-scale (Evans 2010). The critique of the agenda will often rely on the difficulties of including all necessary aspects of this *festivalisation*, such as the *inclusive growth* mentioned in Renfrewshire documents about the case of Paisley.

Mega-events are criticised on both conceptual and specific grounds: some problems arise out of specific circumstances such as underestimating costs or neglecting community engagement described above. More generally, a large proportion of mega-event organisers and host city local governments have bought into methods for calculating economic gains via standardised models which tend to overstate positive values and underestimate negatives, more closely described and developed in the chapter on economy of regeneration (Dwyer et al., 2015). McPherson and McGillivray (2012) predict more protests as democracy and social accountability are lacking in the current system. Although mega-events are not a major source of social protests yet, they may serve as rallying points for previous unrest (Vieoff & Poynter 2015). Being in the global arena, and thus politicised for a long time, issues of democracy and accountability is increasingly surrounding mega-events: the 2014 Sochi Winter Olympics and Paralympics, the 2016 Rio de Janeiro Summer Olympics and Paralympics, 2022 FIFA World Cup in Qatar (Petersson et al. 2015; Talbot & Carter 2017; Ganji 2018).

Müller (2015), self-admittedly radical in this opinion, suggests that mega-events are disconnected from urban regeneration. He contends that mega-event organisers and bidders may do events for urban regeneration reasons, creating the wrong incentives and allocating resources differently than someone primarily interested in the event. Kassens-Noor (2019) underlines how infrastructure may well be negatively rather than positively affected by a large event, and Fotheringham (1999) describes Montréal's struggle with post-Olympic city-wide problems, though aimed at urban renewal. Although Müller's explicit advice against it, hosting mega-events for the sake of urban regeneration is contested.

Major event sites

A mega-event, and even the more inclusive *major* event, is an endeavour on a major infrastructural and investment scale (Müller, 2015). Existing resources need to be utilised to the greatest extent possible. It is not uncommon to see joint bids to share costs and even achieve the required number of arenas; Korea Japan Football WC 2002, the unsuccessful Portsmouth Southampton bid for UK City of Culture 2017. Bids may also be framed as joint ventures despite being in the same country, and mega-events habitually take place in more than one city; the unsuccessful Stockholm Åre 2026 Winter Olympics bid lifted both cities as a part of a winter sports destination branding for northern Sweden: “cosy Swedish wonderland with a buzzing town [...] most magical, almost otherworldly, elements” (Swedish Olympic Committee, 2018), whilst giving the legitimacy of the regionally important city of Stockholm.

Jones (2020) has created a typology for the physical spread of mega-events: diffused spread (many smaller venues), urban nodes (a few confined areas), anchored platform (single platform within the city), and satellite platform (single campus outside the city). For the same reason major sporting events may spread out across several cities, cultural major events will spread out within a city (Jones, 2020:7). In larger cities, the access to potential cultural venues is good with some creative repurposing: the Edinburgh Fringe is a well-known example of an event where the impressive number of venues (sometimes reported to be between 300-600) is so commonly referred to that the Fringe themselves explicitly avoids presenting the number (Edinburgh Fringe, 2019). This spread-out approach has been out of fashion for other major events, but seems to be facing a revival, according to Jones (2020); the Paris 2024 Olympics have not opted for the monolithic Olympic area popular in the past decades.

All major events engage in peripheral activities in the streets, in smaller venues, and around town. Cultural major events, however, can typically draw advantage from the plethora of activities by making them part of the central theme: the World Cup is a set of defined games with surrounding activities being secondary, whereas cultural festivals may, and frequently

choose to, include a wide variety of cultural items in the main programme. Whilst the number of visitors to major sporting events and cultural events can be similar (in the low millions, depending on event; Müller, 2015), the rights to television contracts and sponsorship deals are much higher in sporting events. The exceedingly high amount of circumferential investment and prestige in sporting events has seen cases of corruption both in FIFA and the IOC (Jennings, 2011). This also affects the feasible venues and organisation, adding to the decentralised organisation of some cultural events.

2.5 Culture-led Regeneration

The most prominent of the ways of using culture as a driver of urban regeneration is culture-led regeneration (Tallon, 2021). According to this method, investing public means in culture and creativity correctly, one can expect economic, social, and aesthetic benefits (Miles & Paddison 2016). A central approach to the study of culture-led regeneration is presented by Bianchini and Parkinson (1994). In their work, several of the prevailing tools of analysis and critiques used in today's literature are presented. Identifying the rise of economic development as a major concern based on the shift of European politics to the right in the 1980s and presenting the 'culture industry' (a term borrowed by Adorno and Horkheimer, 1939) as something which culture-led regeneration wants to boost with limited evidence of long-term effects, the political landscape allowing for this strategy is problematic and complex. Bianchini and Parkinson (1994) present three categories of dilemmas: cultural funding dilemmas, economic dilemmas, and spatial dilemmas. These correspond to the problems of how culture can be financed with both temporary and permanent investment (such as an event and a building, respectively), how cultural consumption and payments can be matched with production, and how the city centre can be developed without compromising its periphery. The implications of these three dilemmas are still central to the study of culture-led urban regeneration, and subsequent studies use the nomenclature, or the method implied (García 2004; Papanikolaou 2012). Bianchini and Parkinson's (1994) dilemmas all lie at the heart of event evaluation relating to culture, and are thus presented:

The *cultural funding dilemma* relates to the issues of differentiating between temporary and permanent investments (Bianchini & Parkinson, 1994). In essence: what is the ideal rate of increased investment, which will be paid for later by decreased means then? As García (2004) points out, the same problem will occur in other types of regeneration as well. Striking a balance between spending and expected return on investment is a dare game; paired with the overoptimism observed in some event-related schemes (Lowes, 2004) and unexpected events out of the organisers' control (Osborne & Kirkup, 2008), the dilemma becomes a multi-faceted problem. Barcelona has been lauded for its ability to make use of the large investments around the 1992 Olympics (García, 2004), whereas Sydney has been criticised for the opposite during the 2000 games (Toohey, 2008).

The *spatial dilemma* (Bianchini, 1993:203) relates to the problems of creating high-profile developments for cultural purposes, and affluent groups being attracted to live near these attractive areas. The dilemma is central to the critical assessment of culture-led regeneration and the Renfrewshire Council approach described in Chapter 1. Some of the proponents of regeneration based on creative sectors (most prominently Florida, 2002, as brought up previously in this study; García, 2004) accept this readily. At the same time, the centre-periphery issue is a central line of criticism against strong investment in cultural businesses, as they tend to create exclusive cultural quarters, leaving others out (Mooney, 2016). One of the consequences of this is a tendency towards gentrification (Lees, 2016): attractive, cultural areas fill up with like-minded people. This potentially strengthens the centre-periphery problems, with displacement, hollowing out of initially equitable interventions, and decreasing social cohesion.

The third dilemma, the *economic development dilemma*, relates to the issues arising when expecting quick results from phenomena where long-term investment is needed in at least one part of the production chain. In García's (2004) terms, it is easier to encourage cultural consumption than cultural production. The dilemma is not limited to the short-sightedness of supporting an event instead of supporting an event venue – event venues and mid-term cultural infrastructure is rather a strength of culture-led regeneration schemes. They are straightforward, require a one-off budget allocation, and leaves something to show. Cultural production goes deeper, requiring long-term attention, feeding back to the first dilemma of

time scales.

In the literature on culture-led regeneration, examples such as Glasgow, Bilbao, Barcelona during the early 1990s are frequently mentioned as early examples (García, 2004; Bianchini & Parkinson, 1994). Even earlier cases are used for historical context, such as Montréal. Montréal serves as an early example of a city achieving international renown for its usage of events as a lever for urban development, with the World Fair in 1967 and the Olympics 1976 (Paralympics were hosted in Toronto) (OECD 2010). However, the success of Montréal case has been contested (Taks et al., 2011). Though the events did indeed put Montréal on the map and contributed to an attractive image of the city, it left local government with high debts (Whitson & Horne 2006). The Olympic stadium was ridden by lengthy workers' strikes and corruption scandals (The Guardian 06-07-2016). Stadium costs soared, and organisation costs for Expo 67 were more than double the planned, making some researchers criticise the over-optimism (Roult & Lefebvre 2010; Whitson & Horne 2006).

Likewise, the perceived success of the Glasgow strategy has been challenged by critical scholars: their key tenets included repurposing buildings, focus shift from (failing) industry to creative services, and raised profile on a number of housing and tenants in some deprived areas raised questions. Local representatives lamented that the Glasgow 'place' being sold was not representative, but rather a posh version of the city's working-class history, as well as an example of trickle-down economics that ultimately didn't deliver (Mooney 2016). The gains from the marketing and culture-led regeneration of tenants in deprived-area peripheral public housing was uncertain at best (MacLeod 2002).

These criticisms need to be compared to the results achieved, however. Danson et al., (1997:13) state that Glasgow was officially named "the most deprived locality in Britain" in the 1970s, after losing a quarter of the jobs 1961 to 1981, while one-third of the inhabitants left the city – especially well-educated young people (MacLeod 2002; Pike 2017). After the interventions of culture-led regenerations, Glasgow turned a steep decline into a slow growth of GVA, though not at the pace of some comparable cities (Pike 2017).

Major events such as Glasgow and Liverpool ECoC designations are examples of the culture-led methodology (Evans 2010). Glasgow as one of the early examples defining the methodology, while Liverpool's ECoC year was hosted soon after the DCMS report and the government officials' quotes, with a paved way for this influential type of regenerative programme which has been endorsed by public officials. Despite different approaches of the lauded examples of culture-led regeneration, they are similar in their turning of negative trends through cultural programmes enabling other urban change.

In looking at actual effects, aspects of who gains what has been at the centre. This may be extended beyond the planning side of culture-led regeneration, where issues of gentrification and exclusion of peripheral areas have been discussed. Some evidence suggests that higher social classes not only gain more from successful events, but at the expense of more deprived inhabitants (Chalip 2004).

2.5.1 Culture-led Regeneration in the UK

In the UK, the years around 2005 were formative for cultural planning, being the heyday of Florida's doctrine and high British officials wanting to emulate the Spanish success. Another important factor was the production of planning reports from different sources: the influential report *Culture at the heart of Regeneration* from DCMS in 2005, spreading the idea of both event-driven and cultural infrastructure regeneration:

- *Iconic buildings such as Tate Modern in Southwark and BALTIC at Gateshead Quays show how ambitious cultural centres contribute to the economic, as well as the physical, social, and creative regeneration of an area*
- *The competition to become European Capital of Culture in 2008 demonstrated how entire cities can be revived by a substantial programme of cultural regeneration, boosting tourism numbers, and greatly enhancing the quality of life. Liverpool's nomination promises to revitalise the city*

(DCMS, 2005)

Another report, more closely based on urban planning was the Scottish report *Culture at the Centre*, from the same year commissioned by the National Cultural Planning Steering Group (Ghilardi 2005). This report notices and problematises the approach: “An associated risk is that of the banalisation of both cultural production and space” (p. 7). The years leading up to the Liverpool 2008 ECoC saw a great popularity of cultural investment as a vehicle for urban regeneration in the UK than probably anywhere else (Miles & Paddison 2016). The regeneration policies are underpinned by reports relating to social value as well, typically citing the same set of values described in the previous chapter; pride in place, social capital, and sense of community (Ennis & Douglass, 2011). Regeneration perspectives on social value of events are also used in evaluation reports of major events (DCMS, 2013)

The hosting of mega-events, part of the plans for several of the early examples of Culture-led regeneration, has grown into a well-known strategy for creating such diverse effects as policy windows, improved city infrastructure, tourism, and international standing as an events venue (OECD 2008; OECD 2019). In turn, this has led to the creation of new mega-events as the demand outgrew the supply (García & Cox 2013).

2.5.2 Cultural Regeneration

The success of Culture-led Regeneration may have gained from policymakers seeing the methods use as solutions for big structural problems: investing in one area to alleviate problems across the board at a middle-to-long-term time scale. The focus remains on countering deindustrialisation through economic revitalisation. Indeed, culture can sometimes take on the role of a means rather than a goal, such as Florida’s (2002) near-causal explanation model.

Another development of urban regeneration methodology, with less focus on boosting new programmes and more focus on the integration of culture into policy areas, has grown parallel or partially intertwined with the culture-led regeneration: cultural regeneration.

Ghilardi (2005) defines cultural regeneration as the stronger focus on an integration of the economic, social, and creative, and Miles and Paddison (2005) provide a similar view. Evans

and Shaw (2004) add environmental, social, and economic aspects of urban policy. Culture is integrated into policy areas not traditionally associated with cultural policy, and it does not necessarily place urban planning at the centre of this process. Rather, it is decentralised. There is some conceptual confusion even by well-cited authors. Some, such as Zhang et al. (2021) make cultural regeneration to be a process driven by heritage, not least by transforming industrial (deindustrialised) and other heritage sites to create a cultural environment. Della Lucia and Trunfio (2018) adhere to Florida's (2002) concept of the *creative class* as a driver of change in cultural regeneration and showcase how a bottom-up transformation can occur, even in the private sector. Though most theory was published in the early 2000s, around the heyday of culture-led regeneration, the model is still used by those re-evaluating the culture-led focus on the economy.

The difference is not clear-cut, though: the terms have sometimes been used interchangeably (as in Wansborough & Mageean 2010), or without clearly defining the difference (such as Liu 2019). As the term culture-led regeneration has gained ground as a popular term for all urban regeneration with cultural traits, but because the need of differentiation, the alternative route will henceforth be called cultural regeneration. Part of cultural regeneration is a counter-reaction to culture-led regeneration, and indeed, is an answer to some of the issues raised from within the culture-led method mainstream.

2.6 Critical Event Studies

The traditional academic perspectives in the event sector have increasingly been critiqued and replaced by alternatives. Lamond and Platt (2016:29) mean that the prevalent "dominance is a symptom of a neo-liberal economic agenda that seeks to de-politicise and, to some extent, de-culturate many events into some quasi-homogenous, 'Western'-influenced, entertainment.". More cautiously, Robertson et al. (2018:866) state that the origin of the critical movement is the problem of a "preoccupation on event instrumentality" —that is, their ability to add value to allied sectors — "instead of an examination of an events' intrinsic value." Criticism of event priorities and the negative consequences are in no

way unknown to scholars who do not adhere to the critical tradition. Getz (2012) encouraged scholars from other disciplines to join the event studies area; the number of articles in event studies has increased since, not least critical scholars. Foley et al. (2012) also problematised the current event paradigm in their book on event policy, claiming that other studies still being the exception. These and others were early examples of a critical body of research, with the term now being used in articles after the 2016 book *Critical Event Studies* (Lamond & Platt, 2016).

Critical event studies make use of critical theory, which in turn is based on 20th-century Marxist thought, not least the Frankfurt school (such as the previously cited Adorno & Horkheimer, 1939). Aiming to unveil how power operates in society, the critical event scholar will point towards postcolonial, gender, sexuality, and physical ability (Tyson, 2023:370). Thus, not simply criticising economism and narrow scope, the critique extends to the event industry as a whole through a critical theory lens. Silk (2014) discusses the displacement in the wake of the London 2012 Olympics; displacement not related to gentrification or general urban regeneration, but the tearing down of fully functional communities for the greater sake of the Olympics. De Lisio et al. (2019) focus on the role of sex workers during the Rio 2016 Olympics, who experienced hardships related to policies against prostitution, as well as poverty, drug use, and urban planning. Studies such as Silk (2014) and De Lisio et al. (2019) display how event organisers are complicit in active policies with negative social (and economic) consequences. The critical event studies above are engaged in the analysis of power structures underpinning the event industry. Other studies may be *critical* in the sense that they criticise the precarity of guest workers, corruption, and inflated multipliers, without adhering to a critical studies tradition.

Critical perspectives add to the understanding of power relations; some of the additions where it has contributed to this study include strong arguments for including negative values and methodological fallacies. Being quite opposed to the economic mainstream, it is unlikely to find a common way with the currently prevailing evaluation techniques. Similarly, economic methods are ill-equipped to integrate some of the critique, especially those only or mostly looking at transactions. The next chapter covers bidding for events, arguably the

politically most important period for a city wanting to host an event. That is where event-led approaches are laid out and political battles fought; winning bids are not as contested.

2.7 Summary

This chapter presents the field of study, event studies, as well as the key theoretical tool, public value. This serves as an empirical and theoretical baseline, on which the rest of the work is contingent. A summary of key concepts is presented below, with key concepts from table 1 in italics.

Urban regeneration strategies relating to culture have shaped investment strategies in many cities and have been a topic for scholarly inquiry since at least the 1980s (Myerscough, 1988). Investment in culture is, in several aspects, a more indirect type of intervention than other popular regeneration techniques. Physical regeneration, retail regeneration, hyper-regeneration, and waterfront developments all make use of brick-and-mortar or incentives to existing businesses. Cultural investment in regeneration aims to incentivise new groups to move to the city, turn the economy towards services, and increase the city's reputation (Paddison & Miles, 2020). Flagship developments include museums and venues, major events (or even mega-events), and ongoing cultural programmes, not skyscrapers, utopian architecture, or inner-city malls.

The classical approach, aggressive investment in cultural infrastructure and events, is called culture-led regeneration. This has been criticised for spurious results and using public means for what is essentially a gamble (Miles & Paddison, 2005). The alternative approach which grew out of that critique, cultural regeneration, instead focuses on incremental change and integration of culture into every aspect of public life, such as healthcare and urban planning (Wansborough & Mageean, 2010).

Considering that both approaches are not likely to see full results until many years of improved reputation, changing consumption patterns, and new inhabitants, it is relevant to discuss and critique evaluation methods. Public value, which has taken on a significant position in the understanding of the public sector (O'Flynn, 2021), has the potential to add

to this area of study. Public value, as discussed by O’Flynn (2007) can be understood both as an empirical way of finding out what people (“the public”) actually value, and a normative set of values which are considered more useful to guide the public sector than those suggested by NPM.

Bozeman’s (2015) adheres more to the former, aiming to include the public in evaluating the public sector. Through of normative consensus (in Nabatchi’s, 2012, understanding), a tentative common view of a policy intervention can be used as a way of maximising value according to those affected by it. Public sphere, the possibility to communicate and deliberate about value becomes a value in itself. Finally, progressive opportunity, giving everyone (a more) equal chance of making use of their abilities to achieve their goals, is a somewhat more normative stance, though hardly politically loaded expressed this way, though the policy implications may be.

Armed with these tools: the basic understanding of value and the theoretical understanding of the intentions of the Paisley interventions, the next chapter looks at the methods for achieving the hosting of major events.

3 Bidding for major events and events in Scotland

This study explores the values created by the public event programme in Paisley. The driving force of the event economy for the years studied, 2016-2019, was the bid to become UK City of Culture 2021. The bidding process was not a naïve investment in the face of tough odds. It was rather a calculated risk and expectations were high no matter the outcome of the bid, which ultimately proved to be a losing one, but certainly not a *failed* bid according to several of those involved. Bidding for event-related designations has gone from relative obscurity to a high-profile affair with intense political and financial focus from the city and region (Getz 2004). Indeed, it may have a national importance, not just when the country's economy and infrastructure need existential upgrades, such as in the Football World Cup in Qatar 2022 and the Baku, Azerbaijan hosting of major events (Dickinson et al., 2016). Paisley's bid was not created in a vacuum. It was a part of a movement, informed by a body of literature; in addition to the use of academic expertise in the partnership, the findings in Chapter 7 will show that academic literature gave inspiration to the investments. The event bidding literature is explored in this chapter, both to get a better understanding of Renfrewshire Council's decisions and to create an orientation of major event bidding.

The bidding rationale is crucial for the understanding of what values were expected by policymakers. Bidding for a major event may be due to any reason mentioned in the literature, including urban regeneration (Tallon, 2021), supporting the event/designating organisation, competitive bidding for glory (both Roche, 2000), reputation (McGillivray & Turner, 2017), economic influx (Chalip, 2004), attracting affluent people (Florida, 2002), or social gains (Zawadski, 2020). Bidding for events may drive and shape urban regeneration with the policy windows opened in the specific setting of that event, as discussed in the last chapter. In the case of this study, understanding the bidding processes is crucial to understanding the policymaking behind the regeneration approach, but also of the specific organisation of events and their touristic/community foci. The chapter also covers mega-events (or major events), which define the academic field in which this study places itself.

This chapter starts with the history of how major event hosts have been designated. It proceeds to discuss the understanding of the potential effects of bidding; winning, losing, and legacy programmes. What is expected of bidders and how they are designated. The chapter also looks at motivations for bidding and the outcomes expected by those bidding for major events, even in cases where the expected outcome is not primarily winning the bid. This is followed by an in-depth discussion of the UK City of Culture, major events, and event bidding in Scotland. The literature inspiring and detracting bidders today is explored. The chapter ends with discussing the different approaches to bidding for events, and the controversies of bidding processes.

3.1 The bidding process

Different events handle their bidding processes in different ways, corresponding to the designating organisation's needs. Though there are commonly seen features, the expected outcomes for the designating organisation (and the bidders) may entice different approaches. The archetypical bidding processes of the World Expo, Men's Football WC and the Olympics share the feature of open bidding processes, where several contestants remain after a shortlisting process. A final vote is held, with several contestants remaining. In both of these cases, one member (state) of the BIE, FIFA, and IOC respectively will decide the host in a closed-ballot vote with a one member, one vote principle. This is not the case in all major events. The European Capital of Culture decides a country to host the event, with a city being decided in a domestic bidding process. This European Union approach to lifting all member states is analogous to the EU presidency, ambulating every six months.

Other major events use other approaches, or indeed other institutional norms: the Commonwealth games frequently see shortlisted contenders leave the bidding process; on occasion, all but one have withdrawn. The UK City of Culture, discussed more below, is another example, where direct member democracy is not used. International University Sports Federation, the organisers of the Universiade World University Games, also makes an Executive Committee decision rather than a member vote (FISU, 2022). These bidding

processes mean that different types of requirements are made; convincing each of the delegates of the IOC, where governments might take an active role is different from swaying an executive committee which formulated the specifications for bidding.

Bidding for a mega-event is invariably means investments requiring political attention and priority. Even in the cases where sportive or cultural infrastructure is already nearly sufficient to host the event, transport infrastructure and major redevelopments around the Olympic Village is common practice (Kassens-Noor, 2013). Demonstrating the capability to successfully host the event and being good ambassadors for the event trademark is a given requisite to winning. In an open bidding process, showing interest in a bid for a mega-event is announced not just to the organisation responsible for the designation, but also publicly. Contemporary mega-event bids are part of a strategy to raise awareness of a city, even in the case of a losing bid (OECD, 2019). Though the strategic investment in the bidding process varies with several factors, in contemporary major events they are designed to overlap with reforms the administration would have liked to see in the city anyway, including new public transport services (Kassens-Noor, 2019). Indeed, it can constitute a boost in infrastructure which would have been virtually impossible otherwise: Preuss (2004, cited in Müller, 2015) claims that a correctly carried out programme can “accelerate [a city’s] infrastructural development by up to 10 years”.

In the case of several mega-events, pulling out of the bid is viable, even common, which may be due to unforeseen needs to divert investment, changed priorities, a poor forecast for the city’s ability to win the bid, or realisation that the city will not live up to the expectation (Paulsson & Alm, 2020; Jackson & Scherer, 2013). As Jones and Ponzini (2018) put it: “For both the 2022 Winter Olympic and 2024 Summer Olympic bids, four out of six candidate cities withdrew from the competition. The long-utilized equation of the mega-event as an opportunity for mega-expenditures and mega-constructions no longer adds up for many cities.” The practice is more common in some events; in the Commonwealth Games, a single contender has sometimes been left after bids withdraw post shortlisting. Others, such as the summer Olympics, maintain several viable bids with tight security around what bid is ‘in the lead’.

3.2 The Role of major events

A common term used to designate large, recurring, predominantly ambulating events is 'mega-events' (Hiller, 1995; McGillivray & McPherson, 2012; Paulsson & Alm, 2020). The term is used in this chapter and throughout the study to denominate the Olympics, the World Expo, the men's World Cup in football, and similar-sized events. This chapter's title uses the word 'major event'. It is used to *also* encompass slightly smaller events: Commonwealth Games (Preuss et al., 2007), Grand Prix (Abelson, 2011), European Capital of Culture (Müller, 2018). Müller (2018) has proposed a typology based on visitor attractiveness, cost, reach, and urban transformation. Müller's typology guides the nomenclature of this study, though without calling the Summer Olympics the unique 'giga' event. The UK City of Culture (though not mentioned by Müller) will be deemed a major event due to its focus on urban transformation and visitor attractiveness, and often substantial public and private investments in a variety of areas.

With the current state of major events as a market on which large state and private actors compete for contracts on designations, sponsorships, and other deals, the literature around bidding is crucial not just for those wanting to participate in the market, but also for those wanting to understand events. Not least because the bidding process takes up a considerable amount of the time, attention, PR, and money spent by winners and losers alike. The influence of regional institutions such as the EU and the OECD, has inspired the creation of new events, not least other regional versions of the "Capital of Culture" concept (OECD 2019). It has also provided an explicit motivation behind bidding, and the "play to lose" option of bidding for events. The seemingly contradictory globalist and nationalist ideals of the Olympics shape our understanding of all mega-events, bolstering both competition and friendship.

Roche (2002) also discusses nationally significant events as mega-events, including annual sports cup finals, party days in totalitarian states, and labour celebrations in socialist states. Some of these are ambulatory, others stationary. National celebrations are seldom open for

bidding in an open competition, which makes the UK City of Culture different from well-studied events.

In both the case of the national and international mega-event, the significance is particularly important during three phases: the bidding process, the actual runtime of the event, and the legacies. As Li and McCabe (2012) explore, the legacy can be both of a winning and a losing event. Their typology of effects aligns well with other broad-level discussions of value created by culture: tourism, infrastructure, economic boosts, environment, image and reputation, social value (Li & McCabe, 2012). These effects can all be discussed in both bidding, runtime, and legacy terms.

3.3 Outcomes and expectations

The most conspicuous outcomes presented by bidding enthusiasts are those of economic gains and improvement of the urban environment; primarily for the hosting of the event, but also for the bidding process and the leverage it creates (OECD, 2018). The former is discussed at length in Chapter 4, from the perspective of the flawed evaluation methods at disposal. The latter is discussed in Chapter 3. It is difficult to exclude the urban regeneration effects of hosting events, these topics overlap. This subsection thus gives a synthesised discussion of expectations, as well as presenting those not covered by economic methodology and urban regeneration.

Public communication in the mega industry aims to invoke positive values such as intercultural exchange (Roche, 2002). Though these efforts are honestly meant by organisers, approval from all political levels engaged in a mega-event bid to reallocate resources into a bid will depend on other outcomes, as well. Breaking even, or making a short-term profit is a highly selling argument for policymakers, and in many studies, a mega-event is treated as mainly an economic venture for the public stakeholders deciding to bid and host an event (Müller, 2015; Kassens-Noor, 2019). Some desired outcomes are also outwith the scope because they are not directly related to event hosting; Johansson (2023:87) discusses the media impact of sports events as related to the number of medals

won by a certain team or athlete. Such factors cannot be easily designed by event organisers.

The public (and private) interventions in urban infrastructure will likely begin before the bid is even submitted. McGillivray and Turner (2017) discuss the strong political and social forces pushing for carrying out the bid policies: “The desire to compete and ‘win’ the rights to host a major event and to ‘defeat’ competitor cities and nations further fuels this process, and major events begin to represent a form of ‘civic blackmail’”. The contrast is stark to the more level opinions of OECD’s guidance (2019), giving some evidence (and indeed advice to prospecting bidders) that even losing bids may benefit economically and socially should they invest wisely and plan for an ambitious legacy for losing scenarios as well. Thus, the bidding processes have taken on a life of their own and may be a major selling argument used to close a deal with a sceptical group of stakeholders: ‘it doesn’t matter if we win’, or even ‘winning might well be worse than losing’ (Müller, 2015).

Before or during a bidding process, anticipated earnings from staging the (mega-)event are formulated in several terms. The anticipated economic outcomes have the potential of being a central indicator of value, being a tangible figure possible to relate to. These values are reported as key figures after hosted events, such as the £740 million generated for Scotland during the 2014 Glasgow Commonwealth Games (McGillivray & Turner, 2017). The methodology used for calculating the economic benefit varies, but as shown in the previous chapter, it is highly contested. Gross Value Added (GVA) models and Economic Impact Assessment (EIA) are very flexible, depending on how the method is implemented. This has resulted in critical literature on the subject of event evaluation methods, also developed at length in previous chapters.

Even though the probability of bidding success has been studied (e.g. Chalip, 2017, noting that mega-events typically go to the bidder spending the most money on the bid). De Nooij (2014) argues for a probabilistic CBA approach to bidding, where the value of hosting the event should be weighed against the probability of hosting. De Nooij uses the term “unsuccessful” and does not discuss the values of a bid in itself, thus taking a different stance than the ‘we win even if we lose’ optimism.

These methodologies for evaluation may be decided beforehand; estimated gains are presented to stakeholders as ready-made calculations. This is a dangerous road; Chalip (2017) starts his bidding chapter in the *SAGE Handbook of Sports Management* by several pages of listing the (sometimes unexpected or wishfully ignored) costs associated with hosting a mega-event. Understanding the calculation errors requires both considerable expertise and a will to get it right. Double-counting or other types of overestimation may be in the interest of policymakers, especially a posteriori. Even in cases where the policymakers are not trying to deceive anyone, they may not ask many questions about a positive result (Abelson, 2011). Lowes (2004) warns against the double counting of event hosts to inflate negative economic numbers into positives. Whitson and Horne's seminal work includes an article which cuts straight to the chase: *Underestimated Costs and Overestimated Benefits? Comparing the Outcomes of Sports Mega-Events in Canada and Japan* (2017). In these publications, bidders are warned not to make the mistake of underestimating the risks just because the gains may be positive (but again – even positive results and success stories may also be blown out of proportion). On the other hand, an evaluation bordering on insincerity may keep the partnership together, paradoxically creating a better result because of co-operation through bidding, possible hosting, and legacy programmes. These over-estimations constitute one of the many specific problems and disruptions relating to bidding for major events. The next section looks at the negative aspects of bidding processes.

3.3.1 Leverage or legacy?

The two main tools for creating value outside the runtime of the festival are legacy and leverage. Legacy can broadly be understood as any permanent change or continued efforts (legacy programmes) by the event organisers beyond the runtime of the events. Getz (1991:340) defines it as: "The physical, financial, psychological, or social benefits that are permanently bestowed on a community or region by virtue of hosting an event. The term can also be used to describe the negative impact, such as debt, displacement of people, pollution, and so on". Leverage is instead "activities and initiatives aligned to but outside the normal running of an event that results in one-off or longer-term benefits" (Sport New Zealand, 2023). It hopes to make the event act as a lever for other sectors. These are not

clear cut: legacy will often be part of creating leverage, and they are not necessarily mutually exclusive.

Kassens-Noor et al. (2015) discuss the different types of legacies of a (mega-)event as depending on whether the event was hosted or a lost bid and whether the strategies put in place for renewal were part of older programmes. Legacies have different outcomes depending on strategies, reasons for bidding, and bid success. When legacies are intended to revitalise an urban environment, it may have baggage from previous policies and strategies. These capabilities for legacy completion are closely monitored by the designation owner and become part of the decision made about whose bid wins (Kassens-Noor et al., 2015). It is typical that legacy covers a wide range of policy areas, or at least policy areas which are not related to the sports-culture-tourism sectors which are central to its operation. Transport infrastructure is typical for continued efforts even after the event, but also wider urban development, heritage development, and social gains (Kassens-Noor et al., 2018; Chalip, 2006; DCMS, 2021).

Considering the brief definition above, leverage could be confused with outcomes. Chalip (2006) provides a differentiation: outcomes are aimed at “event evaluation”, has an “*ex post*” (italics in original) focus, and treats the event “in isolation”. Leverage relates to “strategies (and tactics)”, analyses events “with reference to destination product and service mix” and has an “*ex ante*” focus. Leverage is the conscious action of using resources to work toward an increased result. Typically, it includes both policy and economic features: Chalip and Heere (2013) divides economic leverage into “(a) enticing visitors to spend, (b) lengthening visitor stays (which also increases visitor spend), (c) minimizing the booth effect (i.e. keeping event expenditures in the local economy), and (d) using the event to foster business networking and enhance business relationships”. The UK are “using events as a strategy for leverage rather than one of asserting legacy, and they are using these to sustain communities, develop artists, and attract investment” in their mega event strategy (McGillivray & McPherson, 2015). The same shift towards creating a breadth of goods and supporting mechanisms creating multipliers, external effects, economic interest, and consensus building is echoed by Chalip (2017): “Strategic planning to combine an event into the mix of products and services at the host destination can enable leveraging tactics to

foster targeted economic and/or social benefits”. Chalip criticises the legacy model for its reliance on techniques without solid evidence supporting it.

The ‘legacy’ paradigm is being increasingly questioned by scholars warning that it may focus on the wrong values (Chalip & Heere, 2013; Chalip, 2017). Rather than seeing leverage and legacy as two faces of the same coin, they mean that strategic leverage has the potential to create real value, whereas legacy is a way of motivating any vaguely event-related intervention for a prolonged period. Leverage may be difficult to evidence; increased long-term spending, status, or international networks are difficult without robust difference-in-differences studies. However, legacy programmes may give a false sense of creating change because they keep bringing outcomes. A legacy programme is only as good as its opportunity cost.

Demonstrating how to deliver legacy and leverage are needed to win designations. Failed attempts to do so can result in crashing bids (Kassens-Noor, 2019). Chalip (2017) warns against the problems of an ambitious bid with ambiguous goals. A doctrine of promising everything for everyone: increased business, raised the profile of the city, investments in infrastructure, support to community organisations, and additional funding is a dangerous road; as Chalip notes, even allegedly successful host cities of winning bids have found that multipliers and business advantages do not meet the initial expectations. At the same time, offering nothing but blood, toil, tears, and sweat will likely not get relevant actors on board.

3.4 Problems and disruptions

The problems with bidding, though sometimes continuing into the execution of a winning, or the legacy of a losing bid, are to some degree unique to that process. Kassens-Noor (2019) discusses a list of problems arising during Boston’s bid for the 2024 Summer Olympics, specifically designed for transport infrastructure. It overlaps with several of the key publications in the area. Slightly modified for general use, with added references to relevant sources, it describes some common bidding problems:

1. High risk project (Torkildsen, 1993)
2. Complex issue, connecting many parts of society (Chalip, 2017)
3. Lacking prior knowledge
4. Challenges social consensus
5. Deadlines
6. External change (McGillivray & Turner, 2019)

The *high-risk* aspect pertains to the volatility of applying for a major event. It is uncertain whether the bidder will win the designation, which might be crucial for the expected positive effects to occur. Not winning might also stifle the ongoing leverage due to lost momentum. Investing in a bid might be a large loss of means and prestige if the bid does not take off (even long before the designation is made).

The bidding process is *complex*, with expectations and the need for deliberate designs in a range of policy/business areas over a long time including bidding, execution, and legacy (Chalip, 2017). Actors across the private, public, and non-profit sectors need to display some degree of previously mentioned consensus. If the common investment of time, prestige, and resources falters, it may have dire consequences not just for getting the designation, but also the potential legacies of a losing bid (Kassens-Noor, 2019).

Lacking prior knowledge is partially poor understanding of what is deliverable, leading up to disappointment or disillusion. As Stewart and Rayner (2016) put it: “Bid documents often lack specificity about the details of the legacy benefits, framing them in ways that are vague and encompassing without clear strategies to achieve the proposed benefits.” Lacking prior knowledge is also a lack of experience in carrying out large-scale events. Springer has published a series of books on mega-event planning (Springer, 2021) and OECD has published a series of encouraging reports (OECD, 2019). These were in part initiatives to improve policy by reducing the number of localities making use of non-evidence-based or strongly criticised policymaking; a discussion on non-evidence-based culture-led regeneration techniques can be found in Chapter 2. Unless a city has bid for a mega-event before, several challenges do not have ready-made solutions for the administration

(Kassens-Noor, 2019).

Though consensus was discussed above, *social consensus* might be a separate issue: the will of people living in the bidding city or nation. Negative effects may be published in the news, causing protests already during the bidding. This may lead to confidence problems, or even cancelled bids (Paulsson & Alm, 2020). In the case of Boston's 2024 bid, which Kassens-Noor's typology was based on, it did indeed lead to protests, both directly related to the Olympics and other issues, where the Olympic bid worked as a lever (Kassens-Noor et al., 2019). The problems may grow if the event ambitions are enforced with violence and repression, such as the Rio de Janeiro protests around the 2016 Olympics, which also included LGBT and other social protests (Talbot & Carter, 2020). It also relates to conflicts between stakeholders. Conflicts of interest may arise from the different goals of designating authorities and hosts. Evans (2011, citing Boyko, 2002) shows how this can play out in the regeneration-centred expectations of ECoC: "For instance in Bruges where a clear conflict emerged between resident and tourist identification with its historic character - the very reasons CoC and hallmark event status was granted in the first place - and the bid organiser's motivation to change the image and cultural profile of the city as a competitive contemporary place".

Deadlines are tight in major events. Though they are announced years in advance, in the case of Qatar 2022, twelve years(!). But even with a four-to-six-year schedule, major infrastructure will have to begin before the designation is made (Kassens-Noor, 2019). This is indeed regularly a part of the plan, to have large projects already underway in the case of a losing bid (OECD, 2019). Chalip (2006) mentions the problematic Montréal Olympics, with an unfinished tower of the Olympic stadium. These deadlines may be deterring to bid support and functionality: a 'we will not make it in time' factor.

The changing environment is a broad variable, from political shifts (including a new administration), global economic fluctuations (Osborn & Kirkup, 2008), or change in opinions about the destination or event. Calculations of the effects of events tend to be overly optimistic "best-case" scenarios with generous multipliers (Mules & Dwyer, 2005). Chalip (2017) goes as far as saying that "when economic estimates are considered afterwards, the

data suggest little or no economic gain, particularly for mega events". If the changing environment gives an indication already during the bidding process, actors may retract support, or budget planning may break apart.

These six categories (adapted from Kassens-Noor's original seven) are problems seen specifically in the bidding process of major events because of their unique need to allure both the general public and community actors engaged, keep cooperation and investment from the private sector, and the public sector's both executive and political branches interested. And in timelines spanning over a decade from inception to event hosting, it is not surprising that the bidding and preparation processes sometimes break down. This general typology can be complemented with some specific issues, including a developed discussion about external problems (which is more elusive than primarily local problems) below.

3.4.1 'White Elephants'

A crucial commitment of mega-event bids, even for large cities, is the overexertion of funds; promising too much whilst getting the designation and having to deliver. This includes the building of venues for sport, culture, or trade exhibitions, as well as transport infrastructure, typically very expensive (and deadline-critical) ventures. These are not just costly but may take up large, attractive inner-city public spaces which turn into exclusively event-related zones, though it opens a potential for a culture/sports event district afterwards (Silk, 2014).

The need to find good use for the infrastructure may be a key problem; not all cities host a thriving events programme with tens of thousands of visitors coming often enough to motivate a range of tens-of-thousands capacity venues. The legacy of the events may be heavily impacted by the ability to make use of the infrastructure already paid for: Kasimati (2015) describes the inability to make use of the 2004 Olympics' investments as a great inhibitor to reaching a positive bottom line for the event. Atkinson et al. (2008) discuss the feasibility of discussing a price tag on hosting the events considering that the planning for legacy is so central to the actual benefits. Their examples include the 2000 Sydney Olympics, where many of the facilities had already fallen into disuse a few years after the games. Toohey (2008) describes "Future Olympic city hosts be warned. Despite the stunning sell-out

success of the 2000 Games' Sydney's \$200 million Olympic Stadium is shaping up as a white elephant of mammoth proportions. And the other sports venues and facilities at Olympic Park are not doing much better.”

Already in 2000, the investments in Sydney were branded as a ‘white elephant’; costly, unnecessary, and of little use (Burton, 2000). However, the term was used to describe the games as early as the 1908 London Olympics in a research publication by Cameron (1909). Such cautionary tales contribute to the understanding that winning a major event is not enough for a positive bottom line. Instead, an active, planned legacy is needed from early in the bidding process. Paired with the lessons from bad will surrounding the construction work (such as preparations for Montréal 1959 and Qatar 2022), the current guidelines, such as the previously discussed OECD (2019) ones, include ambitious planning of the whole process from announcement through many years after the event’s actual runtime. With lacking focus on leverage, in Chalip’s and Heere’s (2013) sense, the strategic goals may well break down into what could be understood locally as a failed gamble.

Not just venues may suffer from this, but also other infrastructural changes, over-dimensioned for continued use. Matheson (2012) mentions two luxury hotels built for the 1994 Olympics in Lillehammer, which were out of business shortly after the Olympics. Müller (2015) discusses oversized airport terminals built specifically for major events but with anticipated general growth; the expected long-term influx of business and tourism failed to appear.

3.4.2 Global changes

The time between a city showing initial interest in a mega-event and the actual hosting of it is several years. Some mega-events, such as the Olympics and the FIFA Men’s World Cup may be announced in pairs, such as the 2018 and 2022 WC announced in 2010, and the 2024 and 2028 Summer Olympics announced (International Olympic Committee, 2022; FIFA, 2010). The Qatar 2022 bid was officially announced in early 2009, almost 14 years before the world cup took place.

These time frames and investments are comparable in size to other public projects, which also makes them susceptible to changes in society. The UK minister for Olympics, Tessa Jowell, famously said in 2018 'Had we known what we know now, would we have bid for the Olympics? Almost certainly not' (Osborne & Kirkup, 2008). The comment referred to the then-ongoing economic crisis. The same problems were underlined during the covid-19 pandemic: the Dubai 2020 expo, the Tokyo Winter Olympics, the Beijing 2022 Winter Olympics, and indeed the 2021 UK City of Culture in Coventry were all heavily affected by the pandemic, and it is not unlikely that high ranking officials have said, or at least thought, the same thing Jowell did (Zhang et al., 2022; Aytug et al., 2022).

It is not unlikely that disruptive world or regional events will take place during the 10-or-so years from instigation until the event is hosted. Thus, global changes and instabilities need to be part of the calculated risk. With insufficient consideration taken, the event and its legacy may be tarnished. The 2016 Rio de Janeiro faced human rights protests on-site (with brutal police response), but also international public health experts criticising the decision not to postpone the games despite a Zika virus pandemic (Talbot & Carter, 2018; Xu et al., 2021).

High-profile events are so intensively covered by media that both positive and negative occurrences will be noticed; problems and disruptions will be part of any major event. As a simple example of the extent, the Wikipedia page for "Concerns and controversies at the 2020 Summer Olympics" lists over 100 incidents, and references over 300 sources (2022). During the timespan between the instigation of a bidding process and the ending of the last legacy programme, there will be disruptions, global changes, crises, and controversies. Failure to handle this may cause the issues mentioned previously: bankruptcy, retracted bids, bad will, dwindling diplomatic relations, corruption, protests, boycotts, or failed legacies.

3.4.3 Corruption and problematic designations

Nunkoo et al. (2018) discuss how a large number of stakeholders and the huge increase in resources available during a mega-event project have a high risk of increasing corruption. Observed in several of the major event organisations such as FIFA and IOC as discussed

below, it has tarnished the status of these, as well as the bidding cities.

The most conspicuous examples of the last years include the 2015 FIFA scandal where representatives of the executive committee were charged with corruption charges; fraud and money laundering. Rowe (2017) notes that whilst the major sports world is ridden with “spousal abuse, performance/image enhancing and recreational drug use, public intoxication, match-fixing, corruption, marital infidelity, sexual and racial discrimination”, these types of ‘scandals’ are of another type altogether than corruption. Individuals lacking moral fibre is less relevant as an object of study in terms of event evaluation. Jennings (2011) lists some of the requests from some IOC officials: “Cash. Sex. College places for the kids. Hip replacement operations. Cosmetic surgery. And – yes, really – one visiting party of IOC members demanded, and got, a violin, piles of Viagra and a vibrator!”

Chalip (2017) evaluates a range of studies, concluding that “public support, stakeholder management, the quality of the bid committee, and the overall quality of the event plan each contribute to a successful bid”. At the same time, he notes that there is a strong correlation between spending the most money and the bid winning the designation. This could be due to several reasons, but the expensive bids are more prone to offer luxurious conditions for officials, as seen above.

Corruption has a long history in sports and events, but the ever-increasing economic dimension inflates the problems. This is flamboyantly summed up by Fotheringham: “There’s a myth growing, on this Olympic mess, that it all started with the tacky, overcommercialised Summer Games in Atlanta. Which led to all the bribes and greed of Salt Lake City. It’s a nice myth, but it’s wrong. The real sleaze got its start with Jean Drapeau and the 1976 Olympic Games in Montreal. There was the blueprint for corruption.”

(Fotheringham, 1999). Indeed, the Montréal Olympics were problematic; as mentioned in Chapter 3, they are the first well-studied example of the prevailing urban regeneration through the events paradigm. At the same time, they were an early and clear example of where poor planning and corruption severely affected the city, long term. Observed in the IOC as well, the most highly publicised case has been around FIFA, with resulting scandals and resignations (Rowe, 2017). Direct payments or promises of advantages have shaped the

bidding processes, mirroring the extremely high stakes associated with the investment and prestige put into a bid for a global event.

The corruption may be exacerbated by the spending in bids, which have grown to very high levels. Chalip and Heere (2013) have shown how the city spending the most on their bid will likely win the event designation. Though not outright corruption, it might be an alarming insight that 'buying' winning designations is the standard *modus operandi*. A higher spend will mean a more ambitious bid presentation but might also compromise the actual qualities needed to host mega-events.

Having covered the anticipated outcomes and problems with bidding for major events, the focus turns to the specific events and event scenes relevant to this study. These problems and expectations are recurring themes in discussions on major events in the UK, which will be revisited in the analysis.

3.5 UK City of Culture

The major event UK City of Culture has been hosted since 2013, instigated immediately after, and because of, the success of Liverpool'08 (UK Government 2010). The intention was to create a regional version of the European Capital of Culture, organised by the European Union. The same thing has been done (with less success) in other parts of the world, including Capital of Islamic Culture (Kherbouche & Djedid, 2019) and Capital of Arab Culture, which is supported by Unesco (Unesco, 2009). These designations do not have an open bidding process and do not typically present individual websites for their designations. The American Capital of Culture (The American Capital of Culture, 2023) has a similar layout: though backed by the Organisation of American States, it does not have its own website, and the 2023 winner Aguascalientes in Mexico does not communicate publicly about the designation. UK City of culture is thus the closest counterpart of European capital of culture. In recent years, ECoC has been moving towards smaller cities and towns, whilst at the same time increasing the number of cities from the original one to two or three capitals of culture each year. UKCoC is hosted every four years, in a single city. The shortlisted and winning

cities have, to a large majority, been mid-sized cities between 150,000 and 400,000 inhabitants. So far (including 2025), three cities in England and one city in Northern Ireland have hosted the UKCoC. Paisley and Dundee are so far the only Scottish shortlisted cities (in the case of Paisley; town). The designation is increasingly popular, with 20 bidding cities for the 2025 designation (UK Government, 2022).

The bidding processes are open and in some cases highly publicised. The concept is designed to boost urban regeneration, culture, and local business; this is mentioned as a *primus motor* for the UKCoC project (Department for Culture Media & Sport 2017). The contained size of shortlisted cities, the open process, and the design of the bidding process all contribute to the idea of an urban regeneration event. The apparent preference for mid-sized cities seems to argue that a cultural festival of this size – large for the city but hardly on a global scale – will provide the best boost to that type of city.

The UKCoC focuses on sustainable funding, existing and developing cultural assets, community values, and local pride. The language aligns well and covers a large amount of ground in relation to typologies of social and economic value at urban regeneration via events, such as the seminal work by Getz and others (Brown et al. 2015, Getz, 2004), Bianchini and Parkinson's discussion of cultural urban policy, and Smith's et al. (2021) six categories of social value for community events. The full breadth of economic, social, public, and urban regeneration values expressed by this press release is not often comprehensively covered by singular studies. Snowball's (2005) economic and social evaluations of events in South Africa and Báez and Herrero's (2012) discussion of social heritage values as quantifiable come close, and Lundberg's et al. (eds., 2017) book on the value of events looks at different events from a range of viewpoints.

UKCoC is a product not just of the European counterpart and the Liverpool success, but also the optimism surrounding UK culture-led urban regeneration after the 1990s successes of Glasgow (and Barcelona/Bilbao) discussed in the previous chapter. The bidding agenda is changing with time depending on what is politically attractive and research-based evidence. As the UKCoC is a relatively new concept, any history will suffer from the small *n* available;

but specificities can be highlighted, and the changing bidding process can demonstrate the changing political landscape of UK urban regeneration and culture policy.

In 2017, the event was hosted by Hull, being a uniquely relevant case in that it is the only UKCoC year not stifled by covid (Coventry 2021) or being a test or a pilot for a potential future permanence (Derry~Londonderry 2013), as well as the ongoing UKCoC when Paisley was bidding for 2021. The final evaluation report for Hull from University of Hull was co-authored by well-known scholars, with Franco Bianchini as the first author (University of Hull, 2021). They also commissioned a smaller evaluation based on the UK Green Book, thoroughly discussed in Chapter 4 of this study. Based to a great extent on the work of Fujiwara (2014) and O'Brien (2010), it remains the foremost tool for understanding the value of culture in the UK with economic quantification of cultural experiences, based on wellbeing economics.

The urban regeneration agenda is strong, especially in the growth-development-placemaking triad in the seven key areas. However, as seen above, the agenda contains a range of other goals too: social benefits and environmental sustainability are priorities not necessarily part of the communication about major events. These are novelties in the 2025 process, even compared to the 2021 application: the 2021 and previous applications were more rooted in classic culture-led regeneration language: a high-quality cultural programme, lasting social regeneration, demonstrable economic impact, maximising the legacy and evaluating the impacts, realistic and credible plans (UK Government 2017).

This demonstrates the political aspects of the UKCoC: it is meant to be a tool for the contemporary development of urban spaces. A stronger focus on demonstrable social and environmental effects appeared between 2017 and 2022. Liu's (2014) discussion about lessons learned, uses "sustainable development" from culture-led regeneration as a key theme, but interestingly, Liu is focusing on *cultural* sustainability. Though the climate-related understanding of sustainability is mentioned in passing, it is not analysed in the article. The decade which has passed since Liu wrote his article has brought climate to the top of the agenda, which is mirrored even in the basic requirements of bidding cities. In Hull, the 2017 UKCoC, the Hull City Council does mention environmental sustainability as part of their

preparations in 2016. Its sustainable profile can “reflect city living in Scandinavia and Northern Europe in a way that is not credible for any other UK city” (Hull City Council, 2016:7. Cited in University of Hull, 2021). Yet, in both evaluations and official communication, the sustainable profile is still a minor occurrence compared to other themes, two years after the Paris Accord.

3.6 Major events in Scotland

By attempting to attract large events, Scotland aspires to be an event nation, as some other smaller nations have managed to do before. An example of that would be Singapore, which attracted scholarly attention in the first decade of the millennium due to its allure as an event host (Foley et al., 2009). The Grand Prix (Wood & Thomas, 2009), several mid-to-large sized arts festivals (Chang & Mahadevan, 2014), and more locally tinted major festivals of food and culture (Matheson et al., 2006) all contributed to making Singapore into “the events and entertainment Capital of Asia” (Foley et al., 2009). This attractiveness made Singapore transcend the regular dynamic of proactively attracting festivals, instead being able to pick and choose what events they wanted to host which fit their profile.

Scotland hosts a range of mid-to-major events; each year sees some peripatetic event in Scotland – in 2023 it is the UCI Cycling World Championships, projected to attract one million mostly local spectators and up to 200 million viewers remotely (Visit Scotland, 2023). This event would score towards the higher end of a major event though safely below mega-event according to Müllers (2015) scoring method discussed above: all four operationalised criteria (visitor attractiveness, media reach, cost, and transformation budget) are below the mega-event level. Scotland is also hosting several events which are fitting Scotland’s profile and international reputation well; Orkney is hosting the 2025 Island Games (an alternative ‘Olympics’ competition specifically for islands and Island nations), and 2024 sees the AIG Women’s Open in St. Andrews, one of the largest women’s golf majors. The Edinburgh Fringe is another large event, and as customary for cultural events, it has fewer of the typical mega-event features of the bidding process, central venue, peripatetic structure, and strict safeguarding of licensing.

3.6.1 Government support of events in Scotland

Scotland's event agency EventScotland, a part of the tourist agency Visit Scotland sports the slogan "Scotland: The Perfect Stage". Their stake in the bidding games of major events is considerable, providing guidance, workshops, and education for prospective bidders (Visit Scotland, 2015). McGillivray and Turner (2017:41) describe this action as a (deliberate or not) way of staying away from the "bid gurus" who are available for hire after having worked with a successful bid elsewhere. Instead, keeping a long-term body of knowledge with national and public competencies in terms of major events has been the idea. These capacities come to use in a range of events in Scotland each year, hosting peripatetic events of different sizes. The Scottish government offers funds to aspiring event hosts, with the same types of expectations seen in the events strategy and public communication. Their grants require applications to demonstrate how they will:

- "Generate substantial economic benefits for Scotland through increased visitation including tourists, spectators, and participants
 - Highlight Scotland as an events and tourism destination through high-profile, international media coverage
 - Enhance Scotland's opportunities to host further major events"
- (Scottish Government, 2023)

It is noteworthy that social benefits are less prominent in the must-have requirements, whereas they are flaunted in the full text. Indeed, the events strategy notes there are still gaps in the knowledge: "There is a need for research into the long-term personal, social and cultural impacts of event attendance, participation and organisation" (Scottish Government, 2015).

Most of the major and mid-sized international events hosted in Scotland are not selected by an open process, but rather by an executive committee. Still, support from the public agencies is provided and bids are followed closely as "We must also build upon the good

work of the EventScotland team and partners in bidding for major events and upon our iconic signature events” (Visit Scotland, 2015). One of the 2015-2025 Scotland events strategy’s key messages in how to deliver events is propagating a *partnership approach* (Visit Scotland, 2015). Collaboration and keeping a unified idea are indeed a crucial part of a successful bid, as expressed above.

The public organisations in charge of a bid regularly invite private sector organisations and NGOs to different types of cooperation; the Scottish events strategy and OECD (2019) encourage this leverage approach. Failed partnership funding models may result in an excessive final bill for the taxpayers of the host city, such as in the Montréal near-bankruptcy and the Nagano Winter Olympics, leaving the city £20,000 in debt per Nagano household (Emery, 2002).

3.7 Summary

This chapter presents the literature on bidding for major events. The Paisley public events programme, as it presented itself during the studied period, was essentially a tool to showcase event capabilities for the UKCoC 2021 bid. Thus, the expected return on investment, the design of those events, and the event evaluation were all aimed at a greater end. Similarly, the UKCoC was wholly considered to be a major event, with mega-event methodology and motivations. This is discussed thoroughly in the analysis. The summary includes key concepts from Table 1 in italics.

The process of selecting host cities for large peripatetic events may use an open call for bids (McGillivray & Turner, 2017:2). This is not least true for mega-events, a contested concept where Müller’s (2018) definition based on visitor attractiveness, cost, reach, and urban transformation has been used here. This disqualifies several national and international events which still may aspire for great impact or be costly, major events. Each stage of a major event is the subject of elaborate design, and bidding (Getz, 2004), runtime (Jones, 2020), and aftermath (Chalip & Heere, 2013) are all subjects of investment, development, and scholarly inquiry.

Bidding may open policy windows for great change, and OECD (2019) guidelines state that even losing bids may create great momentum for local businesses, one of the reasons that ‘underdogs’ choose to bid for major events. Similarly, the legacy (continued event-related programmes post-runtime) and leverage (external effects created beyond the scope of the direct event-related transactions) have been lauded as the major effects of events. This should be treated with caution, as the methodologies used to evaluate legacy and leverage are not always robust and may overstate positive effects to portray the event as a positive intervention (Chalip & Heere, 2013). Even potentially positive value may be problematic due to structural problems; underuse of built facilities, unstable global economy, or funds leaking into corruption (Kasimati, 2015; Zhang et al., 2022; Rowe, 2017).

The UK City of Culture was created with bidding underdogs, leverage, and culture-led urban regeneration in mind (University of Hull, 2021). Led by the UK government’s penchant for the success of Liverpool’s ECoC in 2008, the regenerative potential created incentives for a local version (Gonzalez, 2010).

These problems with evaluation make bidding for a major event a spurious venture without the right expertise. The tools at the disposal of event evaluators are described in the next chapter: the good, the bad, and the potential areas of development.

4 Event economics and public project evaluation

This chapter provides an overview of evaluation techniques used for public interventions in the culture sector, specifically events. Brown et al. (2015:136) state that “Despite recognition of evaluation’s vital role in policymaking, managerial improvement, and event design, it has been a minor theme in the literature on planned events.” In the time since 2015, the literature has grown but still mirrors the limited understanding of the values created, especially in the areas not directly relating to the economy (Mair et al., 2021). This chapter lays out the mainstream approaches of Economic Impact Analysis and cost-benefit analysis, as well as presenting social value methods and their backgrounds. These methods and insights are then used as theoretical underpinnings to answer research objectives 1 and 2.

Cost-benefit analysis is a method based on economics, with tools fitted for economic and quantitative measurement, as well as a focus on monetary values. By contrast, social value is primarily used by other social scientists and humanities scholars, developed by psychologists (Hartley et al., 2017), sociologists (Vanclay, 2003), political scientists (Beck Jørgensen & Bozeman, 2015), but also economists (Stiglitz et al., 2009; Meynhardt, 2009), as well as interdisciplinary scholars such as Kahneman et al. (1999). This means that the tools for those types of value are better fitted for their corresponding academic disciplines. This study suggests that these models are complementary and that a strong understanding of value creation related to culture will likely use some concept of both economic and non-economic evaluation.

To some extent (and to a varying degree), the focus on social and public value is developed in opposition to the extensive measurability of New Public Management and the ideology underpinning its extensive use throughout the public sector (Conolly & van der Zwet, 2021). Several features are shared between NPM and CBA: strong quantification, private sector tools for public sector use, the risk of understating human wellbeing and suffering, and a rise during the 1980s and 1990s (Sager & Sørensen, 1998; Bronsteen et al., 2013). The innate conflict between these perspectives complicates joint use. As will be demonstrated, a large portion of social value metrics are considered impossible or too unreliable to measure by

CBA theorists. Thus, the two perspectives of public/social value and quantitatively demonstrable CBA may share only a small overlap. The attempts to make use of these different methods for evaluating culture are discussed in this chapter.

The chapter will start by discussing event evaluation in general, and then go through the economic perspectives starting with cost-benefit methodology, the most popular evaluation method for large events, and its underpinnings. Then follows a presentation of economic impact analysis, the most popular evaluation method for small-to-medium events. Their use, the way they understand and calculate value, and controversies are all covered. After that, social value is presented separately. The chapter ends with a section on UK evaluation methods for events, public interventions, and social value. These policies shape event evaluation in Scotland in both explicit and implicit ways.

4.1 Event economics

Until the second half of the 20th century, hosting large events was seen as a way of showcasing technological, athletic, and artistic capacity, as well as displaying ideological ideas of rationalism and national pride (Roche, 2002). Nowadays, the focus on economic, and increasingly also social benefits has grown into the foremost argument for hosting large events, even though the reputation of the city remains important (Herrero et al., 2016). Events may have the positive effects of gathering interest, investment, and increased local economic momentum, and hopeful event organisers may want to turn the inevitable expenses of a large-scale event into a profit. Major events, typically ambulating and recurring (McGillivray & Turner, 2017:13), require great financial outtakes financed by common stakes from all sectors of society and loans or redirection of money. Global events are amongst the largest infrastructural projects countries typically take on: Müller (2015) calculates that the mean cost for hosting a mega-event is 18 billion USD and that one cycle of his studied mega-events costs 163 billion USD, a figure rising with each passing cycle. By contrast, community events are habitually organised on shoestring budgets, the work, effort, and in-kind resources might still be significant, especially if translated into worked hours. With this breadth, different perspectives on evaluation will fit different needs.

Event evaluation as an academic field of study is changing. Traditionally, the evaluations have been primarily focused on very large events, for several reasons. One, it is worthwhile putting in the resources needed to evaluate, and often create a purpose-made scheme for the evaluation. Two, a large event is possible to study from a multitude of angles, making it attractive for a greater number of scholars. And thirdly, the best methods for public interventions were fitted for large projects, such as cost-benefit analysis. The main alternative to CBA, economic impact analysis (also known as input-output analysis), with a more limited scope, is presented further down in this chapter.

4.2 Cost-benefit analysis

Originally designed for large public projects in physical infrastructure (Dasgupta & Pearce 1972:12), cost-benefit analysis is now used in a variety of applications, including private companies, NGOs, and smaller applications (Burgan & Mules 2001). It is quite likely the most popular method of structured evaluation of public projects around the world, which not least grew out of Ronald Reagan's policy that federal projects with revenues over \$100m invariably needed to perform a CBA, typically before the initiation of the project. For other applications, a similar methodology can be used for a *post hoc* evaluation: King et al. (1978) noted three uses of CBA: A planning tool, an after-the-fact evaluation tool, and a political tool for giving scientific weight to an argument.

CBA is a tool intended to account for all positive and negative effects of a project, compared to other alternatives and a status quo (Boardman et al. 2018:29). This is achieved by calculating an economic value, positive or negative, on every anticipated effect of the project. If the beneficial values outweigh the costs, the project should be initiated. The status quo is represented by a null hypothesis – the 'no intervention' alternative. In large-scale infrastructural CBA, it is common practice to look at several alternatives, calculate all costs and benefits, and recommend the alternative with the best result.

Human utility is estimated and then priced according to models accounting for the lack of

market behaviour. These non-market behaviours are calculated by two main methods: revealed preference and stated preference. Revealed preference is calculated by aggregating existent data on behaviour such as consumption, travel, or attendance (Mishan & Quah, 2020:175). Weights are put on these behaviours, calculating the preference of each individual. Stated preference is any method in a CBA where the evaluated individual is asked what their preference is. Samuelson (1948) noted that the majority of consumer theory was based on revealed preference methods, due to its higher validity: consumption is measured in practice and can thus reliably be used as indicators for consumption in similar settings. The problems are comparatively small depending on the setting; erroneous public statistics (such as the black market), extrapolation of data (to other people, times, or sectors; Grüne, 2004), and market failures not visible in the statistics. Stated preference will typically be more confined and less theory-building (as per Samuelson above; 1948) but can gauge preferences in areas where no market behaviour is possible to observe, or crosstab consumer data with other questions. These, like all aspects of CBA, are the subject of scholarly contestation and have their advantages and disadvantages.

Instead of calculating all values, CBA aims to find out how well the costs will solve the main task; how many litres of water will be treated each year by a plant, and what each litre will cost (Mishan & Quah, 2007). It does not extend to including externalities or studying consumer behaviour beyond the main usage of the goods produced. This makes it fitting for medium-sized infrastructural projects, but problematic for goods where the outcomes are diverse and a matter of debate; few events use it.

4.2.1 Welfare economics

The field of Cost-Benefit Analysis arises out of welfare economics, which is a branch of economics engaged in evaluating the preferences, *utility*, of humans on a society-wide level. This, in turn, is derived from the work of Italian economist Vilfredo Pareto. According to his model, it is desirable to strive for *Pareto optimality* through *Pareto improvements* (Dasgupta & Pearce 1972:54). Pareto improvement is a change where some people are better off than before the intervention, whilst no one may be worse off. For example, creating an efficiency boost in a business and creating more output without a cost could likely be regarded as a

strict Pareto improvement. In turn, the Pareto optimal situation is where no Pareto improvements can occur in the current setup. The strict Pareto model had to be modified to get wide social applications and account for external effects: policymaking will be difficult when no one can be worse off ever (Dasgupta & Pearce, 1972).

The most important modification for the development of CBA is the Kaldor-Hicks criterion: an intervention is an improvement if everyone could *potentially* (but not necessarily) be compensated for the loss suffered in the intervention, whilst still leaving at least one person better off than before (Adler & Posner, 2009:27). Hicks (1939) presented the concept of *compensating variation* to explain the adjustment in income needed to compensate a consumer after prices change: if it is positive, the consumer is worse off after the price changes. Conversely, *equivalent variation* is the amount of additional income which would have the same utility effect as a change in prices¹. Mishan (1971) gives the example of a non-smoking department on a train. Who should compensate whom? If the smoker compensates, it is called Compensating Variation (for the lost utility to the non-smoker). If it is the non-smoker, it is Equivalent Variation (for the lost utility to the smoker). See Table 1 for relation to WTP/WTA. The best Pareto outcome depends on which of these is lower.

Table 2. WTP/WTA in relation to compensating/equivalent valuation. Source: Mishan, 1971:125

	Smoker	Non-smoker
Permissive rule Equivalent variation	Willingness to Accept compensation for forgoing the right to smoke	Willingness to Pay for the benefits of a smoke-free journey
Restrictive rule: Compensating variation	Willingness to Pay for the right to smoke	Willingness to Accept compensation for foregoing the right to fresh air

The Kaldor-Hicks model can be used to derive a *social welfare function*, which ranks different situations as better, worse, or indifferent aggregated preferences. These situations are based

¹ That is, CV looks at the ‘after a price change occurs’ compensation, and EV ‘if a price change should occur’ compensation.

on *individual utility functions*, that is, how a person's wellbeing is affected. Furthermore, the utility functions are assumed to be *ordinal* rather than *cardinal*, i.e. an individual can rank their preferences, but cannot compare them to others' in a 'utility points' calculation. Even though cardinal utility is still used by some (Köbberling, 2006), it is considered to have a low validity for evaluation purposes; creating methods to get closer to cardinal utility with ordinal means has been part of the economic literature at least since Baumol (1958). In the ordinal application, an individual can only prefer or not prefer two alternatives, without a real possibility of discerning how *much* better or worse off this makes them on a graded scale.

Cost-benefit analysis makes use of a range of tools, some described below, to convert ordinal data into quantifiable terms: Nyborg (2012) discusses how aggregating willingness to pay/willingness to accept can create a Pareto welfare function without individual levels of utility, but simply telling us whether people are better or worse off. By measuring such preferences and tethering them to monetary values via some framework (e.g. cost-benefit analysis), one can gauge utility with monetary figures as a proxy, without needing to accept cardinal measurements. This is susceptible to several types of critique, discussed below. To be able to trust the individual statement of their utility, and the basic ordinal ranking of choices, there is an assumption that *information* and *transitivity* are necessary, i.e. the ability to make an informed and ranked choice about one's wellbeing.

4.2.2 Opportunity cost

Policymakers will face many, and competing, suggestions for the usage of public means. Some of these are already based on a general knowledge of what the resources will result in – such as evaluating different bids for a commissioned building. Others are much wider: what should public means be used for? Local policymakers have some autonomy in the decision but will often need guidance from experts calculating the effects of different scenarios. The difference between the cost of a good or service and the best possible alternative is called *opportunity cost*.

The concept of opportunity cost is important in choosing the best possible way of spending

public resources. Considering all alternatives, the cost of choosing an alternative as opposed to another becomes visible. CBA alternatives are presented in a way that makes opportunity costs apparent: a simple sum of costs and benefits.

Typically, in cost-benefit analysis, the projects are long-term public investments. In public projects, spending is needed in advance, or over a long period. An important consideration is thus how value changes over time. As such, a *rate of discount* must be taken into consideration. A pound tomorrow is worth less than today due to interest, inflation, value depreciation, obsolescence, economic growth, and opportunity cost of investment. The social rate of discount, that is, the rate of value depreciation each year is standardised at 3.5 % for UK public sector investments unless further inquiry decides otherwise for the specific project (HM Treasury, 2023).

The transient nature of events also makes the calculation of continued utility more difficult, even though it exists in the shape of leverage, legacy, and economic multipliers (see more below; Chalip and Heere, 2013; HM Treasury, 2022). These are contested and long-term value is poorly understood. Major events have short-term runtimes, despite long-lasting bidding processes, preparations, and legacies. This makes interventions much more concentrated around a short period compared to a typical infrastructural project. The infrastructural *aspects* of a major event, such as venue building and transport are projects with discount rates at the heart of evaluation, including long-term environmental consequences (Cabral & Silva Jr, 2013). That type of evaluation will typically have a different scope than for example social value studies of direct event projects, or indirect legacy effects.

4.2.3 Evaluation in CBA

Many tools are used to quantify event value and to get a full picture, several will likely be needed. A basic understanding of what alternatives are available must be compared to a so-called null hypothesis, the assumption that no intervention will yield the best effect. This is known as a *counterfactual*, calculating the value of both no intervention and viable interventions. In any project where all other alternatives result in less value than the

counterfactual, no intervention is done.

The final product of a social CBA can be presented in several ways, though a popular way is displaying a Net Present Value (NPV) figure. This is calculated by subtracting costs from benefits, adding the value created over time, but taking the project rate of discount and inflation into account. The NPV neatly presents as the value of a project, from the horizon of the present. Net present value is typically presented similarly to equation 1 (Beaves, 1993).

The net present value of an intervention is equal to:

$$\sum_{t=0}^n \frac{a_t}{(1+k)^t} \quad (1)$$

Where

t is a period, e.g. a year.

n is the amount of time units which the project will consider as relevant (e.g. before obsolescence)

a_t is the value change during the period t

k is the discount rate; a percentage per time unit (3.5 % per year in UK public sector)

In the simplest form of decision-making, and the classic criterion of a CBA, any project with a positive NPV should be undertaken (Remer & Nieto 1995). The underlying assumption is that any problems arising from the execution of too many projects (such as high-interest payments of loans or restriction of economic activity due to high taxes or displacement of private investment) will show up as sufficiently big counterweights in the “cost” category, giving a negative NPV. In a properly executed CBA, better opportunity cost projects will be listed, and chosen anyway. There are policies delimiting areas of public intervention, different ideas of risk management, ideological ideas about what should be publicly funded and not, and an analysis tool capable of unequivocally deciding what level of public investment is Right does not exist. CBA cannot decide the tax rate, being a microeconomic model (Borge & Rattsø 1995). Ideological opinions and behaviour of voters also restrict the possible options of public expenditure, despite local government being a main actor in

public projects on culture (Benito et al. 2012). Taking into account the social effects of changing whole areas of policy is beyond the scope of realistic CBA (intangible effects and/or externalities, see below), and thus there is a certain degree of limits to policymakers asking for CBA analysis.

Whilst different understandings of value may cause controversy, there are tools in CBA created to manage the types of value not easily captured by standard economic models of market transactions. Goods not supplied on a market, but rather by other means, so-called *nonmarket goods* also need to be understood. In the case of public events, they may be free of charge, thus moving tickets – typically the largest single expense – from market to nonmarket goods.

4.2.4 Limited information

The basic microeconomic models define demand, indifference, and surplus from consumer (and producer) behaviour in an open market. When evaluating public sector goods, that is far from always possible. Most of the public sector's work is not reliably comparable to market conditions, though exceptions exist (some major events would fit the description). One of the key problems CBA solves is to make non-market goods comparable to market goods.

Non-market goods denote the broad category of goods not offered on an open market (Hanley, 1989). It includes such diverging things as unpaid household labour, public transport, and a good environment (Costa & Kahn 2003). In CBA, it typically means values created by public sector organisations not active in a competitive market. In addition to tangible things such as child-rearing or a nearby nature reserve, non-market goods also include intangible and difficult-to-define values such as admiration by others, prestige, sense of community, and social capital (Orlowski & Wicker, 2019). Free-of-charge events are treated as non-market goods despite having possible competition from commercial interests; the behaviour of visiting the public event still needs non-market evaluation to be understood as there is no transaction. Many or even all the values created there may be

non-market goods due to free entrances, voluntary work, and public funding of additional features around the event.

When speaking about economic value, the *exchange* value refers to the worth or value of a commodity or good in terms of its ability to be exchanged for other goods or services. However, all value does not come from use or potential exchange. Instead, value exists in many forms, which is true not least in the case of culture and events. This is well-understood also by public providers of services (Bakshi et al., 2015). Use values can be divided into direct use – such as experiencing a performance, seeing a piece of art, or hearing a recording, and indirect use, for instance, culture’s bolstering effect on the renown of a place, or increased social interactions. Non-use values are those which are not directly linked to the person experiencing the value. It could be the positive sense related to knowing there is an opera scene in my country without using it or the knowledge that there are still white rhinos in the world without plans to visit them. Non-use and indirect use values are more unlikely to be bought on a market, though non-use values are not a subset of non-market goods or vice versa. They are not least important for personal values; Danish studies showed a remarkable willingness to pay for non-use of cultural and environmental goods even when other Danes experienced great use values from them (Lundhede et al., 2013). Andersson et al. (2012) calculate the non-use value of a music festival at roughly 30 % of the total value, including socio-cultural and environmental positive externalities.

Values which cannot be evaluated (or, more correctly, *are not* evaluated) by the techniques available in CBA are disregarded as *intangible* and do not constitute a part of the bottom line. These are invariably non-market goods (otherwise there would be a way to evaluate them) but may be non-use or use values. King et al. (1978) illustrate the CBA view on public goods: “Public agencies are primarily intended to render services. Their products, being intangible, cannot be precisely valued. How, for example, does one estimate the value of a community library service or the existence of a public park? Many of these services have no counterpart in the private sector: no surrogate can be used.” This naturally skews CB analyses towards favouring those projects which have high tangible values, whereas intangibles may be missed.

With a basic understanding of the value types discussed in CBA, it is possible to move on to the methods for dealing with non-market goods and non-use goods, and which goods are then left as intangible.

4.3 Cost-benefit evaluation methods

Cost-benefit analysis makes use of transactions on a market as well as non-market values. To understand the costs and benefits of non-market goods, the value of the utility created from an aspect of the intervention needs to be estimated. The utility can make use of several intermediaries to reach a plausible figure, without needing the problematic measurement of cardinal utility (Adler & Posner, 2009). By tethering the calculation in quality-adjusted life years (O'Brien, 2010), time spent or saved (Mishan & Quah, 2007:179), quantified subjective wellbeing (Fujiwara et al., 2014), or a combination thereof, utilities can be compared through the monetary value that these variables can be estimated at.

Infrastructural projects aim to save time, enable communications, or create a healthier environment. Cultural events do not. It is not always necessary to ask or survey the specifically affected individuals about the time gains for the daily commute; this can be calculated with the help of previous studies and some basic demographic data. In the case of events in sports and culture, it is important to understand either the spending patterns of offered goods (and thus revealing respondents' preferences), ask about attendees' (and non-attendees') preferences, or both. The methods most commonly used in event evaluation based on cost-benefit reasoning are presented here.

There are three branches of methods discussed: contingent valuation, hedonic valuation, and Input/Output (Economic Impact Analysis) evaluation. Contingent valuation is largely what has so far been called stated preference in this context: the utility experienced, whether concerning money or something else, by asking respondents what they think a good is worth, or what they would be willing to give up getting that good. This escapes cardinal utility calculations whilst still placing a direct economic value on a good or service (Adler & Posner, 2009). Hedonic valuation is a revealed preference method, where a good is

broken down into its different parts, evaluating them separately, and then adding the sums (Snowball, 2008:77). Not all goods can reliably be evaluated with the hedonic method due to unknown values or synergy effects. Those that can are effective in the sense that they track real-world behaviour which is considered more valid than experimental or stated behaviour. Finally, input-output (I/O) evaluation uses actual transactions, which do not need any conversion of value as all transactions occur with the same currency as the final product.

4.3.1 WTP/WTA – Willingness to pay/Willingness to accept

Calculating the economic costs of a public event program can be found in budget documents and thus be reported exactly, and values of increased revenue in stores can be estimated through surveys and interviews. A CBA considers individual, subjective preference in addition to public spending (Dasgupta & Pearce 1972:15). To achieve that, consumer surplus needs to be decided. Consumer surplus is the difference between what consumers are willing to pay for a good or service based on their shift in demand when prices change (demand elasticity) and what they pay in the market. It represents the value or benefit that consumers gain when they can purchase a good at a price lower than what they are willing to pay. The CS is expressed in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Consumer surplus in a supply-demand model.

This is generally done by finding out the additional consumer surplus of the project, not captured by observable economic transactions. By aggregating the maximum amount every customer would be willing to pay for a project's benefits, or the minimum amount they would be willing to accept for enduring the project's costs, the monetary value of a project's effects can be measured. This has grown to be an important way of measuring the value of cultural and sportive goods during the last decades (Atkinson et al., 2008). The strength lies not least in its capability to cover surplus value from goods that are not sold at a fully competitive market, or those that are free of charge.

Respondents' utility deriving from a public intervention can be expressed through conversion of expressed preference, and in this case, WTP/WTA becomes a shortcut: the respondent is asked for the monetary figure they place on the utility gain or loss themselves. Invented in the 1940s, WTP rose to prominence within environmental economics, with a range of studies in the 1970s and 1980s demonstrating that consumer behaviour could reliably be simulated by contingent questionnaires (Hanemann, 1991). In these applications, it is as relevant to ask what amount of money a consumer would be willing to *accept to not* get a good (Bredert, 2006). The latter is used for negative values; accepting that environmental values are compromised, or that a commute will be longer. The difference between WTP and WTA can be substantial, often three to five times WTP due to loss aversion (Adamowicz et al., 1993). Kahnemann (1999) has explored loss aversion in relation to happiness and utility, also showing how utility suffers from strong diminishing returns beyond a basic comfortable standard of living.

WTP may act as a substitute for revealed market behaviour (actual transactions or other actions), which has higher reliability (Nessim & Dodge, 1995:72). The WTP method can do more than study actual market behaviour: in an imagined WTP study with perfectly reliable results, complete price discrimination or the calculation of an ideal price for maximum income would be possible as it would reveal the full demand curve, not just extrapolated from small fluctuations in price and behaviour.

A consumer's willingness to pay is dependent on many of the other factors described in this

chapter: consumer surplus, the economic means of the individual, and indifference curves based on bundles. Accepting willingness-to-pay as a tool for the calculation of experienced value still opens for reliability problems. The most cited publication in this area is the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration's recommendations on how to perform contingent valuation (Arrow et al., 1993). A central recommendation from that study is to avoid the very direct question "What would you be willing to pay for this particular good/service?" with an open-ended reply. This may lead to a range of unwanted results, including protest zeroes (see below), replies based on very limited information, and high fluctuation due to the lack of a reference point (Arrow et al., 1993). The reliability of such surveys will be suffering. Breidert et al. (2006), the most cited overview of WTP in later years, calls it an "unnatural focus on price". The contingent valuation method is challenged as a whole: Diamond and Hausman (1994) rhetorically ask: "Is some number better than no number?" due to the problems with reliability and bias. A review from the US Environmental Protection Agency has shown that seemingly small changes in how questions are asked to provide very different results (EPA 1998).

When using indirect Willingness to Pay (WTP) methods, the calculations involved tend to be more complex, using empirical survival distribution functions (Báez & Herrero, 2012), linear and non-linear regression models (Breidert, 2006), logit models (Gensler et al., 2012), and discrete choice modelling. The use of some of these will be explored in the methods chapter. NOAA (Arrow et al., 1993) and Breidert et al. (2006) recommend the use of these more advanced WTP methods including bundled questions or dichotomous choice models.

Other WTP methods

Breidert et al. (2006) provide a typology for WTP methods, including advantages and disadvantages. The latter was quite helpful in the choice of methods for the latter part of this study. WTP is not necessarily contingent but can be based on market data. It is also possible to conduct *experiments*, where behaviour is gauged by either a controlled laboratory environment, experiments in the field, or auctions where consumers' maximal willingness to pay is displayed through (primarily) artificial purchases. True market behaviour is impossible to observe in free-of-charge events, and some kind of substitution is needed to

understand the utility created by events. Some experimental methods are difficult to use in a cultural event setting because the test markets used are not a natural shopping situation for cultural events; experiments are designed to escape the lost validity of the contingent valuation and claim revealed rather than stated preference.

Adding these pitfalls to those described above, there are two main contenders for stated WTP estimation in events: *dichotomous choice* and *conjoint bundles*, the subjects of the following sections.

4.3.1.1 Conjoint methods

Conjoint analysis is an indirect and thus more advanced method associated with WTP where goods are split into *attributes* and *alternatives*. Attributes are “variables”; ways that a product can differ, and alternatives are the different states of an attribute. It is also based on ordinal utility, with a monetary component which can be added to find out a WTP. The researcher wants to know which of the bundle’s attributes are most important to the consumer, and which attribute alternative (or polarity) is preferred. The archetypical application in economics is learning about consumer preference (Green & Srinivasan, 1978). The bundle is split into its different attributes for the analysis: *decomposed* bundles (Breidert et al., 2006). For an example of the model, see Table 2.

The consumer is presented with two or more bundles and chooses one (or sometimes, none). This choice will provide data about the relative preference of different bundle attributes, giving *part-worths*: how much a respondent prioritises one feature over the other.

Table 3. Example of conjoint analysis.

<p>Example of a typical conjoint design (based on Rao, 2020 and Breidert et al., 2006). How to find out what type of restaurant respondents like, and how important the different aspects are. The restaurant concept is split into three attributes with respective alternatives:</p>

1. 'menu' with alternatives 'buffet' and 'à la carte',
2. 'interior' with alternatives 'French bistro', 'Luxurious', and 'American diner'
3. 'price' with alternatives '£10 for a main course', '£20 for a main course', and '£30 for a main course'

A number of orthogonal choice cards (or if there is a digital survey, fully randomised cards for each respondent) with profiles are provided to the respondent, such as:

Alternative 1: buffet, luxurious, £20

Alternative 2: à la carte, luxurious, £10

Several choices like this may be presented to each participant.

There are several reasons for providing a bundle instead of asking about single attributes. A full product profile is an intuitive way of making a choice. Stating individual strength of preference individually and comparatively is part of the issues that make direct WTP questions problematic (as seen above with reference to Arrow et al., 2004). The most common application in consumer research is *full profile* bundles, where all alternatives are presented at once, though partial profiles are used in some studies to make choices more manageable (Bredert et al., 2006)

Conjoint analysis is a flexible tool which can be used based on several mathematical models and for applications in many areas of quantitative research where several attributes can be relevantly differentiated. Kohli and Mahajan (1991) developed a method for making a statement about WTP rather than just comparative strength of preference (and polarity). This is done by comparing a status quo bundle including a price tag, and then using analysis of variance (ANOVA). ANOVA tests determine whether there is a significant difference between the means of groups by comparing the variability between them. By comparing the part-worth of the price attribute with other part-worths, that can be extrapolated to the marginal willingness to pay for each attribute. It is also possible to add a socioeconomic dimension, such as Snowball and Willis (2011), adding a social aspect of affordability of culture with disadvantaged groups. Snowball (2005; Snowball & Willis, 2009) and Chalip &

McGuirty (2004) have presented methods for gauging the value of cultural events with conjoint bundles; bundling based on price, shows, and peripheral services provide broad, discrete categories which can provide significant results.

The utility of any conjoint model can be expressed in terms of the part-worths associated with each attribute alternative in that bundle. The model, adapted from Rao (2020:10) could be written as follows in a model with z attributes:

$$Y_i = U_j(X_{ij}) + \dots U_z(X_{iz}) + \epsilon_i \quad (2)$$

Y_i = The preference rating given to the i th system

x_{ij} = Attribute j value for the i th system

U_j = the part-worths function of attribute j

ϵ_i = The random error for the i th system

The Error can be understood as the random variation of respondents' utility (Rao, 2020:7). When gathering a large enough sample of choices between different bundles, each attribute in a chosen bundle weighs into a positive value, and non-chosen into a negative. The bundles are orthogonal, and all bundles are provided an equal number of times. Thus, each profile counts equally towards the part-worths. The full part-worth profile of a study can be expressed as an equation with the relative value of each attribute alternative. Part-worths are expressed in values between 1 and -1 and can be compared between different attributes, as well as internally between each attribute's alternatives. Even though it is easy to see in the raw data which profile is most and least popular, each attribute and alternative can be disaggregated to see how much each part contributes to that.

There are two main ways of calculating part-worths from conjoint data. Older conjoint methods used regression techniques, but these usually require a respondent to respond to all profiles and a high level of transitivity is required by being able to rank them. This requires a smaller set of profiles to work, according to Rao (2020:6). Instead, modern

designs (from Johnson, 1974) have developed multinomial logit models: a type of regression which estimates the probability of each category (attribute) in which the attributes do not need to be ordered hierarchically. Instead of calculating the continuous estimated value of a variable, it calculates the value of discrete points. In other words, to calculate the correlation between age and test results, an OLS accepts a continuum of variables whereas a multinomial model will need intervals to calculate individually.

4.3.1.2 Dichotomous choice

Dichotomous choice models refer to the indirect methods of WTP (and WTA) where respondents are presented with suggested prices to pay for goods. This model was also invented for environmental purposes, initially by Bishop & Heberlein (1979). Their question asked simply whether a presented price level X would be acceptable. Yes meant that the WTP was $\geq X$, and No meant $\leq X$, a model now called *single bounded dichotomous choice*. Haneman (1985) developed it into a *double-bounded dichotomous choice* where clients are also presented with a starting price X . If the respondent accepts the price, the next question presents another price $>X$, with the same yes/no question. If the respondent does not accept the price, a lower price $<X$ is presented with a yes/no question.

This iterates until the price is so high that the respondent does not accept the price anymore (initial yes), or so low that the respondent finally accepts the price (initial no). Both double and single-bounded dichotomous choice are well suited for events and festivals, although single bounded requires a larger sample; Herrero et al. (2012) use double-bounded for a cultural festival, and Báez and Herrero (2012) use a modified single bounded for a Chilean heritage site. For sports, especially major events, the method is common (Choe et al., 2017; Andersson et al., 2016; Dixon, 2009).

One feature of both conjoint bundling and dichotomous choice is the given starting prices. The decision of a starting point or not is problematic and gives rise to the so-called starting point bias: "Confronted with a dollar figure in a situation where he is uncertain about an amenity's value, a respondent may regard the proposed amount as conveying an approximate value of the amenity's true value and anchor his WTP amount on the proposed

amount” (Michell & Carson, 1989, cited from Herriges & Shogren, 1994). Studies have shown that the starting point primes a respondent to accept that price level as normal, and that willingness to pay will converge around the suggested price (Veronesi et al., 2011). Different solutions exist; the conjoint method has differentiated starting prices built in and price is commonly used as one of the dimensions of the bundle.

The double-bounded dichotomous choice may choose different starting points (one of the alternatives of the iterating price suggestions) or stay with the same for all respondents. Information about the consequences of different alternatives can be added, if it does not create additional bias (e.g. ideological) or overloads the respondents with information. Veronesi et al. (2011) suggest that the conscious design of the study and the “well-balanced and symmetric” price points offered can mitigate most of the bias. Paradoxically, the NOAA (Arrow et al., 1993) and Brediert et al. (2006) both dissuade using a non-starting point design: without anchoring (impossible in some WTP methods), the results will fluctuate even more amongst people who are seemingly similarly minded about a good. The non-anchored model gives rise to other problems too, especially *protest zeroes* and *strategic overbidding*.

4.3.1.3 *Insincere highs and lows*

The “unnatural focus on price” (Brediert et al., 2006) which is a feature of the direct WTP question and to a lesser degree WTP in general, may result in so-called protest zeroes. That is, respondents refusing to answer the WTP question or stating zero because they want to protest the question being part of the survey. For on-site surveys, the respondent may be clear enough that they dislike the question, in which case the response can be treated as an outlier to be removed. Another way to find protests in double-bounded WTP surveys is to present one price so low that hardly anyone will refuse it, and still present zero as a price below that. In terms of event research, Zawadzki (2020) argues that protest zeroes may be an expression of either alienation from the decision-making process or that respondents would have prioritised differently had the funding not been taxpayer money.

The opposite of insincere bidding is present too: strategic overbidding. Posavac (1998) showed how students would display a much higher willingness to pay for the same good if

they believed that in the end, they would not be the direct payers. If a respondent is certain that a good (e.g. a cultural event) will remain gratis, and they think that the event should exist, they have an incentive to state a very high (insincere) price, to skew the study's result in favour of the event. And vice versa, some respondents may dislike the current incarnation of the event and state zero, despite attending the event and experiencing some value. Strategic responses are possible in most surveys, not least when public resources are spent for one's own benefit.

4.3.2 Travel cost analysis

When possible, using the revealed preference method provides a more persuasive argument than some stated preference; there is no real cost associated with what is stated. Real-life consumer behaviour can be gauged with the travel cost method (Mishan & Quah, 2007:295). It is used mainly for goods which are not openly traded on a market, thus deriving a *shadow price*. For trips to expensive shows or experiences, the most reliable indicator of preference is the ticket price. For free-of-charge or cheap experiences such as parks, nature reserves (or events in Paisley), there is considerable demand which is not directly observed through ticket sales. Still, there are constraining conditions. One of them is the distance (and ease of transport) to an experience. The time and cost associated with travelling to natural or cultural experiences can be substantial and is a reliable indicator of a minimum level of consumer surplus.

Providers of experiences may use travel cost to define a market. For example, Paisley speaks of "two hours by car" as the maximum distance where consumers are highly likely to visit even a popular event, thus defining an unofficial outer perimeter of active marketing (Renfrewshire Council, 2018). In more economic terms, longer distances will likely mean that closer experiences are available providing a comparatively higher CS, or that the costs of getting to the event outweigh the utility experienced. Travel cost thus gauges the willingness to pay, but with two advantages in validity: reduced risk of overstated utility, and that each entry has chosen the event in competition with others on offer.

The travel cost method provides a minimum level of WTP; people living close to the

experience pay almost zero time and money thus likely experiencing a higher CS. People living close by are more likely to attend even free events and nature experiences. The travel cost method was originally used for continually available resources, such as heritage sites and nature reserves. This made it possible to generate a continuous demand curve; assuming independence between the events and a constant average, this is called a Poisson distribution. As discussed by Hellerstein (1991), a low supply of days possible for a visit and a higher probability of a given household's propensity to visit the site removes the possibility of treating the travel cost behaviour as a reliable Poisson distribution. The amount of randomness is not sufficient. This is the case of city events, only being hosted a few times per year, attracting many locals, and rendering impossible several other potential activities in the vicinity due to closed roads and other suppliers of experiences fitting their schedule to the large city events.

The cost of an individual's travel is debated. The most common way of estimating the cost of time includes using a fraction of the respondent's wage (McKean, 1995). This can range from 25 % of a person's hourly income to 100 %, with 1/3 being the most common number according to Parsons (2017). Parsons, as well as Chae et al. (2012), agree that the proportion of wages is arbitrary. Chae et al. (2012) well-cited overview uses the motivation "we *felt* that 60% is somewhat higher and *arbitrarily* used 30% of wage rate" (my italicisation). Parsons (2017) puts this into context by noting that some analysts believe "[...] the trip itself may impart some enjoyment to individuals, and one way of accounting for this is by discounting the value of time". None of the models presented above account for that *work* may be more or less pleasurable compared to leisure.

Even though TCM provides a sort of WTP, they are not synonymous; they are not necessarily even overlapping. TCM may use the increased likelihood of locals coming to an event to derive a demand curve which accounts for the surplus, but without some of the required requisites (Poisson distributed data, income data), other methods can be used. One of these is adding a stated preference method to find out what respondents' CS is. Adamowicz et al. (1994) were the first to describe a reliable combined study of direct and indirect methods, mainly showing how these models correlate strongly to display preference. More recent additions (Deely et al., 2017) combine the values into travel cost + WTP. This naturally gives a

higher value than studies only using one of the methods. Admittedly, it is a generous approach, but there is no reason to believe that the sum a WTP respondent is stating is meant to discount the discomfort and cost of their travel. The question of a WTP is not what value a respondent places on an event, but what they would be willing to pay in admittance.

4.3.3 Critique

Cost-benefit analysis provides the most comprehensive approach to evaluation of public sector interventions; it can potentially take on any variable which provides positive or negative values to a project. Several countries require CBA to evaluate all prospective projects over a certain sum. Major events use it as the primary method for reaching a bottom line (McGillivray & Turner, 2017). At the same time, it is a contested theory because of its political tendencies to support market liberal solutions (Frank, 2000), its lack of tools for many types of value (Foley et al., 2015), and its statement that money can be regarded as equal to utility. Some of the problems with CBA-related methods have been mentioned above: the problem of mixing stated and revealed preferences, insincere answers, and the difficulty of accurately estimating one's behaviour. Further down, theories and methods developed as a direct response to the problems with CBA (and indeed focus on economic value overall) are presented. Here follows some of the most relevant critiques for event evaluation not covered adequately elsewhere; other problematic aspects of CBA have been omitted because they do not pertain closely to events (e.g. discounting issues).

4.3.3.1 *Putting a price on human life*

In a CBA, human experiences are put in relation to each other, and compared to a monetary value, equivalent to that amount of utility. Typically, this includes saved time, aesthetic values, safety, and comfort (Pearce & Dasgupta, 1972). However, some of the most common applications of monetised utility deal with serious topics such as suffering and death. Quality-adjusted life years (QALY) is one such application, used in the health sector. QALY provides a yardstick for the number of high-quality human life years saved by a procedure. This makes comparison between different procedures and their cost possible. O'Brien (2010)

discusses how this could be used to measure the value of culture but concludes that it is a limited tool; not every type of cultural experience is easily converted to percentage points of life quality during a year. In addition to methodological problems, it is questioned based on morals: is it right to put a price tag on human life (Frank, 2000)? QALY does not necessarily need a monetary figure, but its use is very limited unless compared to the costs of a procedure. Some organisations therefore have explicit rules against comparing QALY to other, less serious values such as New Zealand's "Social CBA" guide (NZ Treasury, 2015). In transport infrastructure economics, saved lives, serious injuries, and lighter injuries are habitually compared to saved time and cost (Jones-Lee, 1990). These may seem far removed from culture and events and indeed it is most commonly used in health economics, but the quality of life (in the form of wellbeing) and the cost of transport times (in the form of travel cost analysis) are the very types of entities measured both by economic and social value studies of events. The counterargument from proponents is that the public sector will prioritise based on scarce resources anyway, and that information about how that is done, and what the implications are is crucial for healthy debate.

The actual cost is also contested. A saved human life is, in practice, valued at a few million pounds, though the values fluctuate widely between countries and policy areas (€3m in France according to Téhard et al., 2020). Those critical of QALY calculation note that human lives are tradeable with other commodities. This relates to the Kaldor-Hicks compensation criterion; anything which can be compensated is still a conditioned Pareto improvement. Any strict application of utility economics needs backstops and adherence to basic democratic principles to avoid draconic applications. In events, some people have direct, negative experiences, but the greater benefit for themselves and others compensates for it, hopefully manifold. The same is true for any outtake of public resources including taxation.

4.3.3.2 Intangibles and externalities

Cost-benefit methods are best fit for infrastructural projects. Their ubiquity has been preceded by many decades of development to fit other types of value (NZ Treasury, 2015). In the case of culture and events, it requires the operationalisation of values well beyond the easily understood time gains, noise limits, and infrastructural improvements. Social value

may be disregarded as intangible, despite constituting a great deal of the values of an event (Fourie & Santana-Gallego, 2011). Value is multi-faceted; intrinsic and bequest values matter to a great deal, often to the extent that respondents are willing to pay a great deal for goods that they are not able to enjoy directly. Lundhede et al. (2013) show this in the case of archaeological and environmental sites, but Hansen (1997) shows the willingness to finance even a theatre that one never visits, despite that others do visit it. Noonan (2003) noted this similarity between culture and environment. This latter point may be one reason that contingent methods have become popular in these policy areas because they take the shortcut of the stated economic value of an intervention rather than trying to define the social/intrinsic/bequest/non-use value.

Those who developed the Green Book approach (see more below; Fujiwara et al. 2014; O'Brien, 2010) noted the difficulty of translating cultural experiences to monetary values. The demands for a flexible, convertible, quantifiable method made the decision land on a CBA-based approach, monetised subjective wellbeing. With other demand specifications, it may be a suboptimal solution. This is partially a philosophical objection; the idea is to gauge utility, not economic value – the latter is a translated value for the sake of comparison, policy use, and the problems of cardinality that may arise from devising a scale based on 'utility points'. Næss (2015) questions the possibility of gauging (or potentially self-evaluating) utility with the CBA methods available, even on an ordinal scale.

4.3.4 Using CBA tools in events

Most events are not large enough interventions to warrant a CBA. First, because of the most common usage of CBA a tool to decide on prospective projects. Only very large events will realistically use counterfactuals and hypothetical alternatives (e.g. Hull University, 2017). Secondly, because of the sheer costs of a CBA, even as a post-event evaluation tool (which might use more primary data and fewer assumptions). Until recently, due to the undeveloped state of event studies, the tools were imprecise; Carlsen et al. (2000) argue that it was still unreliable then. Though much research has been published after that (Scandizzo & Pierleoni, 2017), many aspects of a plausible CBA, including both legacies and social gains are scarce or patchy. CBA remains a tool for primarily infrastructural, and now

environmental impacts, as discussed above (Cabral & Silva Jr, 2013). As Zhong et al. (2021) demonstrate, classic infrastructural CBA can be performed at a major event without needing to gauge the full event with its complicated intangible and social costs and benefits.

Instead, economic analyses or specific CBA-style tools are used. Scandizzo & Pierleoni (2017) show how evaluations both before and after the event make use of CBA methodology, but because of the characteristics of mega-events, they are primarily *ex-post*. Another advantage of mega event data is that if the data covers enough, others can perform quite sophisticated secondary analysis; Krekel (2021) performs an *ex-ante* wellbeing CBA of the 2020 Tokyo Olympics (which were held in 2021).

Jennings (2013) argues that the myopic focus on measurement might be counter-productive: “persistent underperformance of mega-projects occurs despite trends in administrative reform seeking to impose market discipline on public projects and to scrutinise public policies and spending according to the standards of cost-benefit analysis, cost-effectiveness and value for money.” Mills and Marks (2017) suggest that CEA might be a better choice than CBA because though benefits may be difficult to evaluate, the overlooked factor in event planning is the alternative cost; what could have been done otherwise.

Despite the critique, CBA remains a comprehensive set of tools and a method of transparently accounting for more values than other contenders. Social value evaluation has problems discussed more below, whereas other quantitative economic evaluation lacks the depth and case-by-case assessment of value needed for a fuller picture. The lightweight alternative used by most events today is called input/output or Economic impact analysis (Preuss, 2004).

4.4 Input/output model

CBA is an expensive and resource-heavy methodology which is not viable for smaller projects or smaller actors. Input/Output, or Economic impact analysis (EIA), focuses simply on economic impacts and without crafting alternatives and counterfactuals. The output is

easy to understand, displaying the Gross Value Added (GVA) to the surveyed economy, typically a region or locality (Sterngold, 2004). The single figure of aggregated benefits, which is one of the main advantages for a policymaker using a CBA, remains intact. No contested social value conversions, opportunity costs, or social interest rates are measured. EIA is therefore frequently used for evaluating the economic impacts of events (Eventimpacts, n.d.). EIA grew from the 1980s; during the 2010s it has been the main tool for UK event evaluation below the 'mega' level. Not least the work by Myerscough (1988), an early proponent of EIA, shaped Glasgow's, and subsequently others' use of the method. Myerscough (1988:101) calculated that one tourist visiting for a stage culture experience provided the same employment effect as five locals.

One of the problems of EIA and CBA alike is the misinterpretations of the method: counting some things double and omitting other things, especially when performed by laymen, or being financed by the beneficiaries of good results (Chalip, 2017). Crompton (1995) describes a range of these including errors in calculating multipliers, overestimating spectators by counting 'casuals', not defining a proper impact area, and neglecting the presentation of opportunity costs. Taks et al. (2011) show an even greater flaw of the EIA in an event setting; their study takes a positive EIA result of an event and shows that if all the typical CBA aspects are included, the result is instead negative. A positive bottom line might be based on the very limited scope.

Fine-tuned, cautious EIAs, such as the method described by Eventimpacts (n.d.) (see more below) methodology, will not overstate the impact (Tyrrell & Johnston, 2016). However, the problem may be the opposite. EIA methodology prescribes discounting all local visitors to an event, as they would likely have been spending the day within the area for their consumption anyway. That is not the case everywhere, such as residents of councils near big cities, likely to spend at least a part of their event budget elsewhere. Whilst that is outside the scope of this study, it may be an argument against the usage of EIA for that kind of environment not to significantly understate the GVA or Gross-Value-Not-Lost.

Impact studies are "frequently funded by project proponents, misuse of multipliers, and improper specification of the study area", though the problem is more prevalent in non-

academic reports (Hodur & Leistriz, 2007). Crompton (2016) even argues that EIAs are often carried out to legitimise a political position. Hodur & Leistriz (2007) also discuss the misunderstanding of the difference between direct economic impact and total expenditures; the latter is simply all spending related to an event, whereas the former is the spending which would not have occurred otherwise. It should be noted that EIA does indeed have tools for this and that cautious EIA analysts are well aware (Sterngold, 2004). Beyond this, there is also a risk of misinterpreting the value added from direct economic impact. The local market may have grown, with a certain figure, but considering that evaluation of public projects means spending of public funds, a local market growing by £1 does not mean that £1 spent in public money is a neutral investment. It might well have done better things elsewhere (which CBA is more fitted for). Késenne's (2005) review concludes that an EIA is not at all fitted to guide whether a government should finance an event. That policy decision's implications for the locality (or even its economy) cannot be well understood without a CBA or another framework for opportunity costs or a clear interpretation of what added value will mean. Investment in the wrong industries may even give a *negative multiplier* according to the Green Book, see below (HM Treasury, 2022). Effects of crowding out (Preuss, 2011) and displacement of money (and people; Butler & Aicher, 2015) are too important economic effects to disregard. Dwyer et al. (2016) provide a range of reasons that the typical economic objectives of events using EIA as a yardstick of success cannot be translated into welfare. It does not provide answers to what proportion of the transactions go to short-term work or business (e.g. stalls), RDP does not reliably predict effects on the labour market, no non-market goods are measured (which tend to be the direct focus of free-of-charge event organisers). Looking at overviews of desirable event effects (Getz, 2000; Smith et al., 2021), few are covered by an EIA.

Whilst there are some disadvantages with an EIA, several of the problems are the same as CBA: it can be used to propagate an opinion and gives a false sense of validity no matter how well-crafted it is. A competent analyst can interpret EIA results without bias. The figure does indicate the willingness to spend money within the region. Késenne (2005) gives a good example of what inputs are needed to estimate an event. It would need data or theoretically estimated figures for organiser revenue, organiser spending, revenue, profits, imports, crowding out, unemployment, spending patterns of visitors, ticket sales, multipliers, job

creation, previous infrastructure investments, and tax rates. Only a few of these are typically included in event EIA.

4.5 Externalities

Externalities (also external effects or spillovers) are effects caused by a project, affecting a third party outside of the studied transaction (Buchanan & Stubblebine 1962). These can be positive (benefits) or negative (costs) for the third party. Externalities fluctuate from being almost non-existent to constituting virtually all the values of an intervention. For a free-of-charge cultural event, there may be virtually no transactions directly associated with the events beyond organiser costs and thus all economic gains are external effects. The intended interaction between attendees and the event is not an externality, but all their spending is.

Again, economic externalities arising out of the leverage legacy may be a bearing idea of urban regeneration schemes and cultural developments. Anticipated additional external effects include increased spending in local stores and job creation, but also increased attractiveness for business. External effects are difficult to assess; organisers can seldom have control over third-party interactions beyond communications and partnerships. At the same time, organisers are happy to take credit for it; most of the GVA of publicly organised events, and most of the benefits of urban regeneration are typically between the consumers and third parties. Ignoring externalities gives a very one-sided idea of an event, but Lowes (2004) shows how the external effects can also be inflated beyond reality, just as Talbot & Carter (2017) show how unaccounted negative externalities of an event can skew the reality of evaluation. In Lowes' case, it was a politically motivated inflation of benefits to Australia during the Grand Prix in Melbourne. A large factor of the inflation in cases like this is the *multiplier effect*.

Public spending and tax deductions lead to increased incomes for private firms and individuals. This increased income is in turn spent (and saved), creating additional spending in other private businesses. This increased economic activity beyond the initial spend is called a multiplier effect. Multipliers are important positive (or sometimes, negative)

externalities in some types of public investment (HM Treasury, 2022). The main type of multiplier in public interventions is fiscal. This multiplier evaluates what effect increased domestic spending has on regional (or national) gross product, typically by increased employment. By accounting for economic displacements, a local fiscal multiplier can be used to estimate the impact of public spending. The fiscal multiplier in the UK is estimated to be around 1.0 in recessions, and somewhat lower otherwise (HM Treasury, 2018).

As Matheson (2004:4) put it: “There is no reason to believe that the usual economic multipliers are the same during mega-events, any economic analyses based upon these multipliers may, therefore, be highly inaccurate”. This lack of evidence has led to harsh criticism of event multiplier use overall (Dwyer et al., 2016; Matheson, 2012). The special characteristics of events, with large numbers of temporary visitors, visiting businesses, displacement of resources for some businesses and footfall to others, all contribute to potentially skew the results of multipliers in the region.

One of the reasons that public sources will finance cultural events is that they are regarded as *merit goods*. Musgrave (1956) defined merit goods as commodities that society benefits from without necessarily being able or willing to pay for them. These may be subsidised by the public sector for the positive external effects created. Snowball (2008:13) notes that cultural events and the arts more generally are often considered merit goods. In the case of smaller societies, they also bear some resemblance to *public goods*, where one person’s consumption does not alter your possibility to enjoy it (non-rival) and cannot include some whilst excluding others (non-excludable). In the case of free-of-charge, publicly funded cultural events, this is not far from the truth (within some restrictions). Providing funding for a *merit good* makes it a *public good*.

4.6 Non-monetised perspectives

Whilst economic perspectives are the most prevalent, they are not the only perspectives used to study events. Several alternatives contain some degree of critique of the CBA/EIA mainstream (Grix, 2014:50) – some are created bespoke to challenge it (Public value; Moore,

1995), whereas others are independent but need to motivate why an alternative approach was chosen. The CBA perspective has advantages; it is highly tangible, possible to summarise a public Intervention within the scope of a study, it can potentially make use of virtually any input (though it seldom does), and the convenience of CBA's function as a direct decision-making tool is attractive. The politics of creating unity around a decision also contributes by giving a monetary figure which has the "aura of mathematical accuracy" (Revesz & Livermore, 2008:14). The simplicity of the final figure which makes decision-making easy and comparable to other values is a strong argument for CBA.

Donald Getz, an influential event scholar, has (co-)written several typologies about the values which can be studied in events (Getz, 1989; Carlsen et al., 2000; Brown et al., 2015). These have developed over time, but the main trend is the inclusion of more non-economic value. In 1989, this was novel. In 2012, he called for the inclusion of non-economists to engage more with events studies because of the emerging ways of studying the field (Getz, 2012). This was, if not the starting point, at least a milestone for the current trend where non-economic methods are taking place besides the CBA and EIA.

4.6.1 Wellbeing

One term used by both progressive CBA analysts and their critics is wellbeing. It aims to take human experiences and perceptions into account, rather than just infrastructural advantages. One of the motivators is to move beyond the focus on GDP as the most central variable in human development, as described in the OECD 2018 Global Happiness Report (Durand 2018). PPP GDP constitutes 1/3 of the HDI (the others are life expectancy and years of formal education). Though few propose abandoning GDP altogether, it may be complemented or made equal to other variables. The critique of using GDP (in the case of events below the mega-level, RDP) and other iterations of economic activity as the central scale of wellbeing has been criticised for its crudeness for a long time, as OECD notes in the report. Though wellbeing and happiness have been proposed as better indicators of human welfare, an important step towards the mainstream acceptance of the variables and methods used today was the Report by the Commission on the Measurement of Economic Performance and Social Progress by Stiglitz, Sen, and Fitoussi (Government of Bhutan 2008;

Stiglitz et al. 2009). The report, instigated by French President Nicholas Sarkozy, set out to investigate the weaknesses of GDP and propose alternative measurements, which have been widely used and cited since. Indeed, many wellbeing-related data collection initiatives started soon after 2009, such as the UK subjective (subsequently *personal*) wellbeing report (first experimental report 2011); see end of this chapter.

Despite being a critique of the strong focus on economic variables steering public statistics and goals, wellbeing evaluation does not ensue leaving out economics methodology. Indeed, the 2018 Global Happiness Report mentions the implications for cost-benefit analysis, giving the example of the New Zealand Government's move towards inclusion of wellbeing parameters into the Public Finance Act as well as their CBA-based public policy evaluation and prediction techniques (OECD 2018). One of the authors of the report, Richard Layard, argued strongly in his book *Happiness: Lessons from a New Science* (2011) that material improvements had not been equal to increased happiness, thus being part of shaping the contemporary happiness and wellbeing agenda.

The Report by the Commission on the Measurement of Economic Performance and Social Progress, mentioned above, provides some of the foundations for a CBA with wellbeing applications, an explicit goal of the report (Stiglitz et al. 2009:8). The report contains some basic recommendations about how to move beyond GDP to better include wellbeing, including shifting from production to consumption and income, take a household perspective, and inclusion of non-market activities into the income definition (Stiglitz et al. 2009:12). It goes on to define some of the areas mainly associated with wellbeing, which to a large extent coincides with UK and Scottish wellbeing definitions, such as employment, health, and insecurities. Adding in the different definitions of wellbeing from OECD, Stiglitz et al., and HM Treasury, the following top-level areas are used by the four sources, clearly similar in their styles.

The common feature of several of these; the Green Book (HM Treasury, 2023), the Fitoussi report (Stiglitz et al., 2009), and some OECD applications is subjective wellbeing (SWB). This is suggested as a way of measuring utility with a closer approximation than money and then converting that to a monetary figure. Respondents are asked to state how satisfied they are

with their lives on a scale, finding out how much an activity or good contributes to that state, and then calculating how much compensation a respondent would need to be as well off as they would be without that good. This escapes WTP, but similar problems arise out of the conversion from stated wellbeing to putting a wellbeing effect on a good.

Trying to marry together the intangible with the monetary, SWB has been suggested as an approach taking social value better into account. There are, however, fully adapted social value assessments, albeit usually not compatible with CBA.

4.7 The social value of events

The current trend of the EIA methodology evolved during the 1990s, simultaneously with the development of contemporary foci of mega-events; cities bidding and organising events for the sake of urban regeneration and economic gain. Though economic impact is still the norm, particularly large events and events with a strong interest from researchers or public policymakers will frequently include other types of analysis, including social value (Foley, et al., 2012:34; Getz, 2020). The increase in social evaluation studies is partly due to an increased understanding that social value creation brings real effects to the local area; new methods for gauging social value have made this increasing knowledge possible (Getz, 1989; O'Brien, 2010; Smith et al., 2021).

In several of the most oft-cited studies on the impacts of events, the perspective is *exclusively* economic, also without making use of CBA's potential for social value conversion (Ritchie & Smith, 2016; Lee & Taylor, 2005). The most common scope of these studies is short-term effects (Misener et al., 2016). The redistribution of public resources, temporary and permanent changes in urban infrastructure, displacement, emphasising some aspects of local culture, and the impact on local culture and community are some aspects which may have considerable effects and need to be accounted for (Preuss 2009; Gaffney 2010; Hiller 1995).

Social effects are largely external to the direct transactions between organisers, participants,

local government, sponsors, and contractors. Still, the interplay between residents and stakeholders is a crucial factor which can determine the outcome and external perception of an event (Talbot & Carter 2017). Event organisers are often aware of this, but when they are not, it may cause controversy or riots (Foley et al., 2012). By-projects at different levels of ambition may be aimed at engaging people not directly involved in the event or raising awareness and goodwill for it. A prominent example of this community engagement programme is the 2012 Cultural Olympiad², a £97 million investment in a less-known part of the Olympics, though every Olympics since Stockholm 1912 has hosted one (The Guardian 2012; García 2019).

Distinguishing and isolating dependent and independent variables for social effects is not easily done in valid and reliable ways. Above, a few of the types of social change associated with cultural events were outlined. Different types of social change will require different responses. Analysing social impact is generally not an alternative to analysing economic impact. Rather, they complement each other in providing important information about the specific environment; economic effect looks at transactions and social effects at how humans are affected beyond economic changes. Still, it is well known that social value occur and is relevant and significant. Roche's (2002) seminal work mentions several of the typical values studied by social value scholars despite having an entirely different focus: social cohesion, sense of community, and cultural gains. The same is true for many economic studies: Dwyer et al. (2006) are well aware that social gains are important despite not within the scope of their study.

There is an ongoing debate about how to evaluate cultural experiences and products, in economic or utility terms (Crossick & Kaszynska 2016:8). One of the aspects of this debate is the question of whether economics is a good way to measure culture. While some say that economics are well-equipped with tools to account for monetary as well as intrinsic values (Bakshi, Freeman & Hitchen, 2009), others claim that economic studies often overemphasise the economic aspect of culture, neglecting other values (Belfiore 2018; Crossick & Kaszynska 2016). Tools like subjective wellbeing and quality of life discussed above, as well as more

² Note that an *Olympiad* is the four years starting and ending with the Summer Olympics, not the games.

normative or at least qualitative models of value provide arguments that social value is indeed possible to measure (Foley et al., 2015; Getz, 2010; O'Brien, 2010)

There are several attempts to categorise social value categories, such as those displayed in Table 4.

Table 4. Some examples of event social value categories.

Environmental. Social.	Ennis & Douglass, 2011
Collective. Individual. Negative.	Smith et al., 2021
Community, cultural, place identity and attachment. Communitas, social cohesion sociability. Festivity, liminality, the carnivalesque. Authenticity, commodification.	Getz, 2010

These categories typically contain the same set of values, some of the following: identity, pride (in place), community engagement, sense of community, social cohesion, social capital, community development, professional development, quality of life/wellbeing, and cultural development. Negative dimensions are covered in the next section. Some variety of sense of community, place attachment, and wellbeing are typically included (such as in the table above). These values cover much of what is claimed to be the outcome of successful events and culture-led investment.

Social effects tend to affect locals more than visitors, because of their close relation to community and place. Snowball and Antrobus (2020) note that the difference between the experience of a visitor as opposed to a resident can be substantial. *Community* and *place* cannot easily be differentiated, and Brownett and Owen (2020:2) note that heritage, history, and shared spaces with others may contribute to positive feelings towards a place and the community. At the same time, a shared sense of community spills over to social capital with its notions of increased trust in people and institutions (Ooi, Laing & Mair, 2015).

Wellbeing, mentioned in all the typologies above, is discussed in section 4.6 as a quantifiable social gain used to convert between social and economic gains, such as Fujiwara's (2014) work. Wellbeing is, however, also used in relation to other social value indicators, both quantitative and qualitative. SWB can be used to gauge the states of attendees, as demonstrated in several reviews (Yolal et al. 2016; Snowball & Antrobus, 2020). These are social effects and show several advantages: respondents can more easily give an opinion compared to WTP, no monetary conversion is needed, there are fewer incentives for insincere replies, it applies more equally to all visitors, and the wellbeing of humans is a universally accepted value. Despite this, it may be difficult to argue that SWB provides a reliable meter of long-term value, which community and place-based measurements do. SWB is a contender for an intermediate between social and economic value (O'Brien 2010; HM Treasury, 2023). More long-term wellbeing measurements do not fulfil that condition and instead tend to be 'catch-all' expressions of social value, such as in Wood and Thomas (2009).

An additional effect, which Getz (2010) classifies as a value, is liminality. Liminal experiences can be expressed as borderlines (from Latin *limen*, threshold), a limbo-like state between two conditions, first defined by van Gennep (1909). As an anthropologist, he noticed the three distinct phases of separation, liminality, and incorporation in rituals across different cultures including rites de passage, marriages, and even birthdays. Turner (1974) expanded the understanding to include a more general *liminal phase*, where individuals or groups are temporarily detached from their social roles and norms, creating a space for new possibilities and alternative social structures to emerge. This phase of transgressions and temporarily dissolved norms is intimately associated with carnivalesque states of mind and celebration. Celebration and liminality as a social value have been explored in the context of events by Chalip (2006), noting the opportunity for informal socialisation during liminal, or even *liminoid* (a limited, more individual form of liminality, as defined by Turner) experiences at events.

One aspect of social value, social capital, is a catch-all term for many of the positive social effects, including social cohesion, know-how, and indeed trust. Putnam (1995; 2000)

describes social capital differently from Bourdieu's original definition. Where Bourdieu et al. (2015) focused more on knowledge and 'fitting in', Putnam understands social capital also as the level of interpersonal trust, trust in society's institutions, participation in civil society, and the willingness to help out a stranger or member of the community. Putnam's influential definition has been used not least by scholars of non-profits (Wijkström, 2011; Putnam, 2000), where increased participation and trust have been shown to correlate. It is important not to let social capital mean *everything*; letting it designate trust, sense of community, a social network, and sense of place is close to letting it designate anything positive. Instead of using social capital, this study lets *public value* hold that position, because it has good mechanisms to accept a variety of inputs; the designation between what is and is not social capital, as well as the additional theoretical apparatus needed to properly use social capital left this out of the study.

4.7.1 Negative social value

Negative values of events form an important addition to events studies. Negative values are less prevalent than benefits in evaluations, especially by event organisers whose target is to underline the positive. Some social costs are understood through structural analysis of power relations and what happens several steps down the line (e.g. displacement due to gentrification caused by mega-event urban policy). These negatives are important to understand before major event interventions; individuals may be compromised for an alleged greater good, a similar line of criticism as covered in section 4.3.3 about CBA generally. Critical perspectives on events were covered more closely in section 2.6. Additionally, universally accepted social costs are occurring in direct relation to the events. Delamere (1997:296) lists them as: "disruption of routines, intrusion, overstretched facilities, reduced privacy, community overcrowding, traffic, noise, overtaxed human resources, and litter." These may cause considerable negative impacts, sometimes concealed by organisers (Fitzgerald & Maharaj, 2022). Even high-profile impact reports from events may entirely omit negative values (such as IOC, 2022).

Deery and Jago, 2010 found that antisocial behaviour and injustices not only create a counterweight to positive values but also negate many of the positives discussed above;

behaviour threatening property, health, cleanliness, and general wellbeing are detrimental to the sense of community, pride in place, and social capital typically mentioned as positives. Deery and Jago's (2010) review shows how some studies identify negative feedback loops between adverse social effects and the quality of events, increasing anti-social behaviour and bringing more attendees (or locals) from a "celebratory" to a "tolerating" or even negative sentiment about the event.

4.8 Scotland and UK perspectives

The country in which this study is undertaken, Scotland, is one of the adopters of a wellbeing methodology for calculating progress (Scottish Government, 2018). Wellbeing has been a part of statistical practice and state-led research in the UK for over a decade (Office for National Statistics, 2012), though Scotland has separately taken steps to design separate methodologies and frameworks, especially in their implementation of the Sustainable Development Goals, see section 4.8.3. This section maps some of the policies in Scotland and the UK relevant to event economics and evaluation techniques.

Perspectives are both economic and social; since 2012, The Office for National Statistics in the UK has published a report on the measurement of subjective wellbeing (2012) and several other reports on personal wellbeing (2019), including joint reports on economic and personal wellbeing (2019). These are based on the Annual Population Survey, which has developed the survey through testing on their large number of respondents. Its methodological framework is based on the increasing international literature supporting subjective wellbeing surveys, including OECD (2011).

The OECD approach, to which the UK complies, is rooted in the SWB literature and primarily aimed at time series, as seen above. All scores had a positive trend over the period except anxiety. This report has not been widely used for evaluation policy because it is high-level and cannot single in on particular policies. It shows engagement but can hardly be used for operationalisation.

4.8.1 The Green Book

The most important tool for measuring public interventions in the UK, including cultural, is the Green Book. Though it is essentially a CBA-based method for evaluation, the conversions rely heavily on SWB: “Economic appraisal is based on the principles of welfare economics – that is, how the government can improve social welfare or wellbeing, referred to in the Green Book as social value” (HM Treasury 2018, 5).

This UK-wide document for appraisal and evaluation of public interventions defines the benefit of any project as increased wellbeing, thus making wellbeing equal to social value and the outcome of a CBA appraisal. The Green Book distinguishes between CBA and social value evaluation but implies that CBA will be the more common of the two (HM Treasury 2018, 5). The Green Book is a central document of practice and theory behind UK public economic decisions and is also an essential tool in calculating discounts in this chapter.

The Green Book has specific implementations for evaluating cultural goods. During its design, Dave O’Brien (2010) investigated cultural value evaluation. His report produced a helpful typology of evaluation methods used in several places throughout this study. The approach needed to be quantifiable and preferably easily monetisable, and so the continued work by Daniel Fujiwara and others pushed it in a CBA direction (Fujiwara & Campbell, 2011; Fujiwara et al., 2014; Fujiwara et al., 2021). The Green Book SWB relies on the subjective wellbeing created by consuming culture, and their reference value comes from a 2014 calculation that around £90 of “arts engagement” utility per person and year in the UK (including “watching a film, attending an exhibition [...], attending a music performance event” but also playing music, dancing, creating art) (Fujiwara et al., 2014). SWB created by these activities is converted into monetary values based on an overview and model created by the CASE project in 2010 (CASE, 2010). CASE’s approach was an effort to “developing evidence and analytic tools and methods for addressing fundamental policy questions in the domain of engagement in culture and sport” and uses a model where the quality of life derived from culture is compared to the quality of life typically experienced by increased income (CASE, 2010).

Another issue the Green Book touches on is multipliers. The Green Book warns against unwarranted multipliers in cultural settings, just like Chalip (2017), Evans (2004) and many others. The Green Book approach relies on the same basic principle as some EIA: money exchanging hands within a local authority is discounted. The *What Works Project* (2019) has a guide for local multipliers, referenced as an authority by UK government sources, including the Green Book³. For a multiplier to be credible, it needs to be *tradeable*, that is, put into a sector which mainly trades outwith the local economy. Non-tradeable multipliers are discounted, and “Many [public intervention] appraisals predict significant positive multipliers using ‘input-output’ models that focus on the positive demand-side effects adjusted for ‘leakages’ from the local economy (demand that is served by firms from elsewhere)” (HM Treasury, 2018).

The Green Book asserts that non-economic value exists; “social” or even “public” values are mentioned. These are also to be monetised: “The use of Social Cost Benefit Analysis (CBA) or Social Cost Effectiveness Analysis (CEA) is how cost and benefit trade-offs are considered” (HM Treasury, 2022). The previous phrasing is interesting, as public value is widely considered a reaction against CBA. The “public value” used by Green Book scholars (Fujiwara et al., 2021) does not have a theoretical connection to the public value approach in this study but is simply another way of using the SWB methodology

4.8.2 Eventimpacts

Any complete CBA calculation will cost significant resources. CBA was invented for large infrastructural projects where resources could be poured into making the right decision. The same is true for the Green Book, often recommending ambitious evaluations, even if some goods are evaluated with a comparatively light CEA. To create a solution, the Department for Culture, Media and Sport, Discover Northern Ireland, EventScotland, London & Partners, UK Sport, and the Welsh Government created an I/O tool for events: Eventimpacts (n.d.). The toolkit contains everything a mid-sized event needs to create a simple evaluation. The most

³ In turn, this model is based on a range of studies from OECD countries. Similar models are published by the ONS.

used parts are calculating visitor numbers (for non-ticketed events) and economic evaluation. More parts have been developed over the years and now contain environmental, social, and media impact modules. It is intended as a baseline evaluation tool, ensuring that evidence-based, cost-efficient evaluation methods are used. Basic figures include demographic and attendee data, which can be added to the other, more specific packages.

The economic impact tool uses the I/O (EIA) methodology, counting just that – economic influx to the local economy. Eventimpacts is a self-described “at least” (n.d.) tool, not engaging in overoptimistic multipliers. It discounts casual attendees and locals, and the bottom line is the Gross Value Added to the local economy, which would not have been added otherwise. The flaws of this approach are discussed above, but compared to other tools, it is cautious: only taking into account GVA, discounting local spending and casual visitors, as well as leaving all other value uncalculated. There lies a danger in misinterpreting the results – the single bottom line needs to be interpreted to make sense. The consultancies carrying out reports warn against using this figure too literally as the economic effect of the events; economic influx is not a neutral figure.

4.8.3 Scottish Index of Multiple Deprivation

A publicly visible product of Scotland’s focus on socioeconomics is the Scottish Index of Multiple Deprivation, based on work from the late 1990s at Oxford University by Noble et al. (2003). This index is a relative measurement of seven weighted factors of deprivation: income, employment, health, education/skills, housing, geographic access, and crime. SIMD is used in various settings, not least to pinpoint the problems in an area perceived as deprived in the media or public communications (Clements, 2020). The most deprived SIMD data zone was within the Paisley town limits in the 2016 rendition of the index. In the 2020 index, that zone was upgraded to the third most deprived area, reported locally as a success despite being a relative index (SIMD, 2020).

4.8.4 National Performance Framework

In Scotland, the work with wellbeing measurement has taken a vital role in creating a unique path on the side of other UK nations. In addition to SIMD, the National Performance Framework is the flagship project for a comprehensive understanding of human needs and development as a basis for publicly financed interventions (Scottish Government, 2022). Initially based on early 2000s research on wellbeing and the US state of Virginia's outcomes-based model of achieving social development, it is aimed at measuring social progress in the broadest sense.

The implementation of NPF, being updated' intermittently, changed significantly after adhering to the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (United Nations, 2015). These are now the primary Scottish tools for tracking the progress of the SDGs. The NPF is divided into:

- 11 Outcomes: very wide social areas described as goals. E.g. "We are healthy and active".
- 81 Indicators: narrow data point measurement. E.g. "Percentage of young people who feel adults take their views into account in decisions that affect their lives".

(Scottish Government 2022)

Indicators are grouped into Outcomes, but almost all activity in society can be related to one or more Outcomes. The indicators help make this vague ubiquity more concrete. The 11 Outcomes relate to the 17 SDGs, with their ubiquitous approach, even sharing a similar brightly coloured graphic design. The NPF aims to go beyond government or public sector activity, though the project has not yet been widely (explicitly) implemented by other Scottish stakeholders other than the central government. This is about to change after government pressure, and by 2030, local governments will likely have implemented NPF language and benchmarking more actively than before.

NPF (measuring 'positive' aspects) and SIMD (measuring 'negative' aspects) are major tools for communicating an alternative approach to value in Scotland. Projects aimed at broadening the understanding of value creation in the rest of the UK find their way into official government publications (such as the Green Book) and significant private initiatives

(Social Value UK, 2022). However, their commitment to spreading it across society and publishing public-facing products such as <http://simd.scot> and a doodling contest in 2018 defined a part of the graphic profile and set an informal tone for NPF.

Being Scotland's implementation of the SDGs, they are leading documents in wellbeing policy development. Until 2030 (when the SDGs are supposed to be implemented), they are meant to shape the policy in many areas increasingly; alignment to SDGs can now be seen at public agency websites, university research projects, and local authorities. Alignment at the micro-level also increases, with individual reports and policies calling back to the SDG implementations.

The national perspective on evaluation finishes this chapter. The chapter briefly covers the current debates and techniques used for event evaluation and the main ideologies of cost-benefit and social value assessment. The trajectory seems to point towards greater inclusion of social value, especially with the increased focus on wellbeing in policymaking. The same can be said about the next chapter, which covers urban regeneration and the contested practices used to create it. The following chapter also presents novel ways of investigating the complicated value creation of far-reaching investment into traditionally intangible policy areas such as culture.

4.8.5 Outcomes-based frameworks in other countries

Several other countries have developed frameworks for governmental performance. In the UK, all countries except England have developed corresponding systems (French & Mollinger-Sahba, 2021). These outcome-based, multi-sector systems are aimed at performance management, but also novel tools for improving those outcomes. French and Mollinger-Sahba (2021:379) call this performance attraction, and present how this approach may “build a collective sense of responsibility” and “promote coordinated learning and adaptation across institutional boundaries through building shared commitment towards interdependent values and visions”. The performance attraction models aim to achieve synergies across sectors, although additional administrative (or performance-based) burdens may take extra resources.

Scotland has led the process in the UK (Birrell & Gray, 2018), with their now decades-long engagement. They had a fully developed outcomes-based system in place before the SDGs, whereas Wales and Northern Ireland published them around the time of the SDGs in 2015; all have been affected by the globally ongoing SDG due in 2030; the UK has committed centrally as well. The NPF is a part of the devolved Scotland's "aspiration of a new type of politics" (Elliott, 2023:77). The attraction of a separate management tool from the UK's approach has been part of the rationale for all of the three countries (Birrell & Grey, 2018). This is despite different methods in practice, with Wales accepting a broader range of data input compared to Scotland's operationalised indicators.

4.9 Summary

This chapter presents the methods used for event evaluation. The summary includes key concepts from Table 1 in italics.

The most common method for event evaluation is based, broadly speaking, in cost-benefit analysis. Rather than a single method, it is a broader practice of summing up negative and positive values by putting price tags on them, no matter if they are traded on a market or not. It is useful for decision-makers, showing an easy-to-interpret result, whilst taking into account many variables otherwise omitted. A powerful tool, the usage of money as a universal intermediary makes it susceptible to criticism. As CBA is based on the thought that human utility can be converted to money, the consequences may be ethically problematic when extrapolating to great suffering, or comparisons between the utility of the few and the many. Other popular methods, most prominently versions of Economic impact analysis, are based on CBA reasoning, though removing the most work-intensive parts.

CBA gives access to indirect methods such as willingness-to-pay and travel cost analysis. Although the former is stated preference, and the latter is actually observed behaviour, they both approximate different parts of visitors' experience value.

Assertions about the strongly positive economic effects of events are challenged by critical scholarship. Partially those who put into question the inflated figures of economic gains including frequent double-counting (Lowes, 2004). Another strand of thought is critical event studies, challenging the neoliberal foundations of most mainstream event studies (Lamond & Platt, 2016). Critical event studies suggest a move towards a less economics-centred evaluation, including social value such as sense of community, identity, pride in place, and liminality (Getz, 2010).

4.10 Literature review conclusion

The literature review consisted of three chapters which have largely aimed to achieve two things: present the theoretical framework used for the study and give an empirical background to the study's context.

Public value is the central theoretical concept guiding the study. In Bozeman's (2012) sense, public value is possible to understand as a quantity, not primarily a guiding principle for the public sector, as described by Moore (1995). The ethos of public value, to maximise what is valued by the public (a definition borrowed from Meynhardt, 2009), is central to the study.

One advantage of a public value framework is that it does not necessarily limit itself to a single set of value calculations, such as the final monetary product of a CBA. Thus, public value may incorporate different types of value, but not necessarily vice versa. In this case, the study accepts the CBA product as part of the public value creation. Some data, looking at actual transactions or stated spending (EIA, business statistics), are more intermediaries than actual public value, as money is a means to a public value end (Spano, 2014). Other methods discussed, including travel cost and WTP, can rather be regarded as expressions of the value experienced at events, and thus incorporated into a public value framework.

The value of the events is thus defined as actual transactions on-site plus the public value effect, which is at least as extensive as the value given to it by respondents attending the events. This is part of the development of public value discussed in chapters 1 and 9.

To understand value creation through culture and events better, policy goals guiding the local authority have been discussed and presented. The main concept shaping the early efforts towards UKCoC was culture-led regeneration. Regeneration is centred around cultural investment programmes. It intends to create positive effects in terms of external investments in the local area, reputation, people moving in, a stopped brain drain, strengthened or new businesses, as well as a turn towards a cultural service-based economy. During the second half of the 2010s, and especially after December 2017, this turned towards the related cultural regeneration approach, where culture is incorporated into virtually every aspect of the public sector. It focuses less on direct, high-profile interventions of cultural infrastructure. In Paisley's case, urban planning and healthcare services have been two policy areas where culture has taken a much greater role after the turn.

The policy aspect takes up considerable space in the literature review. It is crucial to understand what Renfrewshire Council is trying to achieve, with what means, and what the alternatives were. Value creation in the public sector is contingent on the intentions of the governmental body, and the value setup will change with changed priorities. These priorities may unveil areas of public value which are intended and give a clearer indication of whether the outcomes were deliberate or not.

Similarly, the discussion of mega-events feeds into the political discussion, as well as the local understanding of what RC was bidding for. Paisley's bid was meant to end up the hosting of a major event, and the literature and arguments backing it up were from the mega-event area. The intended effects as well as the planning thus places the project in the mega-event area. The actual size of the UKCoC event may be contested; it surely does not fulfil Müller's (2015) requisites for a mega-event. However, the less binding term *major event* is in line with Paisley's expectations.

5 Methodology and Methods

The main aim of this study is to create an increased understanding of social and economic value in the Paisley cultural sector. The main studied period will thus be 2016-2019; the bid was lost in December 2017, and the period can roughly be divided into 2016-2017 where capabilities were built to showcase the bid, 2018 which was largely planned and thus hosted 'as if' Paisley would have won, and 2019 which did not see the same rate of expansion in the events programme, though retained at an ambitious level.

Several of the methods and data sources chosen have been given by the conditions surrounding the study, partially but not solely pertaining to the covid-19 pandemic. The first year of the project was spent embedded part-time in Renfrewshire Council's Regeneration Team, conducting exploratory interviews, and learning about the process of shaping the urban regeneration policy in Paisley. This shaped the scope of the study, not least by thoroughly circling in on the case study format. The literature review was shaped by the experience. One of the first tasks was producing a report on Renfrewshire's data collection at publicly funded events, which included access to the series of ambitious event evaluations commissioned by the Council from 2016 on. The data was only rudimentarily analysed and provided an opportunity to use a wealth of quantitative data, mostly untouched. The main impact of Covid-19 for the study, discussed above, was to render impossible some of the planned quantitative and qualitative data collection on-site in Paisley, making a key stakeholder interview series, combined with a retroactive digital survey the best alternative results. This also changed the timescale to primarily 2016-2019 rather than until early 2021.

The main concern of this project is the value created from events and festivals, in a broad sense, and an intention not to restrict this to the tools of a specific paradigm. Several methods and methodologies are needed to accommodate the data showing different faces of value.

This chapter contains the research design and its philosophical underpinnings, starting with the objectives, aims, and objectives. Though the research design changed during the course

of the study, these have remained stable; solutions were found to answer these questions in the face of changing conditions. Then, research philosophy is presented, guided by Tashakkori and Creswell's (2007) understanding of pragmatism. The study is mixed methods, and its approach is not least guided by Creswell (2011) and Bryman (2007), and their critiques of mandatory single-method science. After that, the methods used are outlined. In addition to traditional quantitative and qualitative methods (including observational data), the case study as a method is discussed.

Considerations and consequences of design choices are also discussed. This pertains to research reliability and validity (including generalisability and replicability); generalisability of case studies is typically low, but other strengths in validity may compensate. The same is true with reliability issues. Finally, ethical considerations are brought up. The most prominent are the discussions on the difference between studying contemporary and previous events (or, as in this research, both), the intimate relationship to Renfrewshire Council, and the reliability of using a wide range of tools in a single piece of research.

5.1 Aim and research objectives

The aim of this research is to widen the scope of topics feasible to study with a public value framework, specifically applying it to cultural events and festivals in Paisley to bridge traditionally conflicting methods of event evaluation and improve public investment strategy. This will be realised through four research objectives:

Research objectives:

1. Measure the economic effect of public events in Paisley 2016-2019 through analysis of spending related to the events.
2. Evaluate the experience of those events, based on the revealed and stated preferences of event visitors and local businesses.
3. Understand social and public value impacts of Paisley public events, through a public value framework with social value tools.

4. Explore the possibilities of public value theory as a tool for analysing quantitative and qualitative data from cultural events.

The first and (to a lesser extent) the second objective will be underpinned by cost-benefit analysis. The tools available in CBA provide powerful and evidence-based evaluation techniques in the analysis of market behaviour as well as questionnaires. Techniques such as TCM and WTP are tested and continually utilised in the events area for evaluation of large events. It is also trusted by policymakers, which is not just a bonus, but highly relevant for the result of this study. The second and third objective investigations are underpinned by public value theory. In addition to specific public value tools, social value of events is surveyed as part of the public value framework. The third objective alludes to the development of public value-based tools for event evaluation.

5.2 Research Methodology

For the research objectives to be fulfilled, a mixed methods approach has been chosen to be able to explore motivations and evaluation techniques of social and economic value of events. One useful typology, used in many mixed methods studies, is the typology laid out by Greene (2007). This typology displays the advantages and disadvantages of choosing a mixed methods approach. According to it, four key domains shape research methodology:

1. Philosophical assumptions and stances
2. Inquiry logics
3. Guidelines for practice
4. Socio-political commitments

(Greene 2007)

The first relates to the epistemological and ontological ways of how knowledge can be created in a scientific setting. There is therefore a section outlining how knowledge creation has been treated in the fields this research encompasses. A central contribution of this

research is the usage of both economic and social value in the same evaluation of cultural events. The different norms of knowledge theory are thus discussed below. The underpinnings of this study are based on the pragmatist research paradigm. This is associated with a 'both and' epistemological stance described by Tashakkori et al. (1998) as accepting "Both objective and subjective points of view". This stance was controversial in the so-called paradigm wars (Bryman, 2008) where quantitative methodology, and later mixed methods, were accepted into the mainstream.

The second section takes one step down from knowledge theory to discussion of the methodological paradigm rather than theory of knowledge: How do the pieces of the study fit together, and what is the rationale? The role of the researcher, and how observation is done, are captured by this domain. In this case, the methodology is based on pragmatist ideas; tools which can best answer the questions should be used. In mixed methods, there are two main ways of treating this methodology, namely the multi-paradigmatic approach of Taylor et al. (2012), and the increasingly successful attempt to build a coherent pragmatist methodology (Greene, 2007; Bryman, 2008). This is discussed in detail in the sections on pragmatism and mixed methods.

The third domain is relating to the specific practices of carrying out data collection and the steps taken after the theoretical decisions: methods, analysis, sampling, and other practical specificities of the study. In this case, 'mixed methods' is in between domains two and three. The specific methods utilised are interviews, surveys, and observation. This is also a case study, looking at the case of Paisley. Yin (1994:14) argues that case studies are well-fitted for mixed-methods research. Case studies, according to Flyvberg (2011), are contested as a study approach overall: their status between method and methodology is discussed and motivated in a designated section.

Greene suggests that the socio-political commitments constitute a fourth section. This includes political stances, but also the study's relation to policy and government, and ongoing debates in wider society and the scientific community (Greene 2007). The possibility of normative research has been popularised in mixed methods research via the transformative approach (Dietz & Rogers 2012), about which there is further discussion

below. Normative research provides important methodological tools for policy research as discussed by Robert and Zeckhauser (2011) and critical theory (as discussed in Morrow & Brown 1994). Defining one's relationship to normative political issues is especially important when aiming to provide policy advice and writing in a field of study where critical theory is common. This study stays clear of the normative perspective; it would likely be counter-productive to be divisive whilst trying to join seemingly incompatible evaluation paradigms.

This study adheres to the structure, and each section is aimed at being relevant to answer one or the other of these four dimensions. Greene's typology has helped to make sense of a multidisciplinary study, assigning both economics and sociology/political science considerations at the same levels of analysis. The usage of socio-political commitments as a fourth dimension adds to the policy analysis and advice aspect, keeping it central whilst staying away from a normative approach.

5.2.1 Epistemology

The traditional stance of knowledge creation in economics research is positivist (Caldwell 1980). Far into the 20th century models claimed to be general, causal, and with a good degree of predictive power. This has been challenged from several directions since, and the "paradigm wars" of the 1980s (leading to a "Paradigm peace"; Bryman, 2006) left qualitative methodology as a viable alternative for most social science (Bryman 2008). Economics still relies on the positivist scientific method more than other social sciences. The epistemology is harder and closer to that of natural sciences.

A central theme in debates on economics epistemology is that of positive (as in positivist) versus normative. The critical side of this debate accuses normative statements of being concealed as positive ones. The actors in economic models ideally adhere to a set of characteristics: rational, maximising, self-interested, and consistent. Sen (1977) challenges the assumptions by pointing out that these characteristics cannot be observed, and that they fail to consider very basic human phenomena such as sympathy, commitment, and serendipity. He also develops Samuelson's (1948) argument that "Behavior, it appears, is to be explained in terms of preferences, which are in turn defined only by behaviour."

This critique has led to a re-evaluation of economic knowledge: assumptions of rational behaviour are not positive but rather normative. One of the most influential solutions to this problem is the essay “The Methodology of Positive Economics” by Friedman (1953). Friedman accepts that classical economics may contain unreasonable axioms on a philosophical level. However, the goal of economic models is not to give a perfect model of society, but rather to predict economic events before they happen. According to Friedman, an understanding of society or individuals may be flawed, but the model with the strongest predictive power for the behaviour it claims to understand is also the best model. Sen (1977) notes that the outcomes and the intentions are not always aligned, using a common critique of consequentialist ethics, but according to Friedman, that is irrelevant. Friedman’s model gives the economist an important role in society, being able to predict and steer society’s future, which has been attractive to economists.

Thus, based on Friedman’s theory, one can create economic models with ‘unreasonable’, normative statements such as that *actors will maximise individual utility and act rationally* because these models predict economic reality best. Friedman’s perspective is heavily criticised as normative and skewed towards neoclassical interpretations of the world (Caldwell 1980). The critique is largely realist, against non-foundationalist, normative pragmatic economics. However, Friedman’s ‘instrumentalism’ (prediction is more important than theory) has an interesting parallel to the pragmatism used in modern mixed methods, such as this study. Wible (1984) writes that “Instrumentalists such as Friedman are unconcerned whether their theories and hypotheses actually correspond with anything in the real world” in relation to Dewey’s (Wible, 1984) early works with similar implications. Charles Sanders Peirce devised the so-called pragmatic maxim: “Consider what effects, that might conceivably have practical bearings, we conceive the object of our conception to have. Then, our conception of these effects is the whole of our conception of the object” (Olshewsky 1983); what is practically useful is all that matters. However, the pragmatist position is not essentially non-realist. Dewey turned later in life, praising other pragmatists for being able to combine realism with pragmatism (Wible 1984). Still, scholars discuss whether positivism can be used as a single paradigm incorporating pragmatism (Feiltzer,

2009) and mixed methods scholars discuss whether pragmatism can cover all the needs of positivism or constructivism.

In Chapter 4, Pareto economics are presented as the foundation of cost-benefit analysis. In its offspring, welfare economics, human utility poses a fundamental epistemological question: can we calculate cardinal utility, or must we make do with ordinal (Dasgupta & Pearce 1972)? Though belief in the measurement of cardinality is uncommon, there are different ways of approaching ordinality. In Moscati's (2018) words, the question is whether we believe that utility is an "existing mental entity", or an abstract parameter in use only for our theories. The 'theoretical abstraction' view of utility has been criticised by positivists for its relativism; either utility exists or not (Bruni & Guala 2001). That does not mean that positivists generally disagree with ordinality as a basis for economics; research has not reached cardinal understanding of utility and maybe never will. Neither does ordinality require normativity (though utility is inherently subjective).

Concepts of value are not static in economics. The contestation is ongoing, though an instrumentally inspired view is still popular, as well as CBA leaning towards a limited, ordinal quantification of utility. In the creation of social value, other rules apply, partially due to the lack of a need for a monetary index and often qualitative methodology.

5.2.2 Knowledge creation of social value

Social value is virtually any value positive for society; the discussion on the related public value in Chapter 2 can be taken as an example. Moore (1995) is more prescriptive than Bozeman (2002), with the latter focusing on deliberation to be able to define what is actually valuable to those enjoying the values. Vanclay (2003) gives a sense of the breadth of social value: "aesthetic impacts (landscape analysis); archaeological and cultural heritage impacts (both tangible and non-tangible); community impacts; cultural impacts; demographic impacts; development impacts; economic and fiscal impacts; gender impacts; health and mental health impacts; impacts on indigenous rights; infrastructural impacts, institutional impacts; leisure and tourism impacts; political impacts (human rights,

governance, democratisation etc); poverty; psychological impacts; resource issues (access and ownership of resources); impacts on social and human capital; and other impacts on societies.” These values being very different from each other, and a long way from a simple conversion to a monetary figure, social (and public) value scholars may take a critical stance against those who attempt it (such as critical event studies, discussed in Chapter 3; Platt et al., 2016).

Even proponents and projects using monetisable or economics methods for calculating event value, such as O’Brien (2010), Siegfried and Zimbalist (2006), and Bianchini et al. (University of Hull, 2021) agree that social value is an important indicator. Yet, social value metrics are contested. Critical perspectives underline how common indicators for social value have negative sides omitted from evaluations and the spotlight. Devine and Quinn (2019) show how the understanding of events’ social value production is still poor, despite being flaunted in studies. Wallstam (2022) shows how stakeholders retain a low engagement with social value, despite readily available knowledge. De Lisio and Sodre (2019) show how negative social value, in this case further marginalisation of sex workers, may be sanctioned by mega-events organisers despite efforts to display a socially engaged façade. Trusting the positive values is an issue which is likely to develop. To a decreasing extent, it is still part of challenging problematic economism to discuss social value at all. On the other hand, being overly positive about the social value created through events is problematic, possibly legitimising hidden social costs.

Where the definition of economic value is comparatively straightforward, social value is not easily captured partially due to the difficulty of reconciling what is valuable (Nabatchi 2012). They are typically not compatible without additional tools, some of which may be unattractive to either social or economic scholars. To be able to count social value, there are three ways which are often used by scholars. All have flaws. First, one may use some cost-benefit style calculation which translates social value into monetary figures, and with it follows the problems of leaving important intangibles aside. The social value risks being dwarfed by private interests or missing some of the key points because of lacking methods for calculating some areas of value. This is the approach guiding the Green Book and thus many public UK interventions in the culture sector (HM Treasury, 2022). Second, one may

choose to quantify social value into a non-universal unit of measurement; cardinal utility, QALY, or subjective wellbeing (which works under ordinal utility as well) (these are discussed by O'Brien, 2010; Fujiwara et al., 2021 apply it). These all face similar problems as the CBA; the universal constant is not easily translated. QALY is already accepted as a monetisable constant in several areas, including healthcare (Téhard et al., 2020). Likert-style scales of strength of preference and similar methods are important to gauge opinions but may end up only being comparable to other programmes where the same evaluation model is used. And without the medium of a universal currency, it is difficult to trade off social value; how to compare "pride in place" and "local pride"? Third, social value can be described in terms of strength of opinion, but not put in relation to others. This is the qualitative approach used by most of those primarily interested in social value (Smith et al., 2021).

The epistemological stance of social value evaluation is therefore depending on which way data is treated. Is it quantified to a universal constant (such as money)? If so, a (post-) positivist paradigm is more suitable with its potential to generalise experiences (as discussed critically by Lin, 2013). If not, a constructivist paradigm is a more likely choice. The advantage of using none of these, but accepting both as viable ways to reach knowledge, is that both can be used as input and compared. Several of the methods in the cost-benefit tradition used in this study are based on subjective experiences and their willingness to quantify that experience into a monetary value. Other values, social and public, are analysed by applying exchange rates into direct utility measures. Being noncommittal on paradigms means that these can still be put in relation to each other, and respondents can reflect on whether they prioritised the monetised value or the social value. This gives a point of reference, even though it does not directly monetise e.g. wellbeing such as the Fujiwara et al. model (2014). If the respondent values a social value higher than a value which has been accepted within the study as monetisable, then an 'at least' figure of the social value appears. This is not presented in a bottom-line format but rather becomes a way of escaping the watertight compartments between different types of data.

5.2.3 Pragmatism

Pragmatism is a philosophical school of thought as well as a research paradigm. The “Consider what works” approach could easily be misunderstood as “Anything goes”, but rather than methodological anarchy, it places the starting point not in philosophy but in the question at hand. Brierley (2017) means that this approach will enable finding answers to questions that could not have been answered otherwise. “Starting out with the research question”, in this case, means that the researcher is not bound by methodological boundaries, and is open to any possible manner of finding an answer to the research question. The main issue with this is epistemological: what can we really say about the world, and are we really well-advised if we let that depend on what is convenient? Morgan (2014) explains that “Rather than assigning post-positivism and constructivism a priori to different ontological and epistemological camps, a pragmatist would focus on their characteristic approaches to inquiry.” In this sense, the answer to the question is yes. We may even be helped by different epistemologies. Posed like this, the question is the same as: are interviews a good choice for solving some problems, and surveys for others? Indeed, the paradigm wars of the 1980s showed that many parts of the scientific community will invest their time and prestige in arguing for a single way of understanding the creation of knowledge (Bryman, 2008; Gage, 1989). With this becoming more uncommon, and a live-and-let-live approach dominates, pragmatist epistemology comes off as more sensible.

The word ‘pragmatism’ derives from the Greek ‘pragma’ relating to an action, or something being done – compare to English ‘practical’ (Kalolo 2015). Indeed, the action-oriented approach present in the vernacular meaning of the word transfers to the philosophical school, too. Pragmatism is primarily associated with the American philosophers Charles Sanders Peirce and John Dewey. Peirce’s view of the scientific method contained both ‘abductive’, ‘deductive’, and ‘inductive’ reasoning; the formulation of hypotheses, and two different approaches to testing them were necessary tools for creating scientific knowledge, even from his horizon of a mathematician and geodesist (Burch & Parker 2022). This and the generosity regarding methodology as formulated in the pragmatist maxim (see above), have inspired a paradigmatic development of mixed methods.

Though there are some differing opinions as to what part of a research design pragmatism fits best (Friedrichs & Kratochwil, 2009 still talk about it as methodology), it is generally thought of as a 'philosophical framework' or a 'paradigm' (Morgan, 2014). Getting back to paradigmatic thinking below, for this study, pragmatism is mainly the guiding philosophical framework. In pragmatism, there is not a set of distinct rules for what type of inquiry is possible to achieve. Instead, it accepts the value of different ways of studying a phenomenon, and that these multiple perspectives may give a fuller understanding, despite contrasting philosophical features (Kalolo 2015). The pragmatist scholar may even regard the rigorous adherence to a single method for achieving knowledge as a limitation.

During these 'paradigm wars' (Bryman, 2008) of the 1980s, researchers using constructivist approaches challenged the notion that positivist stances were the only viable for answering many questions in social science. This, in addition to making qualitative research more equal to quantitative, created a renewed interest in Thomas Kuhn's *paradigm* concept as parts of his writing on scientific revolutions (1970). The basic concept is that a way of thinking and doing science reaches the mainstream and is a dominant "normal science". This is subsequently challenged by "revolutions" which brings a new "normal" into the world. Sankey (1993) tracks Kuhn's development, and a key tenet of different paradigms is "incommensurability". In Kuhn's early work, this means "methodological, observational, and conceptual disparity" between different ways of doing science (Sankey, 1993). Kuhn's views grew in prominence in wider social science circles during the paradigm wars as it was an apparent case of "revolution" from one paradigm wanting to break into normal science. Gage's (1989) meant that the qualitative critique was a bad alternative because of its poor feasibility as a full paradigm. Instead, ("old-fashioned") pragmatism was one of the alternatives of the paradigm wars because of its possibility of constituting a paradigm rather than being a critique. Gage's thesis was unfashionable for several more decades; qualitative interpretivist methodology constitutes a less confrontational, second big alternative to quantitative positivist (Creswell 2011). But his discussion of pragmatism as a type of resolution of epistemological tension remains and grows with pragmatism's increasing popularity.

In addition to pragmatism, the major movement of methodology refusing to stay within the boundaries of positivist/constructivist duality is *transformative research*. According to Bryman (2008) and Mertens (2007), it poses a deeper challenge to the existing paradigms than the 'live and let live' approach adopted by pragmatism. In transformative methodology, just like in the qualitative paradigm, positivism's claim to objectivity is criticised. But more than that, the strife of science trying to approach intersubjectivity is put into question (Taylor et al. 2012). Sticking to a single paradigm, even the "so-called inclusive" (Taylor et al. 2012) mixed methods may be an obstacle. Instead, transformative research aims at breaking free from these boundaries and developing, *transforming*, research or society. In transformative research, Kuhn's (1970) theory of scientific paradigms is not just an explanation of progress in the history of ideas, but a definition of where the problem lies: transformative research is partially defined by its will to break free from current discourses and normal science. Dietz and Rogers (2012) mean that transformative research "does not fare well", "does not comfortably fit", and is "difficult to interpret" when looked at through the paradigms of normal science (in Kuhn's meaning of the phrase). It is in this sense a break with tradition, a normative alternative.

The common features of transformative and pragmatism are thus primarily threefold: an unwillingness to stay within traditional epistemological territories, a good fit with mixed methods, and a surge in popularity in the 00s. Biddle & Shafft (2015), arguing for a transformative approach, claim that pragmatism's focus on "'what works' [...] often tends to overshadow 'what works for whom?' And 'to what end?'" This illustrates the normative element of transformative research, and the main point of divergence. Biddle & Shafft (2015) are interested in the revolutionary (in the Kuhnian sense) development of science. Thus, they claim that pragmatism has become 'normal science' (again, in the Kuhnian sense), and that a transformative approach should be the next step. 'Should' is a word seldom used in academic texts, but in discussions of the transformative paradigm, it is warranted.

A third way of accepting a deviation from the traditional paradigms is to reject the notion that paradigms are static. Symonds & Gorard (2008) argue that we need to accept that the old dichotomies of induction/deduction, numbers/texts, and positivism/interpretivism are

not cut in stone, without calling that stance a third road (such as pragmatism). An amount of flexibility, according to them, may be more useful than committing to an entirely new paradigm.

This study has chosen methods based on pragmatist reasoning. The pragmatic framework enables traditionally divergent methodologies, including data typically associated with both cost-benefit and public value analysis. The public value perspective argues openly against the paradigm of quantifiable human values: CBA, NPM, and GDP. A generous methodology is susceptible to criticism from both sides. The cost-benefit perspective will have a limited power of explanation to public value scholars and vice versa. This is where the pragmatic perspective is a useful tool. The opposing angles will paint a fuller picture. This is particularly useful in the intent of informing policymakers. The most used variables for evaluating events: Likert-style satisfaction, number of participants, and gross value added, are limited tools. With dual social and economic perspectives, a higher granularity can be achieved. In the words of Otto von Bismarck; politics is the art of the possible.

Pragmatism, as has been mentioned above, works well in a mixed methods setting. Mixing methods may allow viewing the issue from different viewpoints. Tashakkori & Creswell (2007) have a typology of three ways of asking questions in mixed methods:

1. Separate quantitative and qualitative questions, followed by an explicit mixed methods question.
2. A mixed research objective bridging the different methods, which is subsequently broken down into specific method-apt sub-questions.
3. Constructing questions along the way.

(Tashakkori & Creswell, 2007)

The second and third approaches work especially well with pragmatism, as the bigger issue at hand gets to guide the process towards questions which are more designed for the specific methods available. The third approach, discussed more below, is one of the selling points of both pragmatism and mixed methods – a methodological framework well-fitted for an investigative process.

5.2.4 Mixed Methods

Mixed methods are the practice of combining qualitative and quantitative methods, or indeed other tools such as analysis, concepts, or techniques in the same study. For decades, it was questioned and considered unorthodox due to the epistemological and ontological implications of using several contrasting understandings of knowledge. Mixing methods traces its roots at least back to the multi-trait/multi-method matrix of Campbell and Fiske (1959), and the advantages to validity (and acceptable results on reliability) of using several methods. For decades, it was questioned due to epistemological and methodological concerns, despite influential publications such as Greene (1989). The philosophical concerns are largely the same as those discussed in the previous section, and therefore discussed more specifically relating to methodology here.

Until the 1970s, (post)positivist positions of claiming higher degrees of generalisability and causality enjoyed a higher status than alternative research philosophies (Bryman 2008). During the 1970s and 1980s though, the interpretivist positions with claims of a deeper, but conditioned, understanding of humans was accepted as equally valid in a social science setting (Gage 1989). With this development, social science had two major opposing philosophies to choose from when designing a study. Mixing them was considered controversial specifically because of this opposition. Even though the tools which eventually gave mixed methods their strongest arguments were discussed thoroughly in Greene et al. (1989), it took time to prove its status as a viable option for many studies.

Though a pragmatic approach allows for the mixing of methods at will, a well-designed MM study does not use methods arbitrarily. Rather, Creswell et al. (2003) warn prospective mixed methods researchers that more care must be given to studies beyond the quantitative/qualitative divide. There are different motivations for using mixed methods: *Triangulation* tries to increase the validity of a study by using sufficiently different methods so that irrelevant errors will not covariate (such as previously mentioned Campbell & Fiske, 1959; also used by Yin, 1994 to describe why MM works well in case studies). *Complementarity* uses different methods to increase the power of explanation from one method to the next as a lever. *Development* intends to increase the quality of a study by

making use of one study to develop the other. *Expansion* means to improve the possible scope by studying elements not possible to achieve with only one method. These four concepts, categorised by Greene et al. (1989), are still key arguments for the use of mixed methods.

Mixed methods methodology has partially gained interest because of its strength as a basis for *sequential* designs, (or *development* in Greene et al.'s, 1989 vocabulary) letting an initial method guide a later part of the study using a different method. A preparatory qualitative phase with orienting interviews followed by a survey informed by the interviews (Ivankova et al. 2006) and a survey being used to leverage the results of interviews Creswell (2011) are typical examples. The sequential design is utilised in this study, letting the strengths of one method guide later parts. The preparatory phase is, however, of a similar size as phase 2.

5.3 Methods

With the mixed methods approach presented, the methods may be described. The methods are defined in Table 5, including sampling, presented more in detail in section 5.3.3.2. The following section describes all methods used, strengths of and limitations of those choices. Table 5 shows a timeline of the data collection which is described in the following sections.

Table 5. Methods and sources.

Quantitative	Data source	Sampling method	Collection note
Structured interviews	Attendees (2019)	Convenience + demographic	Interviews conducted by Niclas Hell on-site
Semi-structured interviews (not exclusively quantitative)	Business representatives (2019)	Purposive geographically, sector-wise	Interviews conducted by Niclas Hell on-site
Questionnaire	Online and events (2022)	Convenience	Collected by Niclas Hell via social media recruitment and on-site

Questionnaire (secondary)	RC evaluation reports (2016-2019)	Random	Collected by three different consultancies for RC. Aggregated but not analysed, except parts of 2018; raw data.
Public data index	SIMD (tertiary)	Full population	Collected and collated by Scottish Government.
Qualitative			
Unstructured interviews	Stakeholders (2021-2022)	Purposive	Interviews conducted by Niclas Hell online.
Observation	RC, Scottish government, etc. (2019-2022)	n/a	Observation conducted by Niclas Hell on-site.

Table 6. Timeline of data collection.

	-2019	Q1 19	Q2 19	Q3 19	Q4 19	Q1 20	Pandemic	Q3 21	Q4 21	Q1 22	Q2 22
Evaluation reports	Yellow bar						Red bar				
Informal orienting interviews		Blue bar					Red bar				
Observation RC		Yellow bar						Red bar			
Phase 1 quantitative data				Grey bar			Red bar				
Unstructured interviews							Red bar	Blue bar			
Phase 2 quantitative data							Red bar			Dark blue bar	
Observation SG							Red bar				Brown bar

5.3.1 Case Study

Being a case study, this project has the liberty of choosing data sources freely, rather than conforming to data which can be easily and reliably compared. Yin (1994:14) means that this is a good reason to consider mixed methods for case studies. The features of a case study, especially a single case study, means that the study must argue that the case in itself is an interesting unit of study, as stated by Gummesson (2000:84). One of the major authorities on case studies, Robert Yin, argues that case studies “the case study is a separate research

method that has its own research designs” (2012:20). The research design, in Yin’s terms, does not constitute a separate *paradigm*, but rather giving guidance to “what questions to study, what data is relevant, what data to collect, and how to analyse the results” (Yin 2012:21). In this case, the project could focus more widely on more than one method for event evaluation, accepting a larger and uniquely Paisley-based body of data. In a non-case study, issues with intersubjectivity and validity would indeed have made a different set of data sources and methods for analysis a better choice. Yin (1994:43) describes the potential of a (“highly regarded”) case study using a wide array of inputs: “The main unit was the organization as a whole, the smallest unit was the individual member, and several intermediary units were also important. At each level of analysis, different data collection techniques were used, ranging from historical to survey analysis” (referring to Lipset et al., 1956). Yin’s (2013) perspective on generalisability and validity is discussed further below, in the Limitations section.

5.3.1.1 Paisley as a case study

The study looks at a single case – Paisley. It regards a range of stakeholders as beneficiaries (and producers) of value and takes these into account for the analysis. This design is guided by Yin’s (2009:50) embedded approach; a single case but divided into several units of study. The heterogeneity of data and stakeholders was designed to create data triangulation, which is also discussed above: to “collect information from multiple sources but aimed at corroborating the same fact or phenomenon” (Yin, 2009:114). Yin also underlines the importance of working closely with theory in case studies (1994:28). Whether it is testing or producing theory, the value of a case study for the wider scientific community will be based on its ability to interact with external theory; empirically, a case study keeps within the case’s boundaries.

Renfrewshire Council is the organiser of the events and instigator of the urban regeneration schemes, and thus many of the benefits and costs studied are related to their work and investments. NGOs, private businesses, private individuals, and national agencies are all studied in addition to RC; the case studied is Paisley, not the council.

Alison McCandlish (2019), Conor Wilson (2022), and Lan Pham (2023) have also produced PhD theses about the cultural environment and regeneration of Paisley. McCandlish' (& McPherson, 2021) work studies the hidden cultural heritage of Paisley, with work performed in the midst of the 2021 UKCoC bid. This has been an inspiration in the method of studying and assessing single features of a town in the process of regeneration. Wilson's work on hybrid placemaking in Paisley, and Pham's in wellbeing in an inclusive regeneration scheme have been parallel to this study, creating borders as well as inspiring examples of case studies on the same case.

A large "body of work has been published on the cultural policy, urban regeneration, and events of Glasgow, the local authority neighbouring Renfrewshire (García, 2014; Mooney, 2006; Pike, 2017; Edwards, 2018; Bianchini & Parkinson, 1994). The similar setting, the proximity, Glasgow's status as a textbook example of event-led regeneration, the large number of case studies, that Glasgow's 1990 ECoC (and Manchester 2008) inspired the creation of UKCoC, and that Paisley's effort has been shaped by both Glasgow's policies and the dynamics of living in the shadow of a much larger city, have made many references to Glasgow inevitable, which can be seen throughout this thesis. Most notably, Beatriz García's (2016; 2019; García & Cox 2013) work on policies relating to ECoC and Clare Edwards PhD thesis (2018) on the cultural policies leading up to Glasgow 1990 have shaped the case study approach, and the retrospective perspective.

5.3.2 Observation

Observational data was collected throughout the study. The observation was carried out with the help of some ethnographic practices. Brewer (2000) a standard reference on modern ethnography, notes that ethnography is a method of collecting data, but not easily separated from the methodology, which is also called ethnography. Though observation is not treated strictly according to ethnographic principles, the method is presented below. Using observation and ethnography is uncommon in economics-related research and merits some attention. Ethnography is in essence a systematic study of human culture; in antiquity, Herodotus and Tacitus both employed it (anachronistically speaking; Skinner, 2012). In the 19th century, travellers and proto-anthropologists studying foreign cultures made use of an

ethnographic method which was initially intuitive and unstructured. The modern version is associated with just that — anthropology and ethnology. The basis is still the same; systematically observing humans to better understand behaviour, institutions, and culture.

Just like other qualitative methods, the goal is to gain deeper insight from observed behaviour, a holistic perspective which cannot be reached from quantifying the behaviour. Ethnography allows the researcher to approach the studied subjects much more than most other methods, taking part in customs and learning things as a participant. This opens up for criticisms of subjectivity, sample size, an almost universal lack of replicability, and biases. The type of data from ethnography is often richer than what could have been achieved with other methods (Lashley, 2017). The propensity for bias is countered by barriers and thresholds which the ethnographer can get beyond; into respondents' workplaces, homes, intimate situations, and without the distance invariably experienced by a stranger surveying a respondent visibly and explicitly. Ethnography is also a useful tool in combination with other methods because it can help formulate hypotheses from real-world behaviours which were not part of the researcher's pre-understanding.

In contemporary science, a major usage of ethnography is observational studies (Brewer, 2000). The common feature of observational research is that it happens in the field; neither experimental, quantitative, nor secondary data can be used for observation (Lashley, 2017). A major contributing factor is the relationship between the researcher and the informants. It is a major advantage to potentially gain the trust of respondents through prolonged interactions (Neyland, 2008). It might also be advantageous that the observing researcher gets a deeper understanding, or even embodies experiences of the respondents' reality. At the same time, this creates the biases mentioned above in the ethnographic method; subjectivity and compromised scientific distance and rigour may be the consequence of it. The arguments against qualitative research are particularly true for observational data, but vice versa, ethnographic researchers will point out that the data obtained through observation cannot be reached in any other way. It may give insight to private, secret, or rare occurrences. Madison (2011:8) also criticises the 'objectivity' of positivism as simply being an institutionalised set of values, which might simply harm the scientific process in not admitting that.

5.3.3 Quantitative Methods

Data collection has partially followed the ‘exploratory’ approach described by Creswell et al. (2007). This application of mixed methods begins by collecting quantitative data guiding the following qualitative stages. Secondary and phase 1 data have given tools informing the latter stages of data collection, including the qualitative. Nonetheless, orienting, non-published interviews were also held early on, and quantitative data were collected late in the process as well. More correctly then, the data collection resembles the “complex” designs discussed later by Creswell (2009).

Initially, the pre-existing secondary data was offered by Renfrewshire Council. This data was collected and collated by various commissioned consultants (EKOS, James Law, Culture Republic), though with a similar methodology. Using the Eventimpacts framework (n.d.), questionnaires are carried out on-site at events and festivals. The Eventimpacts framework has several methodological flaws for academic use: the reliance on simple EIA for a “cautious estimate”, the lack of externalities and multipliers and the catch-all treatment of site and local area. The existing Eventimpacts social impact tool is not used in the Renfrewshire evaluations, though other questions than Eventimpacts’ economic analysis are asked. EIA’s and specifically Eventimpacts’ limited scope concerning cultural values is discussed in Brown et al. (2015) and above.

5.3.3.1 Data sources

Phase one spurred a redesign of the objectives and methods. Results from initial data were promising but needed a redesign to cover all information to properly analyse the values created as part of the events programme. For data sources, see Table 8.

Since the start of the UK City of Culture bid, the public events programme in Paisley has looked virtually the same, with the notable exception of the 2020-2022 hiatus (a smaller 2021 Halloween festival was hosted). Leading up to the first phase, data from event evaluation reports by Renfrewshire Council was used as secondary data analysis. This data

was commissioned by Renfrewshire Council, and carried out by consultancies 2016-2019. Its design is robust, continually similar (at least in large parts), using the well-established Eventimpacts tool (n.d.). The Eventimpacts toolkit includes several features, but only the economic assessment (a cautious EIA) and some demographics are used by RC. In the case of 2018, access was given to raw data for five events, which means that each respondent's replies can be differentiated. This meant that crosstab analysis of this data (n=1,978, collected for RC) was possible. The evaluation reports do give important clues, but in an already-analysed format which limits potential analysis. No econometric methods were used by the consultancies. The second phase of quantitative data was more ambitious overall with two WTP questions and a long range of questions about events, festivals, and preferences.

The Scottish Index of Multiple Deprivation provides some insight into the socioeconomic status of respondents. It is covered in Chapter 4 and regarded as tertiary data. It is used as a supplement to decide respondents' socioeconomic status. It is a somewhat blunt tool; based on postcodes and not individual conditions. However, the area covered by each SIMD zone is small and a better indicator than zoned indexes typically are.

Table 7. Data sources presented in Chapter 6.

Phase 1	Site	Respondents	Collection period
Structured attendee interviews	Events	205	Autumn 2019
Shopkeeper semi-structured	In shops	60	Autumn 2019
Phase 2			
Questionnaire	Online + events	202	2022
Secondary Data			
Renfrewshire Council Evaluations	Events	11,000/1,978	2016-2019
SIMD	Public data	Scotland	2020 publication

The initial research plan was to update the phase one questionnaire after the 2019 event season according to a sequential mixed methods design (Creswell 2003). This was cut short in early 2020 by the covid-19 pandemic. During the latter part of 2020, the study was

redesigned to incorporate an in-depth interview series and to make the second phase a primarily digital survey of retrospective questions. During this period, the public value perspective grew into a significant part of the study's theoretical underpinning, based on Bozeman's (2007; 2015) and Nabatchi's (2012) work.

Particular focus was put on developing the weaknesses of the willingness-to-pay methodology and demonstrating public value. The questionnaire was finalised in the summer of 2021 and after deliberation with the project's stakeholders, training in the survey tools, and ethical approval, it could be distributed in early 2022. Bringing in two new methods entirely – online questionnaires and in-depth interviews – changed the focus to a deep mixed methods study.

5.3.3.2 Econometric tests

Calculations are performed as part of the initial data analysis, presented both in the 'findings' and 'analysis' chapters. The statistics presented in this study are predominantly inferential, based on a sample of respondents in Paisley, which are assumed to be representative of a group (e.g. event attendees). The largest use of inferential statistics beyond simple presentation of average and proportion values, are the DBDC and conjoint models. These are explained more in detail above. Except for these, some basic tests were run on the larger data sets.

The tests were OLS regression (providing R^2 and significance values). OLS regressions estimate the relationship between a dependent variable and a number of independent variables (in this case, one). It is one of the most common statistical methods and produces a linear equation. This is based on the lowest sum of squares between the dependent variable's observations and the estimated values from the regression model's equation. It is typically displayed both graphically in a diagram and as a linear equation. R^2 is a measure that describes how much of the variation can be explained by the independent variable, whereas the significance (p-value) describes the probability that the values are at least as extreme as the data suggests given a null hypothesis (that X has no linear effect on Y); the common p-value limit of <0.05 means that researchers accept any risk below 5 % that the

independent variable really explains the difference in the dependent. All tests in this study use the $p < 0.05$ limit. P-values are criticised for being a way for researchers to 'prove' a hypothesis by implying that a low p-value is the same thing as having identified causation. That is not true; other coefficients could be present, or the covariation could be the source of entirely different causes. P-values are one of the tools that can help reject a null hypothesis. Nonetheless, the relation to the null hypothesis is of interest. These three outputs, being some of the most common statistical tools, are typically presented together as a default (such as the OLS tool in SPSS).

The coefficient of determination (R^2) display how well the variance in a dependent variable can be explained by an independent variable. That is, whether a model predicts that one variable depends on the other fits. It expresses the difference between the point calculated by the regression and the observed data for each point. This is calculated through the model below; by dividing the unexplained (residual) differences in data values by all the differences (explained and unexplained), the result shows how different the data is from the regression model. It produces a number between 0 and 1, where 1 is a high degree of explanation.

The coefficient of determination is defined as:

$$R^2 = 1 - \frac{SS_{res}}{SS_{tot}}$$

SS_{res} = the sum of squares of deviations from the predicted values

SS_{tot} = the total sum of squares (proportional to the variance of the data)

The test is expressed as follows:

$$r(n) = x, p = y \tag{2}$$

where

$r(n)$ = the number of cases

x is the R^2 value, and

$p = y$ is the significance

5.3.3.3 Sampling

Sampling in mixed methods is typically more complex than in other studies, as discussed by Creswell (2009). In addition to multiplying the sampling decisions by the number of data sources, it is necessary to consider implications of overlapping and optimising the sample for the broad scope of a multi-method study. In the case of this study, both random, convenience, and purposive sampling were used due to the different nature of the data. The secondary data, collected by a well-financed consultancy team, was random, which gave a good basis for demographic and opinion data, decreasing the need for that type of sampling later on. Subsequent data collection could thus be tuned towards numbers of respondents, or purposive seeking out of the most relevant respondents. Sampling is also described briefly in Table 5.

A downside of the different sampling techniques is that few or no data sets can be joined together; the difference is too great, not just in time or research design, but also in sampling (Robinson, 2014). The advantages, then, were that the developing research design included new needs of the study, that groups which could not be reached by the one sampling method could be reached by another, and that more data could be collected overall. This was an overarching goal of the research.

The sampling methods used were:

60 shopkeepers were chosen based on these criteria:

Geographical location spread equally around the town centre, and in relation to event venues (see Illustration 4). Inclusion criteria were: open to the public, open during at least part of the event or event preparations. This data set was subject to quota sampling (Robinson, 2014), where different types of businesses were part of the choice. This was, however, subordinate to the geographical spread.

1,977 secondary respondents had been chosen by consultancies. These were approached based on approaching every n th person (actual number of n was variable) at events, by three or four consultants at different parts of the event simultaneously. Every event day and different parts of the day were surveyed. This is the most randomised sampling in this study's data.

Phase 1 had 130 respondents collected on-site at events in Paisley, approached during the different days of the events. As more men were unwilling to participate, more men were approached after the first day, to compensate for that. Respondents of different ages were approached consciously. This convenience sampling, with some care taken into getting a variety of experiences, was meant to be the sample used for phase 2 as well.

Phase 2 collected data primarily through social media; local Facebook groups and Twitter. This was a convenience sampling method, intending to reach Paisley inhabitants. 25 of the 202 respondents were collected at the Food and Drink festival in 2022. Exclusion of non-Paisley inhabitants made some analysis less relevant, but meant a closer focus on local social and public value effects.

In the qualitative section, sampling was purposive “based on the researcher’s a-priori theoretical understanding of the topic” (Robinson, 2014), with the 11 in-depth interview respondents chosen based on the following criteria: covering the non-profit, local government, business, and national government sectors. Covering both practitioners, politicians, and representatives. This sampling method required prior orientation in the Paisley political, non-profit, and business sectors. Initial informal interviews with RC representatives, academics researching Paisley, and those active in the Partnership were all used. The definition of the sample universe was expanded during the process to also include Scottish Government representatives.

5.3.3.4 2019 pilot

During the Autumn of 2019, an extended pilot study was conducted. Primary data was collected at three events in Paisley town centre during October and November 2019: the Halloween festival, the Fireworks extravaganza, and the Christmas Lights Switch On (Illustration 3), all of which were organised by Renfrewshire Council. 130 structured interviews were collected from attendees. The questions were based on the ATLAS Event Monitoring Project questionnaire in a shortened version (Association for Tourism and Leisure Education and Research, n.d.). This survey tool was developed to simplify event evaluation by providing a set of basic questions, just like Eventimpacts. ATLAS is not dependent on some specific theoretical tool such as EIA, and therefore more customisable. Being an early pilot, using a benchmark developed by a team of experts and tested by several studies over several years was a good start for sequential development purposes.

Additionally, 60 short, structured interviews were held after the Halloween festival (30) and the Christmas lights switch-on (30) with representatives for local businesses in Paisley (Illustration 4). The Halloween festival is the largest in Scotland, the most ambitious public event hosted in Paisley with five outdoor and indoor venues across two days. The Christmas lights switch-on is a one-night event with amusement rides, a cultural programme, and, tautologically, the switching on of the public Christmas lights across Paisley.

Illustration 3. Paisley 2019, seconds after the Christmas lights have been switched on. Photo: Niclas Hell

The aims of this pilot were threefold: first, to attend the events and festivals in Paisley and interview the attendees and business representatives affected directly by them; the main topic was willingness-to-pay, social value, and satisfaction. The structured and semi-structured interviews used for these groups respectively were comparatively short, but because this was early in the process, respondents willing to speak freely about their experiences gave invaluable information for the continued development of the study. Second, the concepts developed in the early months of the PhD were tested. The attendee questionnaire contains a direct willingness-to-pay question (for baseline figures which are not added to the bottom-line results), reasons to attend the event, and some open-ended reasoning about the qualities of the programme. The interviews with businesses pose questions on their opinion and knowledge of the events, as well as how events affect them. Third, as the pilot was ultimately possible to extend beyond the initial ambition, it became possible to use the pilot as one of the actual data sources of the thesis.

Illustration 4. Map of Paisley with shops visited for interviews and venues for event items. Fireworks, being a short event, was not studied business-side. (Map source: OpenStreetMap)

The usage of on-site primary data event attendee questionnaires was supposed to be the central feature of this study, which ultimately was impossible. The updated research design turned out deliberately more ambitious, and with a wider focus for higher validity. The 60 structured interviews with shop representatives were especially useful, as no other study was found showing both economic and social value according to local shop representatives; shopkeepers may be expected to put their own business first, making their view of social and non-use values less interesting to study. The usefulness of the informal, qualitative features of this first phase contributed to the wide array of methods used later.

The attendee part gathered 205 respondents randomly approached during the events. Though very limited demographic data was collected to keep the survey lightweight, a slight majority of women were willing to respond. Locals were overrepresented compared to RC's surveys, likely because of this study's smaller sample size.

5.3.3.5 E-Survey

Early 2022, an electronic questionnaire was distributed to three sets of respondents. The majority was found in local social media groups, thus focusing on locals rather than a general sample of visitors; these were amply captured by RC evaluation reports. A smaller number of respondents were also approached at Paisley events in the first half of 2022; there had been minor events in 2021, but as covid-19 restrictions were in effect until April 2022, that was the starting point for a regular events schedule. A few of the respondents were recruited via social media posts by Renfrewshire Council. The exact proportions are difficult to estimate precisely due to the synchronous recruitment. 202 respondents completed the survey, although 20 more provided answers to most questions. There is no evidence of poor quality or insincere responses (such as patterned responses from someone clicking through the survey quickly).

The survey collected basic demographic data though some, such as full postcode, were requested by RC to be excluded. The majority of questions related to social value (sense of community, pride in place, social cohesion) and use values of the cultural experience. Open-ended questions proved a fruitful way of getting more data from respondents. This survey moved some of the content from the ATLAS questionnaire, but the overlap was small; no conclusions were made based on either combining the two groups of participants. The 2019 and 2022 phases are not treated as a time series either. The lack of demographic data and the lack of combined samples might have constituted a validity problem. This was deemed acceptable as ample data from Renfrewshire Council's evaluation was available for these types of evaluations collected during the main period of interest, 2016-2019.

The social value questions used a five-point Likert scale from "Strongly disagree" to "Strongly agree", which implies a bipolarity between 'agreeing' and 'disagreeing' (Jebb et al., 2019). Jebb et al.'s (2019) review of Likert scale developments notes that a unipolar scale of "Not at all" to "Extremely" implies something else. Depending on how questions are posed, a respondent could interpret a "Not at all" reply as synonymous to either the 3-point "Neutral" or the 1-point "Strongly disagree", or neither. The Agree/Disagree version was chosen because it is familiar to most respondents, minimising the risk of confusion, despite both being viable alternatives.

This survey gauges willingness-to-pay through double-bounded dichotomous choice (DBDC) and further preferences through the part-worths of a conjoint bundle analysis. These are described thoroughly in Chapter 4. The questions posed and results are described in Chapter 6.

The DBDC first asks whether the respondent would prefer that events in Paisley were financed by tax outtake or direct ticket sales. After that, respondents are asked what they would be willing to pay for the public events in Paisley, assuming that there are 6-8 per year. The amount suggested is random (one of seven categories between £1 and £30 per event). If a respondent says 'no', they are suggested a lower sum, and vice versa, if the respondent says 'yes', they are suggested a higher sum. This continues until either (1) the maximum WTP is reached (i.e. until they have said 'yes' and 'no' at least once each), (2) the respondent says 'no' to the lowest suggestion (£1), or (3) the respondent says yes to the highest suggestion (£30). The randomised starting point reduces the uniform starting point bias, and the iteration provides the highest valid WTP without needing to calculate it through indirect means, such as the survival function used by Báez and Herrero (2012).

The conjoint bundle contains five dimensions, which was considered the best compromise between validity, granularity, and legibility. The bundles consisted of random event programmes based on two-to-three option dimensions. Two of these were three-option interval scales (frequency of events, cost of events), three were two-option ordinal scales (type of shows, event themes, and level of tourism focus). Each respondent is presented with two bundles and chooses the most attractive one. This is iterated thrice with two random bundles each time. From this, the relative preference value of the different dimensions is calculated, as well as the (polarity and) strength of preference for each alternative within the dimension. In other words, how important is the cost compared to the frequency, and which frequency is most preferred?

The tool used for the e-survey was Questionpro, which is an advanced online service for survey management and analysis. Their conjoint analysis and dichotomous choice provide ready-made calculations. At the design stage, the plan was to use direct input calculation of average values for the DBDC, rather than more advanced methods such as the Báez and

Herrero (2012) survival function. Questionpro's default analysis only provides basic calculations of proportions and price elasticity, which fit this study's purposes. The conjoint analysis uses a multinomial logit model, also in line with the initial design. Their methodology (Questionpro, 2023) aligns well with the calculation of part-worths suggested by Rao (2020), though it uses a more advanced statistical model to be able to handle a wider array of functionalities. The alternative would be an ordinary least squares (OLS) regression, which is a good choice for cardinality. The downside is that OLS treats dependent variables as continuous; the logit model is developed to handle discrete choices. With an OLS, the bundles would have required a different, cumulative design rather than the freedom of designing alternatives best suited to the study. There are other advantages including varying choice behaviours in individual respondents and non-linear functions, but these would not necessarily warrant another design.

5.3.4 Qualitative Methods

The data collection of qualitative methods started in 2019 and took place until 2022. Both interviews and observations stretch over a longer period. The former are mainly retrospective, whilst the latter are necessarily focused on the time it was observed.

5.3.4.1 *Interview series*

During 2019 and 2020, seven exploratory interviews were conducted, primarily with officers at Renfrewshire Council, to guide the research design. Only three were recorded by other means than by notes. These are not used as direct data input because they were not recorded and transcribed, and were more structured like informative conversations – the route of the thesis had not been decided at that point. Nonetheless, the early interviews guided the developing design of the research greatly. The interviews were based on the same key questions but were open-ended. This was not least due to the embedded position at RC, where ethnographic observation was part of the research process. The informal nature of some interviews, taking part over lunch or coffee at the common workplace, gave key inputs to the continued process. Still, the interviews were formal enough that

respondents were informed that the discussion was a preparatory phase of a research study, its purpose, and they consented to participating.

In 2021 and 2022, 11 interviews were conducted with a selection of elite actors from the Scottish Government, Paisley community groups, Renfrewshire Council, and local businesses. These are presented in [Table 13](#). This later series of interviews constitutes the bulk of the qualitative source material. The interviews were unstructured and lasted between 24 and 80 minutes. Key questions were asked in a semi-structured style, to achieve what McIntosh and Morse (2015) call the Descriptive/Divergent type of interview, which “applies the same interview guide to disparate groups of participants to discern differences and similarities in perspectives and experiences among them with respect to the dominant discourse that underpins the interview guide” (McIntosh & Morse, 2015). The difference in experiences and relevant topics of respondents made the latter parts of the interview more open-ended, with an open discussion on value, Paisley, and events.

5.3.4.2 Embedding and observation

This study makes use of observational data based on the ethnographic method. Observation was a part of the study from inception, with time spent at Renfrewshire Council as a pre-negotiated part of the project. This was expanded during the time spent in relevant institutions where observation could provide additional information. A low-intensity observation was ongoing throughout the time in Paisley, of which some experiences are shared. As a sole source of data, the low validity and reliability of such data would not suffice. However, the added depth and some observations contrary to almost unanimous responses during formal surveys made this a valuable addition, in some cases just as a justifiable question mark in the marginal.

The experience of being a co-worker and getting a deeper understanding of the regeneration process was a key activity. For a year, from spring 2019 until lockdown in 2020, one working day per week was spent at Renfrewshire House, the local authority’s seat. The embedding consisted of being an integrated team member, to be able to better understand the

organisation, its priorities, and how regeneration can work in practice. This had been agreed as a part of the studentship before recruitment began.

The observational method was also used for three months spent in a PhD internship at the Scottish Government, in the National Performance Framework Unit. The NPF is Scotland's implementation of the UN's Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and constitutes an important piece of the wellbeing agenda for Scotland. It does not only concern the government but the whole Scottish society, increasingly requiring the public sector to align with it in due time before 2030 when the SDGs are supposed to have been achieved. This insight into the national monitoring of public value was important for the deepened understanding of what is considered valuable in the Scottish public sector beyond Cost-Benefit values. For an example of an observation of perceived social value, see Illustration 5. The analysis process of the observation is described in-depth in [section 5.3.5](#)

Illustration 5. An observation of culture-related expressions of pride in place in Paisley. PA2 is the postcode covering southern Paisley. (Image: Niclas Hell)

5.3.5 Data analysis design

Qualitative analysis was primarily performed according to a thematic scheme. The 11 in-depth interviews were between 30 and 75 minutes long and 5000-9000 words. Observation data was less extensive, and far from all the content was interesting for this study. Braun and Clarke's (2016) chapter on thematic analysis in the APA's method handbook proved useful; they argue that the "accessibility and flexibility" of thematic analysis is useful as it allows for "inductive versus deductive or theory-driven data coding and analysis, an experiential versus critical orientation to data, and an essentialist versus constructionist theoretical perspective". This approach, backed up by the more rigidly analysed quantitative data, was very stimulating to the analysis.

Nvivo was used for the analysis of the in-depth interviews. Nvivo's approach to thematic analysis is frequently referred to as "Nvivo philosophy", relating to the practices strongly encouraged by the published and indeed Nvivo's functionalities (QSR International, n.d.). This includes good practice tips, such as 'Write a diary of each coding session' as well as specific opportunities and limitations. Data was manually sorted into coding subcategories, which are themselves part of parent categories. The parent codes used for the interviews were: urban regeneration, economics, bidding, tourism, and social value. Additionally, Nvivo philosophy suggests some other parent codes: opinions, memorable quotes, and miscellaneous. These were analysed by going through each code separately to find the gist of respondents' opinions. Basic numerical tests were run on the qualitative data; word frequencies and proportions of different codes. These tests are of low validity, and even lower reliability for the research objectives, and are thus not presented as results, although important tools to orient the researcher in the data.

Observation data, the other qualitative method, is highly contingent on context. The observation did not follow the direct collection-findings-analysis sequence of other data but also gave an important orientation in policy and practices. This data was thus used throughout the study's process, and the excerpts and analysis in Chapter 8 are only a limited part of the use. At this stage, the analysis was less formalised than the interviews. They were read closely and marked based on importance and tagged with the policy or value area it pertained to. The instances most relevant to key concepts were included in the analysis and

findings. This is not dissimilar from a regular thematic analysis, but less rigid than the Nvivo philosophy.

Finally, the analysis, like the data collection, was guided by ethical principles, and the considerations laid out in the application for ethical approval.

5.4 Ethical approval

Ethics approval was sought and received in September 2019 for phase 1 quantitative data collection; see appendices 7-9 for ethics and consent forms. In August 2021, approval was received for phase 2 data including interviews and questionnaires. The observational method was written into the original PhD project description which received approval before the start of the studentship.

As social science research is frequently carried out with the assistance of human respondents, except for desk-based research, there are several standards of good practice. University of the West of Scotland (2023) has a range of ethical standards which need to be followed by researchers there. In addition to these minimum requirements, codes of conduct are a useful addition. This research was conducted with the APA Ethical Principles (2016) in mind. Privacy, confidentiality, and avoiding harm were at the heart of the design process. The greatest potential harm was that of certain interviewees who because of their line of work might be easily identifiable to colleagues or managers with different opinions. The issue was closely discussed with those affected, especially those where universal anonymity was likely to be difficult to uphold.

The anonymity of in-depth interviewees was a major concern of the ethical considerations. Actors in relevant fields in Paisley are few enough that anonymity is likely to be compromised. This was discussed with all interviewees, and several requested to see the parts where they were featured before publication. No major omissions or changes were requested, but minor clarifications and factual errors were addressed. Those mostly affected by this were professionals with a good grasp of the consequences. The potential difficulty of

speaking freely in a professional competence is discussed below in the section below and in Chapter 9.

5.5 Limitations and bias

This study makes use of a great deal of data; primary, secondary, and some tertiary. The data collection methods are digital surveys, on-site event questionnaires, digital and in-person unstructured interviews, observational data from several institutions, and structured interviews from shops. This makes it difficult to compare the study to others with similar scopes; few studies use a similar set of data sources, especially a one-author study. Some good practice of sequential design (such as the step-by-step guides in Creswell's & Hirose, 2019) has not been followed – partially because of the adaption to a changing event situation. The set of data provides insights and perspectives to a wide array of values, but a higher n in the primary data would have provided higher validity, and more clear-cut policy implications could have been produced. Time series, which was part of the original design, cannot be observed in the primary data. With the declining ambition of the evaluation reports after 2017, a high-quality study of 2019-2021 would have provided a strong addition. Retrospective studies suffer from hindsight bias (Teare et al., 2021), which also limits the scope as the focus remains primarily on 2016-2019.

The nature of these limitations provides some upsides. There is enough material for further analysis in the data, both on the quantitative and qualitative side. Broadening the scope from analysing value production, the data and literature review both have the potential to fill holes in existing research after further work (see Chapter 9). The study also provides (limited) analysis of a large proportion of commonly used methods in evaluation: a smörgåsbord of perspectives which likely decreases the risk of reliability problems as the situations and designs have been so different.

5.5.1 Covid-19 considerations

Soon after phase 1 data collection ended, the global covid-19 pandemic spread, rendering

on-site event research practically, politically, and ethically impossible. The design work of the past year before March 2020 was no longer a viable roadmap for a study, and except for the data collected in phase 1, most of that work had to be redone. As stated in an early informal interview in April 2020, Renfrewshire Council very quickly decided to shut events down for a long time, not expecting full-size festivals to be held for several years. The pandemic did not only mean a redesign, but also that the preparations and resources provided to the studentship were halted: the observation at RC ended and their interest in the project waned considerably.

Studying events in Paisley became much more difficult when there were no events available; no one who could have anticipated the pandemic would have chosen such a project during these years. This was not only true of Paisley, of course, but coming out of the pandemic, event research from the last few years is more theoretical, retrospective, or interview-based than before, which has harmed the progress of the field in some ways. This project ultimately widened the scope to triangulate insight from the different sources of data available. This meant being open to all types of data and choosing the sources most fitted to truthfully and relevantly answer the research objectives: the credo of pragmatism. It is not an overstatement to say that this study was delayed by a year and faced a much more difficult task even after that year of redesign. Still, the results may well prove to be more useful for the field of event studies due to its theoretical contribution and mixed data approach.

5.5.2 Hindsight Bias

The study is set in the relatively near past at the time of writing, primarily 2016-2019. The majority of the primary data was gathered in 2021-2022. This gap between experiences and recounting them is problematic, increasing the risk of hindsight bias. Hindsight grants respondents the ability to evaluate an experience such as a cultural event with the outcome already known, according to oral historian Calvillo (2012: 891, seen in Edwards 2018). The 'outcome' is especially relevant in a case such as Paisley, where the goal is to become UK City

of Culture, and the events programmes are communicated as a way for the people of Paisley to rally support and show capabilities.

In phase 1, some social value is gauged by asking respondents about their opinions of the events programme and open-ended comments about values. The shopkeeper interviews also included discussions about value beyond money. Phase 2 had more room for social value, with Likert-style questions about priorities and opinions. This was based on the social value literature discussed in Chapter 4, especially social capital, sense of community, and pride in place.

For the quantitative side of the study, changed opinions about the cultural programme are quite likely. Renfrewshire Council claims that 80 % of Paisley inhabitants participated in the bid in one way or another. The momentum of such an effort is considerable, not least the influence on public opinion. The 2022 quantitative study must thus take this into account: four years after losing the bid, although with many institutions communicating a retained focus on culture.

Despite the potential hindsight bias, the potentially changing attitudes provide insights about an important factor: the long-term development of social value. The investment from Renfrewshire Council is allegedly permanent, with a *cultural regeneration* perspective for all public sector work. Misener and Schulenkorf (2016) highlight that social change may take long time and require community work. Edwards (2018) study of cultural policy in Glasgow also shows the long timelines shaping contemporary social states. What is needed to retain values beyond the project periods is thus discussed in the analysis.

5.5.3 Bias relating to Renfrewshire Council

Renfrewshire Council are the key stakeholders in the events studied and being embedded is a method for unique insight about an organisation's operation. At the same time, the cooperation with them risks researcher bias. Damschroder et al. (2021) discuss the possible problems with having key interviewees from the organisation where the researcher is embedded. There might be a vested interest or a sympathetic drone pipe towards the

organisation. Though this research contains some criticism of RC, not least from several of the interviewees, this is still a clear risk. Damschroder et al. (2021) notes that it may thus affect generalisability. This is already an issue with the high degree of qualitative elements in the study. Chalip and Heere (2013) warn against taking organiser-funded event evaluation at face value; the large amount of data provided by them makes it a large part of the data points analysed. A critical perspective on the design and methodology of that data has been discussed both in Chapter 4 and in this chapter and is contextualised with the data in Chapter 8.

Reen et al. (2021) advise embedded researchers to acknowledge the “importance of using research methods that can account for the inherent bias of conducting projects in an applied setting.” In this case, the ethnographic observational method has embeddedness built into it, with insights that would likely be impossible without it. Curry et al. (2009) discuss how “in such cases, the researcher (as opposed to, for instance, surveys or questionnaires) is the primary instrument for data collection and analysis.” The observational part of the study, more directly affected by the environment at Renfrewshire House, suffers from this problem of being “in an applied setting”. It is however quite possible to separate from other methods and thus retain those methods’ reliability. There is little to no overlap between the people interviewed and surveyed, and those at the workplace.

The most direct influence of Renfrewshire Council was their veto of some minor aspects of the phase 2 questionnaire. The vetoes were of minor significance, and there was no reason to suspect that the results would be more beneficial to RC due to the vetoes. Renfrewshire Council had committed to distributing the questionnaire via email, which originally was planned to be the sole distribution channel as the indicated number of recipients would be at least 10,000. The final design was accepted in July 2021, but after nine months of administrative process, RC decided not to assist the study as previously agreed. RC posted the study on some of their social media accounts asking for respondents, accruing around 10 submissions.

5.6 Validity

Validity relates to the quality of the design of the instruments for a study, whether the relation between phenomenon, indicator, and data is trustworthy. It also relates to whether general conclusions can be drawn from the data. In the case of mixed methods studies, they have a particular responsibility relating to validity. In studies using several types of data, the design of research instruments must follow the same rigorous procedures as in smaller studies, which is a partial explanation to the typically time-consuming nature of mixed methods.

Creswell and Miller (2000) underline that this internal validity, “the credibility of the causal relationships between independent and dependent variables inferred from data”, is considered lower in case studies. One way to mitigate this is the use of mixed methods for validation through the use of different types or sources of data (Modell, 2005). Yin (1994:14) calls this triangulation and associates it closely with case studies. The “Multiple sources of evidence” have the possibility of not just deepening the understanding, but to help validation of the research.

5.6.1 Generalisability

Typically, quantitative studies aim for a higher degree of generalisability (external validity) than qualitative (Johnson, 1997). If a quantitative study cannot be replicated, the results can be rightfully criticised. According to Creswell and Hirose (2019), mixed methods studies can claim a degree of replicability and generalisability; they should not be designed in a manner where sample size or research design compromises those features. Roberts et al. (2019) note that even qualitative features of mixed-method studies can aim for replicability. Where qualitative scholars tend to think it is not desirable, a rigorous coding scheme and design of sampling can create conditions for replication.

The *case study* method, discussed in this chapter, typically waives some claims to generalisability in the sense that a sample is assumed to be representative of the population. The study accepts data which cannot be found elsewhere as inputs. Yin (2013) challenges this idea, instead proposing *analytic generalisation*: “extraction of a more abstract level of ideas from a set of case study findings – ideas that nevertheless can pertain

to newer situations other than the case(s) in the original case study". The study contains a great deal of qualitative data without the standardised sampling or coding needed for full replication according to Roberts et al.'s (2019) demands. Qualitative data tends to lack the prerequisites for sampling generalisability; especially observation data is unique and significant experiences cannot reliably have general claims, considering their potentially unrepresentative nature. The study does however fulfil the analytic generalisability criterion, constituting the implementation of popular urban renewal strategies in a deindustrialised town. The effects are discussed at the abstract level, potentially giving general advice.

On the other hand, quantitative data may be better suited for understanding the situation in other similar environments. There are unfortunately a range of aspects differentiating Paisley's situation from others. Some of the aspects which cannot be removed from Paisley's situation without skewing the results greatly include: the proximity to Glasgow (and Glasgow's reputation), deindustrialisation, major event bidding, poor reputation, densely populated surrounding area, and a social value ethos in the local authority. It is unlikely that other towns and cities can look at this study to understand their own situation. Instead, some of the tools developed for analysis can be used to find other results in other environments. The theoretical contribution can be easily transferred to another setting. Public value in event studies, as well as cost-benefit tools combined with non-monetised social value within the same limited study provide general solutions to a range of specific research problems.

5.7 Reliability

Reliability goes beyond the design of the study as well, looking at the actual measurement and its quality. The data collection is especially susceptible to *procedural* reliability, where instructions to data collectors and respondents, lacking alternatives, stressed or sloppy data collection, difficulty in communicating, and such measurement errors may all cause reliability problems (Ihantola & Kihn, 2011). There were several procedural reliability issues:

1. In phase 2, the same data was collected both on-site and digitally
2. The DBDC question conveyed a great deal of preparatory information

3. The evaluation reports are financed by the event organisers
4. The phase 1 WTP received many protest zeroes

These are typical measurement errors. Phase 1 problems were adjusted during later data collection. The evaluation reports are secondary data, and though some of it is used extensively, the primary data works as validation. This reliability issue is discussed further in the section on legacy and leverage, as well as continuously in the analysis.

In terms of phase 2, these were consciously designed. The dual data collection was chosen because a low n was considered a greater validity problem (low power of explanation) than the reliability problem of differentiated data collection. The DBDC could not be performed reliably without previous information, and all other WTP methods were disregarded as giving lower validity as well.

5.7.1 Replicability

External reliability is largely synonymous to replicability; would another researcher get similar results (Zohrabi, 2013)? Yin (1994:36) shows that what replicability means is sometimes misunderstood, even by researchers: a researcher would need to do the *same* thing, not replicate the results in a similar study.

Because of the research design, with its (very) mixed methods and data input, a full replication of the study is not a *likely* path for later research. The study was *pragmatic* in both the theoretical and vernacular sense of the word. However, some aspects of the study are fully possible to replicate. Phase 1 data, collected on-site in Paisley, as well as analysis (and collection) of the secondary evaluation reports are both easy to replicate, and similar results would likely be found. Indeed, the evaluation reports have been continually collected each season since 2016 by three different consultancies. Phase 1 is based on the ATLAS event questionnaire (Association for Tourism and Leisure Education and Research, n.d.) and the evaluation reports being based on Eventimpacts (n.d.) are both designed to retain a high validity across studies.

6 Quantitative Findings

The quantitative work started by surveying the RC evaluation reports. Thereby some areas were identified where improvements to the current knowledge could be provided. Beyond gross value added, the evaluations' main indicator, it is evident that great utility is created unrelated to the spending and direct programme item-related activities. Thus, as developed in the methodology, it was necessary to conduct a quantitative study to understand the visitors to the events and their preferences. The primary observed behaviour is their spending, their choice to visit the event (the travelled distance and mode of travel), and the impact on local shops. The key stated preference is the willingness to pay for the event experiences and relative preferences of different aspects of events.

The other side of this study looks at public value, and this chapter presents the quantitative findings from that data. The literature review shows a deficit in mainstream evaluation models of all social value, especially for small and medium-sized events, and public value in particular. Economic value are public as well, though because of their analytical difference, they are separated in both findings and analysis. Within this chapter, social value such as pride in place and sense of community are discussed, as defined by Getz (2014) and Snowball and Antrobus (2020). Bozeman's (2015) concepts of *public sphere* and *progressive opportunity* are used to add equity and access to deliberation as measurable variables.

This chapter explores all primary and secondary data sources gathered with quantitative methods. They are structured into monetisable values and public value, although all value is ultimately under the public value umbrella. Below that, phase 1 (2019) and phase 2 (2022) are split in each of the sections. Below that, methods are subsections. Renfrewshire Council's evaluations have a subsection in the economic value part, but not in the social: the economic value is a bearing part of the economic calculations whereas the social and public value used are limited.

6.1 Monetised data

This section addresses data ending up in monetary figures. It includes direct economic data, but also extrapolated figures from stated and revealed preferences. The common feature is that they are potential inputs into a cost-benefit analysis. Some results are briefly presented here because they require presentation adjacent to the actual analysis in Chapter 8.

6.1.1 Renfrewshire data

With the economic methodology used by RC's commissioned reports, the focus is strongly on spending in the local economy. The full questionnaire for the 2018 Halloween event is presented in Appendix 5 of this document. Some of that data can be used to infer additional values, such as travel cost. The increased *visitor* spending in Paisley town centre was estimated to be £2.2m in 2018 (minus casual visitors). Including local spending the number increases to £5.4m (more in Chapter 8).

The results for spending from phase 1 show consistently lower results than Renfrewshire Council's evaluations. This may be due to a range of reasons:

1. Wanting to please the interviewer when they are regarded as a representative for the organisation, as discussed by Breidert et al. (2006). This study's interviewer clearly stated that it was independent research.
2. This study sought respondents throughout the events, making many respondents unsure about how much they would spend at the whole event as they might have had 1.5 nights left of festival attendance when surveyed. These respondents tended to low-ball their estimates, if compared to actual sums reported later in day 2.
3. The Renfrewshire Council interviews required more time, which meant respondents had longer time to think about their answers, possibly boosting answers.
4. The sample was smaller.

A related variable, important to the evaluation reports' methodology was overnight stays; these are presented in absolute numbers in each report. 4 % (67, n=1934, collected for RC) of respondents did spend at least one night away during 2018 excluding the Pipe Band

Championships which is an outlier⁴. Overnight stayers also spent significantly more, despite a large proportion of these staying with friends (thus excluding hotel costs). The average local spent £31 at the event, whereas the average overnight visitor spent £74.

6.1.2 Travel cost

The access to raw data from five events in 2018 meant that analysis could be performed in addition to the limited presentation in the evaluation reports. One of the most significant resources was respondents' postcodes. In Scotland, there are over 145,000 postcodes: 38 people per postcode on average (National Records of Scotland, 2022). This study uses them for travel cost analysis. Both TCM and WTP will include respondents' willingness to give up time and money to attend Paisley festivals, making them central to research objective 1. This can be further complicated by the willingness to pay for social value (e.g. see discussion on QALY in the literature review), but the analysis remains thoroughly economic, keeping this within the first objective.

Results are presented thoroughly in Chapter 8, but the findings are briefly mentioned here. Travel cost could be partially decided using travel times using Maply's GIS software connected to Google Maps, and the value of travel time based on literature and Renfrewshire's own data for the value of volunteering work. An $n=1582$ (collected for RC) gave an average distance from the event of 15.8 km by seven stated modes of transport, all operationalised in Appendix A. The average direct cost of travel was £5.16 one-way. The value of the time plus cost was estimated at £10.7, one way. A full table is presented in Chapter 8.

Statistical tests were performed to better understand those who spent money at the festivals using SIMD zones to determine socioeconomic deprivation. The spending at events was partially explained by the socioeconomic group (as indicated by SIMDs data zones, which motivates the OLS method) of the respondents with a very high significance, but with

⁴ The outlier was removed because the Pipe band championships had a very different profile than any other event in Paisley. It had a different set of values attached, it only stayed in Paisley for a few years, and likely needs different policy priorities to attract other, similar events.

a low goodness-of-fit according to an R^2 test ($r^2(1768) = 0.04$, $p = <0.01$). The same was true for when looking at individual events. The average socioeconomic profile varied between events, but the spending was consistently unrelated to socioeconomic status. For example, a n R^2 of the Halloween festival gave a poor fit: $r^2(384) = -0.06$, $p = 0.9$).

6.1.3 Monetisable impact phase 1

6.1.3.1 On-site questionnaire

The key question to understanding the perceived economic value in phase 1 was the open-ended willingness-to-pay question. The question was: “If this event was ticketed, what is the maximum you would be willing to pay to attend it?” though with the caveat that there were no plans of actually charging for tickets. This is similar to the original WTP question developed in the 1950s by French researchers such as Stoetzel (1954) and Adam (1958). As discussed by Breidert et al. (2006) and in Chapter 4, the direct method has largely fallen out of favour. The method was changed in phase 2; phase 1 gave a tentative result and opinions about value aired by respondents. WTP was calculated by averages of the stated response, with no weighting applied.

Around 20 % of respondents did not give a monetary value, which was recorded as £0. The zero values are not interpreted as true zeroes, but rather as protest zeroes based on how the responses were given (Cho et al., 2008; Halstead et al, 1992). Thus, by removing these, the average WTP value is, instead, £6.4 (£5.1 with zeroes). Results of the willingness-to-pay question were remarkably similar between events; the 20-minute fireworks show, with only minor activities surrounding the display, received a similar result to the weekend-long, highly ambitious Halloween festival. This underlines the inability or unwillingness to concretise the value of the experience.

According to the Renfrewshire evaluations for the same year, the number of people attending was around 142,000. Paired with the budget of the direct event expenditures for Renfrewshire Council at £1.1 million, this gives a £6.8 public cost for each attendant. There are indications that the figures were not as high as the actual willingness to pay. Several

respondents said that the figures they stated were in fact what they would be willing to pay in addition to supporting the current tax subsidies. These responses would indicate that they interpreted the question as purely the consumer surplus they receive from the events, rather than a maximum price tag. Though the misunderstanding of the questions was problematic for validity, the WTP showed that the current financing at the very least enjoyed support. Lessons from phase 1 were implemented into phase 2.

6.1.3.2 Shop representatives

60 shop representatives (owners when available, otherwise managers) were approached on the Monday after event weekends (30 after Halloween, 30 after Christmas Lights Switch-on). A significant majority of these noticed a change in sales and/or footfall during the events. This effect varied greatly with the type of store and location, illustrated by Figure 2. Footfall universally increased in the area up to around 100 m from venues, though main pathways were much more affected by this. Places for specific shopping needs such as utility stores, underwear vendors, and paper shops did not experience a strong effect. One furniture store noted that “there are lots of people coming by, but no more sales.” Shops outside of this 100m area or off the main pathways did not see as big effects. Areas affected by rerouted buses and temporary parking sites were negatively affected, some severely.

Figure 2. Effect on business according to shop representatives 2019 (n=60, collected by the author)

Half of the total of 60 shops (30) surveyed noticed a positive effect on sales. The strongest effects could be seen with food and drink vendors. Two pub owners said that the Halloween festival was “The best weekend of the year” by a broad margin. The 2019 Renfrewshire Council evaluations estimated a total of £5.3m spent during the 2018 event season. Most of the 30 venues with a positive sales effect received several times the regular weekend business.

The rest of the shops described a neutral or negative effect on sales. Shops beyond the innermost town experienced no effect or did not even know about the events. All shops experiencing a negative effect on business attributed this either to the rerouting of traffic/parking or that they depended on regular customers who did not come into town, or at least not to the stores, during the festivals. Three respondents claimed that it was well-known amongst shopkeepers how events inhibited business. “Everyone knows that”, claimed a shopkeeper just 50 meters from a shopkeeper who conversely reported a strong increase in business. This could be observed also with shopkeepers who experienced positive effects: they tended to use the same words describing the effects. This is significant in relation to the creation of consensus and building support for a bid, analysed in Chapter 8.

6.1.4 Monetisable impact phase 2

The second phase of quantitative data analysis consisted solely of a questionnaire administered online and at Paisley events during the first half of 2022. The survey had a 90 % completion rate for those who replied to at least one question, which is high considering there are over 40 question prompts (the actual number depends). The average response time was 8 minutes. The willingness-to-pay is a primary data indicator of research objective 1, relating to the economic value of events. The lack of ticket data with Paisley having free events makes it an important figure poorly understood before this study.

The second phase of the quantitative data collection saw a redesign of the economic impact models. The WTP questions changed the approach to better fit contemporary literature's recommendations (Brediert, et al., 2006; Scandizzo & Pierleoni, 2019). This made possible advanced methods including bundled choices and dynamic questions. Therefore, the results have a higher degree of validity. The reliability shows signs of being higher as well, as results are less extreme.

The two methods for WTP evaluation showed a consistently higher willingness to pay than phase 1. Due to the yes/no or "preferred alternative" approach, this eliminated the protest zeroes, and no respondents refused to answer or quit the questionnaire at these questions.

6.1.5 Dichotomous Choice

The double-bounded dichotomous choice had informative texts attached to it, designed in liaison with a team of Renfrewshire Council officers.

The information texts before the actual question presented the issue:

"Events in Paisley is a publicly funded service, using council tax and other central government funding. The council tax constitutes 22 % of Renfrewshire Council's budget which is used to pay for many things, including schools, rubbish collection, roads, water, and leisure. Of these, Children's services are the largest (50 %), and adult services including social care (17 %). Leisure including culture and events make up 2.5 % of the Council's budget. Around 0.25 % of

Renfrewshire Council's budget is used to cover the six to eight large events and festivals organised each year in Paisley by Renfrewshire Council."

Respondents could first choose if they preferred tax-funded events or ticketed events in Paisley. 70 % (142) chose tax-funded events (henceforth called 'taxpayers') and 30 % (62) ticket-funded ('ticket payers'). Almost all respondents lived in Renfrewshire, and thus the tax choice was not individually beneficial; they were part of the group paying the taxes for Paisley events. The 'tax-funded' respondents generally had to pay a higher price overall, as they were forced to pay for every event regardless of whether they visited them, whereas the 'ticket funded' respondents could choose whether they would want to take part of the events and their costs.

Figure 3 displays the results of the DBDC. It requires some explanation:

The blue and grey lines represent those who prefer tax outtake over ticketed events. The red and green lines represent those who prefer ticketed events.

The x-axis represents the different suggested price levels in the DBDC. The right y-axis shows the aggregate sum of the willingness to pay (yes/no) at each specific price level. That is, if all those who were willing to pay £10 paid that amount, and everyone else paid £0, the blue and red dots at the £10 levels represent the absolute amounts that this policy would bring in from 'tax' and 'ticket' preferring respondents respectively. The left y-axis shows the proportion of respondents willing to pay that amount or more. The dotted line displays what proportion of respondents were willing to pay for the events at each price level. The table below the diagram highlights the same thing as the dotted lines; the price elasticity (also in Table 9). For example: 6.5 % of ticket payers said 'no' to paying £3. Somewhere between £1 and £3, the price became too high. They are thus presented in price category 1; everyone said yes to the £1 level and thus £1-£3 was the lowest level where price played a part.

Figure 3. Demand for Paisley events at different ticket price levels (n=202, collected by the author)

Table 8. Price elasticity at different price levels (n=202, collected by the author)

Price Category	1	3	5	10	15	20	30
'Ticket Payers'	6,5%	0,0%	32,3%	29,0%	16,1%	12,9%	3,2%
'Taxpayers'	2,8%	4,2%	20,8%	22,2%	15,3%	11,1%	23,6%

The dotted lines show how the willingness to pay for events was universal at £1 per event, and very high up to £5, virtually the same between the two groups. After that, it declines, but WTP remains above 50 % until £10 for 'ticket payers' and £ 15 for 'taxpayers'. Strikingly, the highest aggregated income for organisers would occur at these levels as well, had the events been ticketed: £ 15 for 'taxpayers' and £ 10 for 'ticket payers'. The right-hand y-axis figures can be aggregated to all event visitors from Renfrewshire; implications of the WTP, including 'inclusive growth' and utility are discussed in the analysis chapter.

It is notable that 24 % of the 'taxpayers' were willing to pay £ 30 or more for *each event* in Paisley on their tax bill, a total of around £200 per year per respondent for the public events programme, indicating a high experienced utility. Considering the high number of

respondents willing to pay at least £ 30, it would arguably have been better to make the maximum bid even higher but considering that £ 30 is many times higher than Renfrewshire Council’s spend on each visitor, the current scale serves as a sufficient utility measurement tool.

6.1.6 Conjoint bundles

The second WTP tool, conjoint analysis, shows the relative importance of event attributes for respondents, previously discussed in relation to Snowball’s (2008) approach. Bundles were generated based on five dimensions, and respondents could choose between two bundles, see Table 10 for alternatives and attributes. By choosing one of the alternatives and aggregating the responses, respondents’ preferences are possible to calculate without needing to decide between each attribute separately, which may foster biased or insincere replies.

Table 9. Conjoint attributes and alternatives

Frequency	Finance
Five per year	Equivalent to £3 tax payment per event
Seven per year	Equivalent to £6 tax payment per event
Ten per year	Equivalent to £9 tax payment per event
Shows	Themes
Mainly ticketed, high profile shows and concerts	More focus on celebrating local history
Mainly free-of-charge, public and amateur shows	More general focus on general popular culture
Tourism	
Mainly targeted at locals, fewer participants	
Targeted at non-locals as well to attract visitors	

The attributes are displayed as *part-worths*; how much each feature affects the preference (see Table 11). This conjoint method can answer two questions:

1. Which dimension of the bundles was most important in the decision-making (e.g. price, number of shows)
2. How strongly did the different alternatives affect respondents (e.g. how much difference in preference was observed between the £3 and £5 levels?)

Table 10. Part-worth results of the conjoint analysis (n=202, collected by the author)

Part-Worths			
Feature	Part-Worths		
Frequency	5 per year	7 per year	10 per year
	0.230	0.016	-0.246
Shows	Ticketed, high-profile	Free, amateur	
	0.025	-0.025	
Themes	Local history	Popular culture	
	-0.018	0.018	
Tourism	Local focus	Visitor focus	
	-0.299	0.299	
Finance	£3 tax cost	£6 tax cost	£9 tax cost
	0.147	0.029	-0.176

The part-worths table can be read as a strength of preference. A positive value means a stronger preference. By comparing the strengths of the part-worths, it is possible to see not just the strength of individual dimension preferences, but the relative focus of each alternative.

The attributes most important to respondents were *tourism* and *frequency*, as can be seen in Figure 4. The preferred event was cheap and large, with a focus on bringing tourism to

Paisley. Five events per year were considered better than a higher frequency. This can be compared to RC evaluations, where one of the more common opinions in early evaluations (around 2016) was that respondents wanted more events. This declined when events reached their current amount of 6-8 larger events per year, which seemed to be considered a good level, or regarded as the new normal. In 2022, respondents preferred a smaller number of events.

Figure 4. Priority of attributes. Part-worth calculation used as basis. (n=202, collected by the author)

A more expensive event could be tolerated by a large group of respondents if it contained other values: Halloween festival-style events were good enough that a £9 price tag was acceptable. This was mirrored in the open-ended comments in phase 2; high-profile events including Halloween and the Spree were frequently mentioned as good examples both of what respondents would like to see in the Paisley event programme, and what they thought brought an economic boost to the town. The other two dimensions; what types of shows were on, and what themes the events had, were either a low priority, or respondents had

mixed opinions. “High profile shows” were about as attractive as “focus on local history/community”, which could also be observed in some open-ended comments. The polarity and strength of preference are shown in Figure 5 with a part-worths calculation based on the multinomial logit model described in Chapter 5.

Figure 5. Calculated utility values of conjoint analysis. (n=202, collected by the author).

6.1.7 Open-ended comments and correlations relating to economy

The open-ended questions “What type of event do you think gives the town the best boost in the economy?” and “What sort of events do you want to see in Paisley in the future?” gave diverging answers – respondents did not think their own preferences were necessarily the same as what would give the best economic impact. The former of these gave a wide array of responses. Some (16) mentioned the Halloween festival, the Spree (10), and the

Fireworks (10), already existing in Paisley. More than this, 26 people mentioned that music or concerts would likely bring the greatest spending, and 25 people mentioned family activities. The Spree, which is almost exclusively a ticketed event with different high-profile live acts, is the only event with music as a main attractor, and the 26 people mentioning it might well call for more of just that. The latter questions underline the wish for more music: 56 people, more consistent than any other theme in any open-ended question, wanted to see music events in Paisley in the future.

In order to find out more about the behaviour of those who visited events beyond willingness-to-pay, R^2 tests and OLS regressions were run to see whether other variables correlated with the WTP. Only a few tests were significant and of good fit; it is likely that most of the variables correlating with willingness-to-pay are indicators of a third, unprobed variable. Other relevant tests combining income, spending, socioeconomic status, area, and age, were not significant.

Spending in local shops or income were not significant indicators of whether the respondent preferred ticket or tax-funded events, despite the 'ticket' respondents being willing to pay less for events. The WTP showed a weak but significant correlation to household income ($n = 202$, $r = .226$, $p = .029$, collected by the author) and spending in local shops was correlated with willingness to pay (dichotomous choice method ($n = 202$ $r = .490$, $p < 0.001$, collected by the author)). The same variables could also be demonstrated in a regression model with WTP being the independent variable, see Figure 6.

Figure 6. OLS regression of WTP in relation to spending during events. (n=202, collected by the author)

This model, with four removed outliers in the Y-axis shows a moderate R^2 value of 0.335. The respondents who reported spending at least £ 1 spent £ 65 on average.

6.2 Quantitative public value

The public value of public interventions is arguably more than the sum of the typical social value indicators. This is echoed in Renfrewshire Council's policy documents. The 2016-2026 Paisley town centre action plan (Renfrewshire Council, 2016) notes how public engagement and consultation are crucial to the improvement of Paisley's reputation (and for the 2021 process). The commitment to equitable development is echoed in economic strategy (Renfrewshire Council, 2020). These closely align with public sphere and progressive opportunity values (Bozeman & Johnson, 2015), feeding into the third research objective of developing new methods for event evaluation. Bozeman and Johnson's (2015) notion of progressive opportunity is the degree of opportunities given to each individual within a society. A more equal provision and an overall higher quantity of opportunities are the targets of this measurement. This is similar to equity, as conceded by Bozeman and Johnson, but does not necessarily imply strong economic redistribution.

6.2.1 Public value phase 1

The key factors of public value surveyed in phase one were to a large extent the dimensions described in the literature on social value of events. As developed in Chapter 4, the primary variables are sense of community, pride in place, and social cohesion. Beyond this, the study can point towards creation of wider values, which in the theoretical framework above are called public value. These are discussed in a sub-heading below.

6.2.1.1 *Progressive Opportunity*

The *inclusive growth* agenda, aimed at less privileged groups in addition to the traditional, affluent beneficiaries of high culture and event venues. In Renfrewshire Council's own evaluations, high degrees of participation from more deprived areas have been regarded as successful 'inclusive' framing of festivals and events. With a total of 142,000 unique event visits in 2018, this is a substantial increase in the culture consumption and stage culture specifically in Renfrewshire. These inclusion criteria can be seen throughout the evaluations. The consultants used Experian's Mosaic tool (Experian, 2017) to distinguish different socioeconomic groups. Mosaic has been shown to give additional useful information beyond SIMD and its English and Welsh counterparts despite similar layouts (Wami et al., 2019). However, for the sake of this study, SIMD is useful due to its ranking of all zones, with the respondents' SIMD deciles displayed in Figure 7 (6,976 in the 2020 implementation).

Figure 7. SIMD deciles in 2018 Renfrewshire Evaluation Data. (n=1738, collected for RC)

This aggregate 2018 data, not analysed in the evaluations, shows the extent of the progressive opportunity (n=1738, collected for RC). The effect is even stronger in the primary Phase 1 data but with much lower significance with its smaller sample (n=172, collected by the author), shown in Figure 8. Each decile represents 10 % of Scottish population. The evaluations are likely more relevant, rather than a time series effect.

Figure 8. SIMD deciles in 2019 Primary Data (n=205, collected by the author)

Not all respondents were willing to share their full postcodes, and many of those who did were reluctant to do so. Several more statistical tests could have been run with postcode data in phase 2, but Renfrewshire Council were not willing to support a survey asking for that demographic information; only the first three figures were collected. This was deemed acceptable because of the much larger sample of accessible RC evaluations with that data intact for SIMD and travel cost analysis.

Figure 7 shows that disadvantaged families did indeed attend the events to a higher degree than others, despite a relatively even distribution of SIMD deciles across Renfrewshire inhabitants. The progressive opportunity is underlined by another question, probing whether attendees would consider attending if there was an admission fee. Out of those who replied “No”, 31 % came from the most deprived decile, a much larger amount than the other deciles.

6.2.1.2 Public Sphere

Returning to the definition from Bozeman and Johnson (2015:61) the public sphere as a public value is: “any place, either physical or virtual, functioning as a setting for expansive communication among citizens about the meaning, development, conservation, or revision of public values.” A key reason for the investment in equalising measures such as the “inclusive growth” commitment was to offer culture with low thresholds for participation, both economic and cultural. Therefore, the socioeconomic profile shown above is a clear indication of the construction of a public sphere in Paisley.

The comments point towards different views of what public value are offered. Five respondents claimed that the best thing about the events was that “Something’s on”, a clearly different comment than “It’s good to see the town come alive”, or “A good community feeling”. In essence, it is a comment about the public sphere; it is communication that this type of entertainment, as opposed to other things on offer in Paisley, appeals to the respondent and provides them some value.

Adding to this, shopkeepers who were not informed about the schedule of the events by Renfrewshire Council, or invited to discuss how to handle the events, expressed that they were disappointed. Around a dozen of the shopkeepers expressed that they were usually not able to participate as they had to work in the store, but several noted that they felt part of it due to the ambience spreading even to them. Only one of the shopkeepers was disappointed in the lack of information mentioned that her business might suffer for not being able to stock up, whereas the others simply felt left out of the dialogue and flow of information.

6.3 Public Value phase 2

As in phase 1, social value is regarded as a part of the public value creation. The phase engaged more deeply with the issue of being able to demonstrate value in broader fields than the standard implementation of the economic and social value of events. Due to the sequential design of this study, the first phase informed the second. Several of the weaknesses of the first phase were corrected, including the WTP methods and the stronger engagement with public value. The second phase survey took roughly three times as long as the first to complete, which is mirrored in the fruitful results.

In both the open-ended questions on what respondents would like to see in terms of events, and what they thought would bring the most economic impact, around ten replied with a perspective on public value creation. “Community interaction”, “Community-based” and events that “bring the residents together” were responses which clearly showed that these issues remain top of mind for some respondents, despite the more practically posed questions about what type of events should be held in Paisley.

6.3.1 Progressive Opportunities

No data on specific postcodes was collected during phase two, only the first three characters. Instead, there was a question on household income. This proved surprising results: around 60 % of respondents registered values above the median household income in the UK (£ 31,400 for 2021), see Figure 9. This may well be explained partially by that the question is the least answered question in all the surveys, with 84 % of respondents. If these non-responders came from predominantly economically weaker households, which is not unreasonable, this would make up for the unexpected results. This question was designed for online distribution, and when it was used on-site, some respondents were uncomfortable with it. Others refused to answer. A single open-ended comment read “Why are the demographic questions so noseey?”, possibly a hint to the low response rate to that question.

Figure 9. Income brackets of phase 2 respondents (n=202, collected by the author).

Though the focus on finance was limited in the bundle WTP presented above, 22 % still shows that the cost of the events was a significant factor. The price range in this part of the survey was between £3 and £9. As a comparison, even the highest value in that range is less than an average small-venue concert or theatre production in Glasgow or Paisley. The tickets to non-family shows at the Spree are several times the maximum £9. Finance being such a large part of the decision to attend a festival, even at comparatively low sums, shows how free shows enable the consumption of culture in groups that would not otherwise have done so.

6.3.2 Public Sphere

Figure 10. Preferences of social and public value in phase two data (n=202, collected by the author).

The Likert scale questions scored significantly high as shown in Figure 10, with none of the values going below the Paisley reputation question, at 4.21. 4.21 is also a remarkably positive result but the same question also had the highest “Neutral” and negative answers at 16 % and 2 % respectively. All Likert questions about which values are associated with the hosting of festivals in Paisley received high marks, between 4.2 and 4.7. The exception was “If festivals were to be hosted exclusively online for the foreseeable future, I would still

attend”, which received 2.1, equal to the “Disagree” range. Only 40 % “strongly agreed” with the claim that Paisley’s reputation had improved from the events, significantly lower than the others.

The public sphere evaluation is evidenced through a range of these questions, including the questions on reputation, that Paisley “liven up” and that it is important that festivals are hosted physically. These, and the only question with a negative result (that is, below the ‘Neutral’ 3), “If festivals were to be hosted exclusively online for the foreseeable future, I would still attend” where only two respondents “strongly agreed” that they would attend festivals digitally, show the need for a physical, public arena to share. The high number – a majority – of respondents willing to provide open-ended comments next to this Likert-scale list of questions shows the want for communication and deliberation about the values created around the cultural investment programme including the festivals.

6.4 Social Value phase 1

In the open-ended questions on what the best things about the festivals were, 45 % of comments were related to specific practical arrangements or shows, but 55 % talked about *social value*. The 45 %, notably, were not just specific attractions or acts, but also opinions like “It’s fun”, “Lots of activities”, and “The Display”, as well as “Good for families”; the latter was frequently combined with comments about that it felt “Friendly” and “Safe”. These correspond well to a range of aspects of social value. The priorities can be seen in Figure 11.

Figure 11. Open-ended comments by attendees, 2019 primary data. Absolute numbers (n=202, collected by the author)

The most common opinion about what was best about the Paisley public events and festivals was some version of “The town comes alive”. One respondent in the Renfrewshire evaluations for 2018 said they were “happy to show their friends” Paisley during the events. The event programmes, according to these respondents, make Paisley the best version of itself.

The next most prevalent section – the positive atmosphere – is clearly related to the town “coming alive”, but more than that, it shows a sense of belonging. 88 % of these comments came from locals, a clear overrepresentation. The comments noting that the events are “Good for families” partially express a categorisation of the use value: accessibility and having achieved attracting several types of attendees. It is also a statement about the other attendants. Paisley’s tattered reputation and the fact that beer tents, purpose-built patios, loud cover bands, and other examples of “grown-up” culture might indicate that the events are not suitable for children. The respondents citing family fun assert that Paisley can put on a good show, including alcohol and loud music, whilst behaving well enough for families to happily attend.

Though only 6 % of respondents cited that the events were good for the community as the

best thing, this is still particularly notable. The phrasing – it is good for the community is particularly altruistic considering that the question was posed in a very open manner: what do you like best about this event?

6.4.1 Shop representatives

Figure 12. Shop representatives' opinions about events in Paisley (n=60, collected by the author)

Comparing Figure 12 and the similar chart in the section on economic impact, many of those who experienced negative business were still positive about the events (50 % positive economic impact; 62 % positive about events). Most of the neutral comments came from those who were not affected because of the distance to the event. Those who were affected negatively were *less* positive but still, only 4 out of 60 were negative overall. Despite this mixed effect on sales, close to all respondents spoke positively about the events programme: the most common phrase used was “it’s good for the town”. The opinion “It’s good for the town” echoes from the attendee interviews, which was the most common specific answer to

why shopkeepers liked the events. The coherence in responses shown is not just a sign of caring for the town's best, but also an indicator of conformed communication from Renfrewshire Council and other central actors with a common narrative. Many respondents stated that they had seldom or never attended a cultural event in Paisley, but still had strong opinions on the issue. These findings clearly relate to objective 2, contributing to the understanding of social value. More in-depth interviews about what *is* good for the town would have been beneficial, but hardly possible considering the large *n*.

6.5 Social Value phase 2

As seen in the table above, value is created in a range of the categories of social value presented in Chapter 4: pride in place, sense of community, wellbeing and, more tentatively, community development. The responses are strong indicators of positive feelings towards the town and the cultural transformation narrative presented by Renfrewshire Council and the Business Improvement District amongst others.

Several of the data points gave significantly less favourable results than similar questions asked by Renfrewshire Council. The average favourability of events was 6.95 (on a ten-point scale), the lowest being the Monte Carlo Rally start with 5.84, and the highest being the Halloween festival with 8.39. This can be compared to previous evaluations: Renfrewshire's evaluations show very high satisfaction, with as many as 98-99 % reporting "satisfied" or "very satisfied" with the event, with the latter sometimes being in the 90s. The most common comments about negative aspects, between 10-20 %, in these evaluations ask for more shops, better shops, and cleaner streets – things that do not relate to the events themselves. The same is true for positive comments, not typically relating to the shows.

Figure 13. Responses of event satisfaction, 1-10 where 10 is best. (n=202, collected by the author)

The ranking of events displayed in Figure 13 also placed the ambitious festivals aimed at non-locals and locals alike in the top: the Halloween festival, the Food & Drink festival and the Spree were all in the top.

The most common responses as to why respondents visited events in Paisley were that they “liked the event”, it was “Something to do with family/friends” and to “Support the community”. Especially notable is that the programme is several times more uncommon as a strong motivation to visit. Respondents could submit as many as they wanted, with an average of slightly over 3 submitted per respondent. It is not in search of novelty, specific acts, or even the quality of the performances that attracts the respondents.

Figure 14. Motivations for visiting Paisley events (n=202, collected by the author)

The opinions about which positive values are associated with events in Paisley showed a suspiciously even distribution, see Figure 14. This might indicate that the question is not correctly put or that respondents do not have a strong feeling about it. Notably, the second least submitted response is once again the programme items. A similar trend can be seen in Figure 15 about what is 'good for the town'.

Figure 15. Respondent opinions about positive values associated to Paisley events (n=202, collected by the author)

In the free-text comments about what values are added by the events, there are five recurring themes:

1. The assertion that the events bring in business for the town centre, several comments add a superlative statement as a supporting argument: “Boosts local economy which is much needed. The town centre is dying.”
2. The events help the community and bring Paisley together. Some respondents frame this as an ‘underdog’ dynamic. “[...] I continually find the events program bring a sense of community spirit to the town. We are a town, and so are small enough to recognise people when attending events or be recognised by others. This would never happen in larger centres such as Glasgow. [...] Glasgow may have a bigger spending budget, and more international clout, but Paisley must try harder to compete, and the results show.”
3. It makes the respondents feel proud of their town, wanting to show the world what Paisley can do. Sometimes, it is implied that the usual, non-festival Paisley is not really worth showing, but far from all comments contain this undertone: “Events in Paisley give me a sense of pride in the town. I like to invite friends (not from Paisley) to the town on these days and it feels like a special occasion.”
4. Negative comments. “Litter and tatty buildings detract from the impact of events. Road works coinciding with events as the ones in Back Sneddon over the light show are a disaster for the image of the town.”

Open-ended comments paint a predominantly positive picture of the events programme in Paisley, with minor preferences for change. This despite the apparent affiliation of this study with Renfrewshire Council which might have made the study a suggestion box: both the university’s and the council’s logos were displayed on the front page. On the other hand, studies associated with the organisers of events tend to get higher scores (Chalip, 2014).

6.6 Negative Impacts

In the phase 1 data, there were some negative comments amongst the attendees. 26 negative comments were recorded, 13 % (n=203, collected by the author). Out of these, there were no strong trends; no single issue received more than two negative comments except that “there should be more alcohol” – said in a joking manner, though the opinion may well be honest. Both economic and social negative impacts are previously poorly understood, and their contribution to research objectives 1 and 2 widens its explanatory power significantly. The critical perspectives of Lamond and Platt’s (2016) book discussed in the literature review as well as Chalip’s and Heere’s (2013) call for cautious evaluation both contribute to not only refraining from overestimated benefits but also accounting for negatives.

Amongst the shopkeepers, the negative values were more clearly expressed. They were asked in their position as business owners or managers, and as the events did affect business to a great extent, either positively or negatively, this was likely more relatable and top of mind to them compared to the attendees. The negative impacts were mostly related to their own businesses, discussed above, though a few also mentioned the temporary parking sites, rerouted traffic, and buses as an obstacle for goods, services, and people in large parts of central Paisley for as long as three or four days. This was echoed by two attendee respondents: the extensive rerouting of traffic was perceived to be unnecessary.

In the Renfrewshire Council evaluations for 2018, the only open-ended question asks respondents to compare this year’s festival with previous years. These responses are close to universally positive, but the low response rate of these questions indicate that few respondents had any opinion at all about how it differed. The few negative results are about specificities: changed drink menus and a specific band not showing up as last year.

6.7 Conclusion

The quantitative findings lean more towards the economic part of the data. Public value relevance can be found in a range of them but need theoretical context to make full sense

and be put in relation to other value. Even with analysis presented in Chapter 8, the social and public aspects are not very granular, despite some interesting findings. These are more extensive in the qualitative data, shown in the next chapter. Similarly, the economic data on the qualitative side is limited. This was expected, and a part of the reason to use a mixed methods approach.

7 Qualitative Findings

The initial literature review of bidding for mega events, urban regeneration, and event economics shaped the data collection of the first quantitative phase. The redesign resulted in a digital survey, added new observational data sources where the original were cut short, and added an interview series.

The qualitative data provides information about the sentiments and priorities of a range of elite actors in Renfrewshire and beyond. The primary aim of the qualitative data is to find sources of value, as they are understood by these actors. Some of these were not anticipated by the prepared questions but uncovered by the respondents who spoke freely about their opinions.

Observation data contains observations from four years of research-related interactions with public actors. Thus, it is wider in scope and more diverse than the interview series or the quantitative data. The observation data, and to a lesser extent the interviews, include a discussion on policy priorities, primarily in Renfrewshire Council. This gives a strong contribution to understanding what value Renfrewshire Council wanted to create with the event-related interventions. Results can thus be analysed in relation to these priorities; Bozeman's (2007) discussion of public value *failure* analogous to market failure provides the idea that a public value is a fulfilled need.

The in-depth interview series consisted of 11 elite actors in business, civil society, local government, and national government. The sampling, described in section 5.3.3.3, was purposive, and aimed to include the most closely related areas of public administration, as well as the most centrally placed people in business, non-profits, and politics in Paisley. The rest were chosen as especially interesting individuals who had been identified by speaking to other respondents and prospecting informal discussions elsewhere; two respondents were chosen because they were influential local figures who were known for having contrasting opinions with the RC agenda, which was not easily found as the establishment figures in Paisley mostly had formal ties to the Paisley 2021 Partnership or RC. All except respondent 5,

working nationally in Scotland with culture and events, were based primarily in Paisley and Renfrewshire for their professional or non-profit engagement. These are discussed in the first half of this chapter. The second source of data, and the latter part of this chapter, is observational. Observation took place at Renfrewshire Council locations in Paisley 2019-2022, primarily during 2019-2020. In 2022, a three-month placement at the Scottish government was used for additional observations on the wellbeing approaches of Scotland, incentives for local authorities to liaise with the government, and culture's role in the wider public strategies.

This chapter is structured after these two main sources of data. Observational data is not as methodologically standardised as the interview series. For clarity, the structure is similar throughout the chapter and follows the scheme below, see Table 12. The structure is similar to the previous chapter in that economic value and other indicators are separated. The analysis chapter is differently structured, and more relating to the three research objectives. These are continually cited throughout this chapter to keep the proximity to the analysis structure.

Table 11. Chapter 7 structure

Chapter 7 presentation structure, hierarchical

Level 1: **a.** In-depth interviews **b.** observation data

Level 2: Value type. **a.** Economic value **b.** Public value (**c.** Social Value; part of public)

Level 3: Partially structured after concepts associated with the value type (e.g. progressive opportunity, public sphere in the public value section).

7.1 Interview Series

Though interviews of different kinds were conducted between 2019-2022, including quantitative, the bulk of qualitative interviews used in the analysis were held in the Autumn of 2021 (with two additional interviews in 2022 and one already in April 2020). These were selected to mirror those having a stake in, and contributing to, the values created by events and festivals in Paisley, see Table 13. Some were primarily associated with the bidding process, to give a background to that environment, whereas most discuss the political values and priorities of the current cultural policy and its implication for events. Values and priorities are discussed broadly and openly. The focus has revolved around the values created by the boosted events programme in Paisley and the bidding process and its effects on festivals and events. In the cases where the respondent's connection to the Paisley public events programme was weaker, cultural policy priorities in Paisley were discussed. Some respondents have had the right to review their contribution to this study before publication. This was especially, and understandably, requested by civil servant respondents who were trying to give a balanced account of their workplace's achievements.

Table 12. List of respondents in the in-depth interviews

Respondent	Name in findings
Local business owner, music	Respondent 1
Trustee in local museum society	Respondent 2
Business Improvement District representative	Respondent 3
Prominent person in local social NGO	Respondent 4
Events officer in Scottish public agency	Respondent 5
Councillor, Renfrewshire Council	Respondent 6
Prominent person in local community group	Respondent 7
Renfrewshire Council officer, Urban Regeneration	Respondent 8
Renfrewshire Council officer, Urban Regeneration	Respondent 9
Renfrewshire Council officer, Leisure	Respondent 10
Renfrewshire Council officer, Events	Respondent 11

7.1.1 Economic value

Economic value are typically analysed with quantitative rather than qualitative methods. The generalisability, specificity, and predictability are suffering with a small number of respondents and an increased focus on diverse, subjective experiences and open-ended answers. As argued in the methods chapter, this makes the qualitative findings a complement to the quantitative findings in terms of economic value. The respondents are direct beneficiaries (NGO workers), organisers (Renfrewshire council), and indirect beneficiaries (private sector) of the festival programme and bidding process.

7.1.1.1 The Bidding Process

RC were interested in hosting a major event early in the process of turning towards culture-led regeneration, as stated in *Paisley: The Untold Story* (Renfrewshire Council, 2014). Bidding became a driver of events, reconstruction of important buildings in the town, and increased financing of both urban regeneration and culture more generally. The knowledge of culture-led regeneration partially came from the local university (University of the West of Scotland), where tourism and event scholars had frequent contact with the Council. According to respondent 10, the work with the bid started in 2012, soon after beginning the culture-led efforts. This was one year before the first-ever UKCoC was hosted in Londonderry. It was also two years before the Commonwealth Games in Glasgow (designated in 2007), which brought significant attention to the previous and ongoing culture-led approach in Glasgow (Christie & Gibb, 2015). The know-how partially came from the OECD (2008) publications on bidding for mega-events. According to these, advantages can be demonstrated event for cities that to not win the designation. Respondent 8 echoes this: “That was partially what convinced me, reading the OECD book. It seemed possible to win even if we did not win”. Respondent 8 also mentioned consultations with OECD experts which further convinced them: “The OECD guidance was really helpful in providing an external view on our investment. We made it part of our diligence process, to decide whether it was a worthwhile investment. I would say we got assurances from those voices all the time. They were saying that we were doing this for the right reasons, not as a vanity project.” Several respondents also meant that the bidding process opened a type of policy window: the surge

in popularity for cultural investments made possible the multitude of interventions, projects, loans, and campaigns instigated between 2014-2017.

During the interview with Respondent 8, the interviewer (mistakenly) referred to the bid as 'failed'. The respondent immediately replied: "I would not call it failed. You may call it lost, yes, but considering the values it brought to the town, it would not be correct calling it failed". The semantics are not irrelevant, even though some of the literature cited in Chapter 4 uses the term 'failed' for bids that are simply lost (Paulsson & Alm, 2020; Horne, 2007).

7.1.1.2 Private sector and BID

The local Business Improvement District, Paisley First, collects the majority (over 600 members) of the night-time and retail economy of Paisley. They are the main benefactors of direct economic impact in the town centre. Their participation in the partnership work was central, and the sustainability of their businesses has been a key priority of Renfrewshire Council's regeneration policy long before the cultural focus; retail-based regeneration was a strategy previously used in Paisley. Because of the lacking data from business how much additional money is spent, research objective 1 is helped by the business-side opinions of the programme, adding to the stated spend by attendees.

Respondent 3, a representative of the Business Improvement District (BID), primarily sees events as a driver of footfall. The BID organises its own events, less focused on a cultural programme with shows and more on daytime, town centre entertainment. Their programme is a complement to public events and will likely remain no matter what happens with event funding in Paisley. There is a degree of overlap: both the BID and Renfrewshire Council engage amusement rides, attract street vendors, and host children's activities. The BID's events are carried out in deliberation with but separate from Renfrewshire Council. Their evaluation is based on footfall and turnover: "We organise events such as an Easter trail, a Winterfest, and a Lego festival. We go out into the business afterwards and ask them whether our members see more people in their shops [...] They are able to tell us whether increased footfall and sales come from these events" (Respondent 3).

Some restaurants and bars in Paisley organise activities during council-organised events: build beer gardens in the streets, hire live bands, and extend opening hours. Most of these businesses are members of Paisley First, but the BID does not engage officially with the events. The internal surveys are not carried out after the Halloween festival. But Paisley First is not uninterested in the community. The businesses active in Paisley get to vote on whether they want a BID. This practice comes partially from North America, where BIDs have a greater power over urban planning in their districts; they may hire private security to patrol the streets and redesign urban spaces to their liking with their own means, to get a more attractive or luxurious shopping experience (Morçöl & Zimmermann, 2017). This is not the case in Paisley, but the BID nonetheless hosts a vote every five years. The results are positive, and the BID takes pride in it: “It’s just good for the businesses, and if they do not want us any longer, they would have voted us out” (Respondent 3)

The BID takes pride in being an active part of the community in Paisley; several business owners want to “give back” to the community after according to Respondent 3. When the Paisley Centre, one of the two shopping centres in Paisley, was sold to a private developer, the BID had been “in meetings [with Renfrewshire Council]. I asked what they are doing with the property, how we can help them [...] get the community involved in what they want to see and just support any application that they have. Red tapes are a nightmare, and we just want to support them”. This includes dialogue around expropriations, a constant issue in Paisley with derelict buildings, unused floors of commercial buildings, and undeveloped brownfield spaces.

“It is very difficult to do regeneration in Paisley. The Council only owns very few buildings. The rest are either privately owned by businesses, but a lot of them roll owned by investors, investment bankers down south. It can be difficult even to know who owns them! You cannot compulsorily purchase a building that's privately owned, all we can do is encourage and support the Council.” (Respondent 3)

Key strategies of Paisley regeneration include the retail and hospitality businesses which form the bulk of the BID’s members. Respondent 3 links this type of support to more explicit community work, such as local charity contributions. The BID created “The Pride of Paisley

2016”, an exhibition across Paisley where 25 natural size lion sculptures were decorated by local artists (Paisley 2021, 2016). After advertising them as an art trail, they auctioned the lions off for the benefit of two local hospices, raising almost £80,000. Some of them are still visible around Paisley where the buyers decided to place them.

Despite very broad support for the bidding process, the economic situation is not universally accepted as cooperative between the council and business. Respondent 1, in charge of several local businesses relating to arts, music, and events, is unhappy with some of Renfrewshire Council’s priorities:

“They could have gone local first to see if they could get the quality needed. Some local businesses have the capacity to support any major projects in music or media. I supported the Council in some small projects during the last few years, but they never got back to me about the bigger ones. I had a meeting with them recently where I told them this. It was a bit uncomfortable for them, but you know, we need to discuss these things. We need to grow our own capacity.”

Respondent 1 considers it problematic that the Council, despite high ambitions for supporting a local scene, is not making use of resources in Paisley for their own events and festivals. Many contractors are brought in from outwith Renfrewshire to host the events, as reported in the consultancy reports.

The voices of such as Respondent 1, unhappy with the cultural programme’s inability to engage local artists, claiming that this was one of the key points of the regeneration based on culture, are not prominent in the ongoing discussion in Paisley. Instead, major actors such as the Council and the large institutions, invariably engaged in the programme themselves, define the discussion to some degree. The positive tone of events as drivers of business is shared by other private actors, such as the Business Improvement District. Indeed, none of the respondents speak about local creative businesses as a provider or contractor for the public events programme, or culture overall. Attracting creative businesses is a crucial part of the deindustrialisation shift towards a thriving service sector, and Renfrewshire Council is providing the businesses with incentives and assistance.

7.1.1.3 Tourism and placemaking

The improved profile of Paisley was of considerable importance to several respondents. Relatively unrelated to direct social value, reputation was more involved with potential revenue streams than other policy priorities. The events in Paisley formed part of a drive to attract businesses and peripatetic events. The ambitious Paisley Book Festival was hosted for the first time in 2020 (a local initiative, though supported by Renfrewshire Council), and the 2022 UK-wide UNBOXED festival had one of its two inaugural events in Paisley. Branding cities as festival or event cities has become an important tool in cities' communication (Todd, 2022). These values are relevant to business and are underlined by RC claiming that £4.3m in PR value have come from the media coverage of Paisley's cultural efforts (Renfrewshire Council, 2019). The social value aspect is covered below.

Respondent 9 argued that there was still a lot of potential to realise: "I think Renfrewshire has a fantastic range of opportunities to offer on the on the tourist trail as well, and it is something that has much more potential for development at the moment. It's something that's very much on the partnership radar for Future Paisley". This was an important point of the bid and now its legacy programmes including the events; to develop and showcase the tourist potential. Still, the boost in tourism had not reached levels anticipated by the Renfrewshire tourism plan before the pandemic; the main touristic developments (such as the museum) in Paisley were delayed by several years.

7.1.1.4 Return of investment

Respondents 9 and 10, both with long experience of culture-led urban regeneration work discussed the Renfrewshire approach with slightly different perspectives. Respondent 9 underlined how the current path, in which major investment programmes are ending in 2024 for several public sectors, has intended to build capacity for "self-sustaining models". Public bodies will need to sustain themselves and keep the cultural profiles, having been

built up with initial funding. Respondent 9 notes the successes which are likely to keep going: Paisley now has "Outdoor event space that can be used for huge events and obviously the momentum has been building in terms of things like our signature events that are now in place", giving the example of the Halloween festival now carrying its own weight.

Respondent 10 took a slightly different perspective. Whilst acknowledging the successes of cultural programmes, their focus was the long-term engagement from the local authority and others: "Looking for inspiration, the effects seen in Glasgow around 2010 when Paisley started their journey were the results of over 20 years of legacy work; the City of Culture was in 1990. The equivalent for Paisley would be looking at what can be achieved by 2041. That is the timeline we should have." Respondent 4 also asked for the continuation of as many programmes as possible, as they considered it a "strategic investment" to bolster "employment of young people".

Though investments in culture are hardly contested in Renfrewshire, the timelines are. Respondents 9 and 10 do not necessarily disagree, but their foci differ; looking at the best equilibrium possible without boosted funding or asking for a more long-term strategic view for development although both respondents speak about both things. Early 2020 (two years after the bid was lost), new strategies were laid out, still according to the step change approach from the bidding process. These were aimed at 2035, and especially for the post-2024 reality of reduced funding, including events and festivals.

7.1.2 Public Value

One drawback of the changing design of this study in the wake of covid-19 was that the events studied were becoming a more distant past. RC also conducted a course change after the bid was lost, of which the most important one was the shift from culture-led to cultural regeneration, discussed in depth in Chapter 3. This shift made a deeper focus on wellbeing and public life related to culture a priority across all of Renfrewshire, in all parts of the public sector; cooperation was instigated with NHS Scotland (the national healthcare provider), Glasgow School of Arts, and other institutions not under Renfrewshire control. This public

value shift has had a transitional period where funding and training of an initial build-up phase is ending in 2024.

In the section of the interviews discussing public value, the political priorities were the most underlined. One key public value creator discussed below is Renfrewshire's "culture at the heart" approach. It is also possible to use Nabatchi's (2012) work on *normative consensus*, with the respondents working to perform, gauge, and create consensus in order to shape and understand what might be valuable in Paisley.

7.1.2.1 Normative Consensus

The normative consensus of priorities could be observed to a large degree in Paisley during the bidding process, as underlined throughout this study. Respondent 10, showing some doubts about the priorities, states that a consensus around the cultural transformation process has been of great importance. A consensus that might be waning away in the years after the intense years of the bid:

"There was very little detail about how we activate [the cultural] strategy and then report and measure the achievement. There was a risk of different disruptions, not least due to covid. [...] But we've got to make sure that we're focused on what the direction of travel is."

The partnership was pivotal in creating the momentum needed, according to several respondents. Respondent 7 underlined the importance of getting others on board: "We really pushed health organisations and youth organisations and housing associations, et cetera, to really feel as if the bid was something they could influence and be part of." From the other end of the same issue, respondent 4 noted that their organisation was not apparently connected to the issue of cultural events, but that the persuasive campaigning made them realise the potential; the cohesion and the common direction created by the partnership in itself.

The support for the bid and the strong engagement arising out of that became a key factor in the success story many perceived the bid to be. Even after losing the bid, Respondent 7

noted that: “When they announced that Coventry would win, there was this element of sadness and deflation. But people rallied to it quite quickly, having the determination of ‘we are going to do it anyway, maybe with less money’, and this was strongly communicated throughout the community and got people back onboard” Respondent 10 echoes the last point; part of the ambience post-2017 has been assertive: “It feels like the legacy of commitments from the bid for 2021 contain a sense of ‘we didn't get it up. We're gonna do it anyway.’” This feeling of a common goal was a driver of the process: “There was a sense of enjoyment around the process, the project and the expectation because the work was involved in community engagement” (Respondent 7).

A few years after the bid, with partnership ties starting to weaken, even the consensus is starting to decline. This is perhaps best phrased by Respondent 2, who is clearly in two minds about the project in 2021: “You know we backed the bid, and it would have been wonderful if we had won. It had been a lot of work, and it couldn't be taken back. At least we appreciated that. Good in a way that we didn't win, because it would have been a terrible time to be City of Culture.” This is not unlike Tessa Jowell's statement about the London Olympics ' after the 2008 financial crisis: 'Had we known what we know now, would we have bid for the Olympics? Almost certainly not' (Osborne & Kirkup, 2008)

7.1.2.2 Public Sphere and Progressive Opportunity

The rhetoric of equity is a key part of the arguments for culture in the post-bid environment of Paisley. This can become a very personal thing, described by the councillor, Respondent 6:

“We aimed for the 2021 win, but our main goal is to provide cheap, effective, local access to lots of sports, leisure, and culture activities [...] which I think are crucial to quality of life. I am someone who is from a working-class Scottish background. I grew up in a mining village. I was born just after the pit closed and being able to access cultural activities really opened up the scope of life for me, and so I am very proud.”

This is displaying a clear priority and sentiment for equity. The “step changes” for the regeneration scheme, aimed to be implemented in 2027, contain different ways of achieving

“inclusive growth” and its research objective 3 connotations. Respondent 8, regeneration officer, views the hospitality sector as having a substantial equity-driving potential: “We have large ‘tackling poverty’ and social deprivation programmes running to improve the life chances and the social outcomes for local people, for this was the fourth step change. Then all of that manifested itself in terms of the vibrancy of our town centre.”

Civil servants and NGO representatives interviewed would spontaneously mention equity as one of the public sector’s priorities. Respondent 4 discusses equity as the access to free culture: “I don’t think everybody always gets what’s needed. I think this is what’s needed, like a free ticket, for instance, without realising that for some people, that’s just not enough.” In this case, the event offered special perks for those who paid, whereas other tickets were free. Respondent 4’s organisation works with creativity and playfulness as tools of overcoming social and psychological problems, but also supplies typical social support and food. Respondent 4 also expresses a discussion on progressive opportunity differentiating between equality and equity and the value of the latter. The social non-profit was always open to people in need, but the increased attention from the bid lowered thresholds. People from groups notoriously difficult to reach with social interventions showed up; their own figure is that the activity was increased by 60 % because of the bid.

Increasing the reach of cultural interventions, in this case, provided progressive opportunity indirectly through the exposure of the organisation. According to Respondent 4, events relating to the bid even brought in substantially increased volumes of volunteers with low socioeconomic status. These stood far from the labour market, which according to the respondent could help the levelling: “When I think about whether something can be done, I look at whether we can help develop social economy skills like volunteering; maybe two years down the line to get a job from those skills.”

7.1.3 Social Value

The social value is ever present in the in-depth interviews; the bid relied on expertise as well as Scottish and local policy using culture-led/cultural rhetoric; the same categories as discussed in Snowball and Antrobus (2002), and Getz (2010) show up although without the

same terminology. The second research objective is of great interest to respondents, with several noting the difficulty of measuring this important metric: “I think soft outcomes are really important. I think the experience for people is almost as important as things like making money. These outcomes are harder to measure” (respondent 7).

The main means of getting all types of stakeholders in Paisley to work in the same direction was the Partnership board. The board is mentioned by respondents as a positive spiral where increased contact between stakeholders created trust and excitement about the bid further strengthening the partnership approach. It was described as a success by several of the stakeholders, including respondents 3, 4, and 7. For the respondents living and/or working in Paisley and Renfrewshire during the bidding process, that time was universally regarded as a time of strong change and predominantly positive experiences of the town ‘coming alive’.

The partnership initially incentivised some of the smaller organisations with economic support. Though several respondents agreed that the funding provided by the council as part of the partnership approach was small, it still brought several stakeholders together. “The bidding process made it more feasible for us to apply for other funding, including some larger sums which really did have the potential to make a difference” (Respondent 8). RC has used a similar approach later with the “Great Places” scheme, offering small contributions to positive changes in the area.

With the bid underway, there was little political dissent after major actors were on board. The councillor, respondent 6, notes that: “Politically, things can often be challenging. But actually, in terms of the bid, it was very much a case of everyone thinking that it was beneficial to the town and to Renfrewshire. So, we were all supportive of it”. They express a sense of ownership of the issue; though the strategy was laid out during a Labour administration, the SNP has chaired Renfrewshire Council for most of the execution, and more importantly, it was instigated with across-the-board support and deliberation. The social value agenda was communicated and integrated to community groups as well. Respondent 4 meant that performing that work was important for the community as well: “It is an opportunity for our members to do some work, but it is also an opportunity for us

as a population to both enjoy the events and not lose sight of the fact that this is part of a wellness agenda”. Further underlining the value of this agenda, Respondent 4 saw the potential for employment and social leverage: “Cultural activity and enjoyment can lead to kind of gateways and pathways to experience building that can then help young people, particularly to any employment.”

7.1.3.1 Tourism and attractivity

Respondent 10, a Renfrewshire Council Officer in the Leisure area, supported the cultural approach of investing in culture and events but wanted to open the discussion up to potential changes to the current approach. According to Respondent 10, there are several potentially lucrative changes overlooked in the current approach which focuses spending and energy on flagship developments:

“We should be turning towards a sort of marketing that is not necessarily getting investment right now [...] There's a lot of leisure activities that can [attract people who currently are not coming here]. Activities for the whole family. If there is a brilliant leisure centre with a swimming pool and slides and a lot of things, they could do that in the morning. Maybe the museum in the afternoon? There's maybe something for parents in between as well.”

The expected return of investment is both social and economic. The long timelines were discussed from a range of perspectives by different respondents. Respondent 11 underlined the need for long-term maintenance of softer values such as pride and trust. That interview was conducted in April 2020, and though the quote pertained to the covid-19 situation in relation to events, the degree of foresight was not common at that time: “We need to rebuild trust slowly. We will not be able to return to 40,000 visitor festivals straight away but will need to slowly work our way up to the regular numbers.” It took until May 2022 before an event was hosted under normal circumstances. The issue was not discussed as touristic; getting attendees to show up was the case of building mutual trust and social capital.

The large-scale developments of the town hall, museum, and library tend to overlook the potential influx of people looking for a day of leisure, easily available in Glasgow and even Braehead, the shopping centre on the border between Glasgow and Renfrewshire. Respondent 10 mentions the “2-hour drive limit” family weekend, a key demographic in Scottish leisure developments, also utilised by Renfrewshire Council to define the boundaries of who will likely go to events in Paisley. This is a touristic method of thinking, but also about providing attractive activities for locals and gauging competition. An important demographic for the Paisley town centre is the affluent areas near Paisley, which are now seeking leisure, culture, and indeed identification with Glasgow rather than Renfrewshire. Respondent 10 addresses the dynamic; Paisley “needs to be reducing that distance, whether it’s a mental distance or a real geographical distance, or where you want to increase the distance mentally to say we’re not Glasgow. Still, we need to communicate that people do not overlook us when visiting Glasgow.” Respondent 3 (BID) mentions a living town centre, and Respondent 6 (Councillor) discusses how Paisley (and Renfrew) needs to be the hub for the local area and also points towards the inclusion of locals as main users of the local space.

Values created in this area are not always easily communicated to policymakers. McGillivray and McPherson (2015, citing Foley, 2011) argue that the economic potential remains at the centre of event bidding: “At the level of governmental justification and media interest, the economic imperative remains the single most prominent ideology in bidding for events and for creating new events as part of public policy implementation”. This can be seen both seen in the “almost” caveat from respondent 7 (in this section) and Respondent 9, a RC regeneration officer who develops the thoughts on social benefits: “They are very real benefits. And I think at times, [...] that people really had to have felt like they had to make the case for the instrumental benefits of culture just to keep funding coming in from different sources. This is not just true for Renfrewshire, extending beyond it as well”.

7.2 Observation data

During the first part of this project, observation data was collected. The observation was primarily conducted at and around Renfrewshire Council. From April 2019, one full day per week was spent working at the Regeneration Team's office. This meant taking part in all regular meetings, social events, and activities carried out by that team, even when it did not coincide with the designated weekday spent at Renfrewshire House. The embedded position meant taking place in several working groups. The observations at Renfrewshire Council and Scottish government were collected through field notes. Because the time period was extended (dozens of full days in both cases), it was recorded intermittently during the days based on themes: policy issues, regeneration, events, City of Culture, and miscellaneous. The informal interviews were filed with the rest of the observational data.

Some work was performed outside of the project, for the Regeneration Office. The work was clearly related to the wider idea of measuring the value of events in Paisley, such as writing a report on the expediency of the commissioned event reports' methodology. In addition to this, presentations were held throughout the project with updates on progress, findings, and methods at the Partnership Board and in other Renfrewshire Council contexts. As part of the embedded position, 10 semi-formal discussions-interviews were held with Renfrewshire Council officers. These were only recorded via notes, and are treated as background conversations, rather than data sources. They are not included in the in-depth interview section. Instead, they were used to inform the sequenced research design during its development, as well as provide observational data, which is not attributed to a specific respondent.

Lockdowns due to the covid-19 pandemic were put in place in mid-March 2020. During the early days of the lockdown, there was no clear indication whether it would continue for a long time. Though the observation agreement was not formally terminated for a long time, there were no technical solutions in place to keep up to date with the team's transition to remote work (e.g. computer with Renfrewshire Council VPN), and the marginal value of observation was diminished when informal chat in the corridors was removed.

Other types of observation were added along the way. Four out of five observational sources are directly or indirectly related to the work at Renfrewshire House. These are not treated as

separate sources. In 2022, three months were spent at the Scottish government’s National Performance Framework unit, at the heart of the wellbeing strategy in Scotland. This was treated as a separate source of data and thus has its own subsection at the bottom of this chapter. See Table 14 for a full account of observation sources.

Table 13. Observational data sources.

What?	When?
Co-worker Regeneration Team	Early 2019-Mid 2020
Future Paisley Partnership Board	Early 2019-2023
Visitor Strategy Data and Insights Group	Early 2019-Mid 2020
A Vision for Paisley Town Centre 2030	Early 2019-Mid 2020
Internship Scottish Government	March-June 2022

The observational data does not engage exclusively with evaluation. Findings pertain to strategic priorities, practices, and motivations behind the Paisley regeneration programmes, including events and festivals. In the case of Scottish Government, it looks at current and future policy discourse on wellbeing and sustainable (social) development. This is an area where Paisley was a forerunner in deeply connecting cultural policy with social priorities; their legacy ambition is well-aligned with the SDG approach.

7.2.1 Economic value

The work with culture and events in Renfrewshire focus to a large extent on attracting tourists. The priority is shown partially with the work with data analysts, academics, and the ambitious branding processes for Paisley. Measuring and following up tourism numbers was a priority for the council. In the questionnaire used in 2018 for Renfrewshire Council’s commissioned event data collection, 11 out of 31 questions were nearly exclusively aimed at people visiting Paisley from outside Renfrewshire. These evaluation priorities remained across the whole studied period. This even though some of them, such as the number of hotel nights in Paisley due to participation in festivals and events, was typically small (see Chapter 6). Other low-scoring questions in the 2016 (and to some extent 2017) evaluations

were removed, such as the added value from volunteer work. Volunteers were only used to a minor extent by Renfrewshire Council, and the methodology used did not prioritise finding out other organisations' commitments; the question was dropped.

Being part of the Visitor Strategy Data and Insights Group gave insight into this work. The group is a cooperation between the Regeneration office and other parts of the council, developing a dashboard for tourism in Paisley. During the observation period, the results were meagre, but hopes were still high that it would turn; new tourism interventions were planned, such as the launch of Future Paisley and the finalised version of the new town centre. These hopes were important factors in the hopes for a creative economy in an attractive Paisley even 1.5 years after the lost bid; observation of the group ended with the onset of the pandemic. The duality was underlined in the meetings:

Excerpt of notes from Visitor Strategy Data and Insights Group meeting, early 2020

The new tourism dashboard was rather ambitious, with statistics, geo-locations, and one-click data analysis features. It had been fed the 2019 data which was used to try out the functionality. It was benchmarked against the central tourism target numbers. Virtually all numbers were below, or much below, the target. The irony about the fact that the successful implementation of the ambitious dashboard showed negative numbers was expressed through snorts when data points were discussed. Especially the number of hotel nights were below the expected.

Policymakers in Renfrewshire were keeping a positive tone about the scheme throughout the observed period, keeping the economic aspect central. One policymaker alleged at a partnership meeting that the regeneration programmes had increased visits to Paisley by 300 % (as previously noted in Hell & McPherson, 2022), despite some negative data (such as the tourism dashboard). Not all hopes had been fulfilled, and the positive or negative perspectives could be portrayed; the positive prevailed not just in touristic communication, which was to be expected, but also in-house to those with a bird's eye view of the project.

The future of the town centre was still unclear: discussions about a reconstruction of High Street, a vision for 2030 and beyond, had gone far enough that architects had created mock-

ups (360 Architects, 2020). At that point, the current High Street with its pedestrianised streets was only about a decade old. The developments underway aimed at creating a “cultural district” stretching a kilometre between the Coats church (at that point, the Baptist parish were in negotiation with the council about financing and usage rights) in the West End through the university, the museum and library, the shopping on High Street, down to the town hall and Abbey. This district is largely synonymous with the event venues, save for the arts centre near the middle of Illustration 4. Events in Paisley are likely to stretch out throughout the district rather than focused around the Abbey/Town hall.

Illustration 4. Repeat of the data collection sites and event venues from Chapter 5 (map source: OpenStreetMap)

7.2.2 Public Value Priorities

There are two organisations/campaigns closely related to branding Paisley as an attractive destination, Paisley Is (primarily during the bid and immediate aftermath) and its successor Future Paisley (launched in 2020). These work with placemaking, bringing in high profile events after having achieved a surge in the viability of Paisley as a stage, and cooperation

across a wide range of local and national actors. The latter are related to cultural, academic, social, and other organisations (NHS, Police Scotland). Future Paisley list as their key strategic priorities the step changes designed for the bidding process. The goals are considerably overlapping with this study's area of interest:

1. Radically change Paisley's image and reputation in Scotland, the UK, and internationally.
2. Raise prosperity and increase wellbeing in our communities.
3. Paisley will be recognised for its cultural innovation.
4. Transform Paisley into a vibrant town centre.
5. Develop a sustainable and resilient creative economy in Renfrewshire.

(Renfrewshire Council, 2023)

The broad public value commitment was also expressed during participation at meetings for the Partnership Board, part of both the PhD studentship and the placement at Renfrewshire Council. The partnership board, discussed in detail in the qualitative findings, being a key method for engaging and maintaining contact with the broad array of actors working for culture and development in Paisley. Topics of wellbeing methodologies, approaches to urban regeneration through culture and events, as well as discussions on comparable towns' solutions to similar problems were frequently part of the discussions by politicians, civil servants, and academics.

The Partnership Board programme items were related to the hosting of specific events and local planning decisions, with their implications for the wider regeneration programmes. Still, despite the loosening ties of the Partnership described by some respondents of the in-depth interviews, these values were at the core of the group. Instead, the most visible sign that the Partnership was not as thriving as it had been, was that a large portion of guests did not show up and that the same organisations left their chairs empty. Respondents stated that attendance, especially from non-Paisley based organisations (primarily government and Glasgow-based) and representatives with a private business-oriented position was higher during the bid.

7.2.3 Social value

During the time in the regeneration office, culture and regeneration through cultural means were high on the agenda for the working group. In the chapter on urban regeneration, discussions about events- and culture-led regeneration as a varnish rather than a long-term commitment stand out as some relevant criticisms. In the regeneration office, these programmes had priority in at least the same order of magnitude as more classical brick-and-mortar projects. The creative economy, widely speaking, is a priority in the regeneration schemes. RC offers incentives for these types of businesses. As a type of introduction to Paisley in the first weeks of the observation period, a regeneration officer gave a tour of the town. High-profile brick-and-mortar developments were shown, such as the newly constructed flats on Cotton Street and recently expropriated derelict houses. In addition, a handful of creative businesses were pointed out: graphic artists, and production companies. These had either started with the help of RC or moved in from Glasgow for the lower business and housing rents. These were described as key in the transformation in Paisley. One pound of business in Paisley was not neutral. Instead, the creative economy was important in the rebranding. With an increased creative sector, Paisley would seem more attractive, and possibly more compatible with potential inhabitants and professionals from the middle class.

Social value was observed in the same areas as discussed in the literature review and findings above. This was not least visible during the event runtime:

Excerpt of notes from visiting the Food and Drink Festival, May 2022

Several of the non-local food stalls described that they were surprised by the ambience in the town in spontaneous conversation; Paisley was louder, more festive, and more crowded than similar events in other parts of Scotland. The town did light up, literally and metaphorically, and it was easier to find willing respondents than during the Autumn season events. Several people spontaneously interacted with me even after I had removed my clipboard and visible identity card, which is otherwise unusual in the streets of Paisley.

These experiences were the norm at the events, as seen in the quantitative results. However, the observations showed more negative results as well, seen in the following subsection. These were not captured by any other type of data.

7.2.3.1 Observation of dissent

As seen in the interviews, some local business owners (Respondent 1) were unhappy with the engagement from the council, requesting more investment in local businesses. The criticism was based on a general agreement that regeneration and culture went well together, and that Renfrewshire Council's general priorities were sound. Respondent 1 was not the only person in Paisley related to creative businesses with a less-than-eager attitude towards regeneration. Representatives for both business, local government, and non-profits all had a balanced view of the positives and negatives of the cultural interventions, usually leaning towards the positive (see the discussion on normative consensus above; Nabatchi, 2012").

The story was sometimes different when representatives did not know they were speaking to an academic doing research on Paisley; there was sometimes a threshold in terms of confidence and openness. On the other hand, observations being made in informal situations were very rich. A meeting with a foreigner, seen as a tourist or a person staying for a short time in Paisley, made people in the streets tell their own stories and opinions about what Paisley is, was, and might be. This was not least seen in the meetings with people in their workplaces:

Excerpt of notes from visiting hairdresser in Paisley, spring 2022

The barber contextualised the shop's situation to the cultural investments. The Paisley branch of the barbershop never received new gear, renovations, or interest from management. This was attributed to the low status of Paisley. The barber saw this as evidence that Paisley was left far behind. Although he did not mind culture or events, the investments were largely misplaced according to him. The money should be used to invest in service businesses such as the barbershop. The implausibility of competing with Braehead

was underlined: they have cinemas, a climbing centre, and lots of entertainment which people are actually willing to pay for, but are unlikely to be seen in Paisley.

When asked informally, the hopes of the bidding years had waned to some degree. Several people spoke unprompted about how Paisley was not able to compete with large shopping centres like Braehead and cities like Glasgow. That the reputation was not likely to recover on the current trajectory, or indeed the hopeless notion that *no* trajectory would take Paisley out of the current negative situation except perhaps gentrification into another Glasgow suburb.

These expressions of dissent were not aimed at the content of the public cultural programmes (though it was considered futile by some). It may give a background to the discrepancies between in-depth interview answers and observational data. One interaction with a Renfrewshire Council officer was especially significant in underlining this. Renfrewshire Council has a “Business incubator and retail academy” called InCube. Their most visible function is their InCube shop, open five days a week on one of Paisley’s most attractive addresses. They sell local artists’ and designers’ work, as a kind of tourist bureau and showcase. Several Renfrewshire Council officers have given accounts about being proud of the shop and buying presents there. In April 2022, the covid-19 pandemic restrictions were still slowly being lifted. Still, most of the store’s lights were off, despite having been open for hours. The clerk, who had an administrative position in Renfrewshire Council in addition to working at InCube, was sceptical about selling a few items laid on the desk. They clearly indicated that the wares were not worth the cost, despite very moderate prices compared to comparable giftshops in e.g. Glasgow. Their final words were “Paisley is rubbish. Don't spend any more money here”.

‘A person with a lower management position in the tourist agency felt like she fooled someone who bought gifts for less than £ 50 and felt prompted to dissuade anyone from shopping there. This observation was unlike most experiences of Renfrewshire Council representatives; any expression of criticism is normally followed up by contrasting positive judgement or a plea to keep their opinion secret. This observation may indicate that dissent laid deeper than the elite actors interviewed. Business owners and respondents at events

were positive, but the talk may be different in other circles, such as the negative ‘bubbles’ of business owners discussed in Chapter 6.

7.2.3.2 National Performance Framework Unit

During 2022, three months were spent full-time at the Scottish government to participate in the work and observe the work on strategic wellbeing. As described in the chapter on event economics, the National Performance Framework is an institution aimed at broadening the horizons of social progress and values created. The NPF is based on the United Nations’ Sustainable Development Goals (United Nations, 2022). Other tools based on the SDGs tend to develop methodologies contrasting from New Public Management practices. This can be seen in models such as the European Commission’s (2020), and indeed already the Fitoussi report as discussed above (Stiglitz et al., 2009). The same is true for the NPF. Social value is prioritised, in practices at the expense of monetary estimations.

One of the issues with NPF is proven to be the handful of competing frameworks with overlapping goals in the Scottish public sector. The conundrum was particularly clear during conversations with Scottish Government officers who had a hard time aligning to all frameworks at once. The knowledge of what frameworks existed was good in related policy areas. Social and family welfare were examples of areas where more than one framework competed for attention in reports and publications. There were expressions of fatigue in some branches of government: not everyone knew how their work related to which frameworks, and the courses offered were usually a general orientation of the framework rather than a specific operationalisation of how to comply to the framework.

Several findings were made researching the frameworks:

1. Making public bodies comply to frameworks is a preferred method for Scottish Government
2. These frameworks are tools primarily used for evidencing social value
3. Social value is a prioritised area of evaluation in Scottish Government
4. There is an over-establishment of frameworks, at least compared to competence and willingness of government organisations

5. There is not sufficient coordinating action as to how many frameworks need attention from individual branches of government

Public sector organisations in Scotland are tinted by a spirit of equity and social pathos: Curriculum for Excellence (Priestly & Minty, 2013), SIMD (Scottish Government, 2020), NPF (Scottish Government, 2018), the early implementation of United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child (Scottish Government, 2021). This is true for local government as well: the projects studied in this thesis focus on holistic developments such as *inclusive growth*, *cultural regeneration*, and community partnerships.

This rhetoric enjoys strong support in several parts of the public sector (and wider society), but not everyone is ready to do the extra work, namely the administrative and analytical. All major publications, in principle, are supposed to align to the NPF. Annual reports and strategic route maps especially. Despite this, in the strategic documents studied during the internship at Scottish Government, around half mentioned NPF at all, despite a large amount of them related to the heart of at least one Outcome, and often closely relating to at least one Indicator.

Lacking knowledge and willingness to align with many frameworks lie behind some issues of implementing these. There is no part of the government *enforcing* the use of wellbeing across public sector. The NPF Unit monitors progress and to some degree informs about it. It is not particularly difficult to superficially align a public body to a framework – that is, report on progress using buzzwords in strategic documents. However, turning the whole organisation towards alignment is difficult and requires dealing with institutional norms, the creation of value, and fine-tuning statutory requirements in liaison with central government. It seems to me some parts of the public sector do not want to do the former, as they cannot currently do the latter. Central government seem to want the latter to start achieving the former.

The NPF Unit and other wellbeing efforts have a tailwind in the sense that the general goals and values are shared by the public sector. The lack of willingness to develop expertise, delivering non-statutory change, and some scepticism about the vagueness of some

operationalisations remain problematic for the wider implementation. This half-committed engagement still shows a strong will to enact symbolic interventions for equity and social value.

8 Analysis

Results above clearly show how the Paisley events programme produces a positive result even within the confines of a cost-benefit analysis stripped of social conversion of value, both in directly observed consumer surplus and economic influx. The relatively modest investment of £1.1m per year in the direct organisation of the events thus repays itself several times over according to any metric used in this study. This chapter analyses the values brought to Paisley through the means of the public events programme, financed and/or organised by Renfrewshire Council with the tools defined in chapters 2-4. Being a mixed methods study, as well as a sequential one, data sets have thus far been kept separate. In this chapter, the approach is thematic rather than separated by types of value. Being a case study, all available data is considered and analysed according to its power of explanation, without a process of standardisation or generalisation based on what is available elsewhere. The following chapter uses thematic analysis as described in 5.3.5. but retains call-backs to research objectives. Table 15 shows the relation between data sources and the objectives.

Table 14. Research objectives in the thematic analysis.

	Objective
Cost-benefit analysis	
Spending	1
WTP/TCM	1 & 2
Inclusion and equity	
Accessible culture	2 & 3
Supporting NGOs	2 & 3
Thriving town centre	1 & 2
Urban space	
Heritage and non-use	2

Liminality	2 & 3
Tourism	1
Good for the town	1 & 2
Negative values and disruptions	1-3

The literature review identifies the overarching themes as event evaluation, urban regeneration in events, and event bidding. Tools have been developed based on these three areas, and this typology guides the thematic analysis below. During the collection of data, some perspectives were found which did not have an apparent homestead in any of these chapters. In the case of policy and strategy, it was covered in the literature review, but proved to be more relevant to many of the interviews and observational data; it thus has its own section. Protests, dissent, and negative values were not a considerable part of any data source. Still, they are discussed in their own category as they are inherently different. Negative values are not the same as the critical voices from interviews; the critical discussion of RC officers remain within the internally acceptable discussion of a public body.

Monetisable values (as defined in the methodology chapter) are analysed in a partial cost-benefit analysis early in the chapter. The typical cost-benefit practice of recalculating social value into monetary figures is not performed, but social value remains within that realm in absolute terms, though discussed in relation to monetary values. In the CBA section, values are estimated and given a monetary weight. This is discussed in relation to a null hypothesis: no public intervention in the events and festivals industry. Though it is unlikely that a town of Paisley's size would not host any events at all, the 6-8 large events hosted in Paisley each year are outsized compared to similar towns in the UK, especially as Paisley is in such direct competition with Glasgow. Several smaller events hosted by Renfrewshire Council or in Paisley are not included in the analysis; the Paisley Book Festival, the Renfrewshire Doors Open Days, the range of events hosted by Paisley First, and all Hogmanay events. After the cost-benefit analysis, other values are introduced. Cost-benefit compatible findings are discussed in relation to these, but an effort is made not to double-count values.

Before the direct analysis, this chapter starts with a discussion and reiteration of key themes. An outline of the political situation in Paisley as found in the data and other public sources is provided, not specifically tied to categories of value, nor the general overview seen in the introduction. The direct analysis of findings based on literature begins with a cost-benefit analysis, performed on the economic data. This compiles the economic data from the previous chapter's different data collection stages. Finally, public value analysis is performed on the rest of the data not included in the previous sections.

8.1 Cost-benefit values revisited

Cost-benefit analysis is the most prominent method for the evaluation of public interventions, designed primarily for infrastructural projects but now used for virtually every branch of the public sector (Boardman et al., 2018:249). By counting all negative and positive values associated with each alternative public investment, a bottom-line figure is presented. According to CBA, an alternative ending with a positive bottom line is, if the analysis is correctly made, worth doing. This study breaks some of the rules which would be applied to typical rigorous CBA studies: there is no social rate of discount (the lasting value is not calculated) and not all variables are quantified and valued or deemed intangible (some of them are instead treated as public value, subject of separate analysis).

The CBA methodology is used to analyse a large portion of the quantitative data. This is particularly related to research objective 1, based on economic theory. There are three methods for calculating the willingness to pay used in this study.

1. A baseline direct, open-ended question during the 2019 first phase of data collection.
2. Double-bounded dichotomous choice. Respondents were presented with a random starting value and asked whether they were willing to pay that amount for the public events, the sum iterates until at least one 'yes' and one 'no' has been recorded, giving a maximum amount. This aggregated maximum willingness to pay gives a direct figure which escapes many of the reliability problems of direct WTP, such as

starting point normality bias (Arrow et al., 1993), lacking starting point and protest zeroes (at least partially).

3. Conjoint bundles. Respondents are presented with two randomised bundles of hypothetical events programmes, with seven variables (number of festivals, type of shows, etc.). The respondent chooses one of these two. The bundle exercise is repeated two more times. By calculating the relative weights, it is possible to extract the aggregated preferences in each of the options of the seven variables as negative or positive numbers. This does not give a direct WTP sum.

A large part of the cost-benefit values analysed outwith the WTP are secondary data from RC's evaluation reports. These include questions about money spent in the town centre and touristic potential, but also an EIA. The priority shows in the retention of questions relating to hotel nights, which kept being recorded for several years despite mostly showing modest figures. Some questions around touristic opportunities, reputation of the town, and opinions about Paisley in general were only recorded for the most intensive period of the bid, in 2017. It is noteworthy that the evaluations are already quite ambitious based on the events' size, especially some of the smaller ones, where as many as ~10 % of all attendees responded to a 35-question survey.

The CBA works as an input in the overarching public value framework. Though its results are interesting on their own, it needs to be understood in relation to other variables to be useful information: we get a calculated monetary equivalent, but equivalent to *what*? The Meynhardt and Jasinenko (2020) approach, with a suggested generalised model for public value operationalisation might go part of the way, but even more may be achieved by integrating the CBA as a public value input.

8.2 Public value

Public value has risen as an alternative to traditional economic evaluation methods, aiming for inclusive and comprehensive value creation. Initially, it was a framework for assessing

the impact of public interventions (Moore, 1995). It focuses on assessing value that aligns with the needs and priorities of the public, by public value (as in 'shareholder value') and public value (as in an organisation's core values) (Fukumoto & Bozeman, 2019).

Normative consensus is the process of reaching an agreement on what is valuable and how valuable it is within a society (Nabatchi, 2012). Though impossible to achieve a true consensus on subjective matters, it is essential for democratic decision-making to reach a tentative agreement. With aligning values and less target conflict, more utility is experienced. In the public sector, normative consensus involves understanding and reflecting the preferences and values of the public in policy and decision-making processes. Normative consensus does not necessarily imply a normative approach to public value, though the debate is ongoing whether PV is a prescriptive way of organising the public sector or a way to gauge the public's preferences and thus experienced value (O'Flynn, 2021).

The public sphere, as a public value, refers to the opportunity for public communication and discussion about values and resource priorities, presented by Bozeman and Johnson (2015) as additions to other, more typical social value. It is part of Bozeman's deliberative approach, emphasising the importance of public engagement and participation. The public sphere gauges open and accessible discussions that shape public value and inform decision-making processes.

Progressive opportunity is another specific public value presented by Bozeman and Johnson (2015) focusing on creating conditions for equal realisation of individual potential. Not simply aiming for increasing equity, it addresses structural inequalities and historical differences in opportunity structures. Progressive opportunity evaluates people's chance to reach their full potential. A lack of progressive opportunity is seen as a public value failure; collective action and equitable, structural policies are likely to alleviate such failures.

Developing public value analysis of events is the main theoretical contribution of this study, largely synonymous with research objective 3, exploring novel ways of event evaluation.

Analysed here are the findings' relation to these theoretical concepts, and their implications for event policy.

8.3 Social value

Social value analysis may relate to any evaluation relating of values affecting the society rather than the economy. The difference is not always clear-cut, neither in events nor in other areas (Getz et al., 2017). It exists in all types of public evaluation, as social value is the end goal of most public sector operations. CBA can incorporate some social value (Fujiwara et al., 2014) and conversely, EIA has a method for social impacts (Eventimpacts, n.d.).

The social value of events has grown into a body of literature with recurring themes. Several of these are utilised in this study. The main values discussed are sense of community, pride in place, social cohesion, and social capital (a typology used by Smith et al., 2021). These are closely related to research objective 2, the social impacts of the events programme. These are used to evidence other types of positive effects than economic

8.4 Cost-benefit analysis of Paisley events

This section performs a calculation of costs and benefits, negative and positive values associated with the Paisley events programme. The period used for the CBA is the season November 2017-October 2018, whereas other figures are used for comparison and time series data. The reason is twofold: first, raw data was only available for five events in 2018 – the rest was lost by consultancies and RC. Second, because the investment and ambition were still at their peak, and thus not affected by the decline in momentum of popular support and investment after the loss. Benefits and costs are divided by direct and indirect effects. The indirect effects are externalities, being outwith the direct control of RC, which organises all events studied. This full section relates mainly to objective 1, relating to the economic value creates in the events programme. The argument that TCM and WTP include social value spills over to objective 2, but only to a limited extent, considering the strong economic profile of these methods.

As part of the analysis, the target of investments is also discussed, being part of Renfrewshire Council’s strategy and thus interesting to demonstrate understanding of the efficacy of their interventions. Costs primarily rely on the stated investment from the organisers, but also negative economic value. Few negative values are discussed in these sections, partially because of the very low reporting of negative aspects from quantitative respondents. Values discussed in this section are displayed in Table 16.

Table 15. Types of CBA data and their properties.

Data included	Value	Source	Polarity
Willingness to pay, dichotomous choice	Use + non-use	Phase 2 quantitative	Positive
Willingness to pay, conjoint bundle	Use + non-use	Phase 2 quantitative	Positive
Willingness to pay, direct question	Use + non-use	Phase 1 quantitative	Positive
Spend in town centre during events	Use	Renfrewshire Council Evaluations + phase 2 quantitative	Positive
Displaced spending	Use	Phase 1 quantitative	Negative
Volunteering	Use	Renfrewshire Council evaluations	Positive
External support	n/a	Renfrewshire Council evaluations	Positive
Direct investment in events	n/a	Public sources	Negative
Investment in cultural infrastructure	n/a	Public sources	Negative

8.4.1 Costs

8.4.1.1 Direct Costs

The key direct cost of hosting the events is the organiser’s expenditure. At around **£ 1.1m per year**, the figure can be brought into perspective by rephrasing it as **£6.80 per unique event visit**, or **£6.18 per Renfrewshire inhabitant per year** (or **£14.2 per Paisley inhabitant**). This million per year in funding constitutes around 0.25 % of Renfrewshire Council’s budget. The proportion of the council’s funding used for events was disclosed in the online questionnaire as a part of the information box by the willingness to pay questions. In Table 17, direct costs are displayed. The direct costs are easily understood, being the only category without the need for theoretical discussion, as the RC payment is relatively unequivocal.

Table 16. Direct event costs paid out by Renfrewshire Council in 2018, compared to Culture Republic’s, EKOS, and James Law Research Associates’ consultancy Eventimpacts reports. Christmas lights switch-on and Fireworks extravaganza taken from 2017, as those were not evaluated in 2018.

Name	Details	Direct Costs	Estimated Benefits	Sum
Food & Drink festival	April 2018, benefits include £16k direct organiser income	- £62,655	£147,279	£84,624
Halloween festival	October 2018, benefits include £63k direct organiser income	- £217,702	£982,200	£764,498
Monte Carlo Rally start	January 2018, no organiser income	- £42,000	£36,723	- £5,276
Pipe band championships	May 2018, benefits include £31k direct organiser income	- £195,000	£500,776	£305,776
Sma Shot Day	July 2018, benefits include £2k direct organiser income	- £109,400	£111,329	£1,929
The Spree	October 2018, benefits include £80k direct organiser income	- £231,500	£295,730	£64,210
Christmas Lights	December 2017, benefits include £2k direct organiser income	- £133,000	£163,701	£28,701
Fireworks extravaganza	November 2017, no organiser income	- £111,000	£167,866	£56,866
Sum		-£1,102,257	£2,405,604	£1,311,880

Based on the critique of the method used for reaching this GVA, one could instead display all spending, as in Table 17.

Table 17. Identical to Table 17, except that estimated benefits also include local residents' spending.

Name	Details	Direct Costs	Estimated Benefits	Sum
Food & Drink festival	April 2018, benefits include £16k direct organiser income	- £62,655	£543,398	£480,743
Halloween festival	October 2018, benefits include £63k direct organiser income	- £217,702	£2,181,251	£1,963,549
Monte Carlo Rally start	January 2018, no organiser income	- £42,000	£65,326	£23,326
Pipe band championships	May 2018, benefits include £31k direct organiser income	- £195,000	£696,144	£501,144
Sma Shot Day	July 2018, benefits include £2k direct organiser income	- £109,400	£384,495	£275,095
The Spree	October 2018, benefits include £80k direct organiser income	- £231,500	£640,657	£409,157
Christmas Lights	December 2017, benefits include £2k direct organiser income	- £133,000	£654,739	£521,739
Fireworks extravaganza	November 2017, no organiser income	- £111,000	£527,432	£416,432
Sum		-£1,102,257	£5,693,442	£4,591,185

The direct costs increased significantly during the bidding process. The Monte Carlo Rally Start began in 2014, the Food and Drink Festival began in 2015, the British pipe band championships began in 2016, and the Spree a few years before that. The Halloween event has kept growing since 2017, with increased capacity and expectations. These are thus a part of the ongoing investments in culture, emanating from the UKCoC bid. These are set to “go mainstream in 2024”, as Respondent 8 in the in-depth interviews puts it. The investments will go back to a long-term model, not boosted by the temporary decade-long increase.

It is noteworthy that even if these events would keep going, the peripheral functions associated with the programme might not remain fully funded: the Renfrewshire Council officers hired year-round to develop the events programme and the organisation for regeneration and placemaking, Future Paisley, might not receive the same comparatively generous funding as during the last decade.

For the £1m investment in each year's event programme to be worth the cost, it needs to either directly bring in money to RC, motivate a tax raise, or be valuable enough that other costs can be

Renfrewshire only receives around 17 % of the costs back in direct income. But a shift in perspective will give a picture of the cost situation. 1.1m is a small cost compared to other categories of spending in Renfrewshire, and even cheaper considering the wide array of positive effects which may substitute other public programmes. Even if the events were seen as simply entertainment for locals, the costs would still be acceptable to the visitors. Cost per Renfrewshire visitor varies between £6 and £8 per event. This is a price that 80-85 % would be willing to pay according to the DBDC method, and near the mean level for the direct question WTP.

8.4.1.2 Indirect costs

Many of the negative effects are not easily quantifiable into monetary figures. Those who are likely candidates – increased littering, disrupted commuting, noise – would require specific data collection from sources not covered in this study. Some of these are instead left to the thematic analysis of public and social value below. The only significant discussion of negative values, despite ample opportunity to do so in several data sets, comes from the evaluation reports, where a sizable group of respondents are discontent with the general cleanliness and attractiveness of Paisley's urban spaces, unrelated to the events.

In the Autumn of 2018, the newly commissioned consultants James Law changed the estimate by deducting money spent by the organiser in the local economy. This can be related to interviewee 1 from the in-depth interviews, who spoke about the lack of event-

related spending from Renfrewshire Council in the local economy. In Chapter 4, this is discussed as the booth effect – keeping resources within the local market (Chalip, 2017).

Local investment amounts to around 10-20 % (£110,000-£220,000) of total organiser spend, according to evaluation reports; fluctuating between different events and different years but always within that spectrum. This can hardly be considered a high proportion in a local authority of some 120,000 people, with most resources readily available in the confines of the local authority.

The proportion — estimated above at 10 % — of business lost in Paisley due to the events is in reality a displacement of resources from retail to mainly hospitality. Some central retail locations benefitted greatly, but the bulk of the extra spending went to pubs, restaurants, and cafés. This is not necessarily good — older strategies of urban regeneration in Paisley were aimed at supporting retail to retain a thriving town despite the nearby Braehead shopping area and online shopping. However, cultural investments have a lower engagement with that side of commerce as Tallon (2020) and Evans (2011) discuss, retail investment is another type of regeneration scheme with some overlapping aspects, including increased footfall. The difference can be highlighted by Respondent 6 who attested that the BID hosted events with light entertainment: rides, petting zoos, and street vendors rather than a cultural programme. Attractive hospitality services have been important in the offerings for the event trade was mentioned in several in-depth interviewees.

Some of the negative costs may well have economic effects, but are not visible in an economic analysis due to their social framing, with the costs showing up at the other end. The cost of displacement is real. Rocha and Xiao's (2022) review shows as diverse effects as stark increase in cost of living, segregation, demolition of public/social properties, and removal of jobs. Certainly, the UKCoC is not the Olympics, but the investment in culture is strong enough for there to be a displacement effect, observed at least in the ECoC case (Hughes et al., 2003). Even though job and home loss are textbook examples of long-term negative consequences, their economic aspects are also relatively well understood (Kahneman, 1999).

8.4.2 Benefits

As the costs, benefits are divided into direct and indirect categories. Direct benefits relate to the observable effects of the Paisley events. This includes spending at the events (which is very limited), but not spending at other stores; these are considered externalities (see Chapter 4 for discussion). Not all indirect benefits will be covered here. The second half of this study, the public value analysis, is an extensive collection of indirect benefits where no monetary conversion has taken place. They constitute most of the benefits, as the direct sales of a mostly free-of-charge event programme remain naturally low. It is also notable that no multiplier is added to the values; multipliers' extents are contested and may contribute to uncertain and overoptimistic evaluations (Baade & Matheson, 2016). Still, because of the relative lack of direct incomes, indirect figures constitute most cost-benefit compatible values.

8.4.2.1 Direct benefits

In Table 17, the benefits accrued from hosting public events are greater than the costs according to the RC methodology. The trend is similar throughout the years during and after the bid, with a slowly increasing trend of positive results with the increasing number of visitors. The picture is greatly different when only observing direct payments to the organiser. The direct income varies between around 0 % (Sma' Shot Day, Monte Carlo Rally Start) and 30-35 % (Halloween, The Spree, Food and Drink Festival) of the expenditures (around 17 % for a full season). Events and festivals do not ensure a great influx of direct resources to Renfrewshire Council. Nor do they constitute central functions of a local authority's operation. The literature surveyed in Chapter 3-4 shows how overoptimistic organisers explain the values associated with hosting events to the public and local businesses despite not pulling its weight directly (Næss, 2011; Baade & Mathesen, 2016). This is partially to keep a frail consensus together, and in turn, because events and festivals can be regarded as simply entertainment, not worthy of unwavering attention and continuous economic support.

The estimated *benefits* column in Table 17 are the full economic benefits calculated by the consultancy reports commissioned by Renfrewshire Council. As findings (and indeed the EIA methodology) show, touristic events are favoured by EIA. Community events do not show up at all, making some events show directly negative effects. Policy makers know full well that the EIA does not tell the whole truth. In this case, commissioned evaluations do not provide policy advice which is then acted upon: the events producing a negative bottom-line value are not removed or substantially reworked to fit the model. This relates strongly to research objective 1 — a good enough account of economic value that it can be acted upon. A method which can easily be disregarded could be directly counterproductive.

Table 17 includes spending by visitors (residents excluded), organiser direct income, and organiser direct expenditure. The problems with the Eventimpacts (and indeed other EIA) methodology have been discussed thoroughly above, but the benchmarking serves an important point: this value, in addition to the number of attendees, is the key figure used by decision-makers and that should not be overstated. Renfrewshire Council pays a team of interviewers and analysts to calculate this figure and base their opinions about events' success on this figure. Eventimpacts is a cautious tool (communicated openly by themselves: Eventimpacts, n.d.). In the case of Paisley, it is plausible to add in value spent by locals; only a very small amount of this additional value would have reached the hospitality economy in Paisley, had the events not been hosted, see below. The same idea is noted by Culture Republic in their evaluation reports for RC: "The expenditure of Local residents is not included in the Eventimpacts methodology; however, it could be argued that the Halloween Event was the catalyst for expenditure that may not have been spent by residents within Renfrewshire. This is particularly valid given the proximity and attractions offered in nearby Glasgow.". The mercantilist idea of running on a positive balance of trade as a goal is criticised in Chapter 4, not least backed by Abelson (2011) in the event setting.

All the while, the figure of a GVA or a "money added to the local economy" measurement is not equal to that gain for Renfrewshire Council, or that increase in living standard for Renfrewshire inhabitants. The figure is dependent on where the spending ends up, where those businesses' owners live and their production chains. The figure is not equal to the 'value of PR' or of the willingness to pay or travel cost. The positive externality of extra

spending in Paisley is relevant but cannot easily be put in relation to e.g. public spending without context.

Medium-sized events typically use the EIA method and may add a multiplier of retail and hospitality incomes. The Green Book's approach to multipliers (related to both the ONS and What Works Project toolkits) is complex and requires thorough estimation. It focuses on what is called 'tradable' (HM Treasury, 2018); that is, an output mainly trading with non-local money. Most jobs created in Paisley because of the positive economic effect are non-tradeable. Additionally, public sector jobs (which have indeed been created as part of the events programme) have an unclear effect on employment multipliers (What Works, 2019). Thus, no multiplier is used in this study.

Paisley's strategy, with its *inclusive growth* and *cultural, not culture-led regeneration* has made the conscious decision not to host many ticketed events; the incomes are not meant to reach the local authority. The most substantial income, as seen by the council, is the influx of money to the local economy through the hospitality industry and shopping. The direct benefits we can evidence are simply: **£195,000 in external funding and £6,000 calculated from volunteering.**

8.4.2.2 Indirect benefits

In Chapter 4, values are discussed as being either use or non-use. Non-use values constitute a considerable part of observable and quantifiable values in cultural programmes: O'Brien (2010) gives the example of the value created by simply having a museum in one's hometown, unrelated to the value experienced by going there. A simple distinction is not easily possible – the questionnaire does not entirely differentiate between feeling pride in place because there is an extensive events programme in Paisley and feeling pride in place due to experiencing the ambience at the event. Benefits are indirect when they are not directly observable in CBA terms; cause and effect are at least one step removed. These were only to a small degree, and for a limited amount of time, measured by Renfrewshire in the evaluation reports.

In the relative normative consensus created by the bidding process, some indirect benefits were inflated by the positive feelings and opinions associated with the cultural investments, and specifically the events programme. A considerable intangible value must be ascribed to the non-use values observed. Non-use is especially pronounced in economic and environmental values, as discussed by Lundhede et al., (2013). The heritage (*bequest*) value, and to let future generations take part in things considered important may incite strong feelings and preferences. In Paisley, the non-use is present not least in the “it’s good for the town” statements; when discussed further, it is a broad sense of wanting what is good for Paisley, rather than connected to any utility. This feeds into the discussion about what social value or economic value is; sound policy advice will surely include averted costs in several steps removed from the direct investment.

Renfrewshire Council additionally reports £4.3m in media value from the cultural investments (Renfrewshire Council, 2019). The media value comes from (positive) attention in sources such as the BBC, newspapers, and digital media. This value is not added to this analysis for two reasons; first, because the value is mainly reputational, which is the topic for Wilson’s (2022) doctoral thesis, where the placemaking, media, and reputational aspects are discussed and critiqued. Second, because it is out of scope to evaluate media value. This would require a theoretical apparatus to discuss, but it is relevant to state that RC places this additional value on the cultural investments. It is likely that the positive media attention has contributed to the attraction of national events mentioned in Chapter 1.

8.4.2.2.1 Opinions of shop representatives

Several regeneration methods are aimed at creating a positive bottom line for local businesses in the cases where there are interventions aimed at retail, the night-time economy, and leisure. Tallon (2020), classifies even dining and drinking as cultural activities “in the widest sense”. The night-time economy and the threatened retail sector in Paisley had seen attention from Renfrewshire Council, though little direct focus has been part of the cultural regeneration efforts. Though both the Business Improvement District and RC have communicated publicly the weight of local businesses, none of the 60 respondents spoke about unfulfilled expectations (though a small number of respondents noted that event

income was not as positive as they had hoped). Expectations may be a strong part of the consensus building, as discussed by Chalip and Heere (2013), and Kassens-Noor notes that a house of cards may be the result of unwarranted promises (2019). The data shows no such effect in Paisley.

None of the shopkeepers spoke ill of the events and festivals programme. The bars and restaurants were expected to support it out of self-interest, just as the City of Culture designation would have brought a steady stream of visitors. These were also clearly happier with the programme. However, a majority of those negatively affected by the events (18 out of 60 respondents were negatively affected) due to: rerouted traffic, having a highly specialised business, unattractive location for visitors, or regular customers who did not show up during the bustle of the events, were remarkably positive about the events anyway. Getting business to stay may be part of the same mechanism as bringing tourism in and creating pride in place, as discussed by Ellery et al. (2021). The feeling of belonging and willingness to sacrifice one's temporary benefit for a long-term goal is in accordance with the perspective on social capital offered by Putnam (2000). Paisley businesses willing to take on a negative economic effect can thus be explained both as social and economic resilience, unwillingness to displace businesses, and pride in place. Getz' (2010) wide definition of event value and Snowball's (2008) work take into account the same broad economic and social aspects of events, noting that they can emanate from the same indicators.

The few who were not positive expressed a neutral attitude about the cultural events, even the two who meant that "everyone knows that the events are bad for business". These two were in the same area, which possibly indicates that several business owners on the same street have formed a common opinion about the negatives of the programme. Indeed, they were in a very central part of town, but away from the main streets, and at the same time near one of the temporary parking lots. An extended discussion about informal communities and common values can be found later in this chapter, whilst this section stays closer to research objective 1.

The overwhelmingly positive opinions about events in Paisley by business owners were contrary to expectations. Several of the business owners lived out of town, and all the

negatively affected shopkeepers reported having the same problem with events over time, regardless of the type of event. The negative effects were universally reported to be extensive, most claimed that it almost killed business entirely during the festivals. None of the shopkeepers gave an estimated sum, but the negatives can be described as:

At least several hundred pounds of lost business per day

6-8 times per year

1-3 days per time

Interviewed in the sixth year of the increased-ambition events programme.

Over these six years, thousands of pounds per shop had been lost in direct income due to the events and festival programme, as reported by shopkeepers. This short-term cost was acceptable, even favourable to business owners in the area, due to the belief in the regeneration programme. The 10 % deduction of local spending calculated below was fully accepted by the affected. This does not show up in the bottom line but is an important piece of fulfilling the objective of what values are created with the events programme. This finding is intriguing, considering its implications for how stakeholders in Paisley perceive value, which is discussed below.

8.4.2.2 Willingness-to-pay

The double-bound dichotomous choice showed an all-over average willingness-to-pay of £13.67. This is equal to the consumer surplus, but the £15 category would also have been the category giving the highest revenue based on price elasticity compared to revenue per visitor without the possibility of perfect discrimination. Over 2/3 of respondents preferred to be taxed this amount, and paying the stated amount for *each* event, no matter if they attended or not. **Aggregating this average value to each of the 145,483 visitors equals 2.18m.** The conjoint bundle results indicate some event exhaustion; the lower level of five events per year was preferred by a majority of respondents. The survey communicated a programme of “six to eight” events. An even higher WTP per event would thus likely be possible to achieve with a sparser events programme. The willingness to pay around £100 per year and respondent is well above what Scottish local authorities are spending; over 200

% of the sum RC spent during the most intensive period 2017-2018. This shows not just a consumer surplus but also stable support, especially because 70 % were willing to pay for all events through the tax bill, and very few were only willing to pay the lowest amounts.

Though the WTP sum is an indication of the full economic potential of ticket sales, closely relating to objective 1, the context adds other perspectives. The social value may reach a point of diminishing returns at around five events per year, considering the exhaustion. This does not necessarily indicate that fewer attendees will show up, especially with a touristic, varied programme, thus still leading to positive economic impacts. However, it is quite likely that negative values increase with event exhaustion, including the ambivalent relation to place and community expressed by locals in tourism-dependent towns (Amsden et al., 2010).

8.4.2.2.3 Travel cost analysis

Travel cost analysis aggregates behaviour relating to travel. It thus provides the monetary figure which respondents are at least willing to pay for the experience. Being non-intrusive (revealed behaviour), not risking protest zeros, and with a negligible risk of insincere responses to affect the results in a certain direction, the advantage is that the outcomes have a high reliability, and a decent validity for the 'at least' statement. Other, peripheral spending such as shopping and food and drink cannot as easily be directly related to the willingness to pay for the event experience.

A large proportion of visitors at some events come from outside of Renfrewshire, and even relatively cheap public transportation from the outskirts of Renfrewshire will make the accepted price in parity with the flawed initial WTP method. Still, the value of locals (which make up the majority of visitors) will be low, considering their proximity to the events. Like several other values presented in this study, it is to be regarded as an "at least" value; this is a basic tenet of the travel cost method.

Travel cost analysis is often presented separately as a measurement of the utility derived from a good rather than including other use values, such as previously cited works (Chae et

al., 2012; Bateman et al., 1996; Hellerstein, 1991). Evaluating sense of community, pride in place, and social capital cannot be separated from the values of WTP and/or TCM. The same mix-up of social and economic value can be seen in the shopkeepers' positive opinions. However, the experienced value might be higher rather than lower for those living close to the event in absolute terms, not just because the benefits outweigh the costs in more cases. Thus, travel cost analysis becomes an inversed tool, showing how those who travel from afar are investing more to participate; these two work well in tandem when the social value is not expressing its own economic value.

The best uniform data available for data analysis is the 2018 events data; this was the only data which had not been lost by consultants and Renfrewshire Council. The events available were Halloween, The Spree, Sma' Shot Day, Christmas Lights Switch-On, and the British Pipe Band Championships. The latter was removed because of the very different profile of visitors, and that a large portion of visitors were friends and family of participants who would not have visited Paisley without their personal connection. 1612 respondents were surveyed at the four chosen events, around 400 per event. Out of these, 1583 provided enough information to perform a travel cost analysis. The distance driven was calculated from the postcode of a respondent's home to the lawn outside Paisley Abbey, the most common area for events.

Data was prepared with Maply (2023), a service which calculates GIS data from Google Maps. In this case, it generated flying distance and road distance as well as driving time. The time was set to Friday afternoon driving conditions, as most events are hosted at weekends, and driving conditions in Paisley are seldom as disadvantageous as during large events. The average road distance from events was 16 kilometres. The full operationalisation of travel costs is found in Appendix A, and the results are shown in Table 19.

Table 18. Results of travel cost analysis, one way (n=1582, collected for RC)

Mode of Transport	No of respondents	Average time (minutes)	Value of time	Average distance (km)	Average cost	Value time+cost

Car	692	21.216	£5	18.27	£5.2983	£10.3
Bus	299	14.4	£3.4	10.9	£3.80	£7.2
Train	132	39	£9.2	40.5	£10.5	£19.7
Walk	323	29.3	£6.9	2.2	£0	£6.9
Other	20	36	£8.5	30	£8.7	£17.2
Taxi	55	28	£6.6	8	£22	£29
n/a ⁵	61	20.22	£4.7	33.7	9.773	£14.5
Weighted average	1582	23.5	£5.5	15.8	£5.16	£10.7

The table above shows the results of the travel cost analysis. This is a one-way trip for the respondents coming to Paisley mainly for visiting the event. The two-way trip would thus mean that a comparative value of £21.4 is invested in visiting an event per visitor. This is almost four times the value of RC's investment in events and amounts to a total of £3.1m extrapolated to the 2017-2018 events season's 145,483 estimated visitors (as seen in the table above).

The travel cost plausibly includes social value experienced, but they cannot be singled out without further input. Thus, it gives a partial answer to research objective 1, estimating the economic value of the events programme. Hardly any of the travel cost is exchange value, and the method favours tourists travelling a long way. This aspect is similar to the EIA, with the lopsided focus on visitors. Nonetheless, the high validity of the 'at least' willingness to pay for the experience makes it a useful complement to the WTP.

8.4.3 Results of cost-benefit analysis

⁵ The 'Other' category existed in the data, whereas the n/a signifies lacking data in terms of mode of transportation, but not in terms of domicile. This was given a cautious value, see Appendix A.

The full cost-benefit calculation is seen in Table 20. A brief explanation of the sources of these figures:

Organiser income: 2018 RC figures

Organiser expenditure: 2018 RC figures

Volunteering: 2018 RC figures

Travel cost: Calculated from 2018 evaluation reports, see section “Travel cost analysis”

WTP dichotomous: Calculated from the phase 2 questionnaire, see section “Willingness-to-pay”

EIA calculated influx: 2018 RC figures

Local spending: 2018 RC figures

The 10 and 21 % deductions are defined in Appendix 2, relating to the lost business in Paisley due to the events, and the income which locals would have spent in Paisley anyway.

Table 19. Costs and benefits summation

Benefit		Costs	
Transactions			
Organiser income	195,000	Organiser expenditure	-1,100,000
Volunteering	6,000		
Calculated			
Travel cost	3,100,000		
		TC 21 % casual visitors	-651,000
WTP Dichotomous	2,180,000		
Sum of benefits	5,481,000	Sum of costs	-1,751,000
Benefits minus costs	3,730,000		
Externalities			

EIA calculated influx	2,211,000		
Deduction 21 % casual visitors	-464,310		
Local spending	3,288,000		
Deduction 21 % casual visitors	-690,480		
Deduction 10 %: local spending lost	-328,800		
Sum externalities	4,015,410		
Total sum of benefits minus costs	7,745,410		

It is notable how much higher this estimation is than Renfrewshire Council's approach. The sum of direct costs and benefits is equal to the total consumer surplus from the direct hosting of the event. Added to this as an externality is the shopping which would not have occurred in Paisley without the event.

The method of adding WTP to TCM is discussed in Chapter 4. Though this requires caution in order not to overstate values, it can be regarded as a sort of substitute for plotting a demand curve. The final result of £8,074,210 in value created or being spent in the events in Paisley are equal to £55 per visitor. The meaning of this figure is: *the value the average respondent is willing to give up in order to experience a day of events in Paisley, minus the costs of the organisers*. Theoretically, £3.7m is the sum RC would have to pay directly to consumers for them to experience the same amount of utility as if they did not host the programme. In addition to that, respondents were willing to pay £4m for other goods.

8.5 Scottish, local, and UK policy's effects on Paisley

The most crucial documents surveyed in the literature review were:

The UK Green Book (HM Treasury, 2022) and its preparatory works (most importantly O'Brien, 2010 and Fujiwara et al., 2014), Scotland's event strategy 2015-2025 (Visit Scotland, 2015), The National Performance Framework guidance (Scottish Government, 2018), *The Untold Story* (Renfrewshire Council, 2014), The DCMS guidance documents for UK City of Culture 2021 and 2025 (DCMS, 2017; 2021), OECD's guidance for hosting mega events (2018). These are all potentially influential documents in the hosting of events in Paisley. This section looks at their implementation in Paisley's events programme, to better understand what approach most clearly aligns with Paisley's.

Fujiwara et al. (2014), in the Green Book's development of SWB, state that cultural services do not typically have direct market values. The effects should be identified as far as possible and proportionately quantified and monetised." (HM Treasury, 2022). This approach is leading the way for the influential Green Book, but the strict CBA is not mirrored in the other policy documents surveyed. Nonetheless, it is the UK's preferred method for evaluation, and as such it is mentioned in several documents: *The Untold Story* (Renfrewshire Council, 2014) claims to adhere to a Green Book approach in calculating good value for money. Similarly, the DCMS claims that the UK City of Culture is organised with the Green Book's approach in mind (in addition to endorsing Eventimpacts) (DCMS, 2021).

The same can be seen in Paisley's decision not to incorporate social value indicators, though readily available from the same organisation that made the EIA framework. This is seen in the way that values are spoken about; respondents 3 (BID) and 6 (Councillor) underlined the economy's paramount importance in the previous chapters underline the relation to the economy as being tangible; other values less so, but important. Social value is discussed by all groups of respondents, even on-site attendees, but the validity is lower than the discussion about cultural gains, economic effects, and urban regeneration. Less communication has been done in this area, likely partly because these indicators are not at the heart of the programmes (or perhaps a higher level of abstraction is needed), similar to the lack of discussion of operationalised 'inclusive growth' in economic policy. Accordingly,

Hull 2017 commissioned a *post hoc* Green Book appraisal (University of Hull, 2021). Despite that, there is little trace of a willingness to monetise cultural experiences and social value in the UK City of Culture in the most important documents or evaluations.

Illustration 6. 360 Architects' mapping of existing, developing, and prospective event venues in Paisley (360 Architects, 2020)

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions

The OECD guidelines (2018) were helpful in framing the bid; one respondent notes how these publications became the final convincing argument for some people in the administration. The principle of 'even if you lose, you may still win' resonated well with the Paisley bid (and perhaps the town's underdog mentality). Several respondents discussed it in hindsight: "it would have been brilliant to win, *but*", and "we are better off with a losing bid, considering how things went", referring to the covid-19 pandemic.

Respondent 9 who underlined the importance of policy guidance also noted the development during the last few years: “Economically, it was not too difficult to actually demonstrate what the collective benefit was. The social value was slightly more intangible, but it’s interesting a few years on; we’re actually far more sophisticated now.” This is demonstrated in the literature review as well, how the policy documents have turned towards an inclusion of social value; this study thus brings Paisley’s investment programme closer to the contemporary and future expectations with its second, social value objective. It is notable how NGO representatives can discuss social value with high precision, perhaps partially because they had been part of the partnership’s communication channels. All the while, their knowledge or interest of quantifying social value (indeed, *all* value considering that NGOs seldom have a direct economic impact) was limited; no incentives to do so had been provided.

Looking directly at Paisley’s policy, the *Untold Story* spends more space on heritage assets than events. Heritage as an object of study is closely related to events (Sanetra-Szeliga, 2022); they are both ‘intangible’ assets with a high experience value from the public, both require workarounds to evaluate and most importantly, together they form some of the most important assets of attracting tourists. Similarly, the largest single point of investment is the museum, which is arguably Paisley’s greatest single supply of heritage experiences. The second largest, the Town Hall, is slated to become an event venue, but the refurbishment was needed to keep the historical building in shape, and the intended use is not just for public events, but as a cultural hub (Renfrewshire Council, 2023). Naturally, the UKCoC gets the most attention in relation to events in the *Untold Story*. Eight of the eleven in-depth interviews mention the museum, and seven mention the town hall, virtually all respondents who works close to the council and then some. None mention it as a source of direct revenue, but rather as central pieces of what Paisley is trying to achieve, increasing attractiveness and reputation. The investment in these values, in-between social and economic, defines the Paisley approach which adds to the sometimes-difficult separation of economic and social value.

Combined, the underlying policy documents shaping events and evaluation in Paisley’s

political context encourage both social and economic evaluation. The social aspect has been growing in the last years, essential steps have been taken since 2014 when the Paisley policy was laid out. The social value findings in the previous chapters show a great deal of added utility, but as the understanding is still considered limited (Mair et al., 2021), the third research objective's aim to develop novel methods is underlined.

Cultural regeneration had not fully taken off during the studied period, the culture-led approach with the economy having some precedence over social value was warranted in documents from DCMS, but also from Scottish government. Increased focus on the National Performance Framework, the work with an updated Scottish events policy for 2025-, and the 2025 UKCoC guidelines from 2020 show how Paisley's move towards integration.

8.6 Bidding process

The bidding process for UK City of Culture 2021 in Paisley started long before the 2017 designation was made. The immediate start was the publication of *The Untold Story* in 2014 when the bid was announced, but the first steps were taken at least when the previous regeneration schemes were deemed unsuccessful around 2010, and a culture-led approach was being designed. The bearing idea of culture-led urban regeneration is to revitalise the town centre through investing in culture, which Chapter 3 covers extensively. These are supposed to drive investment in other sectors.

In Paisley, the initial investments and plans were built on the partnership approach devised in Scotland's event strategy 2015-2025 (Visit Scotland, 2015), and the *step changes* devised by the DCMS to evidence long-term development will be taking place. The step changes are as follows:

1. Radically change Paisley's image and reputation in Scotland, the UK, and internationally.
2. Raise prosperity and increase wellbeing in our communities.
3. Paisley will be recognised for its cultural innovation.
4. Transform Paisley into a vibrant town centre.

5. Develop a sustainable and resilient creative economy in Renfrewshire.

These align with many values surveyed in this study; all step-change themes are discussed in one context or another. Interventions which are part of the cultural investment programmes are mapped according to this step change map, and the model has been adopted by Future Paisley after the bid. The partnership approach gathered actors from all sectors in and around Paisley.

The partnership, as well as a public survey of thousands of Paisley inhabitants, were used to design the bid. Respondent 7, who took part of the consultation and campaign to get support for the bid stated that these consensus-building efforts were amongst the most important steps to achieve the cultural transformation of Paisley. They spoke in terms of Kassens-Noor's (2019) warnings about creating an unstable consensus which can easily be retracted, but also about the value of a tentative normative consensus, increasing the experienced value of the local population (Nabatchi, 2012).

Renfrewshire Council has adopted the practice of engaging the public in consultations. The largest one so far was the 15,000 people stating their opinions about the bid for UKCoC, discussed by Respondent 4 even discussed this as a key asset; this could be seen as contributing to (normative) consensus through the creation of a public sphere. The consultancy reports have been a litmus paper for support in Paisley as well, but the more expensive and ambitious 2017 reports, asking respondents about their views of Paisley and knowledge about the bid, were not renewed for the 2018 season. The 2017 reports some surveying of the consensus, despite the lack of deliberative elements. All the same, during that year, the reports were based on over 40 questions, which took a great deal of time for respondents to complete. The results of these more in-depth questions, being overwhelmingly positive, could be interpreted as a general support of the Renfrewshire Council urban regeneration and cultural policies. Things are going in the right direction; no need to change things. Conversely, many respondents who were very content with the events in the first phase of primary data collection still gave low or zero as the maximum WTP. Though there are several reasons for protest zeros, the contrast is still notable; they did not want anything to change with the events programme and were unwilling to quantify the

positive status quo. The consultancy and engagement with public support constitutes a partial creation of public sphere value, but hardly in an open, deliberative format needed for full effect.

As several of the interviews showed, the partnership approach was a strong uniting factor during the bid. This started to lose some pace after the loss, according to the same respondents. The same trend could not be observed in the quantitative data. Instead, the continued development of the events resulted in higher satisfaction in 2019 than in previous years. This was particularly underlined by the difference between Renfrewshire inhabitants and visitors. The former were happier with the events; on a 1-to-10 satisfaction scale, over 80 % of locals said 10, whereas around 60 % of visitors did. This degree of satisfaction constitutes a substantial value, not just because Paisley manages to host a popular events programme, but also in terms of consensus building; a strong connection to place and positive sentiments about the urban spaces. This is despite that such high results can be questioned – local respondents are not neutral, and neither is the situation being interviewed on the street *during* an event. The practice of locals maintaining support out of a sense of responsibility (Chalip, 2017) and the difference between studies before, during, and after events (Kavetsos & Szymanski, 2010) may play into this.

The willingness to defend Paisley's reputation aligns well with the *sense of community* and *pride in place* social value (Stevenson, 2020:9; Collins, 2016:176). The former has been demonstrated in several ways; what is good for the town more generally is what should be prioritised. Renfrewshire Council's efforts to equate the cultural investments with a positive development for Paisley, and in turn something worth defending, has worked remarkably well. An interesting parenthesis contrasting with this value is the observational data, where several people living in Paisley would talk negatively about the town when the situation was less formal and more spontaneous, not a scientific study. The validity of these observations is low, but a range of people has uttered opinions much more negative than *any* of the many comments in the structured data collection. This could be interpreted as a strong sense of community with a lack of actual pride in the place – willingness to criticise informally but externally defensive. This finding remains speculative.

8.7 Legacy and leverage

The legacy programmes in Paisley are set to go ‘mainstream’ in 2024, an expression used by respondents 8 and 10 to signify that the supercharged cultural funding runs out. After ten years of extended investment, the legacies will not be supported by extended financing. That does not mean that the expected effects are over. On the contrary, the whole town is supposed to transform during these years. This was expressed by all the RC officials, whose discussion of the 2024 deadline is covered more below. Goals include creative businesses thriving, inclusive growth continually achieved, and a permanently raised status of the town. In the literature review, the difference between *legacy* and *leverage* has been discussed (Chalip, 2017; McGillivray & McPherson, 2015; Misener et al., 2013). In Renfrewshire Council’s case, there has been a substantial focus on both leverage and legacy in their urban regeneration strategy. Legacy-wise, direct interventions into areas as diverse as education, healthcare, social work, and leisure are all targets of redesign. Though several of these require engagement from partner organisations, such as NHS Scotland, they are revamped public interventions and can be treated as legacies. The leverage includes the partnership; activities that are not directly organisable by Renfrewshire Council, but which occur externally because of the event’s surrounding activities.

The long-term investments in legacy events have shown some significant results. The revisit rates are high, especially the Renfrewshire visitors have virtually always been at another Paisley event within a year before the survey, which feeds into both social and economic value (although visitors are less covered by the social value discussions than locals). The strongest result in the Likert-style questions in phase two also was “It’s important that towns host public events and festivals”, followed by the questions about ‘good for community’, that ‘Paisley livens up’, and that physical hosting of festivals is an important feature. Though all questions received high results, this priority shows what effects of the events programme is most important. The legacy events programme enjoys a strong support because of its role as a positive force for the town, rather than as a vessel for leverage. Businesses and reputation are on the minds of respondents (as seen in all data sources), but far from as prioritised as the direct effects of the events. Thus, the events programme gives an actual sense of local

pride. Though the extent of that pride may be put into, Paisley is perceived to be more attractive and interesting during the events and festivals by those who live there.

None of the open-ended comments from the primary quantitative data connect the events programme to wider social programmes other than that they may be 'good for businesses'. Questions about taxation, satisfaction, and public priorities relating to events and cultural policy are asked, giving potential cues. The events programme seems relatively detached from other developments; but indeed, a good thing in itself. These benefits lie closely to the grouping of Smith et al.; "Identity formation, belonging, civic pride, pride in place" (Smith et al., 2021), central to social value creation. This data does not indicate that the legacy increases contextualisation into other policies, and call people to action. Externalities are thus not top-of-mind by the public.

8.8 Inclusion and equity

Inclusive growth is a leading star for the Paisley process of urban regeneration. Some of the problems in Paisley are related to poverty and other socioeconomic deprivation. Paisley is a potential site for some degree of gentrification in the longer run considering the proximity to Glasgow, but so far, few development projects within Paisley have indicated that possible future. As discussed previously, progressive opportunities (or the social value studied) do not define equity as a value in itself, but rather the opportunity to equally realise one's potential. Bozeman and Johnson (2015) concede that a high degree of equity is desirable for a good implementation, though. Considering the current situation in Paisley, lifting communities out of socioeconomic deprivation would still be a prioritised action for those who would want to level the playing field. Here, the Paisley policy target aligns well with research objective 3; RC has limited operationalised indicators for what inclusive growth is, and the concept is only mentioned in passing in the long-term economic strategy.

The overarching goal for the Paisley events programme during the studied period was to support the UKCoC 2021 bid, and after the loss in 2017, to keep a strong legacy programme. These events can be understood as a driver of the long-term goals of a raised town profile and thus a more prosperous life for its inhabitants, but these are vague indicators of

inclusion and equity. Instead, the main indicators in this study have been:

- provision of cheap, accessible culture
- programme aiming to attract socioeconomically deprived groups
- lowered thresholds for participation
- increased activities of social NGOs
- a thriving town centre

These are also the subheadings of the following section. The following section focuses on research objectives two and three, with the main analysis of public value findings as well as a significant portion of the social value findings. Accessibility and deliberation are mapped to the public value additions: progressive opportunity, public sphere, and normative consensus. These would be unlikely to be properly captured by a social value study.

8.8.1 Accessible culture

The first two indicators: ‘provision of cheap, accessible culture’ and ‘programme aiming to attract socioeconomically deprived groups’ can confidently be described as successful. An outsized portion of respondents from all available data sets have been from socioeconomically deprived neighbourhoods and with lower wages. None of the events except the ticketed *The Spree* stands out as especially unattractive to these groups. Comments in all data sets have been positive, and economic accessibility is one of the most common positive notions. When asked what type of events would favour the town economically, and what they would like to see in the future, many answers were in the line of ‘free events’ or implying that the free tickets are of importance for their participation (‘More events on the streets’, ‘Community interaction’). The events programme also provides a stage for community cultural activities, reaching a larger public than they would otherwise have. Events showcase comparatively high-profile amateur acts (PACE youth theatre, the Abbey boys’ choir), as well as a range of choirs, theatres, bands, and other artists. Providing these groups with an auditorium in addition to publicly provided resources for rehearsal and organisation would add a progressive opportunity to more marginal culture. The latter also relates to the lowered thresholds of participation and letting all make

use of their ambitions and development. This also allows for diversity in more senses than socioeconomic; Bozeman and Johnson (2015) argue from the point that “human diversity begets inequality” – which can be demonstrated in the findings that on-site respondents implied that ‘this event is for us’ was a positive value in itself.

8.8.2 Supporting NGOs

The external effects created by the events programme, such as a place to display local NGOs’ work do not have as robust evidence to support it. Though the full bidding effort did indeed see an increase in community work, the events programme’s role in this is not clearly enough expressed to be a decisive indicator of an effect of the events programme specifically. These social NGOs have an important role to play in the levelling of the playing field regarding equal opportunities; mental health issues and inadequate access to food and shelter are some examples of their work, but the integration was only partial into the events scheme. This is despite very positive sentiments about the community groups from both in-depth and structured interviews. It is relevant to mention the events co-organised by NGOs and supported by Renfrewshire council but not part of the public events programme as defined by RC, usually because of the lack of an open-air profile or exclusively ticketed shows.

The one exception from this is Sma’ Shot Day, organised in liaison with the Old Paisley Society, celebrating local history. RC supports the work of the Old Paisley Society, whose community-run museum provides an admission-free historical and cultural experience six months of the year. The relation was described in positive terms both by Old Paisley Society representatives and RC representatives in the in-depth interviews; the RC support is modest considering the value produced for schools, locals, and tourists. Especially during the many years of a closed Paisley Museum, Sma’ Shot Cottages has been the foremost visitor’s site educating about Paisley’s textile heritage. Though not gauged, it is likely that it scores high in the non-use values. More conspicuously, Paisley’s foremost local history attraction, with its relation to the paisley pattern, comes at a very low cost for RC. The sense of community is a resource which can be effectively used for the common good.

Supporting NGOs can be a cheap way of creating value. Not necessarily a cynical calculation, limited economic support tied several NGOs closer to the council's plans. Respondent 7 noted that: "We received a small amount of funding for culture-related activities. Small, but not insignificant for a small organisation. Culture became the golden thread." These organisations were tied into RC's ecosystem more tightly, making them stakeholders in the council's plans. Engagement in the partnership greatly increased discussions on strategy and policy, as noted by several respondents. This feeds into the public sphere value, and even more closely to the issue of deliberation more widely, though contested in the PV literature (Moore, 1995:181; Bozeman, 2007).

8.9 Urban space

Transformation of urban space is urban regeneration's credo. With the addition of *culture-led* (or cultural, see Chapter 3) regeneration, the transformation may take on a wide array of looks. In Paisley, the physical regeneration of deprived areas has partially been left to more conventional programmes without strategic regeneration funding. This is after the self-assessed failures of previous programmes of urban regeneration looking at the physical environment and retail industry. The most conspicuous transformation of urban space has been the town hall and museum + library redevelopments (Paisley.is, 2017), the ongoing redevelopment of the High Street (360 Architecture, 2020), and the usage of temporary transformation of central Paisley during events. The latter has to some degree been dependent on Renfrewshire Council's decision to keep a large piece of space free from permanent developments in the most attractive addresses in town; a circle around the Abbey, bordering the town hall and Renfrewshire House, the council seat (see Illustration 7). It exceeds ten acres. This area is not the only open-air events venue, but the most used.

The flagship developments were created under the earlier, culture-led regeneration days. These created policy windows for other, smaller projects, but were also central to the idea of a high-profile Paisley. They are not meant to 'pay themselves off' in a way possible to calculate. This is a conundrum of the culture-led approach. There is a high expectation that the investments will yield results (Dwyer et al., 2015). At the same time, brick-and-mortar redevelopments are long-term endeavours. Costs like these can be taken out of the

equation; none of the respondents spoke about the value that these redevelopments will bring. These gains will be long-term, as prerequisites to other value creation and as resources to draw from for a long time ahead. The need for measurability restricts itself to projects that has a clearly measurable component, such as events, where a positive bottom line is crucial to the extent that there are several methods designed to fabricate them (Evans, 2004). Yet the almost entirely *intangible* projects like the renovation of the town hall might not face the same requirements.

Urban space is difficult to separate as a particular policy area or theme; for instance, it relates to equity as well as economic and social aspects. Though more apparently connected to social value, it is also related to spatial equity. Access to high-quality urban spaces is an issue of inequality correlating with socioeconomic status (Tan & Samsudin, 2017). The following section more strongly focuses on social value to make the division more intuitive.

Illustration 7. Inner Paisley. The full area between Cotton St, Gauze St, and White Cart water are without permanent developments save for the town hall, the Abbey, and monuments. (Source: OpenStreetMap)

8.9.1 Heritage and non-use

Events constitute an important part of the change taking place in the physical realm of Paisley. A recurring answer to open-ended questions about events was that respondents would bring friends and family from outwith Renfrewshire to see the events because the town shows its best side. One of these sides is the Abbey's northern wall; projections of light art installations on the historical bricks create a connection between now and then. The paths, lawns, and Cotton Street bridge become a makeshift amusement park with stalls and rides. The transformation during events, to see what Paisley is and can be, lies close to the heart of social value experienced in the events. Especially on-site open-ended comments clearly express its importance. Not all towns have access to an area this central and attractive which can be remade so readily adjacent to the rest of the town's hospitality offers. Paisley also has Scotland's second highest number of listed buildings after Edinburgh (Paisley.Is, 2017), which provides the events with a surrounding of historical sites from

hundreds of years of textile and ecclesial golden ages.

The usage of events as a driver of engagement with heritage is a strategic goal in Paisley. The events strategy includes a considerable mapping of and investment in potential venues. PACE, Paisley Methodist Church, and the Wynd Centre are examples of listed buildings repurposed for events. Not least the in-depth interviews, this was a priority; both the private sector, national agencies and local government representatives mentioned the heritage aspect as important for the Paisley regeneration. Indeed, heritage is similar to some social value in that it is mentioned as apparently important, but in vague in terms of what exactly it provides. Scott's (2010) discussion of heritage as a public value rhymes with this intangible style; it is possible to profit from heritage socially and economically, but the road there is not necessarily easily mapped. During the *Untold Story* years, and 360 Architecture's (2020) vision for Paisley town centre includes several developments yet to see the light of day, and several venues have already been repurposed (several of these, including Coats Memorial Church, are kept within the confines of private or denominational ownership).

8.9.2 Liminality

These preconditions give a head start to Paisley, but also form a contrast to the dilapidated houses even on would-be attractive addresses in scenic and/or central part of town. The recurring expression that Paisley is showing its best side when the events are on has an undertone; 'this is what Paisley *could be*; to "show that there are reasons to visit the town centre" (respondent from phase 2). The transformative potential of these events is expressed in terms echoing liminal experiences, or perhaps more correctly, liminoid, as they not necessarily include the resolution of personal crisis (Turner, 1974). The comments from both phase one and two include the very positive "The town lights up", which is not just a statement of the physical illumination. It includes the faces of locals and visitors, laughter, and the familiar spaces seem to contain something different than usual. Of the 10 reasons respondents could choose as reasons to visit, "I like the event" was the most prominent, outscoring "the programme" and others, an opinion strengthened by respondents' strong preference to keep the programme touristic, whilst not caring much about what the programme featured. This is another testament to the value of events as experiences where

the transformation of place creates pride in place and indeed social capital (for a discussion of liminoidity/liminality as a driver of social capital, see Chapter 3 and Peachey et al., 2015). The difference between being unwilling to bring friends to one's hometown, and on the other hand being proud to do so, is a substantial step. The physical environment is the same, and no expensive clean-up is done before events. It is simply a matter of looking with different eyes and being part of a town come alive. Chalip's (2006) discussion of contributions to social value through increased socialisation. Events are not just a programme, but liminoid social experiences, "a means to enable event participants to meet and to socialise".

8.9.3 Tourism

Events and festivals are leveraged by the site's general reputation and heritage assets. The want to increase Paisley's reputation stems from a wish to seem attractive not just to organisers of major events (though being in their favour had RC's attention during the bidding years) but also to attendees, and indeed Paisley inhabitants themselves. Tourism is, in this sense, both an (economic and reputational) end goal and a way of showcasing Paisley's capacities as a host. In Renfrewshire visitor strategy (2018) 2018-2021, ambitions are extrapolated from 2016 numbers into the future; 54,000 non-locals visiting public events (155,000 visits) in 2016 had grown to 63,000 in 2018, and the ambitious target for 2020 was 100,000 (that was not hit; covid-19 thwarted such ambitions).

Social value is focused on locals in this study; pride in place, social capital and sense of community are unlikely to affect non-locals as much. Their contribution lies not least in their willingness to visit Paisley. These visitors, though not even 10 % of the circa 2m visits to Renfrewshire attractions in 2016 (Renfrewshire Council, 2018), remain as important a figure as any other, signifying a high priority for the council; compare with Myerscough's (1988:101) estimation that five local visitors are 'needed' for the same employment effect as one tourist. Tourism and reputation were at the heart of several of the in-depth interviews, especially those of civil servants. Providing visitors with a full 'day out' for the family (respondent 10). The policies of events and culture are aimed at both locals and visitors, but respondent 10 underlines that these are not easily separable: "It's not just about the

economic benefits that come from tourism. It's not a kind of trickle-down economic strategy. The starting point really is 'what do people need?'. Values created for the one group are meant to benefit the other. This is also seen clearly in the "both-and" policies executed by Renfrewshire Council: a great deal of attention was given to both legacy and leverage. This clearly steered clear of the crashing bid problem (Kassens-Noor, 2019). RC did not focus as strongly on developing artists as they did communities; McPherson and McGillivray (2015) assess that both are important features of the UK-wide strategy towards leverage rather than legacy. The event programme has both more local (Sma' Shot Day) and very general (Halloween) celebrations, but the socioeconomically 'inclusive' perspective and touristic offers are prioritised. This is true for all events except The Spree, where only limited engagement is given to the general public, instead prioritising the high-profile shows. The strategy seems to be working in the sense that not a single of the respondents criticise the idea of hosting outward-facing events. Hosting primarily touristic events (rather than focusing primarily on locals) was the second highest priority of the conjoint bundle method. This indicates that looking inward or only attracting locals is not the best way to build sense of community or pride – all values were high in the popular touristic events. Seeing Paisley through others' positive eyes seemed to be a positive contribution; the Olympics largely aim for similar effects as smaller events, despite not primarily being for locals but for a tv audience. Mair et al. (2021) note that social cohesion and sense of community are central indicators of social gain even in mega-events despite their scale. At the same time, a programme focusing on local history was about as popular as general culture. Though it may seem similar to "targeted to locals/tourists", the former had the highest priority, whereas the latter was the least prioritised. Paisley-specific culture is deemed to have the same potential as general shows, but the events should be for everyone.

Though tourists do not experience pride in place or sense of community in the same way that tourists do, they may enjoy a positive ambience. This is more difficult to quantify, though heritage values are popular targets of cost-benefit analyses (Bravi & Gasca, 2014; Baéz & Herrero, 2012). The cultural experience is an attractive force which is not directly evaluated in this study, partially because of double counting issues. The Green Book approach is fully based on the evaluation of cultural experiences, stating in the early evaluations that cultural experiences in the UK were valued at around £100 per month and

individual (Fujiwara et al., 2014). This instead gets translated to the willingness to travel and consume at the event, and locals' touristic and cultural experiences are also baked into the CBA. The tourists enjoy something which can be correctly described as consumer surplus, and thus remains a more important factor in the CBA than in this section. The locals' experienced values are well-understood by themselves to be unrelated to the actual culture on offer, instead often being summarised as "good for the town".

8.9.4 Good for the town

What is "good for the town" is important for several groups of respondents, perhaps most strikingly the shopkeepers who were willing to lose some economic value themselves for the greater good. Something similar is shown for the values experienced by the quantitative phase 2 respondents; what is most important about the events is that it is ultimately positive for Paisley. This is clearly altruism rather than primarily delayed gratification, but also a sense of belonging and the collective benefit of a better town. "It's good for the town" is seldom concretised to discussions about business, tourism, civil society, or something else. Instead, there is a general understanding that the current interventions are positive in the long run. This relates closely to creation of social capital, where altruism, willingness to help others, and not least trust in institutions are part (Coleman, 1988).

Social capital can here be understood in Putnam's (1995; 2000) terms, relating primarily to participation and trust. In the case of events in Paisley, the participation in a European sense of civil society, organised and perhaps member-based, is only shown in anecdotal data from one respondent (the difference between American and European civil society has been described by Hvenmark & Wijkström, 2004). In a more inclusive understanding of participation, such as Putnam's, the Paisley events programme contributes substantially to social capital. Participation bolsters positive sentiment about fellowmen. The participation in this sense is easier to evidence than the deliberative tenets of central public value clauses (discussed in Chapter 2 in relation to Nabatchi, 2012; Bozeman, 2002; Moore, 1995). Nonetheless, the social capital created is part of public value creation as a social value. Furthermore, the reason they take part is stated to be (at least partially) altruistic, that is, helping others. Thus, Paisley has managed to create a positive feedback loop of social

capital. Dussaillant and Guzman (2015) have written about disasters (e.g. natural) as bases for positive feedback loops, and though it might be rash to call deindustrialisation in Paisley a disaster, there are similarities. The poor reputation and socioeconomically disadvantaged areas are a part of Paisley self-identification for better or for worse. That has led to some defensive behaviour (as seen above), but it also fosters reciprocity, negative or positive (also discussed by Dussaillant & Guzman, 2015).

Wanting the town to fare well is essentially a non-use value; it is separate from one's experience of it. But it is also supported by this feedback loop. In this sense, the cautious voices about the deteriorating partnership approach in the in-depth interviews is alarming for the public value creation. But deteriorating social cohesion also comes from those being negatively affected, and feedback loops can start in that direction too. Respondent 10 noted that Glasgow's cultural priorities had been going 35 years and counting and that a long-term priority of staying on target through periods of tailwind as well as adversity is the real test of the cultural transformation of a town. This echoes Bianchini's (1993) economic dilemma mentioned in Chapter 3, expecting quick results from phenomena which take significant time to build. This feeds into the wider problems of democratic accountability and wanting to show results within a single election cycle.

8.10 Negative values and dissent

In large investment programmes with far-reaching consequences for the urban environment and public priorities, dissent will invariably exist; real consensus is impossible in public policy as discussed in relation to Nabatchi (2012). In events, it has been studied both in terms of protests, such as the Rio 2016 riots (Talbot & Carter, 2017), and more general problems with a failing consensus (Kassens-Noor, 2019). Critical event scholarship identifies another set of negative values through power and structural analysis.

Dissenting voices were scarce in the material, partially but not exclusively due to the research design. As seen above, most data suggests that an overwhelming majority of respondents were very content with the events and festivals on offer in Paisley and thought that it brought out the best in the town. In terms of business owners, there were a few vocal

negative voices. Respondent 1, the local cultural entrepreneur, was unhappy with the low degree of local sourcing of services for the events (the booth effect; Chalip, 2017); using the respondent's venues and services in light and sound would have been a viable alternative for growing local creative businesses. A higher degree could indeed have been sourced locally which was discussed in relation to the economic effect. This might have produced a stronger normative consensus. The data suggests that the private sector consensus is strong, but creative businesses were only partially probed. The low source of locally sourced work may seem strange, but it is well-known that it is easier to encourage cultural consumption than production (García, 2004).

Considering the proximity to Glasgow with their greater supply of event-related businesses, as well as its experience in hosting large events, price and scale might well have played a part. Especially in central Paisley shops on usually busy cross-streets from the main lanes were negatively affected. These were convinced 'everyone' knew that events were *bad* for business, likely because these microcosms were categorically negatively affected. Where alternative consensuses were able to form, and where the shopkeepers were not in contact with positively affected neighbours, the statements were much stronger; "events kill businesses". Again, this shows the value of consensus-building and negative effects of letting contrary consensuses form. Supporting retail directly was deemed an ineffective method of regeneration in Paisley before 2010. The event-led features in Paisley are working in a different style where support comes from bringing footfall rather than financial support. The flawed consensus was not least picked up in the observation data, and especially in the encounter at the local authority's tourist shop. The negativity towards Paisley displayed an unabashed opinion which was unlikely insular, but rather a part of an acceptable way of communicating about Paisley.

The negative aspects of businesses particularly show the interplay between social and economic value, identified by authors such as Getz (2010) but studied to a limited degree. The socially negative values work conversely against the sentiment that events are "good for the town". The same way that this positive sentiment indicates sense of community, trust, and confidence in the local authority's work, the negative sentiments work the other way.

The business representatives were not happy with how things were done and gave clear signs of a degrading social capital.

Notably, no one gave any indication that there had been negative experiences related to persuasion about supporting the urban regeneration efforts. As discussed in the literature review, problematic methods, lies about results, over-optimistic calculations, and whip rather than carrot incentives to keep stakeholders and local actors together have been commonplace (Chalip & Heere, 2013; Kassens-Noor, 2019) when the bidding prospect is looking negative.

Negatives also included rerouting of traffic; the amusement rides close off one of the bridges over White Cart water, Abbey Bridge. Several bus lines are rerouted, and most of Eastern inner Paisley is affected by makeshift parking. Several of the businesses, even on attractive addresses near the venues, saw a large negative effect on sales because their regulars could not or did not want to come into town with roads and buses rerouted. This aligns well with negative values seen in the literature, which could be labelled 'disruptions' (Smith et al., 2021).

Temporary celebrations affect the urban space. As discussed above, that is to some extent a positive thing; viewing a familiar space painted in (metaphorical or literal) brighter colours. At the same time, disruptions will follow; Delamere (1997) lists the often occurring as: "disruption of routines, intrusion, overstretched facilities, reduced privacy, community overcrowding, traffic, noise, overtaxed human resources, and litter." Though all of these have likely been part of individual experiences in Paisley, not all have been seen in the data. Traffic, litter (and other cleanliness) were the most commented-on negative issues during the events. However, as was shown in the evaluation reports, respondents asked about the general improvement of Paisley town centre (unrelated to events) gave the same answer.

8.11 Cultural Regeneration and events

During the years following the losing bid for UK City of Culture 2021, a range of reforms took place. The common denominator was to turn the focus from a short-term burst of heavy investment in urban regeneration and culture, financed by loans and politically motivated by the prospect of hosting a mega-event. *Paisley.Is* and Paisley 2021 were partially replaced by *Future Paisley* as the PR channel for Paisley, the construction projects including the town hall, the museum, and the library needed to be finished despite no forcing mega-event deadlines. Ramped-up spending in areas such as events and festivals became a matter for discussion – what was going to happen to these comparatively small, but expanded areas of spending in Paisley?

The momentum of Paisley's showcased capabilities as a town fit for events was crucial to reap reputational benefits from the bidding process. This was displayed, amongst other things, with the commitment to the yearly public events programme, and the hosting of the Unboxed 2022 (the £120m UK-wide so-called 'Brexit festival') opening ceremony (Unboxed 2022, 2022). RCs internally reported £4.3m PR value for 2018 is part of the same narrative.

The other side of the coin was the implementation of cultural regeneration. This transition might have meant less spending, but also a change throughout a broader field of policy areas. Whereas turbo-charged tourism, regeneration and culture, and purpose-made campaigning organisations meant a change in the first place, long-term change was arguably meant to affect even more aspects of Paisley. The interview respondents discussing the transition from heavy investment to mainstream had partially diverging opinions. Whereas all saw the necessity of turning the *Untold Story* investment programme into a long-term situation, there were diverging opinions about how that should work. The personnel working with the ambitious events programme were under the threat of losing their jobs.

The updated cultural (rather than culture-led, discussed in Chapter 3) regeneration approach was less focused on flagship programmes and more on deep integration into partnerships and transformation of the public sector. This has the potential to address structural inequalities both in terms of opportunity and participation. Bozeman's (2007) negative discussion of aiming to achieve the absence of public value failures (such as lacking democratic deliberation, or inequitable opportunities) fits well with cultural regeneration. Its

aim of integrating cultural perspectives into every part of society treats culture as a generator of intrinsic value.

8.11.1 Implementation

There were several common denominators between the public value-related perspective found in the Scottish Government's application of the SDGs (NPF) and the cultural regeneration now utilised in Renfrewshire Council. RC's commitment to wellbeing theoretically works well with the NPF, though their documents are not explicitly aligned. During interviews and observation, Renfrewshire Council representatives show interest in alignment with NPF in a part of their work of staying ahead of the development in policy. Several Scottish institutions (Cosla, Improvement Service) indicated during the observatory placement in Scottish Government that the NPF will extend into local government during the years to come: having that competence in due time will likely mean advantages to implementation. More broadly, central welfare functions in government were interested in developing their commitment to the NPF; methodologies, outcomes, and targets were similar to the language they already spoke. For other parts of government, with less obvious (but by all means existing) connections to the SDGs, the same trend could be seen. The wellbeing frameworks, though usually supported in theory, were sometimes seen as difficult to engage with.

Officers with competencies in cultural and urban regeneration sectors in Renfrewshire Council were eager to work with a wide implementation of the cultural regeneration project, wider than culture as a political field generally is in local government. All mentioned wellbeing and socioeconomic factors as overarching goals, which points towards an SDG implementation. Respondent 5 also discusses how social value frameworks are on the rise in gauging value in Scottish Government's work with events and could lead to smoother communication about government support to local authorities.

From the other side of the table, the interviews noted criticism of regeneration implementations, both from the lack of commitment to the partnership from Respondent 7, as well as the call for long-term and broader advertisement of activities in Paisley from

Respondent 10, and the lack of offering work to local cultural businesses from Respondent 1. All these criticisms were from stakeholders in the cultural sector. When asking those who would not have been affected even by a traditional cultural policy, the engagement and knowledge about cultural regeneration is not as extensive.

There are contrary examples where contribution clarity was implemented. Renfrewshire Health & Social Care Partnership (HSCP), Renfrewshire's social care and community health service providers, are an example frequently cited by officers at RC where cultural cooperation with NHS Scotland and other stakeholders has worked. In a local government setting, the HSCP aligns with the regeneration goals of integrating culture as a key part of public life. Symptomatically, their strategic plan for 2022-2025 also demonstrates a deep implementation of the *National Health and Wellbeing Outcomes*, another Scottish outcomes-based framework solely related to the health sector (Scottish Government, 2015). "Through our CAHSC (Culture, Arts, Health and Social Care) coordinator, we will lead work with colleagues and partners involved in the Future Paisley programme through the CAHSC group to develop a range of arts and culture-based activities in a variety of settings to improve health and wellbeing" (Renfrewshire HSCP, 2022), also listing related National Health and Wellbeing Outcomes next to each strategic goal. The cultural part of the HSCP, the *Culture, Arts, Health and Social Care Group*, is explicitly described as coming out of the UK City of Culture bid; it is a part of Future Paisley.

8.12 Concluding remarks

This chapter aimed to make use of economic, social, and public value theory to contextualise the findings presented in the two previous chapters. The public value perspective, despite a limited number of direct questions addressing the operationalised variables, developed the understanding of what has been achieved in Paisley – and not. Some key findings were identified already in the preceding chapters, such as the surprisingly high WTP and the conjoint bundle preferences. Others grew significantly with the contextualisation, such as the width of the value (and values) indicated by the 'it's good for the town' parole of the negatively affected business owners.

9 Conclusions

This study was undertaken to better understand the values created by the public events programme in the town of Paisley, Scotland as a part of their project to become UK City of Culture 2021, and the subsequent legacy efforts relating to events. It aimed to make use of tools from the many sides of several divides: quantitative and qualitative, economic and public value, and monetised and non-monetised value analysis. Despite a broad scope empirically, the case study approach and the limited number of events and stakeholders made it a viable research project, providing new insights both to Paisley actors and to researchers interested in the field of event studies. The increased understanding of how normative consensus may shape event bidding processes and its link to the public sphere, as well as the measurement of progressive opportunity are both novelties which will not only inform previous and prospective bidders but also academics interested in broadening the scope of event evaluation.

The previous chapter revisited the literature review and methodology to synthesise the findings into analysis. This chapter reflects on how the full study has fulfilled its intentions and fulfilled its objectives, it discusses my contribution to knowledge and opens the door for future research.

9.1 Research objectives revisited

Going back to the aims of this research, these four objectives guided the design of the study, are presented in Chapter 1, and are answered from Chapter 6 onward:

1. Measure the economic effect of public events in Paisley 2016-2019 through analysis of spending related to the events.
2. Evaluate the experience of those events, based on the revealed and stated preferences of event visitors and local businesses.
3. Understand social and public value impacts of Paisley public events, through a public value framework with social value tools.

4. Explore the possibilities of public value theory as a tool for analysing quantitative and qualitative data from cultural events.

These objectives imply the use of several methods; social impacts and contribution to the local economy are not fit for the same analytical treatment. Event and culture evaluation tools (Green Book, Eventimpacts) and the scarce scholarship on unified social and economic effects (Snowball, Getz) tend to separate these analyses. This study used mixed methods with data drawn from elite actors in Renfrewshire, Scottish government, on-site event respondents, locals, and business representatives. This has proven to give a broad understanding of Paisley's bidding process and events programme. A broad focus can be seen both as a strength and weakness and is indeed discussed as both below.

Quite different from the first two, the third and fourth objectives are theoretical. Especially objective 4 is much wider, asking broadly about how impact can be measured or evaluated. Herein lies a major contribution to knowledge. The objective is partially answered already in the literature review, going through the most common techniques used to evaluate culture. Whilst happiness research, sociological evaluation of culture and art, and subjective wellbeing perspectives are strong contenders, they lack either the distance from CBA, the breadth, or the quantitative potential needed to respond to objective three. Instead growing literature on the social value of events fulfilled those needs in some areas, developed as a critical tool, but also as a complement to economic evaluation techniques. This increased interest has not least been visible in the official guidance to the UK City of Culture and the official evaluations of major events, where the social value has been subject to more attention during the last years.

9.1.1 Objective one: economic effects of events

The answer to objective one can be summarised by reflecting on the results of the economic analyses in the previous chapter. Looking through a mercantilist EIA lens, there is a considerable influx compared to the spending by Renfrewshire Council, whose outlays constitute almost all direct costs associated with hosting public events in Paisley. The events

contribute large sums to the night-time economy and hospitality sector in central Paisley via consumer spending. The effect is heavily concentrated around the event venues; in zones just one or two hundred metres away, the effect is mixed (sometimes negative), and a five-minute walk from the nearest event venue, the effect is virtually zero. The engagement and knowledge about the events are directly correlated with the proximity to it; just outside the thought “cultural district” shopkeepers hardly know that the events are going on. There was also a modest effect on hotels, with some non-locals staying overnight for local events. Regarding spending patterns, the primary data largely corroborated previous evaluation reports; visitors spent more than locals. According to 2018 RC data, locals spent £30 and visitors £74, feeding into Myerscough’s (and less specifically, EIA) calculations that a visitor is ‘worth’ five times a local’s visit (1988:101). This effect is, however, complicated by other factors, especially social value.

This study, like at least one of the consultancies and some of the literature surveyed in Chapter 4 (Abelson, 2011), critiques the economic impact methodology based on the unique features of Paisley. Only a small minority of locals would spend the same amount of money at the same sites without the event. The relationship between Paisley and Glasgow, especially the relative distance between residential areas of Renfrewshire and the two towns, the demography of Renfrewshire, and its cultural consumption patterns all speak against the rigorous “at least” figure of Eventimpacts. The study does not consider multipliers or other economic externalities, and the figures can still be considered frugal despite the Green Book’s (HM Treasury, 2023) methodology indicating that the multiplier would be very modest in Paisley’s case.

The baseline direct willingness-to-pay gave mediocre results due to protest zeroes and the method’s shaky validity, but still presented figures well in line with what Renfrewshire Council spent on it. Bringing in the other models of willingness-to-pay, the dichotomous choice gave an unexpectedly high figure; over 70 % were willing to pay £10 or more for each event. The highest yield would come from a £15 ticket price, thus being a relevant estimate of the shadow price. The conjoint bundles showing a slight exhaustion indicate that an event frequency of around 4-6 events annually (rather than the ~8 organised during the most

intensive phase of the bid) is a good level. RC seems to be going in that direction already, focusing on semi-autonomous events such as the Book Festival and one-offs such as Unboxed, having dropped the Monte Carlo Rally start and the Pipe band championships. The strong majority (70 %) of respondents wanting to pay for events by tax potentially indicates social value rather than economic.

The supercharged economy has been investing thousands of pounds per Paisley inhabitant into cultural infrastructure, marketing, implementation of cultural practices into the public administration, and actual culture. During this building period, it has been clear that this investment will end. Several respondents were worried about the times ahead, whereas others were confident in that the preparations were sufficient. The worries included both the deterioration of the partnership approach, which had less to offer participants after the loss of the bid, and the 2024 deadline where the funding of everything cultural in Paisley will be turned down considerably. The several hundred-million-pound investment scheme was not intended to pay off during runtime. Instead, it has been a long-needed renovation of the cultural assets of the town and a period for building new assets which are supposed to be lasting without extensive funding.

One fundamental point of the regeneration schemes in Paisley was to re-route resources; to centralise spending in inner Paisley, but also spend more public resources on culture . In the case of events, the money spent has strong support, especially for the flagship and publicly available programmes.

This objective has been partially answered – the influx of economic value is now better understood than before. The economic data used for this objective is not specific; *monetised* values are specific according to a rigorous model of WTP and TCM, but the outflux of money in Paisley is only mapped to a limited extent. The strongest contributions in the economic area are likely (1) the analysis of shopkeepers' locations, opinions, and polarities of economic effect and (2) the usage of already existing data provided by the evaluation reports to analyse how these values can be put in relation to others (costs, social value). The economics-based methods of WTP and TCM are key indicators of quantitative value but do not provide adequate substitutes for the actual economic effects on the town.

9.1.2 Objective two: social effects of events

Most of the primary data was collected to answer non-economic objectives. Each individual or institution may experience different types of value, of which social and public value were considerable. The results showed that social value was described as more important to most respondents than economic value. Few respondents spoke about the economic effects, but rather the social and equitable. Rather than speaking in terms of prosperity or affluence, the developments mentioned were related to cleanliness, fewer people in social distress, and a positive ambience.

The social-over-economic dynamic was especially accentuated by the shopkeeper interviews but to a strong degree also by questionnaire respondents. Stakeholders were more prone to prioritise economic gains, being part of their professional responsibility, though caring for social effects too. The social value priority could be expressed in a few particular findings.

The shopkeepers in Paisley were happy about the events programme and supported it because of how it affected the town, no matter if they benefited from it economically; to those negatively affected, it was an alternative cost of several thousand pounds per year which they were willing to give up. The comment “it’s good for the town” recurred (not easily specified, except that it likely pertains both to social and economic effects), but also more specific discussions of sense of community in which individuals are happy to override their own economic interest for what is perceived to be a greater good.

The same values of social cohesion and sense of community scored high on the questionnaires, both digitally and on-site. This was expected and in line with other similar studies; the Renfrewshire Council evaluation reports had very high numbers on positive sentiments about all indicators of event and town centre satisfaction. The finding that all questions about the quality of Paisley’s cleanliness and culture on offer were answered very positively by locals shows a sense of ownership, and a willingness to defend the town verbally. During the bidding years, Paisley succeeded in creating this sense of pride in place. Local respondents were also willing to pay much more than the cost to host events; more

than the economic influx to the area as well.

The interviews reveal a great deal of value in the partnerships, and the connection between private, public, and civil sectors which is partially kept intact after the bids because of the events programme. The business owners, now represented by the BID Paisley First has ramped up their own events programme during and after the *Untold Story* years. This overlaps with the public programme as some of the same rides and activities are on offer at both BID and RC organised events; a practice of 'what works' has been developed despite the BID's events are more explicitly aimed at "bringing in footfall" according to the respondent. The events and festivals programme has kept together organisations with a stake in at least one of the events. This was accentuated during the bidding period because social NGOs had spaces where they could communicate their messages. Furthermore, the councillor's comment that social value was "almost" as important as economic is not to be seen as either-or; rather that a project that was aimed at lifting a town out of deindustrialisation and create economic momentum ten years ago proved to have unexpectedly great social consequences. The latter was underlined by the transition towards cultural rather than culture-led regeneration and bringing the policies along with the general Scottish development towards inclusion and sustainable development.

The events in Paisley were also gauged based on public sphere and progressive opportunity values which correspond to the second research objective. Though the theoretical development pertains to objective 3, these can be empirically understood as social effects. Public sphere was found to a lesser degree, identifying a possible public value failure on the long-term time scale, according to Bozeman's model (Bozeman 2007; Bozeman & Johnson, 2015). The focus of the events has not been democracy and deliberation past the initial consultations, even though the latter were substantial and had shaped the process: the public support played an important role in building a tentative normative consensus as asserted by in-depth interview respondents (Nabatchi, 2012). This was not least visible in the contrast between observed behaviour and stated opinions; Chalip (2014) describes it as feeling a responsibility to support one's town no matter what actual opinions are harboured. The public support has been continually gauged from Renfrewshire Council; though not necessarily the strongest tool for creation of public sphere values, it is an indicator of how

well the local authority walks in pace with its constituents. The dialogue with smaller, local stakeholders in the civil society is distinctly well-received by both parties during the bidding years and immediately after.

Progressive opportunity was more easily identified. The events programme managed to provide gratis culture which attracted all groups, but where a disproportionate number of visitors came from areas where cultural consumption was lower. The tendency was (contrary to expected results) accentuated in the WTP: despite several statistical tests, few significant correlations could be drawn between income/SIMD zone/spend and willingness to pay for the culture on offer. This managed to align well with the *inclusive growth* paradigm which is a major expectation of the long-term programmes in Paisley. The communication, though scarce in the economic policy of RC, still indicates a want to alleviate lacking opportunities not just for culture consumption, but more widely. This is a case of not just public value, but public values (as per Nabatchi, 2018) aligning with an equitable effort. The most repeated phrase being variations of “there is something on” notes partially respondents being glad to see their town light up, but in many cases, the full response makes clear that the experience is something out of the ordinary. Live culture has come to people not consuming it regularly and will not actively seek it out to a great extent. The catch-all design of events, with both family activities, seasonal attractions, beer tents and cover bands, as well as classical music and activities around the Paisley abbey, have struck a note with people from several socioeconomic groups and people from across the Greater Glasgow area. Visitors are provided with tools for liminality, fine art, new sensory experiences, and partying, whilst the town puts on its best face. This has indeed given a progressive opportunity for equitable outtake and usage of one’s own needs and potentials (Bozeman & Johnson, 2015).

The social value created from Paisley events has been demonstrated to work in the direction of the UN Sustainable Development Goals and the wider Scottish strategies for events and urban regeneration. This is despite lacking explicit alignment beyond the 2015 Scottish event policy alignment, which is more turned towards SDG ideals, though designed before the SDG were published (United Nations, 2022). Designed in liaison with EventScotland, the DCMS guidance for UKCoC bidders, and leading scholars on the values of events, RC’s strategic goals have managed to form a chain which reaches the end users, at least in the events

industry. This is relevant even independently of this study's methodology as the National Performance Framework takes on an increasing role in Scottish society, especially local authorities, and the 2015-2025 Scottish events strategy and 2014-2024 Paisley cultural strategy are nearing the end with evaluation studies coming up.

The investigation of objective two has received reliable results based on a range of methods and operationalisations of social value. The public value framework has provided evaluations of the key social value including sense of community, social cohesion, and pride in place, but also emerging concepts relating to equity, consensus, and co-creation. Validated and problematised in discussions with stakeholders, the values beyond cultural experiences and shopping utility have been explored. This, being the weaker part of the previous knowledge of Paisley events, has given insights into both public and elite actor sentiments as well as actual experienced value. Policymakers can act on this knowledge, showing that sense of community, pride in place, and equitable/inclusive progress have the potential to bring footfall, real social gains (comparable to other costly public interventions), and even that constituents prioritise this perspective more highly. Retaining and developing this perspective is not just about staying on top of contemporary policy development, but also in line with research findings.

9.1.3 Objective three and four: How can the social impacts be measured?

As developed in Chapter 5, these objectives are meant to show the ambition of developing new practices for gauging social effects. The practices explored have worked well; public value analysis is a strong candidate for contributing understanding to events studies. Not just Bozeman and Johnson's (2015) addition of *progressive opportunity* and *public sphere*. The underpinning philosophy of Bozeman's understanding of public value, where the public gets to contribute to the process of defining what is valuable, by also appreciating the public *values* (Nabatchi, 2018), is a tool which might be useful in events. This collective definition of value can be used no matter if that is directly via public sphere expressions or something less deliberation-based.

Both public sphere and progressive opportunity have been tools which would have been

overlooked or stayed in a footnote as an intangible value. Mapping public value according to Bozeman is partially negative, focusing on failures (Bozeman & Sarewitz, 2011). This negative aspect showed up as a limited use of deliberative elements during the process. Even though the policy changed (culture-led to cultural), this was beyond the scope of large-scale deliberative efforts which had previously received some attention.

Conversely, progressive opportunity proved to be a fruitful way of understanding some events' positive (as in positively defined, not normatively good) contribution to what is regarded as valuable by the public. This is likely because of the stronger focus on equitable, inclusive culture than deliberative processes. The relative lack of inclusion and an *agora* for discussing value creation can possibly be explained by one of the problematic features of major events: the need for a strong consensus (Kassens-Noor, 2019); organisers may even benefit from making generous unwarranted promises, suppress growing protests, or withhold detrimental information. There might be limited room for a transparent process of defining values in an ongoing bid.

The toolbox for social value analysis proved to work well in both quantitative and qualitative terms. Several of the direct questions, such as "Paisley events add to the sense of belonging to the town" had very strong support and little discussion or dissent in the open-ended questions. This might have indicated that some respondents gave a 'strongly agree' to any question which associated an event with something positive. The potential insincerities (no-pay overstatement, honour-bound outward support, protest zeroes, overstated satisfaction) have been discussed thoroughly throughout the thesis. Though they cause some limitations, several of these have been handled and analysed based on those insights.

With the ongoing reformation or at least contestation of what is normal science in event studies, these tools are contenders for answering the research objective: *How can the social impacts of public events and festivals be quantified and presented in non-monetary terms?* This objective has been answered with empirical demonstrations of how a wide range of tools can be used, including some new applications of existing methods. Where possible, putting the social value in relation to economic value without trying to monetise the former, may be useful for policymakers. Though exact figures are not calculated, the willingness to

pay more than the lauded economic influx, or the willingness to forgo income for the town's good, are bridges between different types of value which remain relevant to those handling the scarce resources in the local authority or administers national funding.

9.2 Contribution to knowledge

Contribution to knowledge for the wider scientific community relates primarily to the larger data set analysis and the methodological and theoretical development of working with public value in events. Beyond that, the empirical results are highly relevant for Paisley. The priorities are reaching a crossroads where the future financing and policy is being shaped during the time of this thesis' publication. Evidence-based review of local values and their sources will be crucial for an informed decision. Additionally, the interview series of stakeholders gives voice to representatives of all sectors. The debate in Paisley is not particularly lively on either social media or traditional media. Instead, the town is small enough that many stakeholders know each other personally. Despite this, developing the perspectives around the events programme and social value of urban regeneration through culture might be overlooked due to its auxiliary role in the research objectives. To local debate, it might give voice to some less often heard perspectives.

The research is significant for policymakers. In Paisley, large investments have been made, and evidencing what effects these have achieved is crucial for future public resource allocation. This study strongly suggests that event evaluation lacking either economic or public value analysis will be lopsided and miss crucial dimensions. Whereas some social value can be partially substituted for economic calculations (expressed as WTP or travel cost values), others are intangible for economic methods and/or non-use. Progressive opportunity and the value of public sphere showed to be long-term investments in consensus building and inclusive growth. These are unlikely to be understood by economic methods alone.

9.2.1 Theoretical contribution: public value in events

The usage of public value in culture is close to new ground for scholarly inquiry, and this study gives future researchers new tools to work with. The few authors using the term explicitly (Hartley et al., 2016; Foley et al., 2015; McPherson et al., 2017; Fujiwara et al., 2021; Girginov & Preuss, 2022) are either far from the events field of event studies, use the concept 'public value' entirely disconnected from the Moore/Bozeman traditions, or use an exclusively qualitative method. In the two cases of Girginov and Preuss (2022), and Foley et al. (2015), the understanding of public value is not dissimilar from this study, though both work in sports events rather than culture. The four additions that this study makes to public value are: applying a public value framework to a mixed methods methodology, studying primary data from on-site and local respondents, studying cultural events, and combining social/public with economic value. Trying to combine these, whilst acknowledging the ideological conflict between them, is a seldom-trod road towards getting a fuller understanding of values, and entirely new using public value. Fujiwara et al. (2021) in their Green Book approach, instead let the CBA methodology (based on SWB) define public value.

None of the previous public value writings have used primary quantitative data but relied on high-level analysis of events policy or purely theoretical contributions. Thus, the tools designed to study events with a public value framework are novel. This will make studies on public value of events a more accessible alternative for event scholars. Combining deliberation, equity, and consent to add to a model of social change is introduced in McPherson et al. (2017). Using a full model of typical event-related social value (as first defined in Getz, 1989) as inputs to a combined public value framework is new for this study. Using public value as an alternative to CBA/NPM is an explicit reason for its development, but analysing how they relate to each other in the same study is uncommon because of the incommensurability of philosophies and the broad scope needed to achieve it.

One of the theoretical connections coming out of the public value of events is the body of literature addressing consensus-building as a crucial part of bidding, paired with Nabatchi's (2012; concept from Bozeman, 2007) interpretation of Bozeman's (2002) *policy failures*; that a *normative consensus* is needed to optimise public value. This connection is discussed by

Foley et al. (2015) in relation to Roche's (2002) idea that the consent of the people is crucial for events and Bozeman's (2007) argument that "public values being contested in a democracy, requiring consensus building to achieve agreement in practice, thereby echoing Roche's view that events exist within a battle between human agency and social structure" (Foley et al., 2015). The addition made by this study is the usage of normative consensus as a value added to others in a public value model. Paired only with other Bozeman-esque discussions of public value failure and deliberation, it gets a different function. Here, it is a value which can be put in relation to others, which is not least relevant in Paisley, where Chalip's and Heere's (2013) statement about artificial consent seems to have some merit considering the contrast between quantitative data versus some interviews and observational data.

The integration of public value and cost-benefit analysis has meant an improved understanding of the human experiences gauged. By making economic estimations part of the wider public value (as descriptive rather than prescriptive method) of events, these experiences can be understood with higher resolution. CBA always contains reductionism in the translation between human experiences, predicted consequences, and the translation to monetary figures. As argued in Chapter 4, this does not mean that it should not be used for applications beyond the infrastructural project for which it was originally designed. Rather, this study's theoretical additions aim to reduce the distance between CBA assumptions and reality. Using CBA as one of the inputs in a wider discussion on public value has the potential to contribute to this greater understanding. The order cannot realistically be reversed — public value inputs into CBA will need to be monetised or dismissed as intangible, whereas CBA value can be discussed in relation to the other areas in a public value analysis.

CBA variables are relevant proxies to other types of value. Advanced willingness-to-pay methods have the potential to contribute to public value both as normative and empirical knowledge. Though the values are far from always in the same formats, this study has shown the possibility of finding connections in the allegedly incommensurable. This means that there are points of reference between CBA and public value. An example would be the 60 shopkeeper interviews, which provided a tentative result of a WTP of several thousand pounds of non-use value for many of the negatively affected shopkeepers. Although this was

not included in the CBA, this monetary figure was still relevant in a discussion of public value.

Letting PV be the umbrella concept for CBA also has the potential to shift focus from the red or black colour of the bottom line. As was shown in this study, social effects frequently trumped the economic. Public sector funding is a scarce resource, but the public sector's goals are nonetheless not generating revenue but rather achieving value in areas more closely resembling the other areas of value gauged in this study. This can be more clearly visualised with the pragmatic use of these theories.

9.2.2 Empirical contribution: Values created in the Paisley events programme

The value created by the Paisley events programme is now better understood than before the study, and the knowledge can be used to shape future policy, not just for Paisley, but for others interested in culture-led, cultural, or events-led urban regeneration. Indeed, their approach has attracted much interest and attention from Scottish Government and Event Scotland, the national agency for events in Scotland.

The study does provide an insight into the collective strife of a major event bid, and the value gained from sustaining an ambitious legacy programme. This value can form a part of the body of literature discussing the value of legacy and leverage of events. This contribution is the most generalisable in its largely quantitative focus and its monetisable methods. A lost bid may have both negative and positive effects; the pride in place managed to be largely retained in Paisley, but the elite actors were partially sceptical about the long-term potential of events and culture a few years after the bid was lost. The legacy events programme was an almost universally recognised positive outcome of the bid, but question marks about Paisley's achievements as a tourist destination, RC's engagement in local business, and the longevity of the programmes were raised. Interest was centred around the innermost Paisley, where activities and benefits were most prevalent. At the same time, the willingness-to-pay remains high, and the events programme's popularity remains. These findings are well-understood outcomes of major event bids. Similar topics and potential results are discussed in McGillivray and Turner (2017), Kassens-Noor (2019), Snowball

(2008), and Getz (2020). The findings are of particular interest to other scholars of losing UKCoC bids and comparable events aiming for culture-led urban regeneration.

The most surprising find was the strong commitment to the events programme shown by the local businesses. Though businesses are run by people who sometimes have a stake in the local society, the extent was very high. Although no causal mechanisms are analysed, the reasons for this may include long-running engagement with retail regeneration, a newly formed BID with local authority support, BID engagement in the bidding process, predominantly non-chain stores and/or locals working in stores, and a sense that things in Paisley were moving in the right direction. This opens for future research projects.

Scotland is in a developmental process, well on its way to implementing non-NPM solutions and rights-based perspectives to several problems. The SDGs are on its way into the public sector and specifically local government through NPF. The Convention on the Rights of the Child was adopted, and the events strategies of local, national, and UK government are continually becoming more interested in evidencing social value, as shown in Chapter 3. In that sense, this study takes one step on the road to integrating seemingly incommensurable methods. Few studies try to engage with both social value analysis and CBA methodology without letting the one or the other take the upper hand (which CBAx, Green Book, and OECD perspectives could be said to do). This study attempts that. The limitations, and hopefully also the contributions, of the deep mixed-methods methodology show one way of lifting out social and public value as real, important, sometimes clearly overshadowing economical value, whilst at the same time displaying actual CBA-style calculations.

9.3 Limitations revisited

The data used for this study was gathered from a range of sources. This has brought both strengths and weaknesses beyond the general arguments relating to mixed methods. Access to data collection was heavily limited during the Covid pandemic. This delayed the research and changed the scope. This led to a more complex research design, almost a year's delay during redesign and new data collection stints, and thus less of a deep dive in the original

project. In the end, the redesigned project grew to something more complex, interesting, and contributing to the knowledge in events and urban regeneration that will serve to inform policymakers and lead to a sustainable approach to embedding public value in their approach to all service delivery whilst aligning with Scottish Government performance framework.

Speaking with public officials about central policy areas and their workplace's most prestigious project meant some caution on their side. Still, all Renfrewshire Council officers asked for or happily accepted an offer to read the sections including their own contributions to control that they were correctly quoted. The only openly negative reactions on any Renfrewshire Council intervention or policy have been those from one single interviewee, a minuscule number of survey respondents, and encounters in daily life as a Paisley inhabitant. One example of the latter is mentioned in the observational findings in Chapter 7, though they were more plentiful; being read as a foreigner with a non-native English accent, even as a visitor, has its perks as well as its downsides for a researcher. The Paisley inhabitants have often wanted to recount the positives and negatives of living in the town, even after being informed they are speaking to someone who works at the local university. These experiences, though relevant and interesting, are not ethically or methodologically possible to include on a wider scale than anecdotal.

Access to digitally collected data was compromised by problems in communications; not just the unfortunate 80 % data loss which only gave access to five events in 2018 rather than the full 2016-2019 event seasons. The updated questionnaire designed in 2020-2021 was based on the commitment of a partnership organisation which ultimately struggled to facilitate the exposure to potential respondents as first anticipated. This gave the second part of the quantitative data collection a smaller n , but in return, the data responses gathered are now of high quality and gathered with a higher reliability.

The broad scope has meant trade-offs, including deep dives into Renfrewshire tourism data and the wider creative economy, which was originally within the scope. Instead, the breadth of values created is accounted for. This is ultimately a useful holistic view and proof-of-concept for new applications of theory.

Though this study took a wide approach to value creation, the tools for negative value were less extensive than positive. Several authors (Delamere, 1997; Deery & Jago, 2010; Chalip, 2014) warn against the omission of negative values. With the focus being placed on widening the scope of values created, mostly positive values were recorded. This was not anticipated – for example, the positive opinions of shopkeepers have been discussed as a key finding. This study should not be an indicator that negative values can be avoided, but rather that the research design used might not have found all of them.

9.4 Future research

This research develops the use of public value in events research; as a basis for measuring of empirical, quantified social and specifically values defined by Bozeman (2007; 2015). There is a potential in using public value more in event studies. Major event evaluations are transitioning into the cross-disciplinary field Getz (2000) calls for, with a set of well-known methodological underpinnings of the social aspects in events. The literature on critical event studies is growing, as well as a transition from the previous EIA/CBA status quo more generally. Further engagement with public value may become a larger part of that with a focus on democracy, wellbeing, sustainable development, and equity/inclusion. Further, and more singular focus on public sphere and progressive opportunity can be derived from this research in events where public dialogue and equity are on the agenda.

One of the aspects which challenged the validity and reliability of this study was the discrepancy of opinions depending on the setting. Locals were almost universally positive in the quantitative data collection, whereas living and working in Paisley for four years led to many meetings with strangers also (or exclusively) discussing negative aspects. This difference has been discussed, supported by the findings of Kassens-Noor (2019; Kassens-Noor & Lauerma, 2018) and Chalip (Chalip & Heere, 2013; Chalip, 2017). Still, the gap merits further investigation. This should be investigated in terms of the positionality of the researcher, the basis for negative/positive communication about public interventions, and more complex demographic profiling of events respondents.

Major cultural events are becoming a research field with its own body of literature (Jones, 2020; Ponzini, 2023, have both edited books on cultural mega-events recently). Integrating evaluation is still primarily an issue studied in commissioned reports. This ensues problems of reliability (as discussed by Chalip, 2014), and may place focus on goals put up by designating organisations rather than academic or wider society interests. Seeing both perspectives is pivotal. As this study demonstrates, monetary and public value *can* be analysed as two dimensions, both important for understanding what the positive (and negative) aspects of hosting an event is. Event organisers as well as designating organisations and academics may well find such independent studies reliable sources of information in an otherwise highly politicised and medialised area of public sector interventions.

9.5 Closing remarks

This thesis offers the potential for policymakers and event organisers to move beyond the prevailing neo-liberal agenda. It makes use of traditional economic tools, as well as emerging social value evaluation, and novel use of public value theory. Contributions of events must be regarded holistically. Several of the key findings of this research are strong indicators that social and economic aspects can complement each other, though the one does not necessarily follow the other. This thesis will hopefully encourage widened event evaluation scopes, as well as provide an empirical insight into what results can, and cannot, be achieved with the path taken by Paisley. Results from each area unveil values claimed to be important by event organisers, though the tools are still developing. The effects of events are still far from fully understood. This thesis explores an area ripe for further exploration.

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Appendix 1: Travel cost definitions

Data was prepared with Maply (2023), a service which can calculate GIS data from Google Maps. In this case, it generated flying distance and road distance as well as driving time. The time was set to Friday afternoon driving conditions, as most events are hosted in weekends, and driving conditions in Paisley are seldom as disadvantageous as during large events.

Journeys by car are estimated by the Maply service, using Google Maps data (Maply, 2023). This includes a time estimation. No research articles have been published in the last years about true costs of car ownership in the UK (per mile or otherwise). An analysis by Nimblefins (2023) using ONS data stated the true cost of a car is 47p per mile; 29p per km.

Train journeys cost an average of 20-30p per kilometre in the UK (calculated based on data of market value of train tickets and travelled kilometres UK Government, 2020; Ibisworld, 2023, validated against several consumer reports). Shorter trips are more expensive per km. Thus, a value of 25p per km is added to the travel cost, but with a lower limit of half the price of an anytime return ticket Glasgow-Paisley; £3.15.

It is difficult to define an average bus speed. London had an average speed of 9.5 mph in 2019, whereas Glasgow had an average speed of 4.5 mph in the city centre in 2018 (UK Government, 2020; Glasgow City Council, 2018). Typical journeys in the Paisley vicinity take around 60-70 % longer by bus than by car in low traffic, but the difference is small during peak hour. As traffic is taken into consideration, the prudent choice is simply equating car times with bus times. Average fares are also difficult to assess; a 2016 report showed it differed from 7p to £1.80 per mile (Holyrood, 2016). Thus, a single trip is valued at £2.35 in travels below 20 km (longer journeys typically go by train in the area, and these are likely done either by several means of transport or intercity buses), and the 25p per kilometre train constant is used for longer journeys.

Walking is estimated at the Google Maps constant of 4.5 km/h. Paisley is slightly hilly, but not enough to severely affect walking speeds. 10 respondents reported walking distances over 10 km, which are treated as outliers and put in the n/a category.

Taxi journeys in Transport for London's (2023) report fit generally in both time, cost, and distance when compared to some Scottish counterparts; thus, an average number based on their data is set; the average taxi journey to festivals and events is set to £22.

The n/a category aligns very closely with the “Car” category in terms of time driven (which none of the others do). Also, the “Car” category is a low-cost alternative in those distances, making this a prudent choice. A very small number of respondents reported cycling, mobility scooters, private buses, and other modes of transport. These are also treated as car riders, being a prudent, low-cost opinion.

Discussed in Chapter 4, it is not straightforward to pick a value of time. There is no income data available for the evaluation report respondents. In this study, £14.09 per hour is used because it is the number used by Paisley’s 2021 team to equal volunteering. This is flawed, but as no consensus exists on the proportion, £14.09 is a figure used for estimation of time spent willingly within the dataset. Note that even a conservative evaluation, 1/3 of the £ 14.09 would ensue a total loss of <30 % of the estimated value (adding actual cost), still placing it in the same approximate cost bracket.

Appendix 2. Deductions from CBA

All values have been identified above and the results can be summarised. One main point of critique of the more cautious EIA evaluations is the high rate of deduction: value removed from the calculation as not to overestimate the benefit. In this case, there needs to be a proportion decided of visitors who would have attended Paisley anyway, and the amount of money which would have gone into the local economy without the events.

There is some evidence of displaced spending in Paisley. 18 % of businesses reported that no change in revenue was observed during events, and 32 % reported a negative number (the other 50 % reported positive numbers). Only 5 % reported that business was almost zero during events, and the rest a noticeable, but not devastating decline. Several of the positively affected indicated that their revenue increased by several times the normal. Because all the positive effects of shopping are accounted for, the negative must be deducted. Deducting 10 % of local spending to compensate for the negative effects from the events is likely more than enough.

21 % (327 of 1583) respondents in 2018 stated that they would have visited Renfrewshire even if there was no event on, rather than stayed at home, worked, or visited another site. This group would have spent an amount of money in Renfrewshire anyway. Therefore, 21 % of shopping incomes can be discounted from benefits; the real number is likely lower, as events induce higher spending than otherwise, but a figure cannot be reliably evidenced. The same is true for travel costs (see below). Willingness-to-pay is not affected, as all groups were asked about their WTP; these groups may have lowered the final aggregate sum. As these are part of different data sets, it is not possible to calculate at this point. Both the 21 % and the 10 % deductions of added value are arbitrary. These are cautiously high, to not overstate values.

Appendix 3. Phase 1 questionnaire

My name is Niclas, I'm from the University (of the West of Scotland) and I'm conducting research about Paisley's cultural programmes. Would you mind answering a few questions?

What attracted you to the event tonight? *Mark only one.*

I like this event

Entertainment

Spend time with friends /family

Special occasion

To see a specific programme element/performer

The programme

Visiting the area

To learn something

Try something new

Live here

Other:

Have you visited this event before?

Yes No

If yes, how many times?

What do you like and think is good at this event?

What would you improve at this event?

Is the event being free important to you? *Mark only one.*

Yes No

If this event had an admission fee, would you still consider attending? *Mark only one oval.*

Yes No

How much do you think you will have spent attending this event today on travel, food, shopping?

If there was an admission fee, what is the maximum amount you would be willing to pay for attending this event?

What is your postcode?

Appendix 4. Phase 2 questionnaire

Please note that the DBDC and conjoint questions, being difficult to produce graphically, are amended or removed.

Did you attend a public event/festival in Paisley during the last five years?

1. Yes
2. No

Please indicate how satisfied you have been with the festivals that you have attended during the last five years on a scale from 1 to 10 where 10 is the best possible score. Only rate the festivals you are certain that you have attended.

Paisley Food and Drink Festival	<input type="checkbox"/>
The Spree	<input type="checkbox"/>
Fireworks Extravaganza	<input type="checkbox"/>
Monte Carlo Rally Start	<input type="checkbox"/>
Christmas Light Switch-On	<input type="checkbox"/>
Sma' Shot Day	<input type="checkbox"/>
Paisley Halloween Festival	<input type="checkbox"/>
UK Pipe Band Championships	<input type="checkbox"/>

Please rank the festivals that you have attended at least once during the last five years. Put a 1 in the box next to the festival you liked the best, a 2 in the second best, and so on. Only rank the festivals you are certain that you have attended.

- Monte Carlo Rally Start _____
- Paisley Food and Drink Festival _____
- UK Pipe Band Championships _____

- Sma' Shot Day _____
- The Spree _____
- Paisley Halloween Festival _____
- Fireworks Extravaganza _____
- Christmas Light Switch-On _____

What are your 3 main reasons for attending events in Paisley? (Please select any that apply)

1. I like the event
2. The programme
3. For entertainment
4. Something to do with friends / family
5. Try something new
6. Support the community
7. See a specific programme item
8. Learn something new
9. Visiting the area
10. Other _____

How did you mostly travel to the event(s)?

1. By car
2. By public transportation
3. By foot/bicycle
4. Other

Do you think that public events in Paisley are/have (check those that apply)

1. Entertaining
2. Educational
3. Good for families
4. Safe
5. Good for the town
6. Quality programmes
7. Well-organised

8. Other _____

Please indicate how much you agree with the following statements. Please note that these are part of a scientific study and the alternatives are not associated with any suggested changes to Renfrewshire's cultural policies.

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree
It's important that towns host public events and festivals	<input type="checkbox"/>				
The events in Paisley give Renfrewshire residents a sense of pride	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Paisley's reputation has improved in recent years due to its association with culture	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Paisley's cultural heritage has potential to attract more visitors to Paisley	<input type="checkbox"/>				
During much of 2020-2021, events were not hosted physically. Being physically present is an important part of festivals	<input type="checkbox"/>				

If festivals were to be hosted exclusively online for the foreseeable future, I would still attend	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Paisley events add to the sense of belonging to the town	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Paisley events help with the health and wellbeing of the town	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Paisley livens up during the events	<input type="checkbox"/>				
The events are good for local business	<input type="checkbox"/>				
The events are good for the community	<input type="checkbox"/>				

Please give any examples you would like to highlight that Events bring in terms of the social, economic or wellbeing benefits to town and communities? Comments/Suggestions:

Would you prefer that large public events in Paisley were funded by tickets bought by attendees or paid collectively via the tax bill? This is a question asked for independent research purposes, not suggestions for Renfrewshire Council policy.

1. Ticket funded
2. Tax funded

If 1:

Events in Paisley is a publicly funded service, using council tax and other central government funding. The council tax constitutes 22 % of Renfrewshire Council's budget which is used to pay for many things, including schools, rubbish collection, roads, water, and leisure. Of these, Children's services are the largest (50 %), and Adult services including social care (17 %). Leisure including culture and events make up 2.5 % of the Council's budget. Around 0.25 % of Renfrewshire Council's budget is used to cover the six to eight large events and festivals organised each year in Paisley by Renfrewshire Council. You have stated that you prefer events funded by council tax. Would you be willing for some of your tax money to be spent on these events? If so, how much per event? The amount will change based on your answer. Please answer yes or no until the question changes.

If 2:

Events in Paisley is a publicly funded service, using council tax and other central government funding. The council tax constitutes 22 % of Renfrewshire Council's budget which is used to pay for many things, including schools, rubbish collection, roads, water, and leisure. Of these, Children's services are the largest (50 %), and Adult services including social care (17 %). Leisure including culture and events make up 2.5 % of the Council's budget. Around 0.25 % of Renfrewshire Council's budget is used to cover the six to eight large events and festivals organised each year in Paisley by Renfrewshire Council. You have stated that you prefer events funded by ticket payments. Would you be willing to pay for attending some of these events? If so, how much per event? The amount will change based on your answer. Please answer yes or no until the question changes.

Thinking about your own spending at events and festivals in Paisley in recent times. How much did you spent on the following at a typical event:

	£
Food and drink on site	<input type="checkbox"/>
Food and drink in local cafés and restaurants	<input type="checkbox"/>
Travel (bus, train, petrol etc)	<input type="checkbox"/>
Tickets (please state if they were free)	<input type="checkbox"/>
Fairground activities, souvenirs, etc	<input type="checkbox"/>
Spend in local shops	<input type="checkbox"/>

What sort of events do you want to see in Paisley in the future? Comments/Suggestions:

What type of event do you think gives the town the best boost in the economy?

Comments/Suggestions:

Are you...

1. Male
2. Female
3. Other
4. Prefer not to say

Please indicate your age group?

1. 16-24
2. 25-34
3. 35-44
4. 45-54
5. 55-64
6. 65-74
7. 75+

Where do you live?

1. In Paisley
2. Elsewhere in Renfrewshire
3. Glasgow
4. Elsewhere in Scotland
5. Another Country

Postcode (e.g. PA2, G12):

What is your highest level of educational qualification? (please select one)

1. Primary school
2. Secondary school
3. College
4. Undergraduate degree
5. Postgraduate degree

How many persons live in your household?

Which category best describes your annual household gross income? (please select one)

1. £ 0 - 10,000
2. £ 10,001 - 20,000
3. £ 20,001 - 30,000
4. £ 30,001 - 40,000
5. £ 40,001 - 50,000
6. £ 50,001 - 60,000
7. > £ 60,000

Do you have any additional comments on the issue of Paisley festivals and the values it produces?

Appendix 5. Questionnaire used for Halloween 2018 by EKOS consultants for Renfrewshire Council

Are you an.....?

Event Attendee	Continue
Other (e.g. organiser, staff member etc.)	Thank and close

Your Visit to Paisley Halloween Festival

Q1 Can you please confirm your full postcode? This will be used for analysis purposes only and will not be used to contact you. [Please write in the following format - AB12 3CD]

<i>Not relevant, live outside the UK (please tick)</i>	

Q2 Is that? [Tick one answer only]

<i>Within Renfrewshire [PLEASE CHECK: Renfrewshire postcodes are PA1-PA12]</i>	
<i>Elsewhere in Scotland [PLEASE CHECK: elsewhere in Scotland postcodes are AB, DD, DG, EH, FK, G1-G90, HS, IV, KA, KW, KY, ML, PA13-PA80, PH, TD, ZE]</i>	
<i>Elsewhere in the UK (interviewer, please specify town or region in the space below)</i>	
<i>Outside the UK (interviewer, please state which country in the space below)</i>	

**Q3 How many people are in your immediate party at today's event?
[Please write in number of females and males in each category, including interviewee]**

	Female s	Males
<i>Aged 7 and under.....</i>		
<i>Aged 8-18.....</i>		
<i>Aged 18-26.....</i>		
<i>Aged 27-34.....</i>		
<i>Aged 35-44.....</i>		
<i>Aged 45-54.....</i>		
<i>Aged 55-64.....</i>		
<i>Aged 65-74.....</i>		
<i>Aged 75+.....</i>		

Q4 Which methods of travel did you use to get to Paisley for the Halloween Festival? [Please tick all that apply]

<i>Train</i>	
<i>Public bus</i>	
<i>Car</i>	
<i>Taxi</i>	
<i>Cycle</i>	
<i>Walked</i>	
<i>Private coach / bus</i>	
<i>Other (please specify below)</i>	

Q5 [IF METHOD OF TRAVEL: Q4=CAR]

Where did you park your car? (if applicable)

<i>Castlehead High School</i>	
<i>Paisley Grammar School</i>	
<i>West College Scotland</i>	
<i>Hunter St Car Park</i>	
<i>Oakshaw Car Park</i>	
<i>School Wynd</i>	
<i>Paisley Piazza</i>	
<i>Other (please specify below)</i>	

Q6 How did you hear about Paisley Halloween Festival this year? [Please tick all that apply]

<i>Word of mouth [INTERVIEWER: please probe for other sources in addition]</i>	
<i>Paisley Is website – www.paisley.is</i>	
<i>VisitScotland – website or social media</i>	
<i>Other website (write in)</i>	
<i>Facebook</i>	
<i>Twitter</i>	
<i>Instagram</i>	
<i>Other social media (write in)</i>	

<i>Leaflet</i>	
<i>Poster in underground</i>	
<i>Poster on train</i>	
<i>Billboard advert</i>	
<i>Other outdoor advertising</i>	
<i>Radio</i>	
<i>TV advertising</i>	
<i>Magazine or Newspaper advertising</i>	
<i>Online advertising</i>	
<i>Advertising at St Mirren Football Club</i>	
<i>Other (write in)</i>	

Q7 What programme element(s) most attracted you to attend the event? [tick all that apply]

Parade	
Aerial Spectacular performances	
Silent Disco	
Live Performances	
Family activities	
<i>Other (write in)</i>	

Q8 How important was Paisley Halloween Festival in your decision to visit Renfrewshire and / or Scotland? [tick one answer per area]

	It was my only reason for visiting	It was one of my main reasons for visiting	It was one of several reasons for visiting	It had no importance in my visit	I live here
Renfrewshire [Please select 'I live here' if respondent lives within Renfrewshire at Q2]					
Scotland [Please select 'I live here' if respondent lives in Renfrewshire or Scotland at Q2]					

Q9 If you had not attended Paisley Halloween Festival, what would you have likely done instead? [Please tick one answer only]

<i>Stayed at home/gone to work</i>	
<i>I would have still visited Renfrewshire</i>	
<i>I would have visited somewhere else in Scotland</i>	
<i>I would have visited somewhere outside of Scotland</i>	

Q10 Are you spending any nights away from home as part of your trip to Paisley Halloween Festival?

<i>Yes</i>		<i>Go to Q11</i>
<i>No</i>		<i>Go to Q14</i>

Q11 [IF SPENDING NIGHTS AWAY FROM HOME: Q10=YES]

What type of accommodation are/were you staying in? [please select all that apply throughout your trip]

<i>Staying with friends/ relatives</i>	
<i>Hotel</i>	
<i>Guest House/B&B/ Hostel</i>	
<i>Self-catering accommodation/ timeshare</i>	
<i>Second home</i>	
<i>Airbnb</i>	
<i>Other (please write in below)</i>	

Q12 [IF SPENDING NIGHTS AWAY FROM HOME: Q10=YES]

How many nights have/will you stay in each of the following?

Renfrewshire (Enter number including 0 if no nights in

Renfrewshire).....

Elsewhere in Scotland (Enter number including 0 if no nights elsewhere in

Scotland).....

Q13 [IF SPENDING NIGHTS AWAY FROM HOME: Q10=YES]

On average, how much have/will you spend on accommodation (per night) while attending Paisley Halloween Festival [Please write a number for each area, even if it is 0 and if you are unsure, please].

Please exclude any expenditure made on behalf of family or friends - so just the cost per person, per night. Please write a number only in each box (no £ sign).

Renfrewshire (cost per person per night including 0 if appropriate).....

Scotland (cost per person per night including 0 if appropriate).....

Q14 [ASK ALL RESPONDENTS]

What is your (just you, not your whole party) estimated expenditure per day while attending Paisley Halloween Festival.

Please exclude any expenditure made on behalf of family or friends.

(If you are unsure, please estimate, please write a value in each box). Interviewer, please write a number only in each box (no £ sign) including "0" if no expenditure within that category.

Street food vendors (write number inc 0).....

Food elsewhere in Paisley (write number inc 0).....

Drink in Paisley (write number inc 0).....

Entertainment at the event site (write number inc 0).....

Entertainment elsewhere in Paisley (write number inc 0)...

Shopping in Paisley (write number inc 0).....

Transport (write number inc 0).....

Your Views on Paisley Halloween Festival

Q15 On a scale of 1 to 10 (where 1 is very poor and 10 is very good) how would you **rate the quality of your experience at Paisley Halloween Festival?** [please select one rating per aspect]

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	N/A
<i>Information about the event</i>											
<i>Signage and directions on-site</i>											
<i>Being made to feel welcome</i>											
<i>Range of activities on offer</i>											
<i>Range of food and drink</i>											

<i>Value for money of food and drink</i>											
<i>Value for money of other stalls / activities</i>											
<i>Event car parking</i>											
<i>Quality of the event overall</i>											

Q16 How would you rate your satisfaction with the overall experience of Paisley Halloween Festival? [select one option only]

<i>Very satisfied</i>	
<i>Satisfied</i>	
<i>Neither Satisfied nor dissatisfied</i>	
<i>Dissatisfied</i>	
<i>Very dissatisfied</i>	

Q17 Have you attended any of the following events in Renfrewshire previously? [select all that apply]

<i>British Pipe Band Championships</i>	
<i>Paisley Halloween Festival Previously</i>	
<i>Paisley Christmas Lights Switch On</i>	
<i>Paisley Fireworks Spectacular</i>	
<i>Paisley Food and Drink Festival</i>	
<i>Sma Shot Day</i>	
<i>The Spree Festival</i>	
<i>None of these</i>	

Q18 [If Yes to Paisley Halloween Festival at Q17]

How does this year's Paisley Halloween Festival event compare with previous year(s)?

Much better	
Better	
Similar	
Worse	
Much worse	

Q19 [If Yes to Paisley Halloween Festival at Q17]

Could you give me brief reasons for your answer?

The Paisley Destination Brand

Q20 Are you aware of Paisley's destination brand Paisley.is? (Interviewer show graphic of logo)

The logo for Paisley is displayed in a large, bold, black sans-serif font. The letter 'i' in 'Paisley' has a unique design where the dot is a solid circle and the vertical stem is a horizontal bar.

Yes		Go to Q21
-----	--	-----------

No		Go to Q23
Don't know / Not sure		Go to Q23

Q21 Have you visited www.paisley.is?

Yes	
No	
Can't recall	

Q22 Do you follow Paisley.is on any of the following social media? [select all that apply]

Yes - Facebook	
Yes - Twitter	
Yes - Instagram	
No	

Your Details

The following questions help us to understand the views of different groups of people. We recognise that you might consider some of these questions to be sensitive in nature in which case you are free not to answer them.

Q23 Which one of the following statements do you most agree with? [please select one answer only]

<i>I often take short breaks or holidays in Scotland and intend to do so again within the next year</i>	
<i>I sometimes take short breaks or holidays in Scotland and intend to do so again in the next couple of years</i>	
<i>I have taken a short break or holiday in Scotland one or twice before and might do so again</i>	

<i>I have never been on a short break or holiday in Scotland, but would like to</i>	
<i>I am not likely to take a short break or holiday in Scotland in the future</i>	

Q24 How strongly do you agree or disagree with the following statements?

	Strongly agree	Slightly agree	Slightly disagree	Strongly disagree
<i>A holiday in the UK can be every bit as good as one abroad</i>				
<i>I always choose to go to new destinations on holiday</i>				
<i>Scotland is a good destination for the main holiday of the year, not just for short breaks</i>				
<i>I'm likely to spend more time on holidays / short breaks in Scotland in the next few years</i>				

Q25 How important are the following for you in your choice of holiday destination?

	Extremely important	Fairly important	Not very important	Not at all important
<i>Has a great range of outdoor adventure activities</i>				
<i>A place with fascinating history and culture</i>				
<i>A country with really vibrant city life</i>				
<i>A country with great food and drink experiences</i>				
<i>Is great for general sightseeing by car / on foot</i>				

<i>A destination where sunshine is guaranteed</i>				
---	--	--	--	--

Q26 What gender you identify as? [please select one answer only]

<i>Female</i>	
<i>Male</i>	
<i>Other</i>	
<i>Prefer not to say</i>	

Q27 To which of the following age groups do you belong? [please select one answer only]

<i>Aged 16–18.....</i>	
<i>Aged 18-26.....</i>	
<i>Aged 27-34.....</i>	
<i>Aged 35-44.....</i>	
<i>Aged 45-54.....</i>	
<i>Aged 55-64.....</i>	
<i>Aged 65-74.....</i>	
<i>Aged 75+.....</i>	
<i>Prefer not to say</i>	

Q28 Are you.....?

<i>Working</i>	
<i>Retired</i>	
<i>Not working</i>	
<i>Other</i>	

Q29 How would you describe your ethnic origin? [please select one answer only]

<i>White: Scottish</i>	
<i>White: Other British</i>	
<i>White: Other (specify in the space below)</i>	
<i>Mixed or Multiple ethnic groups</i>	
<i>Asian, Asian Scottish or Asian British</i>	
<i>African, African Scottish or African British</i>	
<i>Caribbean, Caribbean Scottish, Caribbean British</i>	
<i>Black, Black Scottish, Black British</i>	
<i>Chinese, Chinese Scottish, Chinese British</i>	
<i>Other Ethnic Group (specify in the space below)</i>	
<i>Prefer not to say</i>	

Q30 Do you or anyone else in your group have an illness, disability or infirmity affecting any of the following? [tick all that apply]

<i>Mobility</i>	
<i>Vision</i>	
<i>Hearing</i>	
<i>Other (please specify in the space below)</i>	

Q31 [If yes to any at Q30]

We have provided a range of facilities to make our event as accessible as possible including a quiet room, accessible viewing platforms, Mobiloo, disabled parking – is there anything that wasn't provided that would improve your experience at the event?

<i>Yes (please give details in the space below)</i>	
<i>No</i>	

THANK AND CLOSE

Appendix 6. Information sheet presented to respondents

Hello,

You are invited to participate in the survey “Experiences of Paisley Events”, part of a research cooperation between Renfrewshire Council and University of the West of Scotland. The questions relate to public events in Paisley. It is important for us to learn your opinions so that Renfrewshire Council can provide the best events and experience possible. The questionnaire will take about ten minutes to complete. The questionnaire is anonymous, and the results will not be possible to trace back to you. Data will not be presented on an individual level. Ethics approval has been received from the UWS Ethics Committee. The questionnaire is entirely voluntary. If you feel uncomfortable answering a question, you may withdraw from the survey or skip that question. If you have any questions or additional comments, please contact Niclas Hell at [REDACTED]. Thank you very much for your important contribution.

Appendix 7. Informed consent sheet

Contact: Niclas Hell, University of the West of Scotland

████████████████████

Ethics approval number: 16743

Thanks for participating in the study *Economic and social value of Paisley events*.

The study investigates the values created by public events in Paisley.

Personal data will be anonymised in all future publications.

There are no known risks of participating in the project. However, the anonymity may be limited by the study's focus on Paisley, a community with a small number of relevant respondents.

By signing you consent to:

I agree to have my voice recorded. I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw at any time without giving any reason. I consent to the processing of my personal information for the purposes explained to me.

Participant

Date	Signature	Name (print)
------	-----------	--------------

Researcher:

Date	Signature	Name (print)
------	-----------	--------------

Appendix 8. Ethics application for phase 1 data. Approved, id number 9267

Filter Questions

- I confirm I have read the UWS and my School Guidelines for Ethical Practice in Research and Scholarship.
(please tick to continue)

Pre-screening Questions

Does your work involve any of the following. (please tick all that apply)

- Human Participants
 Personal Data
 Animals
 Risk to the Investigator
- None of the above

Based on your answers to the above questions you should complete the remainder of this form and submit it to your school ethics committee for approval **PRIOR** to commencing any work on your project. Please click Next to proceed.

Applicant Details

Position of Principal Investigator

Postgraduate

Principal Investigator

Title First Name Surname

Niclas Hel

Email

School

Business and Creative Industries

Are there any co-applicants

- Yes
- No

Supervisor/Director of Studies

Supervisor/Director of Studies

Title	First Name	Surname
Professor	John	Struthers
School	Business and Creative Industries	
Email	[REDACTED]	

Collaborators

Are there any other collaborators?

- Yes
- No

Project Information

Title of Study

Surveying willingness-to-pay of Paisley event attendees

Primary purpose of the study

Postgraduate Dissertation

Where will the proposed research take place?

Paisley public events

How will the costs of the study be met?

Nonexistent or low costs met by Niclas Hell personally.

Previous Approvals

Has the proposed study been considered by any other ethics committee?

- Yes
 No

Purpose, justification, design and methodology

Please give a full summary of the purpose, justification, design and methodology of the planned study: (word limit 1000 words)

As a part of Niclas Hell's PhD research, original research needs to be conducted. This survey is a pilot study aimed at increasing the understanding of the area for improved research design and potential use in the finished PhD project and presentations, presented as a pilot study.

The purpose of the pilot study is to measure the willingness-to-pay and sentiments on the event programme in Paisley. The broader PhD project studies the regeneration efforts of Renfrewshire council as part of the legacy programme after losing the 2021 bid for UK City of Culture, especially in relation to culture. One of the main areas studied is the local events programme, as it is an ongoing project with popular and official engagement, holding an informal status as flagship program since the inception of the bid. The public investments and engagements in the programme are comparatively high, and expanding, despite losing the bid for UKCoC.

This study is performed by conducting a short questionnaire on attendees of Paisley public events. No direct demographic data is collected, but Postcode is collected for travel cost analysis and Scottish Index of Multiple Deprivation (SIMD) placement. The questions revolve sentiments on the event, spending at the event, and the potential willingness to pay (WTP) for the event. Most public events in Paisley are free and financed by Renfrewshire Council, and WTP is therefore hypothetical.

The research is conducted by Niclas Hell and other PhD students helping him as a part of PhD community building. The questionnaire is non-intrusive personally and takes approximately two minutes per respondent to complete. Renfrewshire Council conducts more large-scale surveys at the same events via consultants. These surveys contain circa five times as many questions and asks for most common demographic data as well as data on family and children. The overlap between these surveys is low, and the PhD uses Renfrewshire Council's surveys as secondary data. Due to large attendance (34,000 at the Halloween festival in 2018, 400 people surveyed), the risk of being asked to participate in both studies is low.

A second part of the pilot study is conducted the week after the public event. Local shopkeepers are asked about their opinions on the event and the impact on their business. This is performed because all of the current economic impact analysis data of the event programme lacks input from the business owners, assumed to be the ones benefitting economically from the event programme. These surveys are performed by Niclas Hell and are recorded. No demographic data is collected, only the type of business and location.

How has the scientific quality of the proposed research project been assessed?

- Independent external review
- Review within a company
- Review within a multi-centre research group
- Review within the principal investigator's institution
- Review within the research team
- Review by supervisor/director of studies
- Other

Sample Size

Please explain/justify your intended sample size:

The sample size is set at 100 respondents for the first part of the study. This size is chosen to be able to draw correlations. While keeping the effort at a pilot study level, being able to differentiate WTP in different demographic groups of multiple deprivation and correlate different WTP with sentiments on the event needs a sample size bigger than a minimal study.

The second part of the study is more laborious due to the open-ended questions, and 30 respondents are expected to be collected. 30 businesses will be able to cover a range of areas and styles of products.

Analysis and Presentation

Please explain how you will analyse, present/disseminate the data you intend to collect:

The data will go through basic statistical analysis, partially as a learning experience for Niclas Hell, partially as a way to understand what information can be extracted from the material. After that, a critical analysis of the quality of the result and the method will guide the PhD work towards the larger data collection for the PhD thesis. Finally, presented in output such as the thesis and presentations, the findings will be assessed in comparison to other data and be treated as an early part of the study.

Interviews/Questionnaires

Does the proposed research involve the use of individual/group interviews or questionnaires?

- Yes
- No

Please upload a copy of the Questionnaire or Interview Schedule

Type	Document Name	File Name	Version Date	Version	Size
Default	Questionnaire	Questionnaire.docx	22/10/2019	1.2	37.9 KB

Will proposed interviews or questionnaires discuss topics that might be sensitive, embarrassing or upsetting for participants or is it possible that criminal or other disclosures requiring action could occur during the study?

- Yes
- No

Impact on Participants

Please provide details of how you will recruit participants to your study:

These will be approached randomly on the open street events of Paisley for the first part of the study.
For the second part of the study, Niclas Hell will approach the people working in stores.

Will participants be from any of the following groups? (Please tick all that apply)

- Children under 16
- Adults with learning disabilities
- Adults with a terminal illness
- Adults in emergency situations
- Adults with mental illness (particularly if detained under the mental health act)
- Adults with dementia
- Adults in Scotland who are unable to consent for themselves
- Those who could be considered to have a particularly dependent relationship with the investigator
- Other
- None of the above

Are there any special pressures which would make it difficult for potential participants to refuse to take part in your study? (e.g., relationship to the investigator?)

No.

Will study participants be paid to take part?

- Yes
- No

What is the expected duration of participation in the study for each participant?

First part of the study: 2 minutes
Second part of the study: 2-5 minutes

Will informed consent be obtained from study participants?

- Yes
- No

Please justify your decision not to obtain consent from your participants.

The respondents will be asked if they are willing to participate in a study at UWS, the details can be found in the attached questionnaire document. The simplicity of the study and the lack of compromising information should make this measure satisfactory.

Is the study likely to cause any discomfort or distress, either physical or psychological (see UWS Guidelines for Ethical Practice in Research and Scholarship)?

- Yes
- No

Does the proposed research involve any physically invasive procedures?

- Yes
- No

Other ethical considerations

Does the proposed research involve deception regarding aims, objectives or the identity of the investigator?

- Yes
- No

Will research participants be debriefed after their participation?

- Yes
- No

Are there any other Ethical Considerations you wish to bring to the attention of the committee?

- Yes
- No

Personal Data

What measures will you put in place to ensure the confidentiality of personal data gathered during your study?

No strictly personal data is gathered, and the SIMD analysis will only be used as a representation in demographic deciles, there will be no possibility to trace a respondent.

Who will have access to the data collected during the study and how will you keep it confidential?

After surveying, the data will be terminated except being kept on Niclas Hell's encrypted hard drive.

Supporting Documents

Please upload any additional supporting documents you are submitting with this application

Signatures

Principal Investigator

The information supplied above is, to the best of my knowledge and belief, accurate. I have read the university ethics guidelines and clearly understand my obligations and the rights of study participants, particularly in relation to obtaining valid consent.

Signed: This form was signed by Niclas Hell (B00373886@studentmail.uws.ac.uk) on 22/10/2019 12:32

Supervisor/Director of Studies

I support the above application and I agree to supervise the work.

Signed: This form was signed by Prof John Struthers (John.Struthers@uws.ac.uk) on 23/10/2019 11:40

Appendix 9. Ethics application for phase 2 data. Approved, id number 16743

Filter Questions

- I confirm I have read the UWS and my School Guidelines for Ethical Practice in Research and Scholarship.
(please tick to continue)

Pre-screening Questions

Does your work involve any of the following. (please tick all that apply)

- Human Participants
 Personal Data
 Animals
 Risk to the Investigator
- None of the above

Based on your answers to the above questions you should complete the remainder of this form and submit it to your school ethics committee for approval **PRIOR** to commencing any work on your project. Please click Next to proceed.

Applicant Details

Position of Principal Investigator

Postgraduate

Principal Investigator

Title First Name Surname

Niclas Hell

Email

School

Business and Creative Industries

Are there any co-applicants

Yes

No

Supervisor/Director of Studies

Supervisor/Director of Studies

Title First Name Surname

Professor

John

Struthers

School

Business and Creative Industries

Email

Collaborators

Are there any other collaborators?

Yes

No

Project Information

Title of Study

Social and Economic Values of Paisley Events

Primary purpose of the study

Postgraduate Dissertation

Where will the proposed research take place?

Online

How will the costs of the study be met?

Fully funded PhD stipend

Previous Approvals

Has the proposed study been considered by any other ethics committee?

- Yes
- No

Purpose, justification, design and methodology

Please give a full summary of the purpose, justification, design and methodology of the planned study: (word limit 1000 words)

As a part of Niclas Hell's PhD research, original research needs to be conducted. This survey is a study following a pilot, review reference 2019-9267-7333. The aim is to understand values created due to festivals and events in Paisley's town centre.

The study measures the willingness-to-pay and sentiments on the event programme in Paisley. The broader PhD project studies the regeneration efforts of Renfrewshire council as part of the legacy programme after losing the 2021 bid for UK City of Culture, especially in relation to culture. One of the main areas studied is the local events programme, as it is an ongoing project with popular and official engagement, holding an informal status as flagship program since the inception of the bid. The public investments and engagements in the programme are comparatively high, and expanding, despite losing the bid for UKCoC.

The first part of the study is performed by conducting a digital questionnaire with attendees of Paisley public events. Basic demographic data is collected, but not enough to trace participants. The questions revolve sentiments on the event, spending at the event, and the potential willingness to pay (WTP) for the event. Most public events in Paisley are free and financed by Renfrewshire Council, and WTP is therefore hypothetical.

The research is conducted by Niclas Hell with help from Renfrewshire Council distributing it digitally. The questionnaire is non-intrusive personally and takes approximately ten minutes per respondent to complete. Renfrewshire Council conducts more large-scale surveys at Paisley events via consultants. The overlap between these surveys is low, and the PhD uses Renfrewshire Council's surveys as secondary data.

The second part of the study consists of in-depth interviews with stakeholders and professionals with relations to either Paisley or Scottish events. The interviews revolve around the professional role of the respondents, the Paisley events programme, and the Scottish approach to events policy, public values, and well-being. Attached to the application is a list of sample questions.

The study will take place early 2022.

How has the scientific quality of the proposed research project been assessed?

- Independent external review
- Review within a company
- Review within a multi-centre research group
- Review within the principal investigator's institution
- Review within the research team
- Review by supervisor/director of studies
- Other

please provide details below

Reviewed and accepted by Renfrewshire Council, who will be distributing the quantitative part of the survey.

Sample Size

Please explain/justify your intended sample size:

The sample size is not yet known. Renfrewshire Council have offered for the study to use two separate lists of addresses: one of those in the local resident population who have submitted their email addresses to the council for general contact. The other consists of ticket buyers for the Spree festival. Both of these lists are in the thousands, the latter "1,500-2000". A large portion of local residents have attended at least one of the large public festivals in the last few years, and close to all ticket buyers have attended The Spree. Even if they have not, the non-use values of these non-attendees are relevant for the scope of the study; such insights form important findings in the pilot study. These lists are cleared to be used for scientific purposes by Renfrewshire Council. The research team does not have access to these addresses due to integrity concerns, and they will be sent out by the Council.

Analysis and Presentation

Please explain how you will analyse, present/disseminate the data you intend to collect:

The data will constitute the data backbone of Niclas Hell's PhD thesis. Secondly, it will hopefully include such findings that it could be the subject of a journal article as well.

Interviews/Questionnaires

Does the proposed research involve the use of individual/group interviews or questionnaires?

- Yes
- No

Please upload a copy of the Questionnaire or Interview Schedule

Documents

Type	Document Name	File Name	Version Date	Version	Size
Default	QuestionPro-Survey-8898273-PDF-Export-12-21-2021-T073730	QuestionPro-Survey-8898273-PDF-Export-12-21-2021-T073730.pdf	21/12/2021	3	349.2 KB
Default	Qualitative side	Qualitative side.docx	21/12/2021	1	14.9 KB

Will proposed interviews or questionnaires discuss topics that might be sensitive, embarrassing or upsetting for participants or is it possible that criminal or other disclosures requiring action could occur during the study?

- Yes
 No

Impact on Participants

Please provide details of how you will recruit participants to your study:

Emailing lists owned by Renfrewshire Council, see above.

Will participants be from any of the following groups? (Please tick all that apply)

- Children under 16
 Adults with learning disabilities
 Adults with a terminal illness
 Adults in emergency situations
 Adults with mental illness (particularly if detained under the mental health act)
 Adults with dementia
 Adults in Scotland who are unable to consent for themselves
 Those who could be considered to have a particularly dependent relationship with the investigator
 Other
 None of the above

Are there any special pressures which would make it difficult for potential participants to refuse to take part in your study? (e.g., relationship to the investigator?)

The participants are approached by group emails only. The source will be Renfrewshire council, whose relation to the respondents is potentially complex. However, it is made clear that the data is anonymous and untraceable, and that all respondents may leave the survey at any point without repercussions. No interaction beyond a local authority email will reach the potential respondents.

Will study participants be paid to take part?

- Yes
 No

What is the expected duration of participation in the study for each participant?

Ten minutes

Will informed consent be obtained from study participants?

Yes

No

Please provide details of how you will obtain this consent and the information you will provide to potential participants to allow them to make an informed choice about whether or not to participate in your research.

The survey site starts with the following message:

Hello,

You are invited to participate in the survey "Experiences of Paisley Events", part of a research cooperation between Renfrewshire Council and University of the West of Scotland. The questions relate to public events in Paisley.

It is important for us to learn your opinions so that Renfrewshire Council can provide the best events and experience possible. The questionnaire will take about ten minutes to complete.

The questionnaire is anonymous, and the results will not be possible to trace back to you. Data will not be presented on an individual level. Ethics approval has been received from the UWS Ethics Committee.

The questionnaire is entirely voluntary. If you feel uncomfortable answering a question, you may withdraw from the survey or skip that question.

If you have any questions or additional comments, please contact Niclas Hell at niclas.hell@uws.ac.uk.

Thank you very much for your important contribution. Press "Next" to start the survey.

Please upload a copy of the Participant Information Sheet(s)

Documents

Type	Document Name	File Name	Version Date	Version	Size
Default	QuestionPro-Survey-8898273-PDF-Export-12-21-2021-T073730	QuestionPro-Survey-8898273-PDF-Export-12-21-2021-T073730.pdf	21/12/2021	3	349.2 KB

Please upload a copy of your Consent Form(s)

Documents

Type	Document Name	File Name	Version Date	Version	Size
Default	QuestionPro-Survey-8898273-PDF-Export-12-21-2021-T073730	QuestionPro-Survey-8898273-PDF-Export-12-21-2021-T073730.pdf	21/12/2021	3	349.2 KB

Is the study likely to cause any discomfort or distress, either physical or psychological (see UWS Guidelines for Ethical Practice in Research and Scholarship)?

Yes

No

Does the proposed research involve any physically invasive procedures?

- Yes
- No

Other ethical considerations

Does the proposed research involve deception regarding aims, objectives or the identity of the investigator?

- Yes
- No

Will research participants be debriefed after their participation?

- Yes
- No

Are there any other Ethical Considerations you wish to bring to the attention of the committee?

- Yes
- No

Personal Data

What measures will you put in place to ensure the confidentiality of personal data gathered during your study?

No logging of IP addresses will be available to me as a researcher. Personal data questions are designed to be as uninvasive as possible (including only using the first three figures of the postcode). These are largely based on the widely-used ATLAS template. Using intermediate parties (Questionpro, Renfrewshire Council), neither me nor anyone else will have a possibility to contact or trace the respondents. All data will be stored on UWS encrypted cloud services.

Who will have access to the data collected during the study and how will you keep it confidential?

Only me. See last question for confidentiality.

Supporting Documents

Please upload any additional supporting documents you are submitting with this application

Signatures

Principal Investigator

The information supplied above is, to the best of my knowledge and belief, accurate. I have read the university ethics guidelines and clearly understand my obligations and the rights of study participants, particularly in relation to obtaining valid consent.

Signed: This form was signed by Niclas Hel [REDACTED] on 21/12/2021 15:43

Supervisor/Director of Studies

I support the above application and I agree to supervise the work.

Signed: This form was signed by Prof John Struthers [REDACTED] 22/12/2021 11:41

